

10TH INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE ON
**PREDICTIVE
MODELLING
IN FOOD**

CÓRDOBA, SPAIN, 26-29 SEPTEMBER, 2017
GOVERNMENT BUILDING OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CÓRDOBA

CÓRDOBA, SEPTEMBER, 2017
ICPMF10
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON PREDICTIVE MODELLING IN FOOD

UNIVERSIDAD DE CÓRDOBA

Dear Colleagues and friends,

On behalf of the organizing committee, We kindly invite you to attend the 10th International Conference of Predictive Modelling in Food (ICPMF10) to be held in Córdoba from 26th to 29th September, 2017. As you may know the International Committee on Predictive Modelling in Food (www.icpmf.org), which was founded in 2011, has the mission to promote the development of predictive models and to generate new knowledge in the field that are relevant to food stakeholders, risk assessors and governmental authorities. This objective is primarily achieved through advancing the success and sustainability of the biennial ICPMF-conferences.

Historically, Córdoba city has been an interplay of cultures, ideas and traditions, so we would like to extend this to the field of **Predictive Modelling in Food**.

The scientific program includes plenary sessions, oral communications and panels, where the most relevant topics related to our area will be addressed:

- Systems biology and whole-cell modelling
- Individual-based models
- Modelling approaches using metagenomics (food) data
- Complex systems modelling approaches for food safety and quality
- Modelling microbial dynamics in relation to food microstructure
- Data Bases, software and decision-support tools in predictive modelling on foods
- Predictive models for food safety and quality: decontamination, food formulation, bacterial transfer, microbial spoilage, etc.
- Predictive models for food process simulation: dehydrating, mixing, forming, heat transfer, etc.
- Modelling the impact of microbiological interactions in foods
- Interdisciplinary approaches and new advances in predictive modelling in foods
- Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment and Management
- Predictive mycology.

Three workshops and a symposium on microbial risk assessment are included in the conference registration (e.g. free access to workshops). They take place during the day before the scientific program, that is, 26th September, 2017.

The local organizing committee has prepared a comprehensive and challenging program, and we expect to gather a significant number of participants from over the world. We also encourage the participation of students; whose fresh ideas and enthusiasm are always welcome. To this end, two students supporting programs will be developed consisting of a Travel Support Scholarship sponsored by Elsevier and a Developing Scientist Poster Competition organized by International Committee of Food Hygiene and Microbiology (ICFHM).

The International Journal of Food Microbiology and Microbial Risk Analysis will be the publications supporting ICPMF10 which will host the Special issue of the conference containing the most relevant works presented at ICPMF10, which will be published, after the conferences, according to a peer review process.

In addition to the scientific program, we have prepared an attractive social and recreational program with which we could enjoy weather, history and gastronomy of Córdoba, a city declared a World Heritage Site by UNESCO.

The website www.icpmf10.com is our platform to manage your participation in ICPMF10 and provide you the latest news on the conference. Registration to the Conference will be easily done through the website as well as submission of abstracts, booking rooms in the recommended hotels, and including the main travelling tips for Córdoba, eating places, transport, etc.

We look forward to meeting you for the Conference, in Cordoba, a lovely town, located in the south of Spain.

Kind Regards,
The Organizing Committee

Committees

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Chair: Prof. Fernando Pérez-Rodríguez, Ph.D.

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Vice-Chair: Prof. Elena Carrasco Jiménez, Ph.D.

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Department of Food Technology. University of Lleida, Lleida (Spain)

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Izmir Food Laboratory. Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Livestock, Ankara (Turkey)

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Alejandro Amezquita

Unilever, England

Glaucia Aragao

Federal University of Santa Catarina, Brazil

Fanny Tenenhaus-Aziza

CNIEL, France

Jean Christophe Augustin

Alfort Veterinary School, France

József Baranyi

Institute Food Research, England

Javier Benedito

Universidad Politécnica Valencia, Spain

Heidy den Besten

Wageningen University, The Netherlands

Paw Dalgaard

Danish Technological University, Denmark

Anderson de Souza

University of Campinas, Brazil

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Frank Devlieghere

Ghent University, Belgium

Mariem Ellouze

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Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR), Germany

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Universidad Politécnica de Catalunya, Spain

Úrsula Gonzales-Barrón

CIMO - Mountains Research Centre, Portugal

Lihan Huang

US Department of Agriculture - ARS, USA

Shigenobu Koseki

Research Faculty of Agriculture, Japan

Kostas Koutsoumanis

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

Antonio Martínez

Instituto de agroquímica y Tecnología de Alimentos (IATA), Spain

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National Institute of Agricultural Research (INRA), France

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An Vermeulen

Ghent University, Belgium

Marcel Zwietering

Wageningen University, The Netherlands

INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE ON FOOD MICROBIOLOGY AND HYGIENE (ICFMH)

Since 1953

The **International Committee on Food Microbiology and Hygiene (ICFMH)** was founded in 1953 and officially represents International Union of Microbiological Society (**IUMS**) in all issues related to food microbiology. The ICFMH has observer and/or advisory status in activities of FAO and WHO, ISO working groups related to the detection and enumeration of microorganisms in food.

ICFMH mission

The major scope of the ICFMH is to contribute to food safety internationally, by means of symposia (e.g., FOOD MICRO), workshops, support of international bodies in food safety issues, publications, and by supporting and initiating education and training in food microbiology. The ICFMH particularly focuses on the food safety situation in developing countries.

ICFMH main activities

FOOD MICRO Conference. The initially small ICFMH Symposia and expert meetings developed into the international biennial "FOOD MICRO" Conference. The ICFMH and the national organisers managed to keep track with increasing challenges and complexity posed by diverse areas of Food Microbiology.

FOOD MICRO 2018 will be held in Berlin (Ireland), 3rd-6th September 2018 (www.foodmicro2018.com). Guidelines for organising future FOOD MICRO conferences can be found [here](#).

International Journal of Food Microbiology (IJFM). As the "flagship" of the ICFMH, and published by Elsevier, it has gained and enjoys constantly increasing international recognition.

Scholarships. The ICFMH regularly sponsors qualified countries to participate in international meetings and workshops such as FOOD MICRO. For more information visit: www.icfmh.org.

ICFMH Mobility Grants are short-term fellowships annually sponsored to assist young scientists active in food microbiology and hygiene in pursuing research at a host laboratory.

ICFMH awards for best student communication (oral and/or poster) are regularly sponsored in international meetings and symposia, including FOOD MICRO.

Subcommittee on Predictive Modelling in Food (ICPMF). In 2014, the Executive board agreed to incorporate the **International Committee on Predictive Modelling in Food (ICPMF)** as a subcommittee. The ICPMF has a mission to catalyse the development of predictive modelling in foods, primarily through advancing the success and sustainability of the biannual ICPMF-conferences.

Working Party on Quality Assurance and Quality Monitoring of Culture Media (WPCM) was initiated in 1978 to elaborate a "Pharmacopoeia of Culture Media". The 3rd edition of the *Handbook of Culture Media for Food and Water Microbiology* was published by The Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC) early 2012.

Working Party on Advanced Education in Food Microbiology (WPAEFM) aims to provide a forum for discussion and structuring curricula in food microbiology so that a harmonized set of proposals can be used during discussions with relevant authorities, national bodies and academicians offering courses in food microbiology and food safety.

Workshops and other activities. Workshops on special issues in food microbiology and food safety form part of the international scope of ICFMH. Workshops on Food Safety in Africa have been conducted in South Africa (2003 and 2007) and in Ghana (2014). Workshops on Traditional Fermented Foods were held in Burkina Faso, Denmark and France in 2009, 2010 and 2014, respectively. Within the IUMS Outreach Program, a Food Safety Workshop was held in Bali (2011) and Yogyakarta (2017), Indonesia.

National Delegates and representatives

In order to achieve its goals, it is essential to collaborate with National Societies for Microbiology throughout the world, and to interact with research groups and scientists dealing with food microbiology. We encourage you to directly contact the National Delegate of your country for any issues related to Food Microbiology.

We invite you to visit www.icfmh.org, and to inform and update yourself on the ICFMH. Please do not hesitate to [contact](#) us if you believe valuable information could be uploaded in our website.

Scientific Programme outline

WEDNESDAY, SEPTEMBER 27th 2017

08:30 - 09:00 h Opening conference

09:00 - 09:30 h Keynote Speech: "Predictive modelling transforming food microbiology: where to next?"
by **Dr. Tom Ross**. University of Tasmania, Australia

09:30 - 10:30 h **ORAL COMMUNICATION SESSION 1.-** Interdisciplinary approaches and new advances

10:30 - 11:00 h COFFEE BREAK AND POSTER SESSION

11:00 - 13:15 h **ORAL COMMUNICATION SESSION 2.-** Predictive models and complex modelling approaches for food safety and quality

13:15 - 14:30 h LUNCH TIME AND POSTER SESSION

14:30 - 16:00 h **ORAL COMMUNICATION SESSION 3.-** Individual-based models

16:00 - 16:30 h COFFEE BREAK AND POSTER SESSION

16:30 - 18:00 h **ORAL COMMUNICATION SESSION 4.-** Modelling microbial dynamics in relation to food microstructure and the impact of microbiological interaction in foods

THURSDAY, SEPTEMBER 28th 2017

09:00 - 09:30 h Keynote Speech: "The paradigm change for MRA: translating multidimensional microbial genotypic information into a single measure of risk" by **Dr. Annemarie Pielaat**. Unilever, UK.

09:30 - 10:30 h **ORAL COMMUNICATION SESSION 5.-** Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment and Management

10:30 - 11:00 h COFFEE BREAK AND POSTER SESSION

11:00 - 13:15 h **ORAL COMMUNICATION SESSION 6.-** Predictive models for food process simulation

13:15 - 14:30 h LUNCH TIME AND POSTER SESSION

14:30 - 15:30 h **ORAL COMMUNICATION SESSION 7.-** Systems biology and whole-cell modelling.

15:30 - 16:00 h **ORAL COMMUNICATION SESSION 8.-** Data Bases, software and decision support tools (I)

16:00 - 16:30 h COFFEE BREAK AND POSTER SESSION

16:30 - 18:00 h **ORAL COMMUNICATION SESSION 8.-** Data bases, software and decision support tools (II)

FRIDAY, SEPTEMBER 29th 2017

09:00 - 10:30 h **ORAL COMMUNICATION SESSION 9.-** Modelling approaches using metagenomics data

10:30 - 11:00 h COFFEE BREAK

11:00 - 12:00 h **ORAL COMMUNICATION SESSION 10.-** Predictive Mycology

12:00 - 12:30 h Keynote Speech - Closing Conference: "**Name of the game** – Deterministic laws and randomness play equal role in microbial as well as human population dynamics"
by **Prof. József Baranyi**, Institute of Nutrition, University of Debrecen, Hungary;
Visiting Professor Physics Department, Imperial College, London, UK.

12:30 - 13:00 h ICMFH Poster Awards and Closing Congress

Scientific Programme

WEDNESDAY, SEPTEMBER 27th 2017

08:30 - 09:00 h Opening conference

09:00 - 09:30 h Keynote Speech: "Predictive modelling transforming food microbiology: where to next?"
by **Dr. Tom Ross**. University of Tasmania, Australia

09:30 - 10:30 h **SESSION 1.- Interdisciplinary approaches and new advances**

Chair: József Baranyi (University of Debrecen)

- 09.30-9.45 MODELLING APPROACHES FOR GENOTYPE-PHENOTYPE ASSOCIATION STUDIES BASED ON NGS: APPLICATION ON LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES
Lena Fritsch, Meryl Vila Nova, Jean-François Mariet, Nicolas Radomski, Arnaud Felten, Michel-Yves Mistou, Jean-Christophe Augustin, Laurent Guillier
- 09.45-10.00 MICROBIAL MODELLING COUPLING THE DYNAMICS OF DIFFUSED GASES AND MICROBIAL GROWTH IN MODIFIED ATMOSPHERE PACKAGING
Kirk D. Dolan, Hazel Meredith, Declan J. Bolton, Vasilis P. Valdramidis
- 10.00-10.15 ZERO-INFLATED REGRESSIONS FOR MODELLING MICROBIAL LOW PREVALENCE AND SAMPLING PERFORMANCE FOR FOODBORNE PATHOGENS
Ursula Gonzales-Barron, Marta Hernández, David Rodríguez-Lázaro, Vasco Cadavez, Antonio Valero
- 10.15-10.30 MEAT SPOILAGE PREDICTION MODELS USING FINGERPRINTING('OMICS,SURFACE CHEMISTRY)IN TANDEM WITH AUTOMATED RANKING PLATFORM
Fady Mohareb, Stathis Panagou, George - John Nychas

10:30 - 11:00 h COFFEE BREAK AND POSTER SESSION

11:00 - 13:00 h **SESSION 2.- Predictive models and complex modelling approaches for food safety and quality**

Chairs: Úrsula González-Barrón (Polytechnic Institute of Bragança) and Anderson De Souza Sant'Ana (University of Campinas)

- 11.00-11.15 RAPID DETECTION OF MICROBIOLOGICAL QUALITY OF RAW MINCED BEEF BY MEANS OF ELECTRONIC NOSE AND MULTIVARIATE ANALYSIS
Dimitris Pavlidis, Stathis Panagou, George - John Nychas
- 11.15-11.30 MODELLING OF TTI SMART LABELS RESPONSE FOR MONITORING SHELF-LIFE AND *VIBRIO PARAHAEMOLYTICUS* RISK IN OYSTERS
Kalliopi Kalliopi, Marianna Giannoglou, Theofania Tsironi, Petros Taoukis
- 11.30-11.45 MODELING ADHESION AND BIOFILM FORMATION ON STAINLESS STEEL BY FIVE DIFFERENT SEROTYPES OF SALMONELLA ENTERICA
Marciane Magnani, Juliana de Oliveira Moraes, Ellen Abreu da Cruz, Tereza C R Moreira Oliveira, Verônica Ortiz Alvarenga, Anderson de Souza Sant'Ana
- 11.45-12.00 EXTENSIVE CARDINAL PARAMETER MODEL TO PREDICT GROWTH OF PSEUDOMONADS IN SALT-REDUCED LIGHTLY PRESERVED SEAFOOD
Veronica Martinez-Rios, Paw Dalgaard
- 12.00-12.15 THE PROPAGATION OF UNCERTAINTY FROM DATA TO PREDICTIONS
Akkermans Simen, Nimmegeers Philippe, Telen Dries, Van Impe Jan
- 12.15-12.30 MODELLING AND IDENTIFICATION OF RELEVANT PATHWAYS FOR NUCLEOTIDE DEGRADATION IN FRESH HAKE DURING STORAGE
Carlos Vilas, Míriam R. García, Antonio A. Alonso, Juan R. Herrera, Marta Bernárdez

12.30-12.45 IMPACT OF NATURAL DIVERSITY IN HEAT RESISTANCE OF BACTERIAL CELLS AND SPORES ON SAFETY AND QUALITY
Heidy den Besten, Marjon Wells-Bennik, Marcel Zwietering

12.45-13:00 MODELING ADHESION ON POLYPROPYLENE AND GLASS SURFACES BY DISTINCT SALMONELLA SEROVARS
Marciane Magnani, Juliana de Oliveira Moraes, Tereza Cristina Oliveira, Ellen Abreu Cruz, Verônica Ortiz Alvarenga, Anderson de Souza Sant'Ana

13:15 - 14:30 h LUNCH TIME AND POSTER SESSION

14:30 - 16:00 h **SESSION 3.- Individual-based models**

Chairs: Kostas Koutsoumanis (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki) and Pablo Fernández (Technical University of Cartagena)

14.30-14.45 DESCRIBING TIME-TO-INACTIVATION OF BACTERIAL POPULATION, USING INDIVIDUAL CELL HETEROGENEITY, VIA COMPUTER SIMULATION
Kento Koyama, Abe Hiroki, Shuso Kawamura, Shige Koseki

14.45-15.00 ESTIMATING BACTERIAL POPULATION GROWTH RATES FROM FLOW CYTOMETRY
Antonio A. Alonso, Joao Freire, Míriam R. García

15.00-15.15 UNDERSTANDING AND PREDICTING MICROBIAL BEHAVIOR AT THE BOUNDARIES BETWEEN GROWTH, SURVIVAL AND DEATH
Kostas Koutsoumanis, Theodora Akritidou, Zaphiro Aspidou

15.15-15.30 VARIABILITY OF GERMINATION AND OUTGROWTH OF INDIVIDUAL BACTERIAL SPORES. PHENOMENOLOGICAL AND MECHANISTIC ASPECTS
Jan P. Smelt, Chris G. de Koster, Stanley Brul

15.30-15.45 BEHAVIOR OF INDIVIDUAL SALMONELLA AGONA CELLS SUBMITTED TO MILD STRESS: THE CASE OF SODIUM HYPOCHLORITE
Rafael Chaves, Zafeiro Aspidou, Anderson Santana, Konstantinos Koutsoumanis

15.45-16.00 INDIVIDUAL BASED MODELING OF COOPERATIVE INTERACTIONS IN BIOFILMS
Ihab Hashem, Philippe Nimmegeers, Simen Akkermans, Dries Telen, Jan Van Impe

16:00 - 16:30 h COFFEE BREAK AND POSTER SESSION

16:30 - 18:00 h **SESSION 4.- Modelling microbial dynamics in relation to food microstructure and the impact of microbiological interaction in foods**

Chairs: Marcel Zwietering (Wageningen University) and Antonio Valero (University of Cordoba)

16.30-16.45 MODELLING THE MICROBIAL DYNAMICS & AMR DEVELOPMENT OF *LISTERIA* IN FOOD MODEL SYSTEMS OF DIFFERENT STRUCTURAL COMPLEXITY
Katherine Costello, Jorge Gutierrez, Madeleine Bussemaker, Maria Baka, Jan Van Impe, Eirini Velliou

16.45-17.00 GENERIC GLOBAL REGRESSION MODELS FOR GROWTH PREDICTION OF *SALMONELLA* IN GROUND PORK AND PORK CUTS
Tasja Buschhardt, Tina B Hansen, Martin I Bahl, Donald W Schaffner, Søren Aabo

17.00-17.15 MODELLING EFFECTS OF FOOD CHARACTERISTICS ON INTERACTION BETWEEN LACTIC ACID BACTERIA AND *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES*
Louise Maimann Laursen, Regitze Lærke Pedersen, Ole Mejlholm, Paw Dalgaard

- 17.15-17.30 INFLUENCE OF PH AND STRUCTURE ON SORBIC ACID DISTRIBUTION AND GROWTH OF *C.GUILLIERMONDII* IN FAT BASED PRODUCTS
Irena Soljic, An Vermeulen, Frank Devlieghere
- 17.30-17.45 MODELING THE FATE OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* AND LACTIC ACID BACTERIA IN TRADITIONAL MINAS CHEESES
Fernanda B. Campagnollo, Marcelo D. Feliciano, Rosicléia A. Silva, Clara M. Duffner, Verônica O. Alvarenga, Donald W. Schaffner, Anderson S. Sant'Ana
- 17.45-18.00 MODELLING THE EFFECT OF OSMOTIC ADAPTATION AND TEMPERATURE ON THE NON-THERMAL INACTIVATION OF *SALMONELLA* SPP. IN BAKERY BRIOCHE-LIKE PRODUCTS
Ifigeneia Makariti, Anastasia Kapetanakou, Eleftheria Nazou, Stavros Manios, Konstantinos Karavasilis, Panagiotis Skandamis

THURSDAY, SEPTEMBER 28th 2017

09:00 - 09:30 h Keynote Speech: "The paradigm change for MRA: translating multidimensional microbial genotypic information into a single measure of risk"
by **Dr. Annemarie Pielat**. Unilever, UK.

09:30 - 10:30 h **SESSION 5.-** Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment and Management

Chair: **Alejandro Amezcua** (UNILEVER)

- 09.30 – 09.45 APPLICATION OF NEXT GENERATION SEQUENCING DATA IN MICROBIAL RISK ASSESSMENT: CASE OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES*
Patrick Njage, Clementine Henry, Pimlapas Leekitcharoenphon, Sophie Roussel, Rene Hendriksen, Tine Hald
- 09.45 – 10.00 CAN STOCHASTIC CONSUMER PHASE MODELS IN MICROBIAL RISK ASSESSMENT BE SIMPLIFIED TO A SINGLE FACTOR?.
Maria Inês Neves, Maarten Nauta
- 10.00 – 10.15 FARM TO FORK QUANTITATIVE MICROBIAL RISK ASSESSMENT FOR NOROVIRUS ON FROZEN BERRIES
Robyn Miranda, Donald Schaffner
- 10.15 – 10.30 RISK-BASED STRATEGIES TO ACCOMPLISH "LISTERIA ZERO" POLICY: DRY-CURED HAM AS A CASE STUDY
Sara Bover-Cid, Anna Jofré, Margarita Garriga

10:30 - 11:00 h COFFEE BREAK AND POSTER SESSION

11:00 - 13:00 h **SESSION 6.-** Predictive models for food process simulation

Chairs: **Vasilis Valdramidis** (University of Malta) and **Elena Carrasco** (University of Cordoba)

- 11.00 – 11.15 MODELLING THE INHIBITORY EFFECT OF LAB ON *L. MONOCYTOGENES* AND ENTEROBACTERIACEAE IN A FERMENTED SAUSAGE DURING RIPENING
Vasco Cadavez, Francis Butler, Ursula Gonzales-Barron
- 11.15 – 11.30 GROWTH AND SPORULATION DYNAMICS OF *BACILLUS SUBTILIS* CAN BE MODELED WITH ITS GROWTH LIMITS.
Gauvry Emilie, Mathot Anne-Gabrielle, Couvert Olivier, Leguérinel Ivan, Coroller Louis
- 11.30 – 11.45 DEVELOPMENT OF A TIME-TEMPERATURE INDICATOR BASED ON VERSATILE BACTERIAL PIGMENT PRODUCED BY *JANTHINOBACTERIUM* SP.
Marios Mataragas, María Korre, Vasiliki Mpikouli, Panagiotis Skandamis
- 11.45 – 12.00 MODELLING INTERACTION OF A SAKACIN-PRODUCING *LACTOBACILLUS SAKEI* STRAIN (CTC 494) AND *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* (CTC 1034) IN GILT-HEAD SEABREAM (*SPARUS AURATA*) UNDER ISOTHERMAL AND NON-ISOTHERMAL CONDITIONS
Jean Costa, Sara Bover-Cid, G.D. Posada-Izquierdo, Gonzalo Zurera, Fernando Pérez-Rodríguez
- 12.00 – 12.15 MODELLING *BACILLUS CEREUS* SURVIVAL VARIABILITY TO SPRAY DRYING PROCESS
Verônica Ortiz Alvarenga, Eric Keven Silva, Arhtur Kael da Pia Rodrigues, Mirian Dupas Hubinger, Anderson de Souza Sant'Ana
- 12.15 – 12.30 NEW INSIGHTS ON THE EFFECT OF LACTATE ON THE *L. MONOCYTOGENES* GROWTH IN HIGH PRESSURE PROCESSED COOKED HAM
Anna Jofré, Cristina Serra, Paw Dalgaard, Margarita Garriga, Sara Bover-Cid

- 12.30 – 12.45 MODELLING INACTIVATION OF DIFFERENT MODES OF LIVING OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* TREATED WITH COLD ATMOSPHERIC PLASMA
Marlies Govaert, Cindy Smet, Valeria Angarano, Maria Baka, Jan Van Impe
- 12.45 – 13.00 MODELING THE LOAD OF METABOLITE DIFFUSIVITY ON GROWTH RATE OF NON-STARTER LACTIC ACID BACTERIA DURING CHEESE RIPENING
Tamás Czárán, Fergal Rattray, Cleide Møller, Bjarke Christensen
- 13.00 – 13.15 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE CARDINAL PARAMETERS OF BACILLUS CEREUS STRAINS REVEALED BY A REPARAMETRIZED VERSION OF THE RATKOWSKY MODEL
 József Baranyi, Nathália Buss da Silva, Mariem Ellouze

13:15 - 14:30 h LUNCH TIME AND POSTER SESSION

14:30 - 15:30 h **SESSION 7.- Systems biology and whole-cell modelling.**

Chair: Heidy den Besten (Wageningen University)

- 14.30 – 14.45 MECHANISMS TO COUNTERACT MEDIUM ACIDIFICATION DURING GLUCOSE FERMENTATION: A METABOLIC MODELING ANALYSIS OF E. COLI
Leticia Ungaretti Haberbeck, Bram Vivijis, Abram Aertsen, Chris W. Michiels, Annemie H. Geeraerd, Kristel Bernaerts
- 14.45 – 15.00 MODELING OF ADAPTATION PHENOMENA IN MICROBIAL DYNAMICS: A FLUX BALANCE ANALYSIS APPROACH
Philippe Nimmegeers, Simen Akkermans, Ihab Hashem, Satyajeet Bhonsale, Maria Baka, Dries Telen, Jan Van Impe
- 15.00 – 15.15 TOWARDS A NOVEL GENERATION OF KINETIC PARAMETER ESTIMATION
Philippe Nimmegeers, Simen Akkermans, Dries Telen, Jan Van Impe
- 15.15 – 15.30 COMBINED STATE ESTIMATION AND PREDICTIVE CONTROL OF BIOLOGICAL SYSTEMS USING SOLACE
Satyajeet Bhonsale, Philippe Nimmegeers, Daniel Perrotta, Dries Telen, Jan Van Impe

15:30 - 16:00 h **SESSION 8.- Data Bases, software and decision support tools (I)**

Chairs: Fanny Tenenhaus Aziza (CNIEL) and Paw Dalgaard (Technical University of Denmark)

- 15.30-15.45 HARMONIZATION OF TERMS AND CONCEPTS FOR RISK ASSESSMENT MODELLING AND KNOWLEDGE INTEGRATION
Carolina Plaza-Rodríguez, Leticia Ungaretti-Haberbeck, Virginie Desvignes, Laurent Guillier, Moez Sanaa, Paw Dalgaard, Maarten Nauta, Matthias Filter
- 15.45-16.00 SOURCE ATTRIBUTION OF SPORADIC SALMONELLOSIS BY A META-ANALYSIS OF CASE-CONTROL STUDIES
Ursula Gonzales-Barron, Vasco Cadavez, Vânia Rodrigues, Pauline Kooh, Moez Sanaa

16:00 - 16:30 h COFFEE BREAK AND POSTER SESSION

16:30 - 18:00 h **SESSION 8.- DATA BASES, SOFTWARE AND DECISION SUPPORT TOOLS (II)**

- 16.30-16.45 DEVELOPMENT OF A PROBABILISTIC DECISION-MAKING SCORING SYSTEM FOR QUALITY AND SAFETY REQUIREMENTS OF ALOREÑA DE MALAGA TABLE OLIVES
Antonio Valero, M.A. Bellido, Fernando Pérez-Rodríguez, Elena Carrasco, G.D. Posada, V. Romero-Gil, F. Rodríguez-Gómez, E. Medina-Pradas, R.M. García-Gimeno, F.N. Arroyo-Lopez
- 16.45-17.00 MICROHIBRO: AN EASY-TO-USE FRAMEWORK FOR STOCHASTIC MICROBIAL RISK ASSESSMENT
Árcia Possa, Salvador Cubero, Antonio Valero, Rosa Maria Garcia-Gimeno, Fernando Perez-Rodriguez

- 17.00-17.15 DEVELOPMENT OF A DSS FOR DETERMINING THE SHELF-LIFE OF HAKE PRESERVED IN A MODIFIED ATMOSPHERE RICH IN CARBON DIOXIDE.
Adriana Antunes, Ángela Artaiz, Nabil Halaihel, Javier Raso, Ignacio Álvarez, Guillermo Cebrián
- 17.15-17.30 DEVELOPMENT OF A WEB BASED DECISION SUPPORT-TOOL TO PREDICT REMAINING SHELF LIFE OF MEAT BY TTI DISCOLOURATION
Antonia Albrecht, Stephan Hüwe, Rolf Ibalde, Verena Raab, Werner Reichstein, Dietrich Haarer, Judith Kreyenschmidt
- 17.30-17.45 THE STARTEC DECISION SUPPORT TOOL FOR BETTER TRADEOFFS BETWEEN FOOD SAFETY, QUALITY, NUTRITION AND COSTS IN PRODUCTION
Taran Skjerdal, Edurne Gaston Estanga, Alessandra De Ceglie, Tassos Koidis, Cecilie From, Roberto Mulazzine, Catherine Halbert
- 17.45-18.00 MODELLING MICROBIAL INACTIVATION WITH BIOINACTIVATION, A CASE STUDY
Alberto Garre, Jose A. Egea, Gerardo Gonzalez, Asuncion Iguaz, Paula M. Periago, Roland Lindqvist, Pablo S. Fernandez

FRIDAY, SEPTEMBER 29th 2017

09:00 - 10:30 h **SESSION 9.-** Modelling approaches using metagenomics data

Chairs: George Nychas (University of Athens) and Sara Bover (IRTA)

- 09.00-09.30 THE KEY ROLE OF PROCESS ANALYTICAL TECHNOLOGIES, INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND PREDICTIVE MODELING IN ENHANCING FOOD SAFETY
Fady Mohareb, Stathis Panagou, George - John Nychas
- 09.30-09.45 PREDICTIVE MODELS FOR RISK AND QUALITY ASSESSMENT USING MOLECULAR-BASED SURVEILLANCE IN FOOD MANUFACTURING FACILITIES
Cian O' Mahony, Seamus Fanning
- 09.45-10.00 IN SILICO SIMULATION OF LYTIC BACTERIOPHAGE POPULATION DYNAMICS AND ITS BACTERIAL HOST SALMONELLA TYPHI
Ayman Elshayeb, Abdelazim Ahmed, Marmar El Siddig, Adil EL Hussien.
- 10.00-10.15 A SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH TO SOURCE-ATTRIBUTION MODELLING USING METAGENOMICS DATA
Ana Sofia Ribeiro Duarte, Tine Hald

10:30 - 11:00 h COFFEE BREAK

11:00 - 12:00 h **SESSION 10.-** Predictive Mycology

Chairs: Sonia Marín (University of Lleida) and Jose Martínez Peinado (Complutense University of Madrid)

- 11.00-11.15 MODELLING THE EFFECT OF MODIFIED ATMOSPHERE PACKAGING ON GERMINATION OF FILAMENTOUS FUNGI ISOLATED FROM DAIRY PRODUCTS
Nguyen Van Long Nicolas, Vasseur Valérie, Couvert Olivier, Coroller Louis, Burlot Marion, Rigalma Karim, Mounier Jérôme
- 11.15-11.30 PROBABILITY MODELLING OF GROWTH OF ASPERGILLUS FLAVUS AND AFLATOXIN PRODUCTION IN LOW MOISTURE RAW MATERIALS
Sonia Marín
- 11.30-11.45 A BINOMIAL EQUATION DESCRIBING THE RELATION AMONG OPTICAL DENSITY, CELL NUMBER, AND CELL DRY WEIGHT IN YEAST SUSPENSIONS
F. J. Arranz, E.M. Rivas, E. Gil de Pardo, P. Wrent, M. I. de Silóniz, J. M. Peinado
- 11.45-12.00 HEAT RESISTANCE AND EFFECT OF SUB-LETHAL HEAT TREATMENTS ON THE GROWTH OF *BYSSOCHLAMYS* SPORES.
Juliana Lane Paixão dos Santos, Sonay Merve Gülay, Simbarashe Samapundo, Jan Van Impe, Anderson de Souza Sant'Ana, Frank Devlieghere

12:00 - 12:30 h Closing Conference

12:30 - 13:00 h ICMFH Poster Awards and Closing Congress

General Information

GENERAL INFORMATION

IDENTIFICATION

For reasons of organization and security, it is essential to keep the accreditation card visible.

RECEPTION OF AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS

Located at the Plenary Room. Delivery of audiovisual material in the previous pause of each session.

PLACING AND REMOVING POSTERS

The posters will be placed before 9.00 h in the session to be presented and should be picked up at the end of session (17.00-18.00 h).

CERTIFICATES

Certificates of attendance, speakers, oral communications and posters will be delivered as of the last day.

OFFICIAL INAUGURATION AND WELCOME COCKTAIL

Tuesday, September 26th, at 18:00 h. in the hall of the Rector of the University of Córdoba (Avda. Medina Azahara, 5).

At 20:00 h. there is a welcome cocktail in the Caballerizas Reales (C/ Caballerizas Reales, 1)

WORK LUNCH

Tickets will be delivered during the collection of accreditation, at the Congress Secretariat.

Wednesday, 27th and Thursday 28th, the Work Lunch is in Rector of the University of Córdoba (Avda. Medina Azahara, 5).

CLOSING DINNER

Thursday, September 28th will be held at Bodegas Campos the closing dinner at 20:00 h. (Calle Lineros, 32, 14002 Córdoba).

It is essential to confirm your attendance at dinner during check-in. You must present at the door of the restaurant the bonus that is given to you during the accreditation process.

Abstracts: Orals

WEDNESDAY, SEPT. 27th

09:30 - 10:30 h.: SESSION 1.- Interdisciplinary approaches and new advances

Chair: József Baranyi (University of Debrecen)

001.- MODELLING APPROACHES FOR *GENOTYPE-PHENOTYPE* ASSOCIATION STUDIES BASED ON NGS: APPLICATION ON *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES*.

Lena Fritsch¹, Meryl Vila Nova¹, Jean-François Mariet¹, Nicolas Radomski¹, Arnaud Felten¹, Michel-Yves Mistou¹, Jean-Christophe Augustin², Laurent Guillier¹

1 Université PARIS-EST, Anses, Laboratory for food safety, Maisons-Alfort (France)

2 National Veterinary School of Alfort, Maisons-Alfort (France)

Keywords: *L. monocytogenes*, Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment, Whole Genome Sequencing, Genotype-phenotype association, cold stress.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Intraspecific variability in the behavior of most foodborne pathogens is well characterized and introduced in Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA), but factors (strain origin, serotype,...) explaining these differences are scarce or contradictory between studies. Nowadays whole genome sequencing (WGS) offers new opportunities. Various bioinformatic tools already exist for the treatment of WGS-data of bacteria. Some of these analyses have the aim to compare DNA sequences from strains with the phenotypes of interest (stress survival, growth and or/ virulence) in order to find markers (e.g. absence/presence of plasmids, genes or variants) which are significantly associated with bacterial behaviors. The object of this study is to present and explore the various existing bioinformatic methods to correlate phenotype(s) and genotype(s).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

For this purpose, a data-set of 53 *L. monocytogenes* strains was used. The phenotypic variability of growth at low temperature was determined and whole genomes were sequenced with NextSeq Illumina Technology. Various tools for microbial genomics analyses using raw reads or genome assemblies as inputs were then applied.

RESULTS

Associations between presence/absence of known genes/plasmids and the phenotype of cold adaptation were explored. The variant-based phylogenetic inferences (at gene or whole genome level) were created and compared with the phenotypic dendrogram. Statistical indicators were computed to assess for similarity between these trees. Finally, the associations between all genes from the accessory genome and the phenotypic traits were explored. A list of genes sorted by strength of association with growth trait at low temperature was proposed.

The present genomic analyses were successfully used and applied on the chosen data-set.

CONCLUSIONS

An automatic workflow and more sophisticated statistical analyses will be developed based on this approach in order to be applied easily to other data sets.

Successful associating between WGS-data and specific phenotypes could contribute to better predicting microbial behaviors. Implementing this information in hazard identification and exposure assessment processes will open new possibilities to improve QMRA-models.

002.- MICROBIAL MODELLING COUPLING THE DYNAMICS OF DIFFUSED GASES AND MICROBIAL GROWTH IN MODIFIED ATMOSPHERE PACKAGING

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3 Department of Food Studies and Environmental Health, Faculty of Health Sciences, Msida, University of Malta

Keywords: dynamic modeling, modified atmosphere packaging, chicken fillets, *Pseudomonas*, CO₂, O₂, N₂ mixture

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Modified atmospheres (MA) packaging is widely used, to delay spoilage and extend the shelf life of fresh products such as poultry and fish fillets. Predicting microbial safety of fresh products in modified atmosphere packaging implies to take into account the dynamics of O₂, CO₂ and N₂ exchanges in the system and its effect on microbial growth. The bacteriostatic effect of CO₂ within MAP is primarily influenced by CO₂ absorption into the food. The same stands for O₂ especially when dealing with microaerophilic microorganisms. Therefore, microbial dynamics should be built taking into account the concentration of the dissolved gases.

In this paper a microbial model describing the dynamics of *Pseudomonas* spp. coupling diffused gas concentrations of CO₂ and O₂ is developed

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Previously published data of skinless chicken fillets stored in gaseous mixtures of 10%, 30%, 50%, 70% and 90% CO₂ balanced with N₂, 80:20% O₂:N₂ and 40:30:30% CO₂:O₂:N₂ and control conditions (air) at 20°C were used (Meredith et al., 2014). The carbon dioxide solubility was obtained by monitoring the changes in the headspace volume over time using a buoyancy technique and performing calculations based on volumetric measurements and the Henry's constant. Henry's constant was also used to estimate the oxygen solubility in the chicken fillets. The microbial model was built by extending the elementary model building block of the two first order differential equations for the Baranyi model (Baranyi and Roberts, 1994). The dependence of the maximum specific growth rate on the microbial adaptation, and the diffused CO₂ and O₂ concentrations were introduced.

A total of seven parameters were in the combined primary and secondary models: $\beta_1 = \mu_{opt}$ (1/day), optimal growth rate; $\beta_2 = CO_{2max-diss}$ (ppm), maximum concentration of CO₂ dissolved (ppm); $\beta_3 = O_{2ref}$, dissolved O₂ in water at 760mm HG, $\beta_4 = O_{2min}$, minimum O₂ concentration (ppm); $\beta_5 = N_{max}$, maximum microbial concentration (cfu/mL); $\beta_6 = N_0$, initial microbial concentration (cfu/mL); $\beta_7 = Q(0)$ (cfu/mL), parameter having to do with the microbial physiology

RESULTS

A plot of scaled sensitivity coefficients for the parameters revealed that only two parameters could be estimated. For each combination of gas mixtures, μ_{opt} and $CO_{2max-diss}$ were estimated from the dynamic data. The values of μ_{opt} ranged from 1.5 to 10.7 (1/day), increasing exponentially with N₂ concentration. The values of $CO_{2max-diss}$ ranged from 255 to 3100 ppm, decreasing linearly with N₂ concentration. The relative errors of the parameter estimates ranged from 0.38 to 10.5%. The RMSE of the fits of logN to time ranged from 0.27 to .71 log (cfu/mL) out of a 4-9 log scale.

CONCLUSIONS

These favourable parameter estimation results hold promise to develop more comprehensive models for global regression for commercially relevant dynamic data.

003.- ZERO-INFLATED REGRESSIONS FOR MODELLING MICROBIAL LOW PREVALENCE AND SAMPLING PERFORMANCE FOR FOODBORNE *PATHOGENS*

Ursula Gonzales-Barron¹, Marta Hernández², David Rodríguez-Lázaro³, Vasco Cadavez ¹, Antonio Valero⁴

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Keywords: zero inflated binomial, prevalence, poultry meat, markov chain MonteCarlo

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Microbial contamination of raw poultry meat could occur because of improper handling at primary production and slaughterhouse levels. Low microbial prevalence data often consists of a high amount of non-detections (zero positives), so a flexible framework is required to characterise the underlying microbial distribution and conduct reliable inferential statistics. Thus, the objective of this work was to evaluate the performance of zero-inflated binomial (ZIB) regression models to describe the effects of sampling site (carcass, thigh, breast, wings) on the measured incidences of *Salmonella*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus* on chicken meat. For this aim, a number of fixed- and random-effects models were evaluated and compared, while sampling performance based on mean prevalence estimates was assessed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Poultry samples were taken during three consecutive years from a Spanish slaughterhouse (36 sampled batches from 144 sampling periods). Analyses were carried following ISO methods for each pathogen taking 25 g samples from each site. Carcasses samples were collected before jointing, while thigh, breast and wings were sampled afterwards. For each pathogen, four ZIB models were fitted to the presence/absence data with sampling site as covariate and random-effects due to sampling occasion either in the binomial probability (p) or in the extra-proportion of zero counts (w_0). Models were fitted using the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) technique via WINBUGS 1.4.3.

RESULTS

The data sets of the three pathogens presented a high proportion of non-detections. While *Salmonella* spp. was the pathogen least frequently detected from poultry meat (90.9% non-detections), *L. monocytogenes* and *S. aureus* gave positive results slightly more often (14-15% detections); although in general the frequency of positive results were conditional upon the sampling site. For the three data sets, the sampling site exerted a greater effect on the extra proportion of non-detections than on the binomial prevalence itself, with breast bearing the lowest prevalence estimates of *Salmonella* spp. (mean: 0.0088; 95% CI: 0.0002-0.0195) and *S. aureus* (mean 0.0148; 95% CI: 0.0001-0.0400). The fitting capacity of the models was further improved when random effects due to sampling occasion were placed in the extra proportion of non-detections (deviances decreased from 146.7-156.7 to 140.2-140.6). At any sampling site (breast, carcass, thigh or wings), the mean prevalence was estimated as 0.0135 (95% CI: 0.0015 – 0.0270) for *Salmonella*, 0.0211 (95% CI: 0.0004 – 0.0563) for *L. monocytogenes* and 0.0236 (95% CI: 0.0004 – 0.0512) for *S. aureus*.

CONCLUSIONS

Under a ZIB assumption, most of the variability in the occurrence of pathogens on chicken meat was found to lie in the process producing the extra proportion of zero counts than in the binomial probability itself. With basis on an adequate description of microbial contamination, sampling procedures of poultry meat can be effectively addressed.

O04. - MEAT SPOILAGE PREDICTION MODELS USING FINGERPRINTING (*'OMICS,SURFACE CHEMISTRY*)IN TANDEM WITH AUTOMATED RANKING PLATFORM

Fady Mohareb¹, Stathis Panagou², George - John Nychas²

1 Cranfield University

2 Agricultural University of Athens

Keywords: machine learning, data mining, meat spoilage

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Over the past decade, analytical approaches based on vibrational spectroscopy, hyperspectral / multispectral imaging and biomimetic sensors started gaining popularity as rapid and efficient methods for predicting food microbial quality and safety

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Due to the multi-dimensional nature of the data generated from such analyses, the output needs to be coupled with a suitable statistical approach or machine-learning algorithms before the results can be interpreted. Choosing the optimum pattern recognition or machine learning approach for a given analytical platform is often challenging and involves a comparative analysis between various algorithms in order to achieve the best possible prediction accuracy.

RESULTS

In this work, "sorfML", a web-based application is presented, able to automate the procedure of identifying the best machine learning method for comparing data from several analytical techniques, to predict the counts of microorganisms responsible of meat spoilage regardless of the packaging system applied. In particular up to 7 regression methods were applied and these are ordinary least squares regression, stepwise linear regression, partial least square regression, principal component regression, support vector regression, random forest and k-nearest neighbours.

CONCLUSIONS

"sorfML" was tested with minced beef samples stored under aerobic and modified atmosphere packaging and analysed with electronic nose, HPLC, FT-IR, GC-MS and Multispectral imaging instrument. Population of total viable count, lactic acid bacteria, pseudomonads, Enterobacteriaceae and *B. thermosphacta*, were predicted. As a result, recommendations of which analytical platforms are suitable to predict each type of bacteria and which machine learning methods to use in each case were obtained.

11:00 - 13:00 h.: SESSION 2.- Predictive models and complex modelling approaches for food safety and quality

Chairs: Úrsula Gonzáles-Barrón (Polytechnic Institute of Bragança) and Anderson De Souza Sant`Ana (University of Campinas)

O05.- RAPID DETECTION OF MICROBIOLOGICAL QUALITY OF RAW MINCED BEEF BY MEANS OF ELECTRONIC NOSE AND MULTIVARIATE ANALYSIS

Dimitris Pavlidis, Stathis Panagou, George - John Nychas

Agricultural University of Athens

Keywords: Volatilomics, metabolomics, prediction of spoilage

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The type of meat spoilage depends on various factors, which support specific succession of the microbial association. The changes occurring in their metabolic profile during this process can be used to assess / predict microbial quality of meat. The aim of this study was to apply E-nose as a rapid tool for the early detection of microbiological spoilage of raw minced beef during storage at different temperatures and packaging conditions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Minced beef samples were stored aerobically and under Modified Atmosphere Packaging (80%O₂-20%CO₂) between 0-15oC until spoilage was evident. In parallel, independent meat batches were stored at 4o and 10oC isothermally and under dynamic temperature conditions. In both cases, samples were analyzed (i) microbiologically (Total Viable Counts-TVC, Pseudomonas spp., B. thermosphacta, lactic acid bacteria, Enterobacteriaceae and yeasts), and (ii) with E-nose using a 12 Metal Oxide Semiconductor (MOS) sensors system. Measurements obtained from e-nose were subjected to Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to visualize the results, while regression and classification supervised methods such as Partial Least Squares, Artificial Neural Networks and Support Vector Machines were applied to predict microbial counts and classify the samples into quality classes according to their microbiological load (fresh, semi-fresh, spoiled).

RESULTS

In total, 580 microbiological and e-nose data were collected. Results varied depending on the chemometric analysis employed and the microorganism under study. The Leave one out Cross validation method during model calibration yielded high classification rates with overall correct classification close to 90%. Contrary, the validation experiments at intermediate storage temperatures (4 and 10°C) and dynamic temperature profiles using different batches of meat presented lower performance, close to 80%. Furthermore, the mean values for bias and accuracy factors were calculated close to 1 and the RMSE was 0.63 and 0.75 for calibration and validation dataset, respectively. Lastly, about 90% of the predictions were found to be inside the relative error zone of ±20%. Qualitatively, LY2 sensors of the e-nose were correlated with fresh samples, P10/2 with semi-fresh, while all the others with spoiled meat.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study are encouraging for the early detection of microbiological quality of raw minced meat. More systematic implementation of this approach could be used alternatively to the time-consuming ISO method.

006.- MODELLING OF TTI SMART LABELS RESPONSE FOR MONITORING SHELF-LIFE AND *VIBRIO PARAHAEMOLYTICUS* RISK IN OYSTERS

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National Technical University of Athens School of Chemical Engineering, Laboratory of Food Chemistry and Technology

Keywords: Cold chain; Time temperature integrators; smart labels; oysters

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Time Temperature Integrators (TTI) indicate via an easily measurable response the temperature history of the food product. A TTI based system can be used for a realistic control of the chill chain and efficient shelf-life management, quality changes and risk assessment of bacterial growth. *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* (Vp) contamination of oysters may reach 60% in seasons of high prevalence and Vp growth might occur due to the current practice for oyster harvesting and transportation at ambient temperature. The objective was to evaluate the applicability of TTI smart labels for monitoring Vp risk in oysters during transportation at ambient conditions and shelf-life under refrigeration up to the consumer's level.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

TTI response based on a controlled enzymatic hydrolysis of a lipid substrate expressed as a pH dependent colour change of the solution (from green to yellow/orange and finally to red) was measured instrumentally with a CIELab colorimeter at isothermal and variable conditions (0-30°C). The parameters that allow targeted design of the response characteristics are the concentration of the enzyme (U) and the type of substrate. Oyster (*Grassostrea gigas*) flesh was inoculated with Vp and stored at isothermal and variable conditions (15-30°C). Vp load at predetermined times was estimated based on TTI response and was compared to experimentally measured numbers. Appropriate TTI was selected to fit to the predicted growth of three doublings of Vp in the range 15-30°C.

Aerobically packed, chucked oysters were stored at controlled isothermal and variable conditions (0-15°C). Spoilage bacteria load and sensory scoring at predetermined times were estimated and kinetically modeled. Temperature dependence of microbial growth was modeled using Arrhenius equation. Comparisons between the experimental and the predicted by the TTI quality indices were based on accuracy and bias factors and relative errors

RESULTS

A mathematical model for Vp growth in oysters was validated at 15-30°C and at variable conditions. The temperature effect on Vp growth rate was expressed by the activation energy ($E_a=78.9\text{kJ/mol}$). Spoilage of oysters during refrigeration was dominated by *Pseudomonas* spp. growth. Sensory rejection (score 5 for overall impression) and end of shelf-life coincided with a *Pseudomonas* spp. level of 6 logcfu/g. Shelf-life of oysters was estimated at 13, 8, 5 and 3 d at 0, 5, 10 and 15°C, respectively. A mathematical model which describes the effect of the enzyme concentration and the storage temperature on the response of the enzymatic TTI was developed ($E_a=143.4$ and 105.8kJ/mol for the range 0-15°C and 15-30°C, respectively)

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study indicate that the LP-200U (enzymatic TTI using a mixture of trilaurin-tripalmitin as substrate and 200 units of *Rhizopus oryzae* lipase) can be reliably used as predictive tool in validating improved handling, cooling procedures and recommended temperature during distribution and refrigerated storage of oysters.

007.- MODELING ADHESION AND BIOFILM FORMATION ON STAINLESS STEEL BY FIVE DIFFERENT SEROTYPES OF *SALMONELLA ENTERICA*

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Keywords: attachment; foodborne pathogen; sessile cells; surfaces

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The ability of Salmonella to form biofilms enhances its survival in food-contact surfaces and food processing environments increasing risks of salmonellosis outbreaks. The aim of this study was to develop models to predict the probability of adhesion and biofilm formation by Salmonella enterica serovars, namely S. Enteritidis, S. Infantis, S. Typhimurium, S. Heidelberg and S. Corvallis on stainless steel surfaces.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 480 different combinations of NaCl (0, 2, 4, 5, 6 and 8, 10% w/v), pH (4, 5, 6 and 7) and temperatures (8° C, 12° C, 20° C and 35° C) were performed. The bacterial suspension (6 log CFU/mL) of each test strain was grown in stainless steel (ASI 304) surfaces (2 x 2 x 0.2 cm) immersed in Tryptic soy broth under the experimental conditions over a period of 48 h. The sessile cells on surfaces were assessed using viable counts procedure. Salmonella counts > 3 and ≤ 5 log CFU/cm² were used to assign adhesion and those > 5 log CFU/cm² were used to consider biofilm formation. When adhesion/biofilm formation was observed a value of 1 was assigned to the condition studied whereas 0 was assigned when no adhesion/biofilm formation was observed. The binary responses obtained in adhesion/biofilm formation experiments were fitted to the logistic regression model to predict probabilities of adhesion/biofilm formation by each Salmonella serovar.

RESULTS

The capability for adhesion/biofilm formation under the experimental conditions studied varied among the serovars. In general, the probability of adhesion decreased when NaCl concentrations were > 8% and in temperatures < 8 °C. Adhesion was reduced at pH values ≤ 5 and NaCl concentrations < 6%. At pH 7 and 6, biofilm production was observed up to 6% of NaCl at 35 °C and/or 20 °C, however S. Corvallis was able to form biofilm in the presence of 8% of NaCl at 35 °C and 8 °C. The probability of biofilm formation decreased at pH values ≤ 5 and NaCl concentrations higher than 2% and at temperatures lower than 12 °C.

CONCLUSIONS

The secondary models obtained can feasibly predict the adhesion and biofilm formation by Salmonella on stainless steel and highlight the variability amongst the different Salmonella serovars studied.

O08.- EXTENSIVE CARDINAL PARAMETER MODEL TO PREDICT GROWTH OF PSEUDOMONADS IN SALT-REDUCED LIGHTLY PRESERVED SEAFOOD

Veronica Martinez-Rios, Paw Dalgaard

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Keywords: organic acids, product development

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Interest in and demand for preserved seafood with reduced salt/sodium content is increasing. As a consequence of the reduced salt content potential growth of psychrotolerant pseudomonads to unacceptable high concentration where they cause product spoilage is an increasing challenge. Innovation is needed to reformulate these salt-reduced products and this must be done in such a way that other product characteristics compensate for less inhibiting effect due to salt. Numerous simple predictive models are available to predict growth of pseudomonads in foods at different temperatures. A few models include the effect of temperatures and salt. However, these simple secondary models do not include the effect of a broader range of product characteristics and therefore they cannot be used to predict how the inhibiting effect of salt can be replaced by changes in other environmental factors.

The objective was to develop an extensive predictive model that allows growth of psychrotolerant pseudomonads to be predicted in brined and marinated seafood with a range of different organic acids

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The new model was developed by expanding an existing cardinal parameter-type model for growth of pseudomonads in dairy products and including terms for temperature, pH, aw/NaCl, lactic- and sorbic acids (Martinez-Rios et al., Int. J. Food Microbiol. 216. 110-120, 2016). MIC-values for acetic-, benzoic- and citric acids were determined in broth and terms modelling their antimicrobial effect were added to the model. The new and expanded model included eight environmental factors and their interactive effects. The new model was evaluated under constant and dynamic temperature conditions using challenge tests and storage trials with a total of 78 growth curves in well characterized seafoods including lumpfish roe and brined shrimps

RESULTS

Average bias and accuracy factor values were 1.07 and 1.20 for 69 growth curves at constant temperatures. For nine growth curves at dynamic temperatures 77 % of the growth data (log cfu/g) was within the acceptable simulation zone of +/- 0.5 log cfu/g. The new model can be used to facilitate product reformulation as shown here for brined shrimps at 8°C, pH of 5.8 and water phase organic acid concentrations of 3000 ppm (citric), 1200 ppm (benzoic) and 500 ppm (sorbic). When the water phase salt concentration in this product is reduced from 3% to 1% growth of psychrotolerant pseudomonads change from none in 42 days to > 7 log cfu/g increase in 8 days. However, by including 500 ppm of acetic acid the reformulated prevent growth of psychrotolerant pseudomonads

CONCLUSIONS

The high number of environmental factors included in the new model makes it flexible and suitable to support product development as the effect of substituting one combination of preservatives with another can be predicted.

009.- THE PROPAGATION OF UNCERTAINTY FROM DATA TO PREDICTIONS

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Keywords: Modelling, uncertainty propagation, kinetic models

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Although there is an increasing interest in the use of individual based models and systems biology approaches in predictive microbiology, the models that are used in practice are still mostly grey box models including only a very limited amount of mechanistic knowledge. These models are built using experimental datasets that are commonly characterised by relatively high variability on the measurements, uncertainty on the experimental conditions and limited data. These characteristics should be taken into consideration when building mathematical models in predictive microbiology to achieve the desired accuracy on the model predictions. Therefore, this study is focused on the propagation of variability and uncertainty throughout the model building procedure from data gathering to model predictions. As a case study, a modelling exercise is considered in which the aim is the prediction of the growth of a microbial population as a function of time and temperature.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

To quantify the propagation of variance throughout the modelling procedure, the traditional techniques based on the model parameter variance-covariance matrix and the Monte Carlo method are tested. Moreover, advanced techniques like the unscented transformation (sigma points approach) and (non-intrusive) polynomial chaos expansion are exploited.

RESULTS

As the focus of this study is on the description of the exponential growth rate, the primary model was simplified to a linear description of the logarithm of the population density as a function of time. Because the effect of temperature on the microbial growth rate has been studied extensively in predictive microbiology, the structure of the secondary model for the effect of temperature is assumed to be known. Such models are identified based on datasets at various constant or dynamic temperatures. However, the experimental and sampling conditions are affected by uncertainty and the microbial behaviour by variability. This variance affects the identification of the model, the predictions that are made and even the estimated prediction uncertainty. The analysis also compares the use of a 1-step and 2-step parameter estimation procedure with respect to the model output uncertainty.

CONCLUSIONS

This study is an important step in achieving a better understanding of the effect of experimental uncertainty and variability on the prediction quality of mathematical models used to guarantee microbial food safety and quality.

O10.- MODELLING AND IDENTIFICATION OF RELEVANT PATHWAYS FOR NUCLEOTIDE DEGRADATION IN FRESH HAKE DURING STORAGE

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Keywords: Fish quality; Mechanistic model; Bacterial growth; Nucleotide degradation

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The K-index is a largely employed indicator for fish quality that relates different ATP derived products. The first steps of ATP degradation occur within hours from the moment of fish dead. In this regard, the relevant components during most of storage time are Inosine Monophosphate (IMP), Inosine (Ino) and Hypoxanthine (Hx).

The aim of this work is to identify and model the relevant pathways for IMP degradation in hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) during storage. One important part of the work is to study the contribution of spoilage bacteria to the degradation process as they are known to catalyze some of the involved reactions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

IMP, Ino, Hx were measured by reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography during storage. Two bacterial genera are studied: Pseudomonas counts are determined from the colonies grown on GSP agar plates after incubation at 25 C during 48 h, whereas Shewanella counts are obtained from the number of black colonies formed on IAL after 3 to 5 days of incubation at 17 C.

Sterile juice of fish muscle is used to understand enzymatic degradation without the effect of bacteria. Once the model for enzymatic degradation is obtained, non-sterilized fish dorsal muscle is used to study the contribution of bacteria to the process.

Bacterial growth is described using the standard logistic model with the square-root model to take into account the temperature effect. Nucleotide degradation is assumed to follow first order kinetics with Arrhenius-type temperature dependence.

Model parameters are determined by minimizing the log-likelihood function between model response and experimental data. An optimization algorithm that combines local and global methods is used to find the optimal parameters.

RESULTS

We compared the relevance of all possible routes for the enzymatic degradation using the Akaike criteria. The method selects the best model penalizing those with more unknown parameters. Results show that only a few routes are relevant: transformation of IMP into: (i) Ino; (ii) Hx; and (iii) other products and transformation of Ino into Hx.

On the other hand, we estimated the parameters in the bacterial growth model using the techniques presented in the previous section.

Both models, bacterial and enzymatic degradation, were combined showing, after new parameter estimations, that bacteria mainly act in the transformation of IMP into Ino and Ino into Hx. The final model derived was in good agreement with the experimental data.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have derived a model describing the nucleotide degradation in fresh hake. Such model reproduces the experimental behavior under variable temperature profiles and can be used to forecast quality loss during storage. It also reveals that a pathway usually overlooked in the literature is relevant for describing nucleotide degradation in hake.

O11.- IMPACT OF NATURAL DIVERSITY IN HEAT RESISTANCE OF *BACTERIAL* CELLS AND SPORES ON SAFETY AND QUALITY

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Keywords: variability sporeformers pathogens spoilage organisms

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Heat treatment is widely used during food processing and aims to eliminate spoilage microorganisms and pathogens in food products. Efficacy of control of microorganisms is however challenged by natural diversity between strains and species with respect to their heat robustness. Quantification of microbiological variability allows for realistic predictions of reduction of microorganisms by heat treatments. This study aims to compare various sources of microbiological variability for a broad range of bacterial species, including sporeforming and non-sporeforming pathogens and spoilage organisms.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The heat resistance properties of spores of the spoilage organisms *Bacillus subtilis* and *Geobacillus stearothermophilis* and the foodborne pathogen *Bacillus cereus* were characterized for eighteen to twenty strains per species. In addition, reproduction variability was determined using two biologically independent spore crops for each strain, which were heat treated on different days. A similar approach was followed for two non-sporeforming organisms, namely, the foodborne pathogen *Listeria monocytogenes* and the spoilage organism *Lactobacillus plantarum*. For the latter two species, 20 strains were used as well to quantify strain variability, and heat inactivation experiments were reproduced independently using freshly prepared cultures to quantify reproduction variability. This allowed for comparison of variability in spore heat resistance between and within the different species, and also between spore-forming bacteria and non-sporeforming bacteria. Moreover, a meta-analysis on heat resistance was performed for each species to quantify the overall variability in heat resistance per species and to benchmark microbiological variability.

RESULTS

Strain variability was surprisingly rather similar among the five species, and this variability factor was much higher than reproduction variability for all five species. Reproduction variability was higher for heat resistance of spores than for vegetative cells, indicating that spore production using a standardized approach introduced more variability in heat resistance than preparation of standardized vegetative cell cultures. The meta-analysis on heat resistance of the sporeforming species and non-sporeforming bacteria demonstrated that strain variability explained at least 50% of all variability in heat resistance as found in literature, due to a plethora of causes.

CONCLUSIONS

This comparison and benchmarking of variability factors showed that strain variability is a crucial variability factor to be included in risk assessment to realistically predict shelf life and safety of food products. Scenario analysis using various safe harbour processes highlighted the significance of strain variability when compared to other relevant sources of variability encountered in the food production chain such as variability in process parameters.

012.- MODELING ADHESION ON POLYPROPYLENE AND GLASS SURFACES BY DISTINCT *SALMONELLA* SEROVARS

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Keywords: attachment; glass; Salmonella serovars; prediction, foodborne pathogen, adherence, surfaces

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Bacterial adhesion is the prior stage in biofilm formation. The continuous attachment of the bacterial cells to the surface followed by their growth and production of expolysaccharide form the biofilm. Thus, the best strategy for controlling the biofilm formation is to prevent the cell adhesion on surfaces. Polypropylene is a low cost material largely used in household and industrial itens that has been cited as a material that favors the bacterial adhesion, while glass has been reported as a material of low-bacterial adhesion. The aim of this study was to develop models to predict the probability of adhesion by Salmonella Enteritidis, S. Infantis, S. Typhimurium, S. Heidelberg and S. Corvallis on polypropylene and glass surfaces.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 960 different conditions based on combination of pH values (4.0, 5.0, 6.0 and 7.0), NaCl concentration (0.0%, 2.0%, 4.0%, 6.0%, 8.0%, 10.0% w / v) and temperature (8 °C, 12 °C, 20 °C and 35 °C) were assayed. The bacterial suspension (6 log CFU/mL) of each test strain was growth in the surfaces (2 x 2 x 0.2 cm) immersed in Tryptic Soy broth under the experimental conditions over a period of 48 h. After the incubation period, the surfaces were removed from the growth medium, washed twice with sterile saline solution and the non-adhered cell in the rinsed solution were assessed using viable counts procedure. Salmonella counts > 3 and ≤ 5 log CFU/cm² were used to assign adhesion. When adhesion were observed a value of 1 was assigned to the condition studied whereas 0 was assigned when no adhesion was observed. The binary responses obtained in adhesion experiments were fitted to the logistic regression model to predict probabilities of adhesion by each Salmonella strain.

RESULTS

The capability for adhesion under the experimental conditions studied varied among the strain tested. In glass, the probability of adhesion decreased when pH values were ≤ 5, NaCl concentrations were ≥ 8% and in temperatures of 8 °C. At pH 7 and 6, adhesion was observed up to 8% of NaCl at 35 °C and/or 20 °C, except for S. Enteritidis that showed adhesion up to 6% of NaCl at 35 °C. In polypropylene, the cell adhesion of all strains was reduced at pH 4 and 5. At pH 4, adhesion was observed for S. Infantis, S. Heidelberg and S. Corvallis up to 2% of NaCl at 20 °C. At 20 °C and 35 °C, adhesion was observed for all strains in concentrations of 6% NaCl at pH 6 and 7, while only S. Infantis and S. Corvallis showed adhesion in pH 7 up to 8% of NaCl at 35 °C.

CONCLUSIONS

The secondary models obtained are suitable to predict the adhesion by the Salmonella test strains on polypropylene and glass and show variability amongst the different Salmonella serovars studied.

14:30 - 16:00 h.: SESSION 3.- Individual-based models

Chairs: Kostas Koutsoumanis (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki) and Pablo Fernández (Technical University of Cartagena)

O13.- DESCRIBING TIME-TO-INACTIVATION OF BACTERIAL POPULATION, USING INDIVIDUAL CELL HETEROGENEITY, VIA COMPUTER SIMULATION

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Keywords: probability model

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Deterministic first-order survival kinetics model does not account for estimation of uncertainty of bacterial population behaviour caused by individual cell heterogeneity. Although thermal death time based on decimal log-reduction time has been introduced and widely used, thermal death time will be determined by extrapolation of D-value. Thermal death time based on first-order survival kinetics model is not enough for reliable estimation of bacterial survivors of inactivation treatment, because of variation of bacterial population behaviour. Describing randomly occurring individual cell heterogeneity would enable to propose more realistic estimation of time-to-inactivation of bacterial population than that estimated from thermal death time. In the present study, we aimed to estimate time-to-inactivation of bacterial population, using randomly occurring individual cell heterogeneity, via computer simulation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Computer simulation of bacterial inactivation was conducted using 10^9 virtual individual bacterial cells. Various parameters such as number of initial cells, inactivation rate, and type of inactivation curve were examined in the bacterial survival simulation. In one condition, 100 replicates of bacterial inactivation were conducted and time-to-inactivation of bacterial population was presented as a histogram, which was then fitted by gamma distribution. Death probability of bacterial population was described as a cumulative gamma distribution. In addition, thermal death time based on a first-order survival kinetics model was compared with the estimated time-to-inactivation of bacterial population. All statistical analyses were conducted using R statistical environment.

RESULTS

In all the tested conditions, the time-to-inactivation and the death probability of bacterial population was successfully described as a gamma and a cumulative gamma distribution, respectively. As the inactivation rate slowed, the mean value and variance of time-to-inactivation increased regardless of the type of curve. Likewise, as the number of initial cells increased, the mean value of time-to-inactivation increased regardless of the type of the survival curve. In contrast, the variance of time-to-inactivation depended on the types of inactivation curve. For example, as the number of initial cells increased, variance of time-to-inactivation also increased on curves with upward concavity, was constant on linear survival curves, and decreased on curves with downward concavity, in a semi-logarithmic plot. Overall, the time-to-inactivation of bacterial population we estimated considering individual cell heterogeneity was shorter than those estimated from the first-order survival kinetics model.

CONCLUSIONS

We described time-to-inactivation of bacterial population as gamma distribution and developed a new index of time-to-inactivation regardless of any curvature. We successfully estimated time-to-inactivation regardless of the type of curve, which has not been estimated by D-value.

O14.- ESTIMATING BACTERIAL POPULATION GROWTH RATES FROM FLOW CYTOMETRY

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Keywords: Individual-based models, flow cytometry, parameter estimation, bacterial growth rate.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Bacterial growth kinetic studies constitute the classical approach to a quantitative description. These typically demand a high number of extensive and time-consuming experiments. Model parameters are obtained from the corresponding cell concentrations vs. time curves by system identification methods.

Alternatively, we propose a new fast method to estimate population growth rates in bacterial cultures, which take advantage of the relationship between individual and population bacterial growth rates and the use of flow cytometry.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The method is based on the observation that individual bacterial growth and division follows an individual-based model related to a stochastic size-related variable (Alonso et al. 2014). In addition, the corresponding probability distribution obeys a modified Fokker-Plank equation (Gardiner, 2009) parameterized by the individual growth rate, which in average coincides with the population growth rate.

At the exponential stage of growth, it can be shown that such distribution becomes stationary and can be used to estimate the population growth rate by a simple least squares method which minimizes the differences between the distribution and the stationary Fokker-Plank equation.

The methodology was tested using Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923. Standard bacterial colony counting and optical dispersion reading at 600nm were used to follow bacteria growth curve. We compared the growth rate at 37°C using high and low glucose Tryptic soy broth. At different discrete time points of the bacterial growth, aliquots were analysed in the cytometer (BD LSR Fortessa), in which the side- and forward- side scatter (SSC and FSC) values, and hoescht 33342 fluorescence were recorded to assess both bacteria size and DNA content distribution, respectively. Size calibration beads were used in order to correlate the SSC data with bacterial size and plot the size distribution at each cell growth conditions and time point.

RESULTS

The performance of the cytometry-based method to estimate growth rates at the exponential phase was compared with standardized bacterial growth methods: counting of viable colonies over time and optical dispersion measurements at 600 nm. A homogeneous bacterial culture of *Staphylococcus aureus* was used as cell model and its growth at 37°C under different bacterial substrate conditions were analysed. Good agreement was found in the rates obtained by both methods, being the cytometry-based much faster as it only requires one measurement of the bacterial size distributio

CONCLUSIONS

Individual based modeling and flow cytometry has been combined to estimate macroscopic growth rates in bacterial cultures from mesoscopic bacterial size distributions. The method provides a quick in-line way of obtaining relevant growth model parameters under different environmental conditions without the need of long and tiresome kinetic studies. Biotechnology industries and quality control departments would greatly benefit from this methodology.

O15.- UNDERSTANDING AND PREDICTING MICROBIAL BEHAVIOR AT THE BOUNDARIES BETWEEN GROWTH, SURVIVAL AND DEATH

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Keywords: Salmonella, individual cells, growth/survival/death interface

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Most available predictive models concentrate mainly on the dynamics of microbial populations at growth or lethal environments. Less quantitative information however, is available for the microbial behavior at the boundaries between growth, survival and death. The objective of the present work was to evaluate and model the effect of such intermediate environmental conditions on the kinetic behavior of individual bacterial cells.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The behavior of *Salmonella enterica* ser. Agona individual cells at various NaCl conditions from 0.5 to 26% was monitored using time-lapse microscopy. Cell division and growth was monitored by phase-contrast microscopy using a z-monitored microscope equipped with a $\times 100$ objective (Olympus) and a high-resolution device camera (Olympus DP71). The quality of the images was improved by developing an auto focus procedure with an Extended Depth of Focus (EDF) system using the ScopePro module of ImageProPlus software. Each final image was a result of 10-20 images captured in different z-axis planes. The EDF system allowed the combination of the z-stack images of multi-level focal planes into a single in-focus image. single cell inactivation of *Salmonella enterica* ser. Agona was studied using an inverted confocal laser scanning microscope. Direct monitoring of cell death was achieved with the time-lapse method and the use of Propidium Iodide (PI), a fluorescent nucleic acid dye that is permeant only in cells with damaged membrane thus, enabling the discrimination between dead and alive cells. The cells of the pathogen were surface plated on solid laboratory medium, where micro-colonies were formed, and then covered with the inactivation solution containing PI. A sequence of frames for the selected micro-colony with time was obtained, allowing the monitoring of each cell inactivation, through time-lapse videos. With the aid of an in-house program, the coverage of the cell surface with PI was estimated and, after defining the threshold value for cell coverage corresponding to cellular death, the individual cell time of inactivation was calculated

RESULTS

The results showed a highly heterogeneous behavior. As NaCl concentration increased, the number of cells able to grow decreased and the distributions of the first and second division time were sifted to higher values and became wider. At NaCl concentrations close to the boundary of growth (5-6 %) individual cell within the population were observed to be into a growing, surviving and dying fraction at the same time. A time-lapse video demonstrated the evolution of the three fractions with time. As conditions became more lethal all cells were shifted to the dying fraction, the inactivation time of individual cells decreased and became less variable. The data on individual cell behavior were used to model the dynamics of *Salmonella* populations at the boundaries between growth, survival and death. The model simulation results showed that at such conditions microbial behavior is characterized by the "phoenix phenomenon" where a decline in viable-cell numbers is followed by growth. Validation experiments confirmed the prediction of the model.

CONCLUSIONS

At stressful environments the behavior of individual cells is highly variable and cells can be into a growing, surviving and dying fraction at the same time. This heterogeneity may result in population dynamics characterized by the "phoenix phenomenon".

O16.- VARIABILITY OF GERMINATION AND OUTGROWTH OF INDIVIDUAL BACTERIAL SPORES. PHENOMENOLOGICAL AND MECHANISTIC ASPECTS

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Keywords: Distribution, Monte Carlo, spore, germinant receptors, spore channel, risk assessment.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Spoilage and in many cases food poisoning are mainly determined by elements of lag time and growth rate of the microorganism. Particularly lag time is often subjected to large variability. Reliable lag time data are becoming more available thanks to advanced techniques to study single cells. Based on microscopic studies of *Bacillus subtilis* spores Pandey et al (Thesis University of Amsterdam 2014) could measure the fate of individual spores in all stages from germination to cell division. Thus a better prediction of spoilage risk could be achieved by a description of different environmental conditions on the variability of every stage.

A further development is a mathematical description of germination time in relation to the number of germinant receptor proteins per cell (C. Koster manuscript in preparation). Both developments will be presented and the relevance to quantitative risk assessment will be explained.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

1.1. Microbiology. In most cases spores of *Bacillus subtilis* 168 wild type strain 1A700 (trpC2) were used. Image analysis was conducted by Pandey (Thesis 2014).

2.2. Data handling. Data bases were made in Microsoft Excel. The Excel files were inserted in 'R' and all subsequent manipulations such as fitting and merging statistical distributions were done in 'R' using Monte Carlo simulations. Ignoring variability of growing cells, further development could be described by all numbers of vegetative cells together originating from individual spores.

3.1 Mechanistic modelling. Based on quantitative data on receptor proteins per spore, a mathematical model is presented showing the sequence of events when activated GR proteins are transduced to SpoVA proteins that would eventually lead to germination through release of dipicolinic acid. A set of differential equations was formulated to predict germination.

RESULTS

A model has been proposed based on observed concentrations of Ger molecules in the inner spore membrane combined with the possibility of SpoVA channels that can be reversibly opened and closed. A reliable mathematic description of that model could be made. This model could be made in line with the descriptive model obtained by convolution of the distributions of various developmental stages eventually leading to a full grown culture. The latter model can form the base for secondary models that include temperature, pH, salt or preservatives.

CONCLUSIONS

Whereas in many instances the purely descriptive microbiology of whole microbial populations is satisfactory, live imaging of single cells has great potential for quantitative microbiological risk-assessment. Knowledge of the mechanism of germination will be an aid for formulating mild preservation conditions.

O17.- BEHAVIOR OF INDIVIDUAL *SALMONELLA AGONA* CELLS SUBMITTED TO MILD STRESS: THE CASE OF SODIUM HYPOCHLORITE

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Keywords: single cell, salmonella, sanitizer

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The environment of a food processing plant is inevitably contaminated with microorganisms. Since this statement is an inexorable truth, food industries must adopt rigid protocols for cleaning and sanitizing their facilities. Different classes of sanitizers are used in order to achieve acceptable levels of contamination. Among them, sodium hypochlorite is one of the most used in Brazilian food industries, with concentrations varying from 10 to 400 ppm. When sanitation protocols are unsatisfactory, pathogens viable cells may survive and become more resistant to further treatments. Traditional inactivation studies focus mainly in populations as whole, not taking in account individual cells. Indeed, if, for instance, the consequences of unacceptable levels of a surviving pathogen in a food after processing are grave, the knowledge only of the mean population decline is unlikely to be a sufficient basis for processing design. This work aims to understand the kinetic behavior of *Salmonella Agona* single cells after being submitted to various concentrations of sodium hypochlorite

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Time-lapse videos can provide the necessary information about describing single cell behavior and incorporating heterogeneity of resistance to stresses. Based on the single cell approach, cells of *Salmonella* were submitted to different concentrations of sodium hypochlorite for 3 minutes, centrifuged in order to reduce the sanitizer effect and then plated on TSA in slide, and forwarded to microscopic analysis based on single cell approach.

RESULTS

The results of ongoing experiments shows that at low concentrations of the sanitizer, most of cells are able to divide and form colonies. When the concentration is increased, the percentage of dividing cells drops to considerably, also increasing the time for first division generally.

CONCLUSIONS

The data provided by this research may be used as a guiding tool for the improvement of existing sanitation protocols and the development of new ones based on the variability of individual cells.

O18.- INDIVIDUAL BASED MODELING OF COOPERATIVE INTERACTIONS IN BIOFILMS

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Keywords: Biofilm - Individual based Modeling - Microbial ecology

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Out of all forms of microbial life, biofilms could be the most challenging to understand, predict and control. They are complex bacterial communities that live attached to a surface in a protective polymeric matrix. Consequently, biofilms lie at the root of many food contamination problems due to the difficulty of preventing their growth on food processing surfaces. Cooperation between cells has been highlighted as a factor to many of the growth-related processes observed in a biofilm. For example, the production of extracellular enzymes which help to break down nutrients in the interest of the cellular community. Yet, cooperative strains face competition with cheater strains that do not participate in producing such public resources while exploiting them. Hence, we here investigate the conditions under which cooperation flourishes in a biofilm by constructing an individual based model of the competition between cooperative and cheater strains in a bacterial biofilm. We focus on the effects of diffusivity of the polymeric matrix, mixing and existence of other bacterial species on the relative fitness of the two strains. Understanding how cooperative interactions arise and perturb in biofilms is a key step to unravel the mechanisms behind their growth.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A 2D model in which two strains, cooperative and cheater, grow in a biofilm is implemented using Repast Symphony toolkit. The processes of growth, division and death are described on the cell level. Additionally, cooperative cells allocate part of their energy to produce an extracellular enzyme that boosts the growth of surrounding cells. Firstly, a series of in silico experiments is conducted to investigate the effects of varying the diffusivity coefficient in the biofilm. Furthermore, effects of mixing between the two strains is simulated by inoculating the model with mixed versus segregated cells. Finally, we investigate the relative fitness of the two focal strains in a biofilm dominated by another bacterial species by inoculating the model with high density of a distinct species in addition to the two focal strains. We are interested in how the characteristics of the new species influence the competition between cooperative and cheater cells of the former species.

RESULTS

Simulations confirmed that in case of low diffusivities of the matrix, the cooperative strain can outperform its cheater counterpart, as the beneficial effects of the secreted enzyme become constrained to the producing cells. Segregation between cell lineages has been found to enhance this effect while mixed biofilms gave the advantage to the cheater strain. Lastly, interestingly, it is found that the existence of a cooperative strain of one bacterial species promotes the growth of cooperative strains in other bacterial species existing at proximity.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on our results, we hypothesize that cooperative strains of different bacterial species will dominantly coexist in communities where they indirectly mutually benefit each other.

16:30 - 18:00 h.: SESSION 4.- Modelling microbial dynamics in relation to food microstructure and the impact of microbiological interaction in foods

Chairs: Marcel Zwietering (Wageningen University) and Antonio Valero (University of Cordoba)

O19.- MODELLING THE MICROBIAL DYNAMICS & AMR DEVELOPMENT OF *LISTERIA* IN FOOD MODEL SYSTEMS OF DIFFERENT STRUCTURAL COMPLEXITY

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Keywords: Listeria, Antimicrobial Resistance, Solid(like) systems, predictive modelling, food microstructure

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Recent studies have reported an increase in antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Listeria* species isolated from the environment. Most of the available studies on the AMR of *Listeria* are conducted in liquid systems. However, *Listeria* can be found in solid or solid (like) food systems, i.e., soft cheeses, ice-cream, meat products, vegetables etc. Cells grown in a solid system grow in colonies and experience a completely different environment as compared to planktonic growth which takes place in liquid. More specifically, in a solid system microorganisms evolve as colonies and due to diffusional limitations of oxygen and nutrients as well as due to the accumulation of acidic metabolic products around the colony micro-organisms may experience a shelf-induced (acid) stress that could affect their overall kinetics and environmental response. Furthermore, the microorganisms could develop a different level of AMR development. Therefore, in order to achieve a fundamental understanding of the AMR development of *Listeria* in food systems it is important to conduct kinetic experiments in model systems that mimic as accurately as possible the microstructure of solid or solid (like) food systems.

The present work is a systematic comparative study of the kinetics of surface and/or immersed growth of *Listeria* as influenced by the presence of nisin, i.e., a natural antimicrobial produced by lactic acid bacteria, in solid (like) systems of different structural complexity.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Listeria innocua was grown in liquid (planktonic cells) (TSB) or in (immersed colonies) or on (surface colonies) solid matrices of different composition and internal structure (TSB + xanthan gum, TSB + whey protein, TSB + xanthan gum + whey protein) and in mono- or in co-culture with LAB NZ9700, i.e., nisin producer, or LAB NZ9800, i.e., knock-out strain not producing nisin, at 37°C. Microbial growth curves were compared for all the conditions under study.

RESULTS

The growth kinetics, i.e., lag and/or exponential growth rates and/or stationary phase of *Listeria* were affected by the internal structure of the solid (like) matrices and were different to the liquid. Furthermore, the action of nisin on *Listeria* was different depending on the composition of the gel as well as on the type of growth (immersed/vs surface).

CONCLUSIONS

Our findings give a systematic quantitative insight on the impact of nisin on the growth of *Listeria* in liquid and solid model systems of different structural complexity and point out the importance of taking into consideration the bacterial stress adaptation in solid state when designing decontamination processes with natural antimicrobials (such as nisin).

O20.- GENERIC GLOBAL REGRESSION MODELS FOR GROWTH PREDICTION OF *SALMONELLA* IN GROUND PORK AND PORK CUTS

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Keywords: Salmonella, meat structure, meat pH, storage temperature, one-step regression, growth kinetics, ground meat, surface growth

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Models for the prediction of bacterial growth in fresh pork are primarily developed using two-step regression (i.e. primary models followed by secondary models). These models are also generally based on experiments in liquids or ground meat and neglect surface growth. It has been shown that one-step global regressions can result in more accurate models and that bacterial growth on intact surfaces can substantially differ from growth in liquid culture.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We used a global-regression approach to develop predictive models for the growth of *Salmonella* for three pork matrices: on the surface of shoulder (neck) and hind part (ham), and in ground pork. We conducted five experimental trials and inoculated essentially sterile pork pieces with a *Salmonella* cocktail (n = 192). Inoculated meat was aerobically incubated at 4 °C, 7 °C, 12 °C, and 16 °C for 96 h. One part of obtained log-transformed cell counts was used for model development and another for model validation. The Ratkowsky square root model and the relative lag time (RLT) model were integrated into the logistic model with delay. Fitted parameter estimates were compared to investigate the effect of meat structure on bacterial growth and goodness-of-fit was evaluated by root mean squared errors (RMSE). We used the Acceptable Simulation Zone (ASZ) approach and cross-validation with model-independent data to investigate if generic predictive models could accurately describe microbial growth across all studied pork products and compared our models to already existing generic models.

RESULTS

Our results indicated that the growth of *Salmonella* was affected by product characteristics such as pH and structure, but storage temperature was shown to be the only variable needed to predict growth independent of pH and structural differences. RMSE of 0.54 suggested acceptable goodness-of-fit for the *Salmonella* generic growth model. Model evaluations of the generic growth model showed that described growth responses on pork neck and in ground pork were highly accurate with 86 and 98% of all model-independent observations within the ASZ, respectively. Although growth descriptions showed less accuracy in the case of pork ham, a fail safe model could still be developed. Model evaluation also showed that our model performed better than generic existing models.

CONCLUSIONS

We suggested that generic model with fewer variables might provide a more suitable approach to bacterial growth modeling in fresh pork if pH and the type of pork product are unknown. Our study provides a "ready-to-use" global regression model relevant for a wide range of time and temperature combinations and various fresh pork products. The model should be a useful tool to control growth of *Salmonella* in meat and set critical limits for temperature during production and storage of fresh pork.

O21.- MODELLING EFFECTS OF FOOD CHARACTERISTICS ON INTERACTION BETWEEN LACTIC ACID BACTERIA AND *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES*

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Keywords: Competition factor; Expanded Jameson effect model

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

High concentrations of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) can reduce growth and survival of *Listeria monocytogenes* in food and this has an important effect on food safety for numerous products. To accurately predict growth of *L. monocytogenes* the inhibiting effect of LAB must be taken into account for many of the products where LAB grows to high concentrations. Several primary models are available to describe simultaneous growth of LAB and *L. monocytogenes*. This includes the expanded Jameson effects model where the competition factor (CF) describes how high LAB concentrations reduce growth of *L. monocytogenes* ($0 < CF < 1$); stops growth of *L. monocytogenes* ($CF = 1$) or inactivate *L. monocytogenes* ($CF > 1$). Values of CF may depend on food product characteristics and storage conditions and a secondary model may be required to describe these effects as for other kinetic parameters in primary growth models.

The inhibiting effect of high LAB concentrations on *L. monocytogenes* is well established but it remains very little studied how this interaction effect depends on food product characteristics and storage conditions. The objective of the present study was therefore to evaluate the effect of product characteristics and storage conditions on values of CF in the expanded the Jameson effect model

MATERIAL AND METHODS

87 datasets were collected from previously published studies of dairy, fish and meat products. Each dataset included the simultaneous growth of LAB and *L. monocytogenes* as well as quantitative environmental conditions including temperature, atmosphere, salt/aw, pH, organic acids and smoke components. Furthermore, the LAB microbiota was described as specific species e.g. for protective cultures or as naturally occurring LAB. For each dataset the value of CF was determined by fitting of the expanded Jameson effect model to data for simultaneous growth of LAB and *L. monocytogenes*. Multiple linear regression was used to identify the environmental factors or types of LAB that had a significant effect on CF

RESULTS

Fitted CF-values were in the range from 0.0 to 2.5 with a mean value of 0.9. Overall food product characteristics and storage conditions had a strongly significant effect on CF-values. More specifically acetic acid concentration, benzoic acid concentration and CO₂ concentration in modified atmosphere packed products significantly influenced the CF-values ($P < 0.05$). Furthermore, the type of LAB significantly influenced CF-values ($P < 0.001$). A simple linear model was used to describe the effect of these parameters on CF-values

CONCLUSIONS

This study for the first time provided a systematic analysis of the effect of food product characteristics and storage conditions on interaction between LAB and *L. monocytogenes* in broad range of fresh and lightly preserved foods. The developed secondary model for the effect of food product characteristics and storage conditions on CF is important for the practical application of interaction models where food product characteristics and storage conditions for some types of foods need to be taken into account

O22.- INFLUENCE OF PH AND STRUCTURE ON SORBIC ACID DISTRIBUTION AND GROWTH OF *C.GUILLIERMONDII* IN FAT BASED PRODUCTS

Irena Soljic, An Vermeulen, Frank Devlieghere

Paul Henri Spaak Laan 19, University of Gent, Brussels, Belgium

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Measures to prevent or retard microbial growth in emulsions include adjustments of the product formulation and control of storage temperature. The site of growth of microorganisms in emulsions is the aqueous phase, however, the oil phase is not inert and interacts with the aqueous phase, affecting the concentration of preservatives (Brocklehurst et al. 1993).

We developed a model for the distribution of preservatives in water/oil systems based on pH, K_p and the ratio of water and liquid oil present in the system. This model was experimentally validated by HPLC analysis of simple water/oil systems where the pH of the aqueous phase and the ratio of the aqueous and lipid phase were varied, as well as the ratio of liquid oil to solid fat. Lastly, the model was validated by challenge tests with *C. guilliermondii*, a spoilage yeast isolated from butter.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The model describing behavior of monoprotic preservatives in water/oil systems was developed in Excel and was based on varying pH, ratio of water/oil and partition coefficient (K_p).

Validation was performed by making model water/oil systems comprising of phosphate buffers with 1000 ppm sorbic acid at pH 3.5, 4.5, 5.5, 6.5, mimicking the pH range of commercially available emulsions, and either sunflower oil or sunflower oil and interesterified palm stearine. The ratios of aqueous to lipid phase and liquid oil (sunflower) to solid fat (palm stearine) were varied. The concentration of sorbic acid in the aqueous phase was measured by HPLC analysis under isocratic conditions.

Finally, the model was validated by inoculating *C. guilliermondii* in the aqueous phase of several model systems at a level of 10² CFU/mL. The samples were kept for 72 hours at 22°C and 1 month at 7°C and sampled for microbial growth in similar intervals. Growth rates (μ_{max}) and lag times (λ) were calculated over the Baranyi and Roberts model by DMFit software.

RESULTS

The model elaborates a clear dependency of preservative distribution on pH, K_p and ratio of water/oil in the system. At low pH, the majority of the undissociated acid partitions into the lipid phase, while at high pH's, most of the acid is present in undissociated form in the aqueous phase. Also, [HA]_{aq} decreases in systems with a large oil content and K_p. Surprisingly, at pH 6.5 the [HA]_{aq} increases as the oil content increases.

HPLC analysis confirmed the assumption that at lower pH's, a large portion of the undissociated acid partitions into the lipid phase. At pH's above the pK_a (4.76), most of the acid remains in the aqueous phase, albeit in its dissociated form.

Growth rates (μ_{max}) of *C.guilliermondii* in samples with sunflower oil or palm stearine at pH 3.5 and 4.5 also indicated partitioning of the undissociated acid into the liquid fraction of the fat phase.

CONCLUSIONS

These results complement the scarce information regarding influence of structure on monoprotic preservative distribution and yeast spoilage in fat based products.

O23.- MODELING THE FATE OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* AND LACTIC ACID BACTERIA IN TRADITIONAL MINAS CHEESES

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Keywords: Competition, artisanal cheese, ripening, refrigerated storage

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Artisanal Minas-type cheeses are widely consumed in Brazil and often made from raw milk in small cheese-making operations. The presence of indigenous lactic acid bacteria (LAB) may help control the growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* (LM), although this pathogen can occasionally be recovered from samples in the marketplace. The objective of this study was to quantify the inhibitory effect of LAB on the fate of LM during refrigerated storage or ripening of artisanal soft and semi-hard Minas-type cheeses respectively.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Soft and semi-hard Minas-type cheeses were produced using raw or pasteurized milk with the addition of LAB and LM strains. A total of six LAB strains with known anti-listerial activity (106-107 CFU/ml of milk) were selected. Two LM strains (serotypes 1/2b and 4b, isolated from cheese and raw milk, respectively) were inoculated at 105-106 CFU/ml of milk. Sixteen treatments including LAB alone, LM alone, LAB co-inoculated with LM and only naturally occurring microflora (e.g. indigenous LAB) were evaluated. LAB and LM counts were performed during refrigerated storage of soft cheese (10 °C, 15 days) and ripening of semi-hard cheese (22 °C, 22 days). Maximum growth rate (u_{max}) was calculated using Baranyi and Roberts (1994) model at DMFit Excel Add-In when growth was observed and inactivation rate (k_{max}) was calculated using Bigelow and Esty (1920) model at GInaFIT Excel Add-In when inactivation was observed.

RESULTS

Only LAB was able to grow in soft and semi-hard cheeses made with raw or pasteurized milk containing indigenous LAB and/or inoculated LAB (2.7 to 6.1 log₁₀ cycles). Soft cheeses (made with raw or pasteurized milk) and added LM with only indigenous LAB resulted in LM growth of 1.8 log₁₀ cycles. Semi-hard cheeses with LM and only indigenous LAB showed 1.0 and 1.9 log₁₀ increases of LM (in raw and pasteurized milk, respectively). When inoculated LAB and LM were studied, LM concentration increased 0.7 log₁₀ cycles in soft cheeses (made from either raw or pasteurized milk). Values of u_{max} obtained when only LM was inoculated in semi-hard cheeses (0.052 h⁻¹ and 0.066 h⁻¹, raw and pasteurized milk, respectively) were significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) than values found for soft cheeses with added LM (from 0.006 h⁻¹ to 0.016 h⁻¹). Declines of >5.8 and 4.1 log₁₀ in LM concentration were observed in semi-hard cheeses inoculated with LM and LAB (from raw and pasteurized milk, respectively). The inactivation rate (k_{max}) of LM was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in cheese made from raw milk (0.026 h⁻¹) compared to cheese made from pasteurized milk (0.018 h⁻¹).

CONCLUSIONS

Our results suggest that the added LAB strains were able to inhibit LM growth in soft Minas-type cheese and even result in LM reduction during the short (22 day) ripening period of semi-hard Minas-type cheese. These LAB strains have the potential to be applied commercially to control LM growth during the refrigerated storage of soft cheeses and to inactivate LM during the ripening of hard cheeses.

O24.- MODELLING THE EFFECT OF OSMOTIC ADAPTATION AND TEMPERATURE ON THE NON-THERMAL INACTIVATION OF *SALMONELLA* SPP. IN BAKERY BRIOCHE-LIKE PRODUCTS

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Keywords: Salmonella, inactivation, intermediate moisture foods

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Salmonella spp. is known to survive under low moisture conditions. Bakery products such as cream-filled brioche products acquire a water activity of approximately 0.85, depending mainly on the aw of the filling and the baking they receive, and hence, may support survival of the pathogen. The study aims to model the inactivation of osmotically adapted and non-adapted *Salmonella* spp. in creams and cream-filled brioche-like products

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Fillings (praline, biscuit) as well as whole brioche-like products, containing praline or biscuit filling and 0.1% calcium propionate, provided by the manufacturer, were inoculated with approximately 6 log CFU/g of osmotically adapted and non-adapted five-strain composite of *Salmonella* spp. (Typhimurium, Agona, Reading, Enteritidis) and stored aerobically (in 120 mL screw-capped container) at 15, 20, and 30°C. Adaptation of Salmonella took place in creams (praline, biscuit) with aw adjusted at 0.88, by adding sterile water to the original filling (aw 0.80-0.82) and incubation at 37°C for 1 h. Survival of *Salmonella* was assessed at regular time intervals throughout storage using thin layer agar method (n=2x2) in order to enhance the recovery of injured cells. Inactivation curves were fitted best with Weibull model using the freeware GInaFit tool and the estimated delta and p values were used to calculate the time for 4D reduction-t4D

RESULTS

Inactivation of *Salmonella* increased with temperature, while osmotic adaption of *Salmonella* enhanced its survival in a food matrix-related manner. In particular, the highest survival rates (t4D=75-135 days) of adapted *Salmonella* were observed in cream fillings at 20°C that approximates the recommended storage temperature. Moreover, cream fillings affected pathogen survival differently, with praline filling resulting in higher t4D (75 days; 20°C) than biscuit filling (45 days; 20°C), while both brioche products (praline- or biscuit- filled) resulted in similar pathogen survival regardless of storage temperature. Notably, there was a marked discrepancy between the present data and predicted inactivation kinetics by the existing (generic) models of Pin et al., (2011) and ComBase database (both polynomial models), stressing the need of updating the current non-thermal inactivation models, which are commonly based on laboratory (liquid) media and non-adapted overnight cultures, with the impact of targeted matrix and of prior osmotic adaptation of cells at conditions that closely resemble the matrix where survival is to be assessed

CONCLUSIONS

Adaptation matrix and protocol is critical for reliable assessment of risk due to survival of *Salmonella* in intermediate moisture foods. The present data could be used as a means to identify areas of improving the performance of existing models quantifying the behavior of the pathogen in bakery-confectionery products.

THURSDAY, SEPT. 28th

09:30 - 10:30 h.: SESSION 5.- Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment and Management

Chair: Alejandro Amezcua (UNILEVER)

O25.- APPLICATION OF NEXT GENERATION SEQUENCING DATA IN MICROBIAL RISK ASSESSMENT: CASE OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES*

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Keywords: Whole genome sequencing, Microbial Risk Analysis, *Listeria monocytogenes*, Machine Learning, Random forest

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The massive generation of Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) data presents an untapped potential to improve microbial risk assessment (MRA) through increased specificity and a potential fundamental change in the definition of the hazard.

We propose an approach that inputs NGS data from pathogens/potential pathogens in food and returns an estimate of the resulting risk / health burden at population level with *Listeria monocytogenes* as a case study. Genomewide Association Studies (GWAS) and other statistical approaches are hampered by uncertain stability, statistical power and feasibility of modelling methods due to the high number of variables in NGS datasets and the high data dimensionality.

Machine learning algorithms that "improve with experience" show potential for analysis of such large and complex data sets where relevant "features" in a complex data set enable the ability to make a strong prediction.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sequencing data from 207 strains from food and food environment and 39 clinical strains of *L. monocytogenes* from France collected between 2006 and 2014 were assembled and blasted for 137 reviewed virulence and environmental stress resistance genes. Associated data on frequency of illness for each strain was also available allowing for supervised machine learning models which can be trained to predict frequency of illness from sequence data.

RESULTS

After data exploration and preprocessing, 57 genes were retained for further modelling. The data was partitioned into training, testing and validation datasets and ran through five available ensemble classification techniques, which was followed by model evaluation and selection based on model accuracy and out of sample accuracy. Random forest was selected as the best model for this dataset showing an accuracy of 83% (95% CI: (0.6928, 0.9624) and only 3 misclassified frequencies of illness categories.

The model revealed twenty of the most important predictive genes were based on importance analysis for genes more often used as splitter variables for each frequency of illness class. These genes included recently reported genes whose function has not yet been described. These genes present a potential to develop rapid assays to investigate epidemiological significance of isolated strains of *L. monocytogenes*

CONCLUSIONS

This offers potential for a web-based NGS based MRA tool. Recommendations are made for further model validation using additional data and efficiency. On longer term, we foresee the development of a web-based system, where the model can be used for predicting health risks associated with food chain contamination. The concept offers opportunities for rethinking the current approaches in MRA.

O26.- CAN STOCHASTIC CONSUMER PHASE MODELS IN MICROBIAL RISK ASSESSMENT BE SIMPLIFIED TO A SINGLE FACTOR?

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Keywords: QMRA, Consumer, relative risk, variability

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

In quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA), the consumer phase covers the part of the food chain following production and retail, where the consumer transports, stores, prepares and consumes the food products considered. These consumer practices have a crucial impact on exposure, and a consumer phase model (CPM) always needs to be included in a QMRA to allow an evaluation of the effectiveness of intervention measures in food production and processing in terms of human health risk. However, the development of a CPM is complex because consumer practices can be highly variable and data are scarce. So far, it is unclear to what extent CPMs need to include data on variability and detailed descriptions of the stochastic processes that may result in exposure. We therefore compared the performance of published stochastic CPMs with a simple surrogate CPM that assumes a proportional linear relation between concentration at retail and ingested dose, described by a constant factor.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We performed a comparative study for different pathogens and different food products: *Campylobacter* in broiler meat, *Salmonella* in minced pork and pork cuts and *Listeria* in smoked salmon. Published stochastic CPMs were implemented in @Risk (Palisade) and their equivalent surrogate models were derived, basing the value of the constant surrogate model factor on the absolute risk estimate from the stochastic model. The performances of the models were evaluated by comparing the effects of hypothetical intervention measures that reduce the prevalence, or the mean or the standard deviation of the distribution of concentrations at retail. These effects were expressed in terms of relative risk estimates, as estimated in the risk assessments using the simplified and the stochastic CPMs.

RESULTS

For interventions affecting the prevalence only, a simplified surrogate CPM performs similarly as a stochastic CPM. However, after interventions that result in a reduction of the mean or standard deviation of the distribution of concentrations at retail, the relative risk estimates show that the surrogate single factor models always give a lower estimate of the relative risk than the stochastic CPMs. The difference is largest in the *Listeria* model, where growth during storage is expected to be the dominant process.

CONCLUSIONS

We conclude that the use of a simple surrogate CPM, which does not include the variability inherent to consumer practices, may lead to an overestimation of the effect of intervention measures in a QMRA, especially in these interventions affect the concentrations. For adequate risk assessment, it may therefore be necessary to include the variation in consumer practices (e.g. variation in storage time and temperature, cooking time and temperature and cross-contamination), as described in more realistic and more complex CPMs, definitely if this variation is expected to be large.

O27.- FARM TO FORK QUANTITATIVE MICROBIAL RISK ASSESSMENT FOR NOROVIRUS ON FROZEN BERRIES

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Keywords: norovirus, QMRA, frozen fruit

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Frozen fruit has been linked to several Norovirus outbreaks throughout the world. On farm contamination sources include the use of contaminated irrigation water and infected food handlers. A quantitative microbial risk assessment describing Norovirus prevalence and concentration during pre-harvest, harvest, post-harvest processing, storage, preparation and consumption of berries is presented. The output of the model is predicted number of illnesses. The QMRA was designed to simulate the largest known outbreak arising from Norovirus-contaminated berries, which occurred in 2012 in Germany and was linked to frozen strawberries sourced from China.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The model was built in Excel using the Monte Carlo modeling software @Risk add-in. The QMRA was composed of five modules: in field, processing and packaging, storage, preparation and consumption. Data from the scientific literature regarding Norovirus behavior in fresh and frozen fruit were used to develop the model. The simulation assumed the initial contamination source was the surface water used to apply pesticides to berries in the field. Norovirus concentration decline was simulated based on change in water containing pesticides, change during transport to the freezing facility, the effect of washing in the facility (warm or cold water or sanitizer wash), the effect of freezing, change during frozen transport via ship from China to Germany, and frozen distribution in Germany. Different foodservice preparation methods were evaluated. A dose-response function from the published literature was used to predict illness. Factors considered in the scenario analysis included sanitizer concentration, effect of temperature during transportation and storage, pesticide usage and the effect of seasonality on the prevalence of Norovirus in surface water. A tornado plot was used to compare the relative importance of selected variables.

RESULTS

The concentration of Norovirus in water was reduced when pesticides were added; pesticide reductions ranged from 0.8 mean log reduction \pm 0.5, to -0.2 mean log reduction \pm 0.9. Post-harvest washing of berries with chlorinated water (1.9 mean log reduction \pm 0.4) was significantly more effective than washing with warm (0.8 mean log reduction \pm 0.2) or cold water (0.6 mean log reduction \pm 0.3). The freezing process did not result in a decrease in Norovirus concentration on berries, but frozen storage resulted in log reductions from 0.2 to 1.1 depending on the frozen storage time and freezing conditions. Variables that had the greatest impact on the outcome of illnesses include the concentration of Norovirus in surface water and use of a heat step prior to consumption.

CONCLUSIONS

The model simulated the German frozen strawberry outbreak when the highest concentration of 8 log Genome Copies Norovirus per liter in pesticide application was assumed. Scenario analysis showed that heating the frozen berries prior to consumption was the most effective means to reduce illness.

O28.- RISK-BASED STRATEGIES TO ACCOMPLISH “LISTERIA ZERO” POLICY: DRY-CURED HAM AS A CASE STUDY

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Keywords: Foodborne pathogens; RTE meat products; Modelling; Risk assessment; Non-thermal inactivation; High pressure processing

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Food safety criteria regarding *L. monocytogenes* in ready-to-eat (RTE) food differ depending on the country legislation as well as the market (customer) demands. The zero tolerance often applied poses a challenge for the meat industry, including shelf-stable dry-cured meat products, due to the technical difficulties for the control and eradication of *L. monocytogenes*. The present study, developed in the framework of the private-public collaboration project “Listeria 0”, aimed to model the behaviour of *L. monocytogenes* in dry-cured ham at retail-consumer phase and to assess the associated risks regarding public health and accomplishment of legal requirements

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The survival of *L. monocytogenes* was evaluated by challenge testing in Serrano and Iberian ham. For each, 3 batches showing different aw (i.e. produced with 3 different weight loss) were used. *L. monocytogenes* was inoculated at ca. 6 log cfu/g with 4 different strains (S2, S4-2, S12-1 and S7-2) previously isolated from meat processing environment. Vacuum packaged samples were stored at 2, 8, 15 and 25 °C for a maximum of 6 months and *L. monocytogenes* was periodically enumerated on Chromogenic Listeria Agar. The Weibull model was fitted to estimate inactivation kinetic parameters. The impact of temperature and aw was evaluated using a polynomial equation. A quantitative microbiological risk assessment model was build taking into account distributions obtained from manufacturers’ data for initial concentration of the pathogen and aw and storage time/temperature of dry-cured hams, the developed non-thermal inactivation models, serving size data and the FAO/WHO 2004 dose-response model

RESULTS

The results of the challenge tests showed a loss of *L. monocytogenes* viability during storage at all the assayed conditions and especially in Iberian ham, confirming the intrinsic bactericidal properties of this type of RTE meat product. The inactivation increased by decreasing aw values and increasing temperatures (i.e. 15 and 25°C). The risk of listeriosis due to consumption of dry-cured ham was extremely low (1 ufc/25g was remarkable (36%). Control measures such as a quarantine period or a high pressure treatment could be successfully applied to drastically reduce the “Listeria zero” policy non-compliances

CONCLUSIONS

Levels of *L. monocytogenes* in dry-cured ham are low in terms of prevalence and concentration, and due to its physicochemical properties dry-cured ham is a very low-risk product to cause listeriosis. However, to fulfil legal requirements dry-cured ham producers should design risk minimization strategies to avoid sources of contamination and/or apply lethality treatments before commercial expedition.

Acknowledgements: “Listeria 0” Project (INIA-PA14/83 Lt2).

11:00 - 13:00 h.: SESSION 6.- Predictive models for food process simulation

Chairs: Vasilis Valdramidis (University of Malta) and Elena Carrasco (University of Cordoba)

O29.- MODELLING THE INHIBITORY EFFECT OF LAB ON L. MONOCYTOGENES AND ENTEROBACTERIACEAE IN A FERMENTED SAUSAGE DURING RIPENING

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Keywords: Microbial competition, Lotka-Volterra, interspecific interaction, chorizo.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Earlier research has shown that the survivability of Enterobacteriaceae (ENT) and *L. monocytogenes* (LM) in a Portuguese fermented sausage (linguiça) decreases during the ripening stage, and that such inhibition arises from the adverse conditions caused by the competition with autochthonous lactic acid bacteria (LAB) and the progressively lower water activity and pH. The objective of this work was to mathematically characterise the competition or interactions between LAB, LM and ENT that takes place in fermenting linguiça during ripening.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Four experimental conditions that derived from the combinations of the batter formulation with or without starter cultures, and two constant ripening temperatures (10° or 18°C) were evaluated. Batches of linguiça were inoculated with LM during mixing (~6 log CFU/g), while two batches were formulated with a commercial starter culture (Texel, Danisco) (~5 log CFU/g). ENT, LM and LAB were enumerated immediately after batter maceration (3 days after inoculation or day 0) and during ripening (days 2, 4, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 13). A modified Lotka-Volterra (LV) competition model based on the logistic equation was adjusted to each condition as a system of three ordinary differential equations for the populations N_{LAB} , N_{LM} , N_{ENT} , with inhibition functions assumed to be affected by the interspecific bacterial interactions α_{LM-LAB} and $\alpha_{ENT-LAB}$.

RESULTS

Using a starter culture and a higher ripening temperature increased LAB's maximum growth rate from 0.256 log CFU/day (no starter, 10°C) up to 0.597 log CFU/day, and LAB's maximum concentration from 7.023 to 8.328 log CFU/g. In all conditions, LAB exhibited a greater effect on ENT ($\alpha_{ENT-LAB}$: 8.919-38.71) than on LM (α_{LM-LAB} : 1.868-4.272), although $\alpha_{ENT-LAB}$ interspecific interaction was lower at the higher ripening temperature. From the end of maceration, the shortest time to achieve a one-log reduction in LM was attained by the condition with starter/18°C (4.6 days) while the longest by the condition without starter/10°C (9.8 days). Furthermore, LV models were flexible enough to closely describe the increase in ENT that occurred up to day 3-4 (when LAB reached a critical concentration of 6.8 log CFU/g) and its subsequent decline. Overall, a better agreement between observed and predicted counts was observed when models were fitted with interaction effects (residuals 0.112 – 0.157) than when they were set to zero (residuals 0.134 – 0.182), whereas neglecting the interspecific interactions led to a slight underestimation of LM and ENT counts.

CONCLUSIONS

Microbial interspecific interactions in fermenting meats should be modelled, and the LV model offers a suitable approach. As LM has been recovered from linguiça in the order of 0 – 150 CFU/g, the model suggests that certain modifications should be introduced in the process such as controlled ripening temperature, longer ripening time or even the use of starter cultures in order to ensure the safety of this product.

O30.- GROWTH AND SPORULATION DYNAMICS OF BACILLUS SUBTILIS CAN BE MODELED WITH ITS GROWTH LIMITS.

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Keywords: sporulation, growth limits, cardinal model, *Bacillus subtilis*

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Spore-forming bacteria represent a great deal in the food industry as they are responsible of food poisoning and involved in the spoilage of various processed foods. Predictive microbiology has proved its efficiency to predict vegetative growth and the thermal inactivation but the sporulation is barely taken into account in risk assessment or food predictive modelling. However, the sporulation process occurs in many industrial environments. As the spore germination and resistance abilities are dependent of the sporulation environment, it is interesting to identify the conditions favorable for the spore formation. The aim of this study was to describe and to model the effects of pH, water activity and temperature on the sporulation abilities and the sporulation dynamics of *Bacillus subtilis*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Growth-sporulation kinetics of *Bacillus subtilis* BSB1 were performed in batch, in brain heart infusion supplemented with sporulation salts, with an initial inoculum of 3.0 log₁₀ (CFU/mL), under 250 rpm agitation. The effects of environmental factors were tested independently, the two other factors being maintained to standard values (pH 7.0, 37°C, aw 0.996). Kinetics were monitored by enumerating total cells after plating on agar medium and spores (colony forming unit after a 10 minutes heat treatment at 80°C). The kinetics of growth and sporulation were fitted by a growth-sporulation kinetical model. The values of the growth parameters (growth rate, lag time, and maximal cell concentration) and the sporulation parameters (the incubation time needed to observe the first spore and the maximal probability for the vegetative cells to initiate sporulation and to form a spore) were estimated and modelled as a function of pH, water activity and temperature.

RESULTS

The sporulation abilities were the highest at temperature, pH and water activity conditions which growth rate was maximal. The sporulation abilities decreased as the environmental factors were closer the growth boundaries. As examples, the maximal probability to initiate sporulation decreased from 12% at 37°C to 0.33% at 20°C. The time needed to detect the first spores was 53 h at 20°C compared to 15 hours at 45°C. This evolution of the sporulation abilities could be described by a gamma-concept model, using the growth cardinal values of the strain as input parameters. This model allowed us fitting the time to see the first spores with a mean error of 12% whatever the condition of pH or temperature tested.

CONCLUSIONS

The sporulation could be predicted according to environmental factors using the growth characteristics of the studied strain, i.e. the growth cardinal values. This growth-sporulation model gives the opportunities to target key steps in terms of temperature, pH, aw and time, during food process or agriculture process that could promote the sporulation.

O31.- DEVELOPMENT OF A TIME-TEMPERATURE INDICATOR BASED ON VERSATILE BACTERIAL PIGMENT PRODUCED BY JANTHINOBACTERIUM SP.

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Keywords: TTI, SPOILAGE, TEMPERATURE, MICROBIAL, INDICATOR, COLD CHAIN MANAGEMENT

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Temperature constitutes the most critical parameter along the cold chain affecting the quality of foods. Time-temperature indicators or integrators (TTI) are known tools that can monitor the full time temperature history of chilled products.

The aim of this study was the development of a flexible microbial TTI based on Janthinobacterium sp. violet pigment production (violacein).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The bacterium Janthinobacterium sp. produces violacein during incipient growth, depending on temperature and intrinsic properties of the growth medium. The TTI system consisted of Tryptic Soy Agar enriched with 1% glycerol and spot-inoculated with the microorganism. The input parameters of the microbial TTI were: a) storage temperature (0, 5, 10 and 15°C), b) pH of the medium (5.5, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0 and 9.0), c) initial concentration of the microorganism (1 to 7 log CFU/ml, with step of 1 log CFU/ml) and d) 5 and 30 µl spot inoculation volume. Photos of the plates were taken every day and subjected to image analysis in order to estimate the color change (ΔE) of the spots at three technical and two biological repetitions. Color change was described by the Luminosity change (L^*). Violacein kinetics (L^* curve) TTI end point, i.e., the time at which violet color was obtained (beginning of plateau) were analyzed using the Baranyi-Arrhenius models and Survival Analysis curve, respectively.

RESULTS

All input parameters studied influenced the rate of violacein production. The TTI endpoint with 7 log CFU/spot at 0°C and pH 7 was 308.5 and 395.5 h for the 5 and 30 µL spot volumes, respectively, while the endpoint of 1 log at the same conditions was 691.5 and 754 h. pH 6-8 showed similar endpoints, which were markedly lower than those of pH 9 and 5.5. TTIs with pH 5.5 showed the highest endpoints (1866 and 1253 h for 5 and 30 µL respectively at 0°C and 1 log). E_a ranged from 72.33 ± 0.93 (5 µL spot, 7 log and pH 7) 112.58 ± 2.97 kJ/mol (at 30 µL spot). Totally violet colonies appeared at the beginning of plateau of the L^* curve. Based on the obtained E_a , a decision tree was developed. This tree facilitates the procedure of deciding on which conditions should be used (pH of the medium, initial concentration of the microorganism and spot inoculation level) for the food product under study. Thus, the microbial TTI can be potentially used for different categories of food commodities, spoiled by different organisms, under different packaging conditions, even containing growth inhibitors. The TTI system was successfully validated for monitoring of microbial spoilage of beef minced meat under isothermal and dynamic storage conditions. Based on the E_a of the Specific Spoilage Organisms of this product (*Pseudomonas* sp.) and the decision tree tool, the required conditions of the TTI system were selected. The TTI endpoint matched with the end of the product shelf-life.

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed TTI may be applicable in a wide range of foods and its customization may be achieved simply and cost-effectively.

032.- MODELLING AND PREDICTING INTERACTION BETWEEN A BACTERIOCINOGENIC *LACTOBACILLUS SAKEI* AND *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN GILT-HEAD SEABREAM (*SPARUS AURATA*) UNDER ISOTHERMAL AND DYNAMIC TEMPERATURE CONDITIONS

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Keywords: biopreservation, *Listeria monocytogenes*, ready-to-eat fish, microbial growth

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Global consumption of fresh fish and minimally processed fish has considerably increased in recent decades due to its health and nutrition characteristics. Due to its chemical composition, the fish products are highly perishable and vulnerable to microbial spoilage. The combined use of Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB) as bioprotective cultures and Modified Atmosphere Packaging (MAP) can be used as preservation strategies to control of *Listeria monocytogenes*. The application LAB has demonstrated a high potential in the safety of fish products and good ability to inhibit *L. monocytogenes* growth. The aims of the present work were to evaluate and model the interaction between a sakacin K producing *Lactobacillus sakei* and *L. monocytogenes* in gilt-head seabream (*Sparus aurata*) under isothermal and dynamics conditions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sterile seabream extract was used to simulate microbial growth in seabream fillets in mono and co-culture. The bioprotective culture, *L. sakei* CTC 494 (producing sakacin K) and *L. monocytogenes* CTC 1034 (from meat product origin) were pre-cultured at 30 °C and 37 °C for 18-20 h in MRS (De Man, Rogosa and Sharpe, Oxoid) and BHI (Brain Heart Infusion, Oxoid), respectively. For the experiments in mono-culture the initial concentration of each strain was $ca.10^2$ CFU/mL while for co-culture, three initial concentrations ($ca.10^2$, 10^4 and 10^6 CFU/mL) of *L. sakei* and $ca.10^2$ CFU/mL of *L. monocytogenes* were inoculated in the fish extract, generating three different ratios *L. monocytogenes*:*L. sakei* (1:1, 1:2 and 1:3). The samples were stored at four different temperatures, 2, 5, 8 and 12 °C for experiments in mono-culture and 5, 8 and 12 °C for co-culture. The Baranyi and Roberts primary model was used to obtain the growth parameters of each bacteria specie in mono-culture and the square root model was fitted to describe the influence of temperature on the growth parameters. For the experiments in co-culture with an actual food matrix, fresh seabream fillets packaged in MAP ($37.4\% \pm 0.69$ O₂ and $27\% \pm 0.95$ CO₂) were acquired from a private company and transported (4 °C) to the laboratory, where were inoculated with $ca.10^4$ CFU/g of *L. sakei* and $ca.10^2$ CFU/g of *L. monocytogenes*, corresponding to an inoculation ratio of 1:2. Preliminary studies showed, for this ratio, a deterioration rate similar to that observed in control samples (i.e. non-inoculated). The samples were stored at two constant temperatures, 5 and 8 °C and two temperature profiles in the ranges 2.5-8 °C and 2.5-12 °C. Apart from the target microorganisms, the growth of Enterobacteriaceae, pH and gases concentration were monitored during storage. The prediction of the effect of *L. sakei* on *L. monocytogenes* was simulated by using Jameson effect models and the Lotka Volterra model.

RESULTS

The Baranyi and Roberts model showed a good fit to the experimental data in mono and co-culture with values for the R² higher than 0.96. The comparison of the kinetics parameters in mono-culture and co-culture in fish extract allowed to determine the degree of inhibition in all conditions studied. In mono-culture, *L. monocytogenes* growth was observed for all temperatures (0.01-0.08 log CFU/h), while in co-culture, *L. sakei* was able to inhibit the pathogen growth at 5, 8 and 12 °C for the ratio 1:3 and reduce the *Listeria* growth, considerably, for the ratio 1:2. In packaged seabream fillets the combined effect of *L. sakei* and MAP resulted in no growth of *L. monocytogenes* for both constant and dynamic conditions. The predictions obtained through

the simulation of the Lotka Volterra and a modified version of the Jameson effect model suitably described observations at constant temperatures in fish extract and fish fillets. Furthermore, the analysis of interaction parameters derived from the Lotka Volterra model revealed a greater inhibitory effect of *L. sakei* populations and the rise in the inhibition of this microorganism as inoculation ratio increased.

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrated that the use of a bioprotective culture formulated with a sakacin K-producing *Lactobacillus sakei* could reduce and inhibit *Listeria monocytogenes* growth in packaged gilt-head seabream fillet stored under refrigeration conditions. Predictive models considering microbial interaction and dynamic temperatures conditions, used in our study, are proposed as reliable tools to adequately describe the effect the bioprotective culture on *L. monocytogenes* growth in fish products.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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O33.- MODELLING *BACILLUS CEREUS* SURVIVAL VARIABILITY TO SPRAY DRYING PROCESS

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Keywords: spray drying; strain variability; *Bacillus cereus* spores

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Spray-drying technique is largely used in food industry for processing milk, coffee, tea, enzymes among others substances. However, microbial contamination in products subjected to spray-drying process remains a challenge to overcome since the spores of *Bacillus cereus* are heat resistant. This study aimed at evaluating the variability of inactivation on different *B. cereus* strains yield to spray drying process.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Whole pasteurized milk was separately inoculated with 10⁶ spores/mL of 12 different *B. cereus* strains and further enumerated through the application of heat shock at 80°C/30min followed by count in Mannitol Egg Yolk Polymyxin (MYP) Agar. A bench scale Spray-Dryer was used for producing milk powder (inlet temperature: 190°C, feed flow rate 0.7L/hour, drying airflow rate 1.40m³/min). After the spray drying process, milk powder samples were suspended in 0.1% peptone water and further subjected to heat shock at 75°C/20min and enumeration on MYP. The number of log reduction (gamma) after the spray-drying process for each of the 12 strains was calculated, taking into account the dry weight (spores per gram of dried sample). The strain variability was determined through the coefficient of variation (CV = standard deviation/mean*100) of gamma.

RESULTS

The gamma value for the different strains studied varied from 0.32 log₁₀ to 4.13 log₁₀, i.e., variation of up to 61.1% in the CV value. The results show that variability is an important factor when assessing environmental stress responses of foodborne pathogens.

CONCLUSIONS

Spray drying process is used in food industry to obtain dried foods, even though given the high temperature applied, microbial inactivation can take place. This study shows that inactivation of *B. cereus* may vary from strain to strain, which may have serious outputs for the safety of formulated foods in which dried milk is used. The variability quantification of *B. cereus* exposed to spray drying is of foremost importance, so industries can better know the impact of their processes and practices and apply appropriate conditions aiming to ensure the safety of foods formulated with ingredients such as dried milk.

O34.-NEW INSIGHTS ON THE EFFECT OF LACTATE ON THE *L. MONOCYTOGENES* GROWTH IN HIGH PRESSURE PROCESSED COOKED HAM

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Keywords: high pressure processing; biopreservation; organic acids; foodborne pathogens; RTE meat products; modelling.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

High pressure (HP) processing of food is usually applied to enhance microbiological food safety and extend shelf-life. Product formulation with organic acids (OA) as antimicrobial agents have been shown to affect the lethality of HP. In a previous work, lactate showed a piezoprotective effect for *L. monocytogenes* inactivation in cooked ham. The aim of the present study was to understand the behavior of *L. monocytogenes* during the storage of HP treated cooked ham formulated with lactate and diacetate.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Cooked ham batches were manufactured without OA (control), with potassium lactate (4% and 2.8%) and potassium lactate plus sodium diacetate (2.0% +0.11% and 2.0% +0.45%). Concentrations of OA were selected to inhibit the growth of *L. monocytogenes* at 8 and 12 °C according to the Food Safety and Spoilage Predictor (FSSP v4.0, $\Psi \geq 1$). Products were sliced aseptically and inoculated with ca. 6 Log cfu/g of either *L. monocytogenes* CTC1034 or a cocktail containing 12MOB045Lm, 12MOB089Lm and ScottA strains. Vacuum-packed samples were pressurized at 600 MPa for 3 min. Growth in non-pressurized samples inoculated at ca. 100 cfu/g was also monitored. *L. monocytogenes* growth was monitored by enumeration on chromogenic medium at selected sampling times during storage at 8, 12 and 20°C. Growth was characterized by fitting the logistic primary model to the counts obtained for each product formulation, treatment (HP-/ +), storage temperature and strain. Square root secondary model for the growth rate was applied to quantify the effect of storage temperature.

RESULTS

In cooked ham elaborated without OA the growth rate of *L. monocytogenes* was not affected by the application of HP and strain, being 23% higher than that predicted by FSSP at all assessed temperatures. In contrast, the lag phase was longer in pressurized samples. The combined use of lactate and diacetate (0.45%) completely inhibited the growth of the pathogen at 12 and 20°C. On the contrary, the addition of 2.8% and 4% lactate could not completely inhibit the growth of *L. monocytogenes* at 8 and 12 °C, respectively. Interestingly, a higher number of samples showing growth of pathogen were recorded in HP processed products formulated with lactate in comparison with control HP processed products. At 20°C, the growth rate of *L. monocytogenes* in HP processed cooked ham was 4 to 4.6 fold-higher in the presence of lactate than in control products (without OA), thus specific secondary models are needed depending on the HP application.

CONCLUSIONS

The piezoprotective effect of lactate in the immediate HP inactivation of *L. monocytogenes* together with its increased growth rate during shelf-life in lactate-containing HP processed cooked ham, makes the formulation with lactate (as the only OA) not recommended for cooked meat products intended to be HP processed.

Acknowledgements: INIA-RTA2012-00030, ANSES for providing 12MOB045Lm and 12MOB089Lm strains.

O35.- MODELLING INACTIVATION OF DIFFERENT MODES OF LIVING OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* TREATED WITH COLD ATMOSPHERIC PLASMA

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Keywords: cold atmospheric plasma, biofilms, planktonic growth, colonies, decontamination.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Consumers tend to prefer minimally processed foods and the food industry aims to reduce the energy consumption for food and surfaces decontamination, while in both cases microbiological food safety remains a parallel and equally important target. Cold atmospheric plasma (CAP), as a novel non thermal decontamination technology has a potential for covering the aforementioned targets. CAP is created by applying a high voltage to a gas stream, resulting in microbial inactivation, due to the production of CAP species (charged particles, reactive species, UV). *Listeria monocytogenes* is an important pathogen in the food industry, as it can survive and grow at refrigerated conditions, high salinity and low pH values. It can cause listeriosis, which is a disease with high fatality rate (15-17 %). *L. monocytogenes*, as many other bacteria, can grow planktonically, as colonies, as well as forming biofilms, depending on the substrate and the environmental conditions. The effect of CAP on *L. monocytogenes* different modes of living, i.e., planktonic cells, colonies and biofilms is not known.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In this study, *Listeria monocytogenes* planktonic and colonial cells (simulating *L. monocytogenes* growing in liquid and solid food products, respectively) were cultivated in/on model systems and biofilms on abiotic surfaces (simulating food contact surfaces in the food industry). CAP was created using a dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) electrode for planktonic and colonial cells and a surface barrier discharge (SBD) electrode for biofilms. The log reduction was determined based on plate counts and the model of Geeraerd et al. (2000) was used to estimate the inactivation parameters and compare the influence of the CAP treatment on the different modes of living of *L. monocytogenes*.

RESULTS

Results indicated that depending on the mode of living of *L. monocytogenes* a different resistance towards CAP was observed. Additionally, depending on the cell support system (liquid, solid substrate and abiotic surface), microbial cells were attained in different ways by the CAP species.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study provide promising results for using CAP as a novel non-thermal technology for *L. monocytogenes* inactivation. The observations should be considered when designing future experiments targeting to validate the efficacy of CAP for food and surfaces decontamination.

O36.- MODELING THE LOAD OF METABOLITE DIFFUSIVITY ON GROWTH RATE OF NON-STARTER LACTIC ACID BACTERIA DURING CHEESE RIPENING

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Keywords: bacterial interaction, metabolite diffusivity, Lactic acid bacteria, cheese ripening

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Ripening of cheese consists of complex microbial interactions between starter lactic acid bacteria (SLAB) and non-starter lactic acid bacteria (NSLAB). In an attempt to understand the complex micro-ecological processes during cheese ripening, mathematical modeling was used to study the role of metabolite diffusion within the cheese matrix in determining the growth of NSLAB during ripening.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In the model the SLAB were set to start decaying within the curd immediately after salting or at any time after that. Upon SLAB lysis, "small-molecule nutrients" are directly released from the cytosol or produced by the hydrolytic enzymes of the decaying SLAB cells. These nutrients comprise SLAB cell wall monomer components (N-acetylglucosamine, N-acetylmuramic acid), sugars from hydrolyzed nucleic acids (ribose and deoxyribose), free amino acids, and small peptides (10-15 amino acid residues). All these are assumed to diffuse from the localized, lysed SLAB cells within the cheese matrix. The model was set to predict the growth of NSLAB colonies utilizing the diffusing material as their nutrient source. For simplicity we assume that both the SLAB and the NSLAB are homogeneous with respect to their dynamical properties, i.e., the SLAB strains do not differ in the long-term averages of their rates of death/lysis, and the expected maximum growth rates of NSLAB strains, are also equal. The diffusion rates of the small-molecule nutrients were lumped into a single diffusion parameter. The time course of the total masses of SLAB, nutrients and NSLAB was followed within a small, square shaped region (10 mm side length) of the cheese, using periodic boundary conditions. Defining periodic boundaries amounts to assuming that the focal square region, and those of the same size and shape adjacent to it, are identical, which means that the curd consists of an infinite repetition of the focal region in all spatial dimensions.

RESULTS

The modeling approach, based on realistic assumptions of the component processes of Cheddar cheese ripening and applying parameters for SLAB decay, nutrient diffusion and NSLAB growth taken from the literature, showed that nutrient diffusivity is not a bottleneck for NSLAB growth during ripening. Neither could the growth potential of the NSLAB colonies be the limiting factor, not even at the suboptimal conditions at which they persist during ripening.

CONCLUSIONS

The component process determining the speed of NSLAB growth (and thus also the speed of the ripening process) seems to be the supply of the nutrient that is present at limiting density within the cheese, and that in its turn depends on the speed of SLAB decay.

O37. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE CARDINAL PARAMETERS OF BACILLUS CEREUS STRAINS REVEALED BY A REPARAMETRIZED VERSION OF THE RATKOWSKY MODEL.

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In this study, we established an unexpectedly strong relationship between some cardinal values of temperature-dependent growth models of various *Bacillus cereus* strains, spanning from psychotropic to mesophilic strains. We also showed how the findings can be utilized in practical predictions.

The square root values of the maximum specific growth rates of 12 strains of *B. cereus*, pair-wise belonging to six groups of this organism, as published by Carlin *et al.* (2013), were fitted against temperature by a reparametrized version of the model of Ratkowsky *et al.* (1983). The parameter set of this version of the Ratkowsky model are either the same or directly comparable with that of the cardinal model of Rosso and Robinson (2001), inasmuch both includes the minimum, optimum and maximum temperatures for growth as well as a fourth parameter scaling the resultant mathematical expression along the dependent variable. The modularity of the obtained model was utilized to show an unexpectedly strong linear correlation between the respective parameters of different strains, which even linked seemingly distant (e.g. mesophilic and psychotropic) strains.

The findings not only point to links between strain-specific kinetic parameters of a species, but also can be used to create an overarching predictive model for the fastest growing strains as a function of temperature. This is useful to predict the growth of a cocktail of these strains, or to provide a safe prediction when the strain-composition of a growing *B. cereus* culture is unknown.

14:30 - 15:30 h.: SESSION 7.- Systems biology and whole-cell modelling.

Chair: Heidy den Besten (Wageningen University)

O38.- MECHANISMS TO COUNTERACT MEDIUM ACIDIFICATION DURING GLUCOSE FERMENTATION: A METABOLIC MODELING ANALYSIS OF E. COLI

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Keywords: flux balance analysis; formate hydrogen lyase complex; mild acid stress; budAB operon

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The Enterobacteriaceae family is divided in two groups according to glucose fermentation end products. The mixed-acid group, which E. coli is part, ferments glucose to ethanol, CO₂, H₂ and organic acids. The 2,3-butanediol group, which S. plymuthica belongs, starts with mixed-acid fermentation, and latter switches to 2,3-butanediol fermentation. While for 2,3-butanediol group the medium reaches more neutral pH, for mixed-acid group the medium pH constantly decrease. To survive this acid stress, E. coli uses resistance mechanisms such as the formate hydrogen lyase (FHL) complex. Our objective was to observe E. coli metabolic strategies to cope with mild acidic pH stress imposed by the end products of glucose fermentation. This objective was reached by performing a flux-balance analysis (FBA) model, with special attention to the role of the FHL complex and the advantages for E. coli in harboring genes from 2,3-butanediol pathway.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The strains were E. coli MG1655 wild-type (WT) and its $\Delta hycE$ mutant. Both were equipped with either pbudAB (a plasmid with the S. plymuthica budAB operon required for 2,3-butanediol production) or pTrc99A (the corresponding empty plasmid) yielding: WT-pTrc99A, WT-pTrc99A-pbudAB, $\Delta hycE$ -pTrc99A and $\Delta hycE$ -pTrc99A-pbudAB. Metabolic fluxes were determined in minimal medium with glucose as the sole carbon source during anaerobic growth. Growth parameters were obtained with the three phase linear model. Metabolic fluxes and yields were calculated during the exponential phase. To validate the metabolic flux, a FBA was performed with maximization of the growth rate as objective. The E. coli iJO1366 genome-scale metabolic model was used and adapted for the mutant strains.

RESULTS

A long and variable lag phase was observed. The pbudAB addition decreased the maximum growth rate μ , while the hycE deletion didn't influence μ . Medium pH was governed by the hycE gene. For both hycE+ strains, final medium pH was in average 5.7, while for both $\Delta hycE$ strains, it was 5.0. The main metabolic fluxes shifts compared to the pTrc99A were: pTrc99A-pbudAB produced 2 times less acetate, and $\Delta hycE$ strains produced 4 and 5 times more formate and lactate, respectively. The hycE gene deletion disrupted the FHL complex operation causing a higher accumulation in formate in the media, which was no longer re-imported by the cells.

CONCLUSIONS

The metabolic shift was a balance between constraints imposed by pH, enzymes activity according to pH, redox state of the cell, and, for $\Delta hycE$, the cells' incapacity of re-uptake and convert formate. In minimal medium, the budAB presence did not affect the ability of E. coli to cope with acid stress. The FBA couldn't predict the observed μ , indicating that plasmid biosynthesis reactions and maintenance cannot be neglected in the metabolic model or that other un-modelled mechanisms are dissipating energy and carbon. Still, FBA helps to understand the results at a metabolic level and, as in our case, showed new directions for investigation.

O39.- MODELING OF ADAPTATION PHENOMENA IN MICROBIAL DYNAMICS: A FLUX BALANCE ANALYSIS APPROACH

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Keywords: adaptation phenomena, microbial dynamics, flux balance analysis, systems biology

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The quest for a better understanding of the mechanisms steering biological processes towards the observed behavior, has led to the development of systems biology. Network modeling is one of the key concepts in systems biology, in which observed interactions between different chemical substances within cells are considered as the consequence of underlying (metabolic, regulatory or signaling) pathways. A metabolic network consists of m metabolites (compounds consumed/produced by a cell) and n fluxes (biochemical reactions between metabolites, exchange fluxes between cell and environment or transport throughout the cell). In this work, a multi-scale predictive dynamic model is presented for the microbial growth of *E. coli* as function of time, comprising both macroscopic mass balances and microscopic scale interactions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A dynamic model structure is constructed based on the following assumptions: (i) all cells are considered to be equal to one average cell, hence having the same flux distributions, (ii) the microbial medium is liquid and perfectly mixed, hence biomass and extracellular metabolite concentrations are the same for each cell, (iii) dilution of intracellular metabolites caused by the cell's growth is neglected and (iv) there is no accumulation of intracellular metabolites. By these simplifications, the dynamic intracellular balances are replaced by an underdetermined system, since for the majority of metabolic networks the number of intracellular metabolites is smaller than (or equal to) the number of fluxes. Due to the large number of fluxes, scarce kinetic information and costly identification of dynamic fluxes (in terms of experimental data), the model structure contains a number of degrees of freedom, i.e., the *free fluxes*. Assuming that the cells have evolved to behave optimally with respect to an intracellular objective, a flux balance analysis approach is followed to estimate these fluxes.

RESULTS

For a (reduced) metabolic network of the central carbon metabolism of *E. coli*, the objective governing the exponential growth phase is minimized to simulate how the different metabolic fluxes in the network gradually increase and certain cell mechanisms are switched on/off as a response to changes in the environment.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the metabolic flux predictions, revealed interesting patterns in the activation of metabolic pathways. The model has proven potential for the prediction of microbial dynamics in a more mechanistic way. If critical steps are detected in the predicted metabolic fluxes, strategies to control the lag phase(s) can be designed.

O40.- TOWARDS A NOVEL GENERATION OF KINETIC PARAMETER ESTIMATION

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Keywords: parameter estimation, kinetic models, dynamic metabolic flux analysis

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Microbial responses in food exert complex behavior, which goes beyond the understanding provided by simple macroscopic population balance models. Systems biology aims at gaining a better understanding of the observed behavior by accounting for information at the level of (intra)cellular networks. In this work metabolic networks are considered for the coupling of the macroscopic level with the microscopic level. In practice, metabolic networks consist of thousands of reactions and metabolites, rendering the analysis and identification of such networks almost impossible. Therefore reduced networks (50-200 metabolites), involving only the most important pathways and reactions that are relevant for the considered study, have proven to be more appealing. However, estimating the parameters in the (nonlinear) kinetic functions for these fluxes still remains challenging. The aim of this work is to estimate kinetic functions in a two-step procedure, in which firstly the dynamic fluxes are mathematically parameterized as a function of time and estimated by dynamic metabolic flux analysis and secondly kinetic functions (and thus kinetic parameters) are estimated based on these functions. As a case study, dynamic metabolic flux analysis and kinetic identification are presented for a simulated diauxic growth dataset of fermentation of *E. coli* is presented.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Dynamic metabolic flux analysis (DMFA) is an example of a multi-scale model structure in which the free fluxes are the degree of freedom. Under the assumption that (i) all cells behave as an average cell, (ii) a perfectly mixed liquid medium, (iii) negligible dilution of intracellular metabolites by cell growth and (iv) no accumulation of intracellular metabolites, this model structure allows to estimate time-dependent fluxes in metabolic networks, based on available measurements (e.g., exchange fluxes between cells and their environment, metabolite concentrations, etc...).

RESULTS

A fully nonlinear dynamic parameter estimation approach, based on a B-spline parameterization of the *free fluxes* is extended and applied to estimate the dynamic metabolic fluxes as a function of time. Moreover, advanced techniques as the sigma points approach and polynomial chaos expansion are exploited to estimate confidence bounds on the dynamic fluxes. Subsequently kinetic functions are identified based on these estimated dynamic flux profiles.

CONCLUSIONS

The presented procedure allows to estimate kinetic functions and confidence bounds for the dynamic fluxes, based on state of the art techniques of dynamic metabolic flux analysis and uncertainty propagation. This approach is elegant, since it reduces the complexity of the parameter estimation problem (i.e., less parameters have to be identified at the same time) and allows to select an appropriate model structure with accurate kinetic parameters based on these estimated dynamic flux profiles.

O41.- COMBINED STATE ESTIMATION AND PREDICTIVE CONTROL OF BIOLOGICAL SYSTEMS USING SOLACE

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Keywords: S-System, Biological Networks, Model Predictive Control

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Biological networks are important tools in systems biology to incorporate microscopic knowledge of microorganism in describing macroscopic biological phenomena. Such an understanding can ultimately help in recognizing the metabolic pathways which leads to microbial growth under various stressing conditions. Describing biological phenomena by *S-systems* is becoming popular due to the efficient compromise they provide between accuracy and mathematical complexity. One of the final aims of describing biological phenomena mathematically is to develop control strategies (e.g. to stress the system in a way to minimize growth of microorganisms and production of toxic metabolites in food). In this work, we investigate the use of *Model Predictive Control* (MPC) to develop an appropriate control strategy. One of the main challenges in utilizing MPC is the presence of incomplete and noisy measurements. Hence, an online state estimation strategy has been used to estimate the unknown states.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

S-systems are canonical nonlinear models used to describe complex biochemical networks. These systems form a set of nonlinear differential equations which adhere to the power law form. The states of this system correspond to the concentrations of different metabolites. Each dynamic equation for the dependent state consists two terms one for the formation and other for the consumption of the metabolite. The parameters in the model correspond to the rate constants and kinetic orders which describe the influence of metabolite on each other. MPC is one of the most common advanced control strategies. The idea here is to optimize the future of a process (by solving an open-loop optimal control problem online (OCP)) using a process model, and apply the computed control input only till a new measurement is available. Once the new measurement is acquired, the OCP is solved again to compute the control inputs. This repeated solving of an OCP on a moving window incorporates a feedback mechanism which can handle various disturbances and uncertainties arising out of plant-model mismatch. A similar concept of moving time window is utilized in the *Moving Horizon Estimator* (MHE) which is used as the state estimation strategy. Instead of looking into the future, MHE looks at the past measurements to get an estimate of the cur

RESULTS

The developed state estimation and control strategy is applied to the S-system representing the glycolytic-glyconeolytic pathway. Physically the system corresponds to using phosphate ions to control the glucose-1-phosphate concentration when only glucose-1-phosphate and fructose-6-phosphate is measured. The implementation is carried out in a new, open-source, in-house developed toolkit called SOLACE.

CONCLUSIONS

The results indicate interesting possibilities for control of microbial food safety and quality based on MPC and MHE in presence of incomplete and noisy measurements. Moreover, the efficacy of SOLACE to handle complex biological networks is demonstrated.

15:30 - 16:00 h.: SESSION 8.- Data Bases, software and decision support tools (I)

Chairs: Fanny Tenenhaus Aziza (CNIEL) and Paw Dalgaard (Technical University of Denmark)

O42.- HARMONIZATION OF TERMS AND CONCEPTS FOR RISK ASSESSMENT MODELLING AND KNOWLEDGE INTEGRATION

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Keywords: Metadata description; Information exchange; Knowledge annotation; Harmonized vocabulary

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

In the last decades the food safety community has developed a variety of databases, mathematical algorithms and models, software tools and model-based knowledge. However, the exchange of information between these resources is currently difficult and time consuming. This problem has increased over time due to the lack of harmonized data formats and rules for knowledge annotation. This includes the lack of a common understanding of basic terms and concepts and nonexistence of harmonized controlled vocabularies for metadata description.

In a joint research project between three European Food Safety Risk Assessment institutions (ANSES, BfR, DTU Food), experts work together to establish a new community resource called Risk Assessment Modelling and Knowledge Integration Platform (RAKIP). The objective is to create a platform for sharing risk assessment (RA) resources including models, data standards, open source software libraries and controlled vocabularies. In this context, a harmonized vocabulary for describing information relevant in food safety modelling has been generated as a curated, online, community knowledge base. This will facilitate the mapping of metadata concepts between different existing quantitative microbial risk assessments (QMRA) and predictive microbiology (PM) tools. Furthermore, RAKIP works on a foundation for a joint understanding of general terms and concepts relevant in RA modelling

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The alignment of terms and concepts was carried out through expert workshops complemented by joined work on a white paper called: "RAKIP - terms and concepts". This paper includes the generation of several schemata detailing processes that are crucial for model-based risk assessments. These schemata were structured to clearly communicate and discuss the underlying concepts they encompass. Processes, terms and concepts were finally defined in a glossary that can be accessed and updated online

RESULTS

The RAKIP project established harmonized definitions of terms and concepts used within QMRA and PM as a basis for the envisaged model-based knowledge exchange platform. Among other results, this research provides for the first time a consistent set of terms spanning high level concepts as e.g. defined by Codex Alimentarius up to terms generally used in statistics or data and software science. The harmonized terms can be easily extended and updated by the research community as an online resource. In the future, this harmonization will facilitate the incorporation of new model-based knowledge in different software tools

CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes a conceptual framework on terms and modelling processes that will serve as a foundation for the harmonized annotation of risk assessment models and model components. In addition, the online resource on "terms and concepts" together with other community resources generated during the RAKIP project will serve as an important resource for future software developments and eased knowledge exchange within the RA modelling community

O43.- SOURCE ATTRIBUTION OF SPORADIC SALMONELLOSIS BY A META-ANALYSIS OF CASE-CONTROL STUDIES

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Keywords: Retrospective observational study; odds-ratio; risk factor; routes of transmission; Salmonella

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

A case-control study is a powerful approach among epidemiologists to investigate the causal effect of exposure and enteric illness. The objective of this work was to synthesise the associations between risk factors and sporadic salmonellosis by combining results from relevant case-control studies. For the study-specific exposures to be harmonised within a meta-analysis study, a categorisation scheme was developed that hierarchically grouped risk factors into travel, host-specific factors and pathways of exposure.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Literature search to identify suitable scientific articles was conducted using Science Direct, PubMed, Scielo, ISI Web of Science and Scopus. Primary studies that passed the screening for relevance were marked as having potential for bias if they failed to meet at least one of the methodological quality assessment criteria. From each case-control study, the odds-ratio (OR) measures of association between exposures and disease were extracted, as well as codified study characteristics. Random-effects meta-analyses models were adjusted to appropriate data partitions to estimate overall ORs for every risk factor.

RESULTS

A total of 69 relevant primary studies provided 1310 ORs that were categorised for meta-analysis, of which 207 were marked as potentially biased. The most important risk factors for salmonellosis in the children population are: contact with farm animals (overall OR=5.98; 95% CI: 2.79 – 12.8); person-to-person transmission (OR=4.00; 95% CI: 1.81 – 8.81); drink water (OR=3.25; 95% CI: 1.67 – 6.32); pork meat (OR=3.19; 95% CI: 1.95 – 5.24); contact with pets (OR=3.16; 95% CI: 1.95 – 5.24), milk powder in infants (OR=2.30; 95% CI: 1.68 – 5.15); eggs (OR=1.63; 95% CI: 1.19 – 2.24) and chicken meat (OR=1.44; 95% CI: 1.06 – 1.95). In the mixed population, international travel is the most important risk factor (OR=5.83; 95% CI: 2.33 – 14.61). Within the food vehicles, key determinants of disease are composite food from ethnic establishments (OR=3.72; 95% CI: 2.29 – 6.03); red meats other than beef (OR=2.54; 95% CI: 1.70 – 3.82); pork meat (OR= 2.33; 95% CI: 1.75 – 3.04); eggs (OR=2.26; 95% CI: 1.27 – 4.05) and BBQ meats (OR= 2.06; 95% CI: 0.93 – 4.58). It was also possible to estimate that people who eat undercooked pork or poultry have, on average, ~3.8 (95% CI: 2.15 – 6.18) or ~2.7 (95% CI: 1.25 – 5.10) times the odds of becoming infected than those who simply eat pork or poultry. Eating undercooked eggs increases the odds of infection by 1.25 (95% CI: 1.05 – 1.47) while eating raw eggs by a higher factor of 1.88 (95% CI: 1.28 – 2.67).

CONCLUSIONS

Eating food prepared in establishments was identified as an important risk factor by itself. Foodstuffs that comparatively have the weakest associations with salmonellosis were: fruits, nuts, roots, dairy fats, processed fish, vegetable products, cheese, milk and fish. These results can be used to support risk management decisions in identifying and prioritising areas for interventions.

16:30 - 18:00 h.: SESSION 8.- DATA BASES, SOFTWARE AND DECISION SUPPORT TOOLS (II)

O44.- DEVELOPMENT OF A PROBABILISTIC DECISION-MAKING SCORING SYSTEM FOR QUALITY AND SAFETY REQUIREMENTS OF ALOREÑA DE MÁLAGA TABLE OLIVES

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Table olives are one of the most representatives and consumed fermented vegetables in Mediterranean countries. Aloreña de Málaga table olives obtained the first Protected Designation of Origin in Spain being widely consumed in southern Spanish regions. However, there is an evident lack of standardization of production processes and HACCP systems thus implying the need of establishing decision-making tools allowing their commercialization and shelf-life extension. The present work aims at developing a decision-making scoring system by means of a probabilistic assessment to standardize production process of Aloreña de Málaga table olives based on the identification of potential hazards or deficiencies in hygienic processes for the subsequent implementation of corrective measures.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Microbiological and physico-chemical data were collected over three consecutive olive campaigns (2014 – 2016) to measure the variability and relative importance of each elaboration step on total hygienic quality and product safety. Three representative companies were visited to collect samples from food-contact surfaces, olive fruits, brines, environment, olive dressings, water tank, and finished products. A probabilistic assessment was done based on the establishment of Performance Hygiene and Safety Scores (PHSS 0-100%) through a standardized system for evaluating product acceptability. ANOVA statistical analyses and Spearman correlation tests were conducted to evaluate significant differences

RESULTS

The mean value of the global Performance Hygiene and Safety Score for the Aloreña table olives processing (PHHSFTOT) was 64.82% (90th CI: 52.78- 76.39%) indicating that the evaluated processing steps influenced in a different extension on final product quality and safety. Washing and cracking, and selection and addition of olive dressings were detected as the most deficient ones in relation to PHSSFi values (p

CONCLUSIONS

The present work brings further the development of an easy-to-use, flexible and useful tool for the Aloreña de Málaga table olive food sector and can be potentially applied to other food industries and product.

O45.- MICROHIBRO: AN EASY-TO-USE FRAMEWORK FOR STOCHASTIC MICROBIAL RISK ASSESSMENT

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

In the last decades, predictive microbiology has undergone an important development due to improvements in computers and software engineering. Currently, the development of prediction software has enabled the transfer of knowledge on predictive microbiology to end-users in an easy fashion. However, the integration of predictive microbiology models into stochastic Risk Assessment models remains as an important challenge to industry and academia due to the complexity derived from the multidisciplinary approach required for accomplish risk assessment studies which includes, among others, epidemiology, food technology, microbiology, numerical methods, etc.

The objective was to provide a general and easy-to-use framework for developing stochastic microbial Risk Assessment studies by means of the integration of predictive models, software engineering and database (i.e. MicroHibro).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

MicroHibro, which is an open source tool freely available at www.microhibro.com, has been developed in PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor) and Javascript languages, with open-source license, and based on the three-dimension nature of microbiology models that is: equation, prediction and insight. The software is structured in three main modules: "Predictive models", "Model validation" and "Risk models".

The Risk Assessment framework, i.e. "Risk models", has been devised based on an object-oriented system, in which models from MicroHibro databases can be retrieved and used to develop a stochastic Risk Assessment by defining specific variables as probability distributions. Exposure Assessment is carried out for any specific food process by selecting and joining models considering three microbial processes can occur: transfer, inactivation and growth. Then, risk estimate (i.e. Risk Characterization) can be obtained by selecting appropriate dose-response models included in MicroHibro database. By combining both phases in a stochastic environment, risk values, i.e. risk/serving and number of cases/year can be estimated for the tandem microorganism/food process selected. MicroHibro also contains a sensitivity analysis toolbox, including different methods (e.g. scenario analysis) to analyze and identify significant factors and variables in the quantitative Risk Assessment while it allows to assess risk model performance

RESULTS

A case-study of Risk Assessment of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 associated with the distribution chain of meat products was developed to illustrate the MicroHibro features. The example comprises the four-step scheme for Risk Assessment proposed by FAO/WHO (1999) and establishes some initial mathematical concepts to understand how the microorganisms spread through the Food Chain. The need for training users in the selection of the most suitable inputs and distributions according to the process to be simulated is highlighted through the present example in addition to the importance of performing sensitivity analysis make the model useful from a risk management perspective.

CONCLUSIONS

Microhibro has demonstrated to be a valuable predictive model tool offering end-users with innovative predictive models and applications in the quantitative Risk Assessment field. The dynamic character of the predictive model database assures the validity and use of MicroHibro for different food contexts and processes

as well as microorganisms. Furthermore, this computational tool is relevant educational resource to convey and teach concepts about quantitative microbial Risk Assessment facilitating the development of skills in Risk Assessment for end-users in the academic and industrial sector.

O46.- DEVELOPMENT OF A DSS FOR DETERMINING THE SHELF-LIFE OF HAKE PRESERVED IN A MODIFIED ATMOSPHERE RICH IN CARBON DIOXIDE.

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Keywords: Decision Support Systems, qPCR, fish, shelf-life, Photobacterium

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Total global food losses have been estimated to be around one-third of the total world food production for human consumption. The scenario is even more dramatic for fishery products since the perishability of fish makes it more susceptible to losses than any other food product. Therefore, the future of the fishery sector will be highly influenced by its capacity to address strategic challenges such as the management of the short shelf-life of its products. For this reason, the development of predictive tools able to help decision-making in companies is an evident necessity in order to address these challenges and satisfy the new market demands. The objective of this work was to develop a Decision Support System (DSS) enabling fishery industries to precisely determine the shelf-life of hake fillets preserved in a modified atmosphere rich in CO₂ at different storage temperatures.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Growth curves at different storage temperatures (1 to 10 °C) of ten microbiological groups (Pseudomonas, Shewanella, Photobacterium, lactic acid bacteria, enterobacteria, moulds and yeasts, mesophilic aerobic, mesophilic anaerobic, psychrotrophic aerobic and psychrotrophic anaerobic) found in the modified-atmosphere-preserved hake were obtained and then described mathematically with a microbial growth model.

In parallel a qPCR rapid method for the quantification of Photobacterium phosphoreum in hake was developed.

RESULTS

The Baranyi model showed the best fits to the experimental data, thus, it was chosen as primary model to describe the growth curves. Results of the fits showed an exponential relationship between LAG and VELmax values –for both specific and general flora- and the storage temperature. This allowed us to develop a simple and accurate secondary model. After the integration of the primary and secondary models, final equations were generated and validated.

Results obtained in this investigation also indicated that, in most scenarios, the microorganism responsible for the spoilage of hake stored in a rich in carbon dioxide atmosphere and refrigeration would be Photobacterium spp. This finding was confirmed by 16S rRNA sequenciation studies. However, since quantification of Photobacterium spp. initial load by classical microbiological techniques would last for days -what would make the DSS useless- a qPCR method for the quantification of Photobacterium phosphoreum in hake was developed.

CONCLUSIONS

Our results indicate that coupling qPCR quantification of Photobacterium phosphoreum with the developed final equation would allow estimating the shelf-life of hake fillets preserved in modified atmosphere at different storage temperatures in less than 4 hours. A DSS was built based on these findings and integrated in an excel sheet. This DSS would help fishery companies in decision making. Thus, they will be able to precisely determine the shelf-life of each batch. This DSS might also help in taking other decisions such as batch rejection and/or in fixing quality payment politics.

O47.- DEVELOPMENT OF A WEB BASED DECISION SUPPORT-TOOL TO PREDICT REMAINING SHELF LIFE OF MEAT BY TTI DISCOLOURATION

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Keywords: Remaining shelf life; TTI; decision-support tool; predictive modelling; meat

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The improvement and further development of Time Temperature Indicators (TTIs) in the last fifteen years made considerable progress, leading to reliable systems ready for the market. Even if benefits like temperature monitoring on a single-item basis over the entire chain, usability or great potential in the field of preventing food waste are known, a broad introduction to the market for chilled foods is still missing. Reasons for the delayed implementation of TTIs in the food sector are, amongst others, a lack of decision-support and software tools allowing the interpretation of the TTIs colour value regarding the product quality and remaining shelf life.

The aim of the study was to develop a TTI monitoring software tool to support the decision-making process in the incoming and outgoing inspection in the meat industry based on the colour signal of the TTI.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The software tool was developed for a photochromic TTI (OnVuTM). In the first step, mathematic models were developed for the adjustment of the label to the shelf life of different products. In the second step, a dynamic model was developed to predict the discolouration process of the TTI under fluctuating temperature conditions and to calculate the remaining shelf life of the labelled product. The mathematical models were implemented into a software solution focussing on the practical application of TTIs to monitor the temperature and remaining shelf life. Specific control and warning ranges were defined to support the decision-making process in the cold chain. Afterwards, the applicability of the TTI as an indirect shelf life indicator for fresh poultry was validated in a national poultry chain. During the pilot trial, the colour signal of the TTI was measured by a spectrophotometer, and in parallel, the microbial load of the poultry was analysed in different steps of the chain.

RESULTS

The microbial spoilage of the product was in agreement with the discolouration of the TTI, meaning that the TTI was capable of accurately reflecting the remaining shelf life of the product. For the application as a decision-support tool in the meat industry, the software runs with a web based user interface and allows the submission of supply chain data, such as storage conditions, date of packaging and the measured TTI response. Based on these data, the software output comprises information about the compliance of the cold chain and the remaining shelf life of the product in different steps of the chain. Particular action and warning ranges are computed by the model and can be adjusted to the specific needs of different supply chains. Additionally, an adjustment of the algorithm to different TTIs and specific product specifications is possible.

CONCLUSIONS

The software is a universal decision-support tool for the whole supply chain, facilitating the implementation of TTIs in the meat supply chain, optimising the management of storage and transportation facilities and giving information when action must be taken.

O48.- THE STARTEC DECISION SUPPORT TOOL FOR BETTER TRADEOFFS BETWEEN FOOD SAFETY, QUALITY, NUTRITION AND COSTS IN PRODUCTION

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Keywords: Decision support tool; Listeria; multidiciplinariry; industry; modelling

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Food producers make many decisions regarding suppliers, process conditions, distributors and customers. Even at "business as usual conditions" such decisions are complex. Decision support tools for food safety risk assessments are available, but are not much used in the industry. In the STARTEC project, funded by EU in FP7, a mapping of decision making and food production processes was carried out in three food companies located in three countries. The purpose was to investigate i) how decisions were made in production of advanced ready-to-eat foods, ii) which kind of decisions the industry needed support to make, and iii) which information a new decision support should contain. Based on these needs, the STARTEC tool was developed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The mapping was carried out in workshops and in "walk and talk" meetings in the food production facilities between researchers and staff in the food companies. An interview guide was used for comparison of the three companies. A prototype of an IT tool was developed consisting of a database, models, simulation options and user-interface. A restricted version of the tool, tutorials and a set of exercises were sent to internal and external end-users and experts, who filled a web-based questionnaire.

RESULTS

The main outcome was that decision support is needed when tradeoffs between safety, quality and costs had to be made. The need of support was particularly relevant on strategic level and in case of unintended deviations. Unlike other decision support tools, where pH, temperature and water activity are input parameters, the basis for the STARTEC tool is the process flow chart. Models for prediction of costs, quality and food safety changes were inserted at each process step. The models can be changed with other models in the database and other input data be adapted by the user. Simulations can be done at each step in the flow chart and the output be given either as curves or categorized in a traffic light system indicating "good", "sufficient" and "not acceptable/corrective actions needed". In addition, links to text files with guidelines about possible corrective actions, for instance change in the product formulation, relevant additives or preservation processes, were included.

The content of the tool was developed and tested for two formulations of pasta salad, packed in modified atmosphere or air, and at different temperatures. Among food safety parameters, growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* was focused particularly. Primary and secondary predictive models as well as guidelines for good practice were developed from wet lab studies with model and real products from industry companies.

CONCLUSIONS

The prototype IT tool was successfully developed. Even though the tool is developed for only few products so far, all users found it promising and useful if adapted to their product. The strongest point of the prototype tool is that it is flexible, can be adapted to any product, the multidisciplinary approach, the use of flow charts rather than input parameters many food companies not have in hand, and the categorization output and support section.

O49.-MODELLING MICROBIAL INACTIVATION WITH BIOINACTIVATION, A CASE STUDY

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Keywords: Mathematical modelling, microbial inactivation, non-isothermal conditions, freeware software, bioinactivation

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

A detailed characterization of the response of microbial populations to stresses is required in order to optimize heat treatments in industry. This process is commonly described using a range of microbial inactivation which, usually, contain a set of unknown model parameters. These coefficients describe the response of the bacteria population to the stress, allowing a comparison of the response for different conditions, as well as the generation of predictions.

In most cases, the values of the model parameters cannot be known before-hand. Instead, they must be estimated by performing inactivation experiments in the laboratory. Researchers, then, estimate the values of the model parameters based on this data, quantifying the resistance of the bacteria to the heat stress. The software *Bioinactivation* has been developed with the aim of easing the modelling work-flow. It includes several functions for both the model fitting and the generation of predictions. It is offered in two formats: an R package which can be extended or incorporated in other applications and a web application which serves as a user interface to some selected features.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Bioinactivation includes functions for the model fitting of isothermal or non-isothermal experiments, as well as for the generation of survivor curves and prediction intervals. The calculations are based on inactivation models commonly used in the literature (Bigelow, Peleg, Marfart and Geeraerd). Two fitting algorithms are included in the software (non-linear regression and Markov Chain Monte Carlo) which the user can choose at will. Furthermore, the user has the freedom to fix any model parameter to a desired value during the model fitting.

Bioinactivation is offered in two formats: an R package and a shiny web application. The R package has been uploaded to CRAN, making it publicly available. Hence, it can be extended or incorporated in other applications. The web application is a user-friendly interface to selected features of bioinactivation. It is available online and can be accessed from any computer with an internet connection.

RESULTS

In this communication, the features included in *Bioinactivation* will be illustrated through a case study. For this purpose, a data set of dynamic microbial inactivation generated in the laboratory will be used. This data will be modelled using the functions included in *Bioinactivation*.

CONCLUSIONS

Bioinactivation includes several functions for the modelling of microbial inactivation under isothermal or non-isothermal conditions which can be useful for other researchers in the field.

FRIDAY, SEPT. 29th

09: 00 - 10:30 h.: SESSION 9.- Modelling approaches using metagenomics data

Chairs: George Nychas (University of Athens) and Sara Bover (IRTA)

O50.- THE KEY ROLE OF PROCESS ANALYTICAL TECHNOLOGIES, INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND PREDICTIVE MODELING IN ENHANCING FOOD SAFETY

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Keywords: IoT, risk, communication

INTRODUCCION Y OBJETIVES

The issue of food safety is vital in recent years and although it is constantly reviewed in the light of new scientific evidence, its implementation is not always efficient in many different parts of the food chain. For example, systematic management of food safety via HACCP, GMP, etc., entails raw material selection, as well as control of conditions during processing and distribution with the latter being the weakest link of the system

MATERIAL AND METHODS

To address the issue, Information Technologies (IT), such as cloud computing and storage, big data, Internet of things, mobile web in combination with barcodes and smartphones, can be used to (i) offer the possibility to easily track the processes in the production, storage, transportation, retail, and even using phases of foods, (ii) tackle the important application of food quality (including safety) during processing.

RESULTS

Some quantitative evidence is available from studies and surveys at distribution, retail and domestic level to illustrate the magnitude of the problem. In general, it is well established that food handling and logistics, can substantially contribute to the risk and exposure to certain food-borne hazards. To face the weakest link in the food chain, the implementation of parameter quantification that allows the prediction of the behaviour of pathogenic bacteria or other hazards (mycotoxins) has been introduced in the food industry. It should be stressed however that there is limitation on the accumulation of many different pieces of information, which is essential (1) to understand the rationale for model development, and (2) model validation (if any) under isothermal conditions. In practice, however, temperature fluctuations may be frequent throughout food storage and distribution.

CONCLUSIONS

Information Technology can assist food producers, retailers, authorities and even consumers to take better decisions by providing them with data and tools that enhance decision-making process, consequently allowing better management of the natural resources. The food factory inspection data, government inspection data, testing organizations data and consumers purchasing information are integrated into food safety and nutrient test big data. Utilizing the data to explore the information that is needed by all the parties, can be served as a solution to the risk exchange problem faced by food stakeholders, while at the same time, the food safety problem can be solved through the contribution of different stakeholders.

O51.- PREDICTIVE MODELS FOR RISK AND QUALITY ASSESSMENT USING MOLECULAR-BASED SURVEILLANCE IN FOOD MANUFACTURING FACILITIES

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1 Creme Global

2 University College Dublin

Keywords: Metagenomics Software Risk Quality

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

In the last number of years, whole genome sequencing and metagenomics have become powerful tools in food safety and quality, providing detailed profiling of individual bacterial isolates and the microbiome of various environments and food matrices. However, little has been developed in terms of predictive models using this technology. The Sequencing Alliance for Food Environments (SAFE) project commenced in 2016 in Ireland, and is a three year multi-disciplinary, multi-partner initiative with the aim of gathering and integrating WGS and metagenomics data from manufacturing environments into a set of predictive risk/quality assessment models, as well as an associated software application.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Manufacturing facilities are currently under study from five industry partners, where different areas of the facilities are being monitored at six time points over two years. The participating companies are comprised of three international infant formula grade ingredient suppliers, an international cooked & fermented meat supplier and an SME nutritional ingredient supplier. The project has identified sampling plans customised to each facility that are being used to capture the dynamics of bacterial adaptation and microbial population changes over time and space, using WGS and metagenomic analysis. Specific isolates, identified from monitoring, will be sequenced in parallel with a microbiome characterisation of production environments. Using this data, the molecular epidemiology will be described and predictive models based on both bacterial isolates and their connection with the microbiome will be developed.

RESULTS

A bespoke sampling plan has been developed for each facility, based on the particular raw material flows associated with each and their specific layouts. Additionally, a set of metadata accompanying each sampling plan detailing parameters such as cleaning plans and environmental conditions has been identified. Currently, the first two rounds of environmental samples have been analysed using 16S metagenomics. These datasets will form the basis of a set of predictive risk and quality assessment models for the products produced in each facility.

CONCLUSIONS

So far, this project has successfully developed a bespoke sampling plan for each facility and gathered the first rounds of samples from each location. The first rounds of sequencing results have provided the basis of developing risk and quality models, specific to each facility under study.

O52.- IN SILICO SIMULATION OF LYTIC BACTERIOPHAGE POPULATION DYNAMICS AND ITS BACTERIAL HOST SALMONELLA TYPHI

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University of Khartoum, Sudan

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Simulation of bacteriophages' efficiency is the integration of their lytic cycle in destroying bacteria with those found in the disciplines of mathematics, statistics and computational systems in order to find the exact numbers of phages that can totally lysate bacteria.

This work was conducted to create a simulative model for the development of dynamic interactions between phages and their bacterial host (Salmonella typhi)

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The model was developed from calculations of bacteriophage replication to solve the distinct mechanisms of their efficiency including changes in lifecycles, therapeutic dose and mortality rates. Simulated data are compared with data obtained in vitro to assess the suitability of the model for multiplicity of infection

RESULTS

In vitro observations showed that the strength and mechanisms of bacteriophage can alter the determination of Salmonella typhi as antimicrobial therapy. The exponential growth curves solved the interactions of bacteriophage with their host in certain time decay, the changes in concentrations over time was solved by differential equations used to determine the therapeutic outcome.

The predicting of the potentiality of lytic phages in lysing Salmonella typhi can be estimated by using this mathematical model due the experiments environment conditions. Therefore, it is likely that the mathematical model could be made to work computationally by changing their values according to the laboratorial experiment conditions

CONCLUSIONS

In silico predicting of the potentiality of phages in lysing Salmonella typhi was estimated by using this model due the experiments conditions (in vitro). For more accurate estimations the model was programmed MS Excel sheet and simulated as a simple computer program.

O53.- A SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH TO SOURCE-ATTRIBUTION MODELLING USING METAGENOMICS DATA

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Keywords: metagenomics, source-attribution, machine learning

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The European project EFFORT (Ecology from Farm to Fork Of microbial drug Resistance and Transmission) aims to attribute the antimicrobial resistance found in humans to different animal reservoirs, using metagenomics data.

Most frequently, source-attribution is performed by comparing the distribution of bacterial subtypes obtained from different animal reservoirs and sources with subtypes isolated from humans. Subtyping methods have included serotyping, phage typing, MLVA typing, MLST typing and antimicrobial resistance patterns. The subtyping approach is based on the principle that there is a strong association between dominant subtypes and specific reservoirs.

The transition from typing of single isolates to metagenomics data requires an adaptation of the modelling approach. We hypothesize, however, that the above principle applies also to species-level resistomes, i.e. that there is a strong association between the abundance of particular resistance determinants and specific animal reservoirs. We will explore this using a supervised classification machine learning model.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Within EFFORT, stool samples from several animal species (pigs, broilers, turkeys, veal calves, trouts, dogs, cats and wildboars) have been collected and subsequently sequenced for metagenomics. Initially, we will use data from pigs and broilers.

From each of 20 conventional pig and 20 conventional broiler farms in 9 countries, one pooled sample of 25 fresh faecal droppings were collected representing animals close to slaughter. DNA was extracted for metagenomics analysis with HiSeq sequencing. The reads were mapped to ResFinder, a resistance gene database, in order to obtain the farm resistomes, i.e. the resistance genes present in each farm. In the supervised classification machine learning model, the features "abundances of resistance genes" will be used as predictors for "animal species". Data will be partitioned into training and testing datasets and run through different classification techniques (e.g. random forest). Final model selection will be based on model accuracy and out of sample accuracy. If successful, the model will be used to predict the distribution of the animal sources of resistant determinants found in data from human resistomes. Predictions will be made for data from stool samples collected from farmers and slaughterhouse workers in EFFORT (humans with occupational exposure), as well as surrogate data from city sewage samples (general human population).

RESULTS

Metagenomics has the potential to become a powerful tool in the future of epidemiology and risk assessment. However, data analysis and interpretation stands as a major challenge.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we will explore machine-learning as a tool to overcome the challenge of interpreting metagenomics results, in the context of source-attribution modelling.

11:00 - 12:00 h.: SESSION 10.- Predictive Mycology

Chairs: Sonia Marín (University of Lleida) and Jose Martínez Peinado (Complutense University of Madrid)

054.- MODELLING THE EFFECT OF MODIFIED ATMOSPHERE PACKAGING ON GERMINATION OF FILAMENTOUS FUNGI ISOLATED FROM DAIRY PRODUCTS

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Keywords: Modified atmosphere packaging ; conidial germination ; predictive mycology ; carbon dioxide ; dioxygen

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Modified-atmosphere packaging (MAP) is a commonly used method to control spoilage molds, thus extending food shelf life. The impact of MAP gases on conidial germination has been rarely studied. The present work aimed at quantifying independently the effects of dioxygen (O₂) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) partial pressures on conidial germination parameters.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

First, a specific MAP culture device using high oxygen-barrier plastic film was developed. It allowed simultaneous measurements of gas composition in Petri dish headspace and conidial germination directly on agar medium surface by phase-contrast microscopy. Using gamma-type models, median germination time (τ) and maximum germination percentage (P_{max}) parameters of *Paecilomyces niveus*, *Mucor lanceolatus*, *Penicillium brevicompactum*, *Penicillium expansum* and *Penicillium roqueforti* were then modelled as a function of O₂ partial pressure (CO₂ level set at 0.03% and O₂ levels ranging from 0% to 21%) and CO₂ partial pressure (O₂ level set at 5% and CO₂ levels ranging from 0.03% to 70%).

RESULTS

Gas compositions were stable for both gases throughout the experiments. Independently of the studied species, residual O₂ pressures < 1% or CO₂ partial pressures \leq 70% did not totally inhibit conidial germination. However, O₂ levels < 1% or CO₂ levels > 20% significantly increased τ and/or reduced P_{max} , depending on the fungal species.

CONCLUSIONS

The present method and results are of interest for predictive mycology applied to spoilage of MAP food products.

O55.- PROBABILITY MODELLING OF GROWTH OF ASPERGILLUS FLAVUS AND AFLATOXIN PRODUCTION IN LOW MOISTURE RAW MATERIALS

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University of Lleida, Spain

Keywords: mycotoxins, *Aspergillus*, cereals, nuts

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Human exposure to aflatoxins in foods is of great concern. The aim of this work was to go a step further on the use of predictive mycology as a strategy to mitigate the aflatoxin burden in postharvest raw materials

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The probability of growth and aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) production of aflatoxigenic *Aspergillus flavus*, under static and non-isothermal conditions, was studied. Logistic models, with temperature, water activity and time as explanatory variables, were fitted to the probability of growth and AFB1 production under constant temperature and water activity values. Subsequently, they were used to predict probabilities under non-isothermal scenarios

RESULTS

Levels of concordance from 90 to 100% were obtained in most of the cases. Furthermore, such models were tried to be validated in maize grain, where the levels of concordance were lower. Additionally, an experiment using 20 *A. flavus* isolates was carried out in order to check the impact of the intraspecies variability on the usefulness of probability models, including water activity and temperature as explanatory variables. Regression coefficient intervals of probability of growth models showed clear differences among the 20 growth models. Regression coefficients for the interaction factors were more variable among isolates than those for the individual factors. Based on the ability to initiate growth under marginal conditions it has been seen that the rate of growth is directly related to the easiness of adaptation to the environment, and this adaptation is strain dependent. Models for toxin production showed in general narrower boundaries, that is, toxin production occurred at a reduced number of conditions, compared to growth. However, the boundaries for toxin production are still a trait much more constant across the isolates than the amount of toxin produced, and it seems worthy to be modelled

CONCLUSIONS

The information obtained in the present work could be the starting point to predict the time for AFB1 production by *A. flavus* in several raw materials during transport and storage.

O56.- A BINOMIAL EQUATION DESCRIBING THE RELATION AMONG OPTICAL DENSITY, CELL NUMBER, AND CELL DRY WEIGHT IN YEAST SUSPENSIONS

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Keywords: optical density, cell number, cell dry weight, nephelometry

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The spectrophotometric measurement of the optical density (D) of microbial suspensions is the most used indirect method to estimate microbial biomass in liquids. It is based on the assumption that microbial suspensions follow the Lambert-Beer law, which establishes a linear proportionality between D and the particles concentration in diluted suspensions. It has been experimentally demonstrated that microbial suspensions follow the law up to a critical concentration and, moreover, that a linear proportionality was also observed between D and the dry weight concentration of the microbial suspensions. The objective of this work is to obtain a single equation that could be applied to estimate simultaneously cell number and dry weigh from the D values of yeasts suspensions in the whole range of values of the spectrophotometer, additionally providing the dry weight of a single cell

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Four yeasts genera were used: *Saccharomyces*, *Debaryomyces*, *Rhodotorula*, and *Zygosaccharomyces*. Cells were counted microscopically in a haemocytometer and weighted in filters. To find the better equation, it was assumed a polynomial form, and that the ratio between dry weight equation and cell number equation, which is an estimation of the dry weight of a single cell, should be (ideally) constant. This proportionality between both polynomials implied the following constraints: 1) The signs of the coefficients in both polynomials had to be the same, 2) They could not have positive roots, 3) The polynomials could not cross, and 4) Albeit ideally constant, the real dependence on D of the polynomials ratio must be monotonic. Thus, cell number and dry weight experimental data were systematically fitted to all possible polynomial choices, assuming null intercept, up to degree 5 (namely, monomial 1, binomial 1-2, trinomial 1-2-3, binomial 1-3, binomial 2-3, etc.), checking the fulfillment of the four constraints, and calculating the corresponding mean square error (MSE) in each case. Among the cell number and dry weight polynomial equations which fulfilled simultaneously the constraints, the one with the best fit to the experimental points, measured as the mean of the MSE of both equations, was selected

RESULTS

In this way, the equation which fulfilled the four constraints and had the best fit to the experimental points was the binomial 1-4. Preliminary experiments have shown that the 1-4 binomial equation can be used also for bacterial cultures

CONCLUSIONS

A single and simple binomial equation has been found that relates the optical density of yeasts suspensions, in an extended range from 0 to 2, both to the cell number and the cell dry weight. Additionally, the ratio between both equations provides an enhanced estimation of the dry weight of a single cell.

O57.- HEAT RESISTANCE AND EFFECT OF SUB-LETHAL HEAT TREATMENTS ON THE GROWTH OF *BYSSOCHLAMYS* SPORES.

Juliana Lane Paixão dos Santos¹, Sonay Merve Gülay², Simbarashe Samapundo¹, Jan Van Impe³, Anderson de Souza Sant`Ana⁴, Frank Devlieghere¹

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2 Department of Food Engineering, Istanbul Technical University, Istanbul, Turkey

3 Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Leuven, Ghent, Belgium

4 Department of Food Science, University of Campinas, Campinas, Brazil

Keywords: *Byssochlamys* sp., ascospores, heat resistance, growth, variability

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Heat resistant molds (HRMs) are well known for their ability to survive pasteurization and subsequently grow in high acid food products, causing great economic losses. The heat treatment(s) applied during processing can either inactivate or stimulate (activate) the germination of ascospores of HRMs in food products, which is of great concern to many food producers worldwide. Despite the increase of the number of studies focussed on the heat resistance of HRMs in different food matrices, little is known about inter-strain variability. The aims of this study are: (i) to assess the variability in heat resistance between *Byssochlamys* strains isolated at different processing stages (= raw materials, intermediate and final products) from two high acid fruit processing lines and (ii) to assess the effect of the heat treatment intensity on germination and growth of ascospores in acidified medium.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Byssochlamys strains isolated from strawberry purée and concentrated orange juice processing lines were used in the study. Ascospores suspensions were prepared after 30 days of growth at 30°C on malt extract agar (MEA) plates. The ascospores were harvested as follows. The MEA plates were flooded with 4 ml of sterile distilled water, after which the resulting suspension was filtered through sterile cotton and centrifuged at 8000g for 15 min at 4°C. The suspension were standardized to 106 – 107 ascospores ml⁻¹. Thermal resistance studies were performed on 30µl aliquots of ascospore suspension resuspended in buffer glucose solution (13° Brix, pH 3.5). The heat treatments were performed in a thermal cycler adjusted to 85°C, 90°C and 95°C after which the ascospore suspensions were cooled in an ice-water-bath. Thereafter, serial dilutions were performed in 96-well-plates containing 0.1% peptone broth. The serial dilutions were plated out in duplicate on MEA plates after which they were incubated at 30°C for 5-7 days. To assess the effect of heat treatment intensity on outgrowth of surviving ascospores, 10µl of heat treated ascospores were centrally inoculated on acidified MEA plates (pH 3.7) and incubated at 22°C. Growth was assessed by measuring the perpendicular colony diameters (mm) with a digital calipers in regular intervals.

RESULTS

The effect of heat treatment intensity was observed on survival counts with D-values (at 85, 90 and 95°C) ranging from 0.6 to 16 min. Although the native ascospores had the shortest lag times, the heat treated ones showed faster radial colony growth rates. Strains of *Byssochlamys fulva* showed the most heat resistance and subsequent shorter lag times and faster growth rates. It was also observed that variability between strains decreased with an increase in the intensity of the heat treatment applied.

CONCLUSIONS

The inter-strain variability observed reinforces the importance of considering distribution of inactivation and growth parameters in quantitative approach studies. The data can be also useful to design thermal processing.

Abstracts: Posters

SESSION 1:

Interdisciplinary approaches and new advances

P. 01.- ONE-STEP DIRECT DYNAMIC ANALYSIS AND MODEL DEVELOP IN PREDICTIVE MICROBIOLOGY

Lihan Huang

Eastern Regional Research Center, Wyndmoor, USA

P. 02.- A STOCHASTIC PREDICTIVE MODEL TO ESTIMATE SURVIVAL PROBABILITY OF *SALMONELLA ENTERICA* DURING THERMAL INACTIVATION.

Hiroki Abe, Kento Koyama, Shuso Kawamura, Shige Koseki

Hokkaido University

P. 03.- PERFORMANCE OF MICROBIOLOGICAL CRITERIA FOR HYGIENE CONTROL OF CAMPYLOBACTER IN GERMAN SLAUGHTERHOUSES.

A. Valero¹, F. Reich², F. Schill², L. Bungenstock², G. Klein²

¹ Dpt. Food Science and Technology, University of Cordoba. Campus Rabanales s/n. Córdoba (Spain)

² Institute for Food Quality and Food Safety, University of Veterinary Medicine Hanover, Foundation, Bischofsholer Damm 15, Hanover, Germany

P. 04.- PREDICTING GROWTH OF *BROCHOTHRIX THERMOSPACTA* AT CHANGING TEMPERATURES BASED ON A BIAS-VARIANCE TRADEOFF METHOD.

Mathieu Flinders¹, Philippe Nimmegeers², Simen Akkermans², Vasilis Valdramidis¹, Jan Van Impe²

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²Sustainable Chemical Process Technology TC, Room 00.L020, Technology Campuses Ghent and Aalst, Gebroeders De Smetstraat 1, Gent, BELGIUM.

P. 05.- PHASMAFOOD; PORTABLE PHOTONIC MINIATURISED SMART SYSTEM FOR ON-THE-SPOT FOOD QUALITY SENSING.

George KOUTALIERIS², Paraskevas BOURGOS³, George - John Nychas¹

¹ITRASOFT

²WINGS-IT

³Agricultural University of Athens

P. 06.- APPLICATION OF A MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION ANALYSIS METHOD TO LINK FOOD SAFETY, WASTE PREVENTION AND FOOD SUSTAINABILITY.

Steven Duret¹, Laurent Guillier², Hong-Minh Hoang¹, Evelyne Derens-Bertheau¹, Onrawee Laguerre¹

¹National Research Institute of Science and Technology for Environment and Agriculture

²French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety

P. 07.- GROWTH MODELING OF *WEISSELLA VIRIDESCENS* BY REAL-TIME QUANTITATIVE PCR (QPCR).

Wiaslan Figueiredo Martins, Danielle De Sousa Severo, Fernanda Cunha Marques, Gláucia Maria Falcão de Aragão

Federal University of Santa Catarina

P. 08.- QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF MINCED BEEF USING IMAGE ANALYSIS AND CHEMOMETRICS. VALIDATION UNDER DYNAMIC TEMPERATURE PROFILES.

George-John Nychas, Efstathios Panagou, Ioulietta Fakiri

Agricultural University of Athens, Dept. of Food Science and Human Nutrition

SESSION 2:

Predictive models and complex modelling approaches for food safety and quality

P. 09.- MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF MICROBIAL DEVELOPMENT IN MEAT TREATED WITH ROSEMARY ESSENTIAL OIL AND UVC LIGHT.

Mariana Fernández Blanco, Ana Julia Amasino, Irene del Carmen Pena, Gladys Laporte, Pablo de la Sota, Daniela Olivera, Fernanda Coll Cárdenas

Facultad Ciencias Veterinarias, UNLP

P. 10.- MODELLING SPATIOTEMPORAL DYNAMICS IN A FOOD MATRIX INITIATED BY INJECTED STARTER CULTURES.

Thorsten Stefan

University of Hohenheim

P. 11.- QUANTIFYING THE ADAPTATION OF BACTERIA TO THERMAL STRESSES, A MODEL SEPARATING TYPICAL RESISTANCE AND STRESS ADAPTATION.

Arturo Esnoz¹, Alberto Garre¹, Jose A. Egea², Juan Pablo Huertas¹, Gerardo Gonzalez¹, Pablo S. Fernandez¹, Alfredo Palop¹

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²Departamento de Matemática Aplicada y Estadística, Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena, Antiguo Hospital de Marina (ETSII).

P. 12.- MODELLING THE GROWTH KINETICS OF *PSEUDOMONAS* SPP. ON WHITE BUTTON MUSHROOM UNDER NON-ISOTHERMAL CONDITIONS.

Fatih Tarlak, Cigdem Yuceel Tarlak, Murat Ozdemir

Department of Chemical Engineering, Gebze Technical University, Gebze, Kocaeli, Turkey

P. 13.- GROWTH MODELS OF LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES AND SALMONELLA IN COOKED MEAT UNDER STATIC AND DYNAMIC TEMPERATURES.

Cheng-an Hwang

ERRC-ARS-USDA, 600 East Mermaid Lane, Wyndmoor, USA

P. 14.- BEHAVIOR OF *BACILLUS CEREUS* SPORES IN COOKED BEANS UNDER ISOTHERMAL CONDITIONS FROM 10 TO 49°C .

Vijay Juneja¹, Abhinav Mishra², Abani Pradhan², Tim Mohr³

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²University of Maryland, 0112 Skinner Building, College Park.

³Science Staff, OPHS, FSIS, USDA, 530 Center Street, NE, Suite 401, Salem.

P. 15.- MODELLING GROWTH/NO GROWTH BOUNDARY CONDITIONS OF *BACILLUS* SPECIES SPORES.

Sayuri Kuroda¹, Wataru Ishida², Toshiyuki Miyazaki², Shuso Kawamura¹, Shige Koseki¹

¹Hokkaido University

²Nisshin Seifun Group Inc.

P. 16.- MODELLING OF TTI SMART LABELS RESPONSE FOR MONITORING SHELF LIFE AND HISTAMINE FORMATION IN AQUACULTURED MUGIL CEPHALUS FISH.

Papamichael Eirini, Tsironi Theofania, Giannoglou Marianna, Ntzimani Athina, Taoukis Petros

National Technical University of Athens School of Chemical Engineering, Laboratory of Food Chemistry and Technology

P. 17.- GROWTH PARAMETER ESTIMATES OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN COOKED CHICKEN: EFFECT OF PREPARATION OF INOCULUMS.

Tina Birk¹, Sussi Smith Ottosen², Tina Beck Hansen¹

¹The National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, Kemitorvet, Lyngby, Denmark

²University College Zealand, Campus Roskilde, Maglegaardsvej 8, Denmark

P. 18.- STAPHTOX RISK PREDICTOR – A DYNAMIC MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR PREDICTING THE RISK FOR STAPHYLOCOCCOUS ENTEROTOXIN IN MEAT.

Annemarie Gunvig, Mette Stenby Andresen, Claus Borggaard

DMRI, Danish Technological Institute

P. 19.- ULTRASOUND ASSISTED THAWING OF COD FROZEN FILLETS.

Adriana Antunes, Santiago Condón, Javier Raso, Guillermo Cebrián, Ignacio Álvarez

University of Zaragoza. Instituto Agroalimentario de Aragón

P. 20.- THERMAL INACTIVATION KINETICS OF *SALMONELLA ENTERICA* SEROVARS AND *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* ARE PRACTICALLY SIMILAR.

J. Hein M. van Lieverloo¹, Martijn B. Fox³, Marjon H.G. Wells-Bennik³, Heidy (M.W.) den Besten⁴, Marcel H. Zwietering⁴

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⁴Laboratory of Food Microbiology, Wageningen University, Bornse Weilanden, The Netherlands

**P. 21.- INNOVATIVE MODELING TECHNIQUES FOR THE QUALITY AND MICROBIAL SAFETY OF
FOODBORNE PATHOGENS IN LEAFY GREENS.**

Abani Pradhan, Abhinav Mishra

University of Maryland, College Park, USA

**P. 22.- MATHEMATICAL MODELS FOR DESCRIBING THE EFFECT OF ELECTROPORATION ON AUTOLYSIS
OF YEAST CELLS.**

George Dimopoulos¹, Nefeli Stefanou², Varvara Andreou¹, Petros Taoukis¹

¹National Technical University of Athens, Greece

²University of Ioannina, Greece

**P. 23.- *ESCHERICHIA COLI* STRAINS ACID-ADAPTED TO A CONTROLLED LOW PH SHOW INCREASED
HEAT RESISTANCE COMPARED TO NON ACID-ADAPTED.**

**Leticia Ungaretti Haberbeck¹, Xiang Wang³, Chris Michiels², Frank Devlieghere³, Mieke Uyttendaele³,
Annemie H. Geeraerd¹**

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2 Laboratory of Food Microbiology, Depart. of Microbial and Molecular Systems, KU Leuven, BE

3 Laboratory of Food Microbiology and Food, Preservation, Depart. of Food Safety and Food Quality, Ghent University, Ghent, BE.

**P. 24.- IMPACT OF COOKING PROCEDURES AND STORAGE PRACTICES ON CONSUMER EXPOSURE TO
LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES AND *SALMONELLA*.**

Alessandra De Cesare¹, Eva Doménech², Damiano Comin³, Gerardo Manfreda¹

1 University of Bologna

2 Universitat Politècnica de Valencia

3 Istituto Zooprofilattico delle Venezie

**P. 25.- QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT (SPME/GC-MS) OF SPOILAGE COMPOUNDS AND EFFECTS OF
THERMAL SHOCKS IN *ALICYCLOBACILLUS* SPP. SPORES.**

**Leonardo do Prado Silva¹, Adriana T. Godoy², Juan M. Oteiza³, Bernadette D. G. de Melo Franco⁴, Marcos
N. Eberlin², Anderson S. Sant'Ana¹**

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⁴ Department of Food and Experimental Nutrition, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of São Paulo, São Paulo, SP, Brazil

P. 26.- MODELLING BIOCIDES AND BACTERIA INTERACTION IN CHEMICAL DISINFECTION.

Miriam R. García¹, Marta L. Cabo²

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² Microbiology and Technology of Marine Products, IIM-CSIC, Vigo, Spain

P. 27.- MODELING *WEISSELLA VIRIDESCENS* INACTIVATION BY ULTRAVIOLET RADIATION.

Cíntia Maia Braga, Isabella Medeiros Souza, Leticia Floriano, Larissa Ramos, Josamaique Gilson I Venera, Andreia Tremarin, Jorge Ninow, Gláucia Maria Falcão Aragão

Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC)

P. 28.- PREDICTING THE GROWTH OF SALMONELLA IN CHICKEN UNDER DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE PROFILES.

Tatiane Milkiewicz¹, Daniel Longhi², Alessandro Galvão¹, Weber Robazza¹

¹ Santa Catarina State University, Pinhalzinho/SC, Brazil

² Federal University of Paraná, Jandaia do Sul/PR, Brazil

P. 29.- DEVELOPMENT OF A DYNAMIC MODEL FOR A REAL-TIME KIMCHI FRESHNESS MONITORING SYSTEM DURING DISTRIBUTION.

Ji-Young Kim, Byeong-Sam Kim, Junemo Koo, Jong-Hoon Kim

¹ Korea Food Research Institute

² Kyung Hee University

³ Korea Food Research Institute

P. 30.- GROWTH AND SURVIVAL OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN BLUE MUSSELS (*MYTILUS EDULIS*).

Hjorleifur Einarsson¹, Murad Mufty²

¹ Faculty of Natural Resource Sciences, University of Akureyri, Akureyri, Iceland

² Fish Inspection & Quality Control, Department of Fisheries, Khulna, Bangladesh

P. 31.- COMPARATIVE KINETIC STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF PULSED ELECTRIC FIELDS (PEF) AND HIGH PRESSURE (HP) PASTEURIZATION ON POMEGRANA.

Sotiris Kottaridis, Eleni Gogou, Petros Taoukis

National Technical University of Athens

P. 32.- EFFECT OF OREGANO ESSENTIAL OIL ON THE SHELF-LIFE OF VACUUM-PACKED SLICED HAM STORED UNDER NON-ISOTHERMAL CONDITIONS.

Natielle Maria Costa MENEZES¹, Daniel Angelo LONGHI², Wiaslan Figueiredo Martins¹, Gláucia Maria Falcão de ARAGÃO¹

¹ Federal University of Santa Catarina

² Federal University of Paraná

P. 33.- MODELLING OF *ALICYCLOBACILLUS ACIDOTERRESTRIS* INACTIVATION IN APPLE JUICE USING THERMOSONICATION TECHNOLOGIES.

Andreia Tremarin¹, Teresa R. S. Brandão², Cristina L. M. Silva²

¹ Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC)

² Universidade Catolica Portuguesa, CBQF - Centro de Biotecnologia e Química Fina e Laboratorio Associado, Escola Superior de Biotecnologia

P. 34.- FIELD ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECT OF NATURAL NITRITE SUBSTITUTE ON THE GROWTH OF SPOILAGE ORGANISMS AND *CLOSTRIDIUM SPOROGENES* IN COOKED MEAT PRODUCTS.

Ifigeneia Makariti, Nikolaos Grivokostopoulos, Zavitsanou Artemis, Dimitrios Doultzos, Panagiotis Skandamis

Agricultural University of Athens

P. 35.- MODELLING THE FATE AND SEROTYPE VARIABILITY OF ISOLATED *L. MONOCYTOGENES* STRAINS ON GRATED CURED EWE'S CHEESE AT DIFFERENT STORAGE TEMPERATURES.

Marta Hernández¹, Óscar Esteban-Carbonero², Patricia González-García¹, A. Valero³, David Rodríguez-Lázaro²

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P. 36.- MATHEMATICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE COMBINED EFFECT OF CHLORINE, BENZYL ISOTHIOCYANATE, EXPOSURE TIME AND CUT SIZE ON THE REDUCTION OF SALMONELLA IN FRESH-CUT LETTUCE DURING WASHING PROCESS.

Sofia Cuggino^{1*}, Isabel Bascón Villegas², Francisco Rincón², G.D. Posada-Izquierdo, Alejandra Pérez Agostini¹, Javier Marugán³, Cristina Pablos Carro³, Fernando Pérez-Rodríguez²

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³Department of Chemical and Environmental Technology (ESCET), Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, C/ Tulipán s/n, 28933 Móstoles (Madrid), Spain

P.37.- INHIBITORY EFFECT OF *LACTOBACILLUS SAKEI* AGAINST *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* GROWTH IN SMOKED MEDITERRANEAN FISH PRODUCTS FROM MARINE AQUACULTURE.

Araceli Bolívar, Jean Carlos Correia Peres Costa, G.D. Posada-Izquierdo, Antonio Valero, Gonzalo Zurera, Fernando Pérez-Rodríguez

Department of Food Science and Technology, International Campus of Excellence in the AgriFood Sector, University of Córdoba, Campus de Rabanales C-1, Córdoba (Spain)

SESSION 3:

Individual-based models

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Alejandra Sanín-Villarreal¹, Johanna Andrea Serna-Jiménez², Yessica Lorena Díaz-Martinez², Johannes Delgado-Ospina¹

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Laincer Firdousse, Tamendjari Abderazak, Belkacemi Hayette

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Lubomír Valík, Martina Koňuchová, Anna Šípkov

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Israa El-Nemr, Mohanad Mushtaha, Hammad Asim, Ipek Goktepe

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P. 79.- MODELLING THE INTERACTION OF GROWTH OF A BACTERIOCINOGENIC *LACTOBACILLUS SAKEI* AND *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN COOKED HAM.

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Sigrun J. Hauge¹, Taran Skjerdal², Alessandra De Cesare³, Ole Alvseike¹

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Miguel de Alba Aparicio, Lars Valentin, Christian Thöns, Armin Weiser, Carolina Plaza Rodríguez, Matthias Filter

Federal Institute for Risk Assessment, Germany

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Salvador Cubero González, Arícia Possas, Fernando Pérez-Rodríguez

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Christian Kern, Thorsten Stefan, Jörg Hinrichs

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Maria Sanz¹, Patricia Moreno¹, Maria Consuelo Pina², Maria Dolores Rodrigo¹, Antonio Martinez¹

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P. 89.- MODELING COMPETITION IN CO-CULTURES OF A *SACCHAROMYCES NON-CEREVISIAE* SPECIES AND *S. CEREVISIAE* IN WINE FERMENTATION.

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P. 90.- MODELLING AND STUDY OF DRYING VARIABLES IN THE DRYING OF GRAPE WITHOUT PEDICEL.

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P. 92.- PREDICTING *BYSSOCHLAMYS FULVA* ASCOSPORES BEHAVIOR BASED ON *CONIDIA* DATA.

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SESSION 1: Interdisciplinary approaches and new advances

P. 01.- ONE-STEP DIRECT DYNAMIC ANALYSIS AND MODEL DEVELOP IN PREDICTIVE MICROBIOLOGY

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Keywords: Dynamic analysis, numerical analysis, optimization

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Predictive modeling is an effective tool for estimating the microbial shelf-life and conducting risk assessments of foodborne pathogens in raw and processed foods. Inverse analysis is a method used to determine the kinetics of microbial growth and survival in foods. The traditional inverse analysis in predictive microbiology is a three-step approach that relies on isothermal experiments to determine the kinetic parameters. This approach is time-consuming and labor-intensive, and the errors are accumulated and propagated in each step of data collection and analysis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

One-step dynamic analysis is a new inverse method that directly constructs a tertiary model from dynamic experiments to determine the kinetic parameters and growth boundaries. During one-step dynamic analysis, food samples inoculated with microorganisms of interest are exposed to dynamically changing temperature conditions that may go beyond the growth limits. Differential equations will be used in combination with suitable secondary models to construct a tertiary model that describes the growth and survival of microorganisms under dynamic conditions. The kinetic parameters will be determined by application of numerical methods and optimization for inverse analysis.

RESULTS

This presentation will demonstrate the application of one-step dynamic analysis for a range of foodborne pathogens, including *Listeria monocytogenes* in chicken breast meat, *Clostridium perfringens* in cooked beef, *L. monocytogenes* in cooked pork, *Salmonella* Paratyphi A in roasted marinated chicken, and *Salmonella* Enteritidis in liquid egg whites. The predictive models for these microorganisms are validated with both isothermal and dynamic curves. The results have shown that the root mean square error (RMSE) of the predictions can be as low as 0.5 log CFU.

CONCLUSIONS

The studies have shown that the one-step dynamic analysis is an accurate and efficient method, and can be a viable alternative to the traditional isothermal method for inverse analysis in predictive microbiology.

P. 02.- A STOCHASTIC PREDICTIVE MODEL TO ESTIMATE SURVIVAL PROBABILITY OF *SALMONELLA ENTERICA* DURING THERMAL INACTIVATION.

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Keywords: stochastic model, cumulative gamma distribution

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Thermal treatment intended to inactivate microorganisms in processed foods may cause deterioration of their quality. Therefore, the negative impact of thermal treatment on food quality should be minimised to maintain and improve the quality of the food products. Conventionally, kinetic models, such as the thermal death kinetic model, help optimize conditions of thermal inactivation in food processors. These models indicate changes in cell survival numbers over time, but do not estimate changes in survival probability during thermal treatment. Nevertheless, stochastic predictive models can estimate survival probability and hence would enable optimization of risk-based inactivation condition. This study aimed to develop a model based on cumulative gamma distribution to estimate the changes in survival probability of *Salmonella enterica* during thermal inactivation. In addition, the time required for *Salmonella* inactivation predicted by the developed stochastic model was compared with that predicted by the thermal death kinetic model.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A strain of *Salmonella enterica* Oranienburg was used as a representative of highly thermotolerant strains. Bacterial suspensions with an initial concentration of 1×10^n CFU/100 μ L ($n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$) were prepared by 10-fold dilution of the cultures. Subsequently, 100 μ L of inoculum was transferred into each well of a 96-well microplate to obtain 96 replicates. The microplates were heated at 60, 62, 64, and 66°C in a thermal cycler for arbitrary durations, and further incubated at 37°C for 24 h to confirm death or survival of the cells by measuring turbidity. The changes in the survival probability were evaluated using cumulative gamma distribution. The fitted parameters were described as a function of initial cell numbers and duration of heating expressed as polynomial functions. In parallel, thermal death kinetics of *S. Oranienburg* cells was examined using the conventional method of plate counting of viable cells.

RESULTS

The changes in survival probability over time during heating were successfully described as a cumulative gamma distribution (root mean square error < 0.10). The 50% survival contour line of the function of duration of heating and target log-reduction estimated by the survival probability model was similar to the contour line derived from the survival kinetic model. In contrast, the lower survival probability (e.g. 0.00001%) contour lines estimated by the survival probability model differed notably (137 s at the maximum) from those estimated by the survival kinetic model. The stochastic model based prediction estimated shorter inactivation time than that estimated by the survival kinetics model to achieve the same inactivation effect.

CONCLUSIONS

The stochastic predictive model, which is a risk-based approach, would possibly shorten duration of thermal treatment used for bacterial inactivation and thus, would ensure safety and high quality of processed foods.

P. 03.- PERFORMANCE OF MICROBIOLOGICAL CRITERIA FOR HYGIENE CONTROL OF CAMPYLOBACTER IN GERMAN SLAUGHTERHOUSES.

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Keywords: Campylobacter, microbiological criteria, negative binomial, sampling schemes

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Campylobacter is mostly considered as an important foodborne pathogen having a high impact on public health burden. Source allocation studies identified the broiler meat as the most important single food transmission vehicle of Campylobacter. In this regard, microbiological targets are under development in EU and characterization of microbial contamination seems to be an essential part to implement sampling schemes.

The aim of this study was to analyze broiler batches processed at three conventional slaughterhouses in Germany for their Campylobacter load at the end of processing. Microbial contamination of studied flocks was assessed through the comparison of log normal, Poisson-log normal and Negative binomial distributions. Sampling procedures were subsequently applied to derive consequences for meat acceptability.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Samples of broiler neck skin and caecal content (356 batches) were collected in three German slaughterhouses (A, B and C) for fresh meat production from conventional reared broilers over a period of 36 months from July 2013 to June 2016. Microbial analyses of five-pooled neck skin samples and one-pooled of caeca samples out of ten individual samples were performed in accordance to ISO 10272-2. Different concentration distributions (i.e. log normal, Poisson-log normal and Negative binomial) were fitted to observed data through MLE by using R v3.2.3 (fitdistrplus for censored data and poislog packages). Sampling plan performance was assessed by setting 500 and 1000 cfu/g as microbial limits.

RESULTS

In this study, the individual prevalence of Campylobacter positive broiler batches processed at the three slaughterhouses ranged between 21.7% (95% CL: 21.1 – 22.3%) and 47.9% (95% CL: 47.07 – 48.71%). Significant differences among mean Campylobacter counts in neck skin samples were denoted according to the slaughterhouse evaluated. The results showed that distributions were left-shifted thus indicating a high proportion of low microbial counts in the samples. Negative binomial regression provided better adjustment at low contamination levels (

CONCLUSIONS

The evaluation of possible sampling plans led to the conclusion that microbiological sampling at the end of the slaughter process would be appropriate to evaluate the overall slaughter hygiene and should be implemented as a verification tool for instance in connection for slaughter level intervention measures.

P. 04.- PREDICTING GROWTH OF *BROCHOTHRIX THERMOSPACTA* AT CHANGING TEMPERATURES BASED ON A BIAS-VARIANCE TRADEOFF METHOD.

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Keywords: predictive modelling; growth; dynamic temperature; ComBase; statistical learning; bias-variance tradeoff; *Brochothrix thermosphacta*;

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The bias-variance tradeoff is a key concept of statistical learning. In the context of predicting microbial growth at changing temperature, we show how reducing model complexity – using cross-validation for model selection – can improve predictive performance.

The standard two-step procedure consists in fitting a secondary model, such as the modified Ratkowsky model (MRM) of Zwietering et al (1991) or the cardinal temperature model with inflection (CTMI) of Rosso et al (1993), to growth rates measured at a range of temperatures. Our single-step approach has three main advantages: (i) the objective of the parameter estimation corresponds to the purpose of the predictive model; (ii) the training set is enriched with dynamic data; (iii) the experimental workload is minimized

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We analyze the ComBase (www.combase.cc) data of Baranyi et al (1995) and McClure et al (1993) for growth of *B thermosphacta* in TSB: 25 experiments divided into 5 datasets according to [NaCl], pH and temperature profile. Polynomial splines with $k = 1$ to 4 degrees of freedom relate instantaneous growth rate and temperature. Predictive performance is estimated using leave-one-out cross-validation. Performance benchmarks are provided by MRM and CTMI (both $k = 4$), and the square root model with lag ($k = 3$) of Baranyi et al (1995)

RESULTS

MRM and CTMI provided the best explanation of the data in the sense of minimizing the residuals. Splines with 2 or 3 degrees of freedom made the best predictive models in terms of the standard error of cross-validation. The inherent bias of the spline models is compensated by their lower variance compared to MRM and CTMI

CONCLUSIONS

The approach adopted in this work is applicable to all areas of predictive microbiology. It should be of particular interest to practitioners of quantitative risk assessment and management concerned with the construction of robust and reliable predictive models

P. 05.- PHASMAFOOD; PORTABLE PHOTONIC MINIATURISED SMART SYSTEM FOR ON-THE-SPOT FOOD QUALITY SENSING.

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Keywords: sensors, quality, predictive

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the project is to design and implement a parameterized, knowledge-based, multi-target food sensitive mini-portable system, with heterogeneous micro-scale photonics for on-the-spot food quality sensing and shelf-life prediction.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In particular, the miniaturized smart integrated system will be able to detect food hazards, spoilage (incl. early sign of spoilage) and food fraud through the combined bio-chemical data analysis and additionally will be able to perform food components/additives analysis, food identification and prediction of food shelf-life.

RESULTS

The following use case will be addressed during the project: Use case 1: Detection of mycotoxins in various grains and nuts. Aflatoxins detection. A simple, convenient ultraviolet test makes it possible to detect the possible presence of aflatoxin. Use case 2: Detection of early sign of spoilage and spoilage in fruits, vegetables, meat, fish: combined with estimation on product expiration date. Use case 3: Detection of food fraud: Adulteration of alcoholic beverages, oil, milk and meat. 3 sensor devices will be integrated in the miniaturised smart sensor node: i) a MEMS-based near IR spectrometer (950-1900 nm), ii) a UV-VIS spectrometer (450-900 nm) and iii) a micro-camera. Moreover 3 light sources will also be integrated to support the sensing functionality: i) UV-LED, ii) white LED and iii) a miniaturized IR emitter. Smart signal processing of the spectrum images will be performed by an advanced micro controller, integrated in the sensing device. The data will be communicated to a smartphone device, where the spectroscopy analysis will take place with the help of a cloud-base application connected to a reference database. Advanced detection algorithms will be deployed both in the level of cloud and the smartphone application.

CONCLUSIONS

PhasmaFOOD system will enable common consumers for on the spot food quality sensing and shelf-life prediction.

P. 06.- APPLICATION OF A MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION ANALYSIS METHOD TO LINK FOOD SAFETY, WASTE PREVENTION AND FOOD SUSTAINABILITY.

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Keywords: multi-criteria decision analysis, food waste prevention, food sustainability, cooked ham, food safety

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

For many years, food policy was driven by food safety. More recent concerns for climate change and growing demand of consumers for sustainable foods lead governmental institutions to include other aspects in food policy. An example of the evolution of food policy is the fight of the European Union for the prevention of food waste and losses. However, the inclusion of various aspects in the definition of new policy may be challenging due to possible conflicts between different objectives (e.g. food safety, food waste and energy consumption) and the feasibility of the comparison between various outcomes of those objectives (e.g. disability adjusted life years, amount of food waste, energy consumption in kWh). Hence, methodologies with the capacity to overcome those challenges and the knowledge of their limitations are essential to support decision makers. The objective of this study is to propose a methodology that could support decision making and considering various aspects linked to food safety and food sustainability.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study focuses on the cold chain of cooked ham including refrigerated transport, storage in a cold room in a supermarket, display cabinet, transport by consumer and household refrigerator. First, a model developed to predict time temperature profiles of refrigerated ready to eat foods from the operating conditions (e.g. thermostat temperature setting) of refrigeration equipment was used and coupled to energy consumption models for refrigeration equipment. The time temperature profiles were used in predictive microbiology models to predict the growth of pathogens and spoilage bacteria. Various scenarios were tested to evaluate changes on three outputs: (i) consumer's exposure to *Listeria monocytogenes*, (ii) food waste due to the growth of lactic bacteria and (iii) energy consumption of the different equipment of the cold chain.

A methodology based on hierarchical multi-criteria analysis was applied to identify the most appropriate scenarios considering the different outputs of the model and their respective weights. The contradictions of the three outputs and the limitations of the methodology are discussed.

RESULTS

Results show that the weights attributed to the model outcomes (choice of the decision maker) influence the rank of the scenarios. For example, when more weight is attributed to the food safety criterion, it highlights the importance of setting a lower temperature in the domestic fridge whereas when more weight is attributed to food waste; it highlights the importance for the consumer to plan a weekly menu.

CONCLUSIONS

Multi-criteria decision analysis methods could help governmental institutions in the development of new food policy including aspects such as food safety, food waste and food sustainability.

**P. 07.- GROWTH MODELING OF *WEISSELLA VIRIDESCENS* BY REAL-TIME QUANTITATIVE PCR (QPCR).
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Keywords: Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB), qPCR, recN gene, modeling, *Weissella viridescens*

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The lactic acid bacteria (LAB) *Weissella viridescens* has been reported as responsible for spoilage of meat products. In order to identify, quantify and model this bacterium growth in culture medium, a SYBR-Green Real-Time Quantitative PCR (qPCR) procedure has been developed having the *recN* gene as a target.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

To confirm the efficiency and sensitivity of the SYBR-Green based assay, it was performed a melting curve analysis to check the specificity of the amplification reaction during the qPCR. The growth curve for a *W. viridescens* ATCC 12706T pure culture enumerated by qPCR was compared to that enumerated by plate counts. Experiment was conducted in optimal growth temperature (30 °C) until the stationary phase. Baranyi and Roberts' model was fitted to growth data using Matlab® software.

RESULTS

The results showed that the primers were specific for *W. viridescens* with specific signals in melting temperatures of $81.3 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ for this species. Standard curves presented efficiency values of 112% and suitable correlation coefficients ($R^2 > 0.99$). Limit of detection is 1.2 log DNA copy number, corresponding to 3.7 log CFU, a suitable CFU enumeration range for spoilage LAB, considering that they should be initially present in meat products. The statistically significant difference (p-value of < 0.05) between qPCR and plate count was observed only in the exponential phase (15 hours of cultivation), corresponding to 7.95 and 7.6 log CFU, respectively. The model presented a good fit ($R^2 > 0.99$) for both curves. According to the statistical indices, curve by qPCR presented values slightly bigger (accuracy = 1.5917 and RMSE = 0.2780 log CFU) than the curve by plate count (accuracy = 1.4341 and RMSE = 0.2364 log CFU), except for the Bias value (Bias = 1.0 log CFU) for both. Curve by qPCR presented higher values for growth parameters ($\mu_{\text{max}} = 0.87 \pm 0.17 \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $\lambda = 4.15 \pm 0.82 \text{ h}$) than the curve by plate count ($\mu_{\text{max}} = 0.74 \pm 0.05 \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $\lambda = 2.09 \pm 0.9 \text{ h}$). Indeed, curve enumerated by qPCR and by plate counts are convergent for *W. viridescens* at 30 °C.

CONCLUSIONS

The data presented here shows that the SYBR-Green was suitable for using in qPCR assay which provided a specific and efficient method for *W. viridescens* detection and quantification. These results highlight the importance to combine molecular techniques with classical and predictive microbiology, to provide a new tool for studying the meat products spoilage microbiota.

P. 08.- QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF MINCED BEEF USING IMAGE ANALYSIS AND CHEMOMETRICS. VALIDATION UNDER DYNAMIC TEMPERATURE PROFILES

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Keywords: multi-spectral imaging, meat spoilage, chemometrics

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Hyperspectral (HSI) and multispectral imaging (MSI) have been proposed as non-invasive rapid methods for monitoring quality of foods and in particular meat and meat products. The aim of this work was to monitor spoilage of minced beef using multi-spectral imaging during storage of meat under isothermal conditions and validate further the developed models under fluctuating temperature conditions with different batches of meat

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Fresh minced beef was stored under aerobic conditions at three different isothermal conditions (2, 6, and 10°C). Total viable counts (TVC) were measured throughout storage in combination with sensory assessment (odor, color and overall appearance) for the determination sensory quality (fresh vs. spoiled). Additionally, the spectral fingerprints of the meat samples during storage were recorded by means of multispectral imaging captured in 18 different wavelengths ranging from 405 to 970 nm. The collected spectra were used to develop multivariate models for the determination of minced beef quality. The developed models were validated with two independent experiments using different batches of meat undertaken at dynamic temperature conditions, based on two fluctuating temperature scenarios with periodic changes (2°C@8h/6°C@8h/10°C@8h and 4°C@12h/8°C@12h)

RESULTS

Hierarchical cluster analysis was initially performed as an unsupervised learning approach to discriminate the samples of the experiment undertaken under isothermal conditions. The results were satisfactory, as there was complete separation between the two classes (fresh and spoiled) for all samples, with the exception of three fresh samples that were classified as marginally spoiled. Further on, the samples were analyzed by Partial Least Square Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) in order to predict the quality class of minced beef through the spectrum. The results showed a good separation between the fresh and spoiled samples. Specifically, the overall correct classification of meat samples was 95.38%, while the wavelengths that were related with freshness of the samples were at 630, 645 and 600 nm, corresponding to the different states of hemoglobin. The developed model was further validated with the spectra collected from the dynamic temperature profiles using the samples from the second experiment. In this case, the overall correct classification rate was 100% in both categories

CONCLUSIONS

The obtained results demonstrated that the collected spectral signals could be considered as a fingerprint of an active biological system containing information for discrimination of minced beef samples in quality classes during storage at both isothermal and fluctuating temperature profiles

SESSION 2: Predictive models and complex modelling approaches for food safety and quality

P. 09.- MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF MICROBIAL DEVELOPMENT IN MEAT TREATED WITH ROSEMARY ESSENTIAL OIL AND UVC LIGHT.

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Keywords: mathematical modeling; microbial development; meat; Rosemary Essential oil; UVC light.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Meat's composed of water, amino acids and proteins, minerals, fats and fatty acids, vitamins and other bioactive components, as well as small amounts of carbohydrates (FAO, 2015) that transform it, into a food where microorganisms can easily develop.

Many techniques have been used by the industry in order to decontaminate the meat surface, without altering its quality. Irradiation with UVC light is a process that has long been used because it doesn't alter organoleptic characteristics of product, reduce the use of chemical substances and produce a harmful effect on DNA of several microorganisms. The application of essentials oils, is also gaining adherents for such purpose, since in this case they're natural biopreservatives, rich in phenolic components with antimicrobial activity and recognized as GRAS.

The objectives of this work were to analyze and mathematically model the effect of the combined technologies (UVC light, Rosemary Essential oil, refrigeration temperatures) on the development of microbial flora of meat surface.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We used samples of *Longissimus dorsi* muscle with pH 5.8, which were aseptically cut into circular subsamples. Those were irradiated with UVC light (doses 0.0018 J.seg.cm⁻²) and then were added 1 ml of a solution of Rosemary oil (*Rosemarinus officinalis*) and lactic acid (1: 1). Untreated samples were considered as control. All samples were packaged with polyethylene low density films and stored in controlled refrigeration cameras to 0, 4 and 8°C, for 25 days.

At different times were performed microbial counts of Total Mesophilic Microorganisms, *Pseudomonas sp* and Enterobacteriaceae in specific culture media.

Bacterial counts as a function of time were mathematically modeled by applying Gompertz equation. Derived parameters: lag phase duration (LPD), specific growth rate and maximum population density (MPD) were calculated. When the observed effect was bacteriostatic a linear regression was used. The effect of the storage temperature on the specific growth rate was modeled through an Arrhenius equation and the corresponding activation energies (Ea) were determined.

RESULTS

A good fit of the experimental results with respect to the models was observed. It was found that in all cases the final counts of the treated samples were lower than those of the control samples, presenting the greatest differences at 8°C with values of 1.79 for Total Mesophilic Microorganisms, 1.66 for *Pseudomonas sp* and 0.79 times for Enterobacteriaceae. At 0°C were obtained the minor values of specific growth rate (0.009 log CFU.cm⁻².days) and the lag phases were more extensive (25 days) in this sample set.

Total Mesophilic Microorganisms were the most sensitive to the thermal changes when presenting the highest values of E_a (370.54) while *Pseudomonas sp* was presented the lower values of this parameter (150.60).

CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded that the mathematical modeling is a useful tool to predict the behavior of microbial flora of meat surface treated with these decontaminating technologies.

P. 10.- MODELLING SPATIOTEMPORAL DYNAMICS IN A FOOD MATRIX INITIATED BY INJECTED STARTER CULTURES.

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Keywords: Spatiotemporal Predictive Modelling in Food, Computational Fluid Dynamics, Reaction-Diffusion, Finite Element Method, Optimisation

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Most of the common models used in predictive microbiology lack a spatial component. While this is often sufficient in homogeneous environments, it fails when the food product is heterogeneous, diffusion limitations cause spatial gradients of metabolic products, or the spatial positions of bacterial colonies are important. In these cases, predictions can only be made experimentally, which often comprises a lengthy incubation or ripening period. Such an experimental approach is therefore both time consuming and costly, and has to be repeated when external factors change. This makes a spatially explicit transport model for microbes and chemical species related to microbial growth and metabolism desirable.

As part of a project that develops a novel technology platform for cheese production, a complex spatiotemporal model was built and applied to the ripening period of cheeses of different types and shapes. As the novel technology platform differs from traditional cheese-making procedures in that a solid, extruded cheese is inoculated with a starter culture of lactic acid bacteria in a number of different positions before the ripening period, this results in a number of centres of bacterial activity in an otherwise microbiologically inactive cheese. The model aims to reproduce the main biochemical processes in the cheese matrix and the diffusion processes of bacteria and chemical species in order to identify the optimal injection strategy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The model was built using a commercial multiphysics software that includes interfaces for CFD (computational fluid dynamics) and diffusion processes in porous media (cheese). We used the software to explicitly model the temporal and spatial dynamics of substrate (lactose) and the metabolites lactic acid and lactate, as well as the concentrations of salt and buffer components, the pH and the starter cultures.

Bacterial growth as well as spatiotemporal changes in the chemical species are governed by a system of nonlinear PDEs of reaction-diffusion type. The reaction terms of the model characterise the biochemical reactions, but also bacterial growth, which is limited by the amounts of substrate and product present. Initially, the bacterial concentration is at its maximum at the positions of the inocula and decreases in all directions according to a trivariate normal distribution.

Different cheese shapes, were investigated by examining the effects of various injection strategies on the amount of substrate remaining and the homogeneity of the pH within the cheese at the end of the ripening period. The number and positions of these inocula, together with the amount and concentration of the bacterial suspension injected ultimately determine whether the distribution of metabolic products in the ripened cheese can be regarded as sufficiently homogeneous. We determine the optimal injection strategy of the starter cultures using derivative-free optimisation algorithms.

RESULTS

The right choice of the injection pattern, the number and positions of the injections and the amount of bacterial suspension injected can strongly influence the time required to achieve an even distribution of fermentation products in the cheese matrix, particularly for more complex geometries. While a higher number of injections and

a higher volume of bacterial suspension improves homogeneity of the metabolic products and shortens the ripening time, it is nevertheless desirable to minimise both number of injections and injected volume, as they affect cheese quality. The experimental validation of the model was performed by analysing the local concentrations of the lactic acid bacteria and the modelled chemical species at different points in time during the ripening period.

CONCLUSIONS

The spatiotemporal approach that takes the dynamic changes in the concentrations of microorganisms, substrates and metabolites into account has the potential to substantially improve other predictive microbiological models in the food context.

P. 11.- QUANTIFYING THE ADAPTATION OF BACTERIA TO THERMAL STRESSES, A MODEL SEPARATING TYPICAL RESISTANCE AND STRESS ADAPTATION.

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Keywords: Stress adaptation, mathematical modelling, mild thermal treatments

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Several authors have reported the stress adaptation of bacteria populations to mild heat stresses. This implies that the inactivation during mild on-isothermal heat stresses is lower than the one predicted based on the models fitted under analogous isothermal conditions. Not considering the stress adaptation of the bacteria when designing the heat treatments in industry can be a hazard to public health.

In this contribution, the stress adaptation of *Listeria monocytogenes* to different thermal stresses has been characterized. This has been made in such a way that the typical resistance (i.e. under isothermal conditions) and the one developed due to stress adaptation have been independently quantified.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

As a control, the typical resistance of bacteria has been quantified using isothermal experiments (i.e. D and z-values). On a second step, the stress adaptation under mild non-isothermal conditions using a mathematical model with an independent term for the stress adaptation. This model incorporates model parameters analogous to the D and z-values to account for the stress adaptation.

RESULTS

The model fitted to the isothermal data without considering the stress adaptation overpredicts the microbial inactivation. On the other hand, the model which does consider it successfully reproduces the dynamic experimental data.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the experimental conditions tested a detailed characterization of the response of *Listeria monocytogenes* to mild heat stresses has been developed, taking into consideration the stress adaptation. The mathematical model used includes independent model parameters to describe the stress adaptation. This allows its quantification independently of the typical stress resistance (i.e. under isothermal conditions), as well as allowing the compare the stress adaptation developed by the same microorganism in different media or between different microorganism.

P. 12.- MODELLING THE GROWTH KINETICS OF *PSEUDOMONAS* SPP. ON WHITE BUTTON MUSHROOM UNDER NON-ISOTHERMAL CONDITIONS.

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Keywords: Predictive microbiology; mushroom spoilage; microbiological change; growth behaviour; dynamic temperature

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Although hundreds of mushroom species exist in nature, the button mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) is the most common edible mushroom in the world. *Pseudomonas* spp. have been isolated as the most abundant microorganisms responsible for the spoilage of button mushrooms, and the temperature is determined as one of the most important factors affecting their growth rate. The main objective of this work was to develop primary and secondary models to describe the growth of *Pseudomonas* spp. on the button mushrooms at different isothermal and non-isothermal conditions between 4 and 28°C

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The Baranyi model as the primary model was used to describe the growth behaviour of *Pseudomonas* spp. on the button mushrooms at different isothermal conditions (4, 12, 20 and 28°C). The number of *Pseudomonas* spp. on the button mushrooms under non-isothermal conditions is estimated by solving the differential form of the Baranyi model merged with the Ratkowsky model with Runge-Kutta method

RESULTS

The goodness of fit of the Baranyi model was determined by considering mean squared error (MSE) and coefficient of determination for nonlinear regression (pseudo-R²). The Baranyi model gave MSE values lower than 0.108 and pseudo-R² values higher than 0.996 at all isothermal conditions. Then, the maximum specific growth rates (μ_{max}) obtained from the Baranyi model were fitted to the Ratkowsky and Arrhenius models which are the most commonly known and used secondary models. High pseudo-R² (0.999) and low MSE (1.25×10^{-6}) values indicated that the Ratkowsky model satisfactorily described the temperature dependence of μ_{max} better than the Arrhenius model. Therefore, the Ratkowsky model was selected as the best secondary model. The differential form of the Baranyi model merged with the Ratkowsky model was solved numerically using fourth order Runge-Kutta method to estimate the number of *Pseudomonas* spp. on the button mushrooms under non-isothermal conditions. The dynamic model developed was validated using three different dynamic temperature regimes including linear heating-cooling, sinusoidal and periodically changing temperatures which simulate the deviations in temperature during processing, transportation, retail marketing and storage of the button mushrooms

CONCLUSIONS

Model validation under different dynamic temperature scenarios was done by considering the bias (Bf) and accuracy (Af) factors. Bf and Af values close to one indicated that the primary and secondary models developed can be used to estimate the number of *Pseudomonas* spp. on the button mushroom subjected to various isothermal and non-isothermal temperatures. Because *Pseudomonas* spp. are good indicators of spoilage, the models can also be used to set limits for the quantitative detection of the microbial spoilage and assess product shelf-life

P. 13.- GROWTH MODELS OF LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES AND SALMONELLA IN COOKED MEAT UNDER STATIC AND DYNAMIC TEMPERATURES.

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Keywords: Temperature; Growth kinetics; Listeria; Salmonella; Meat

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Storage temperature is one of the critical factors that affect the microbiological safety and quality of food products during their distribution to the consumers. Therefore, it is necessary to develop mathematical models to predict the growth and survival behaviors of microorganisms in food products as affected by storage temperature. A common approach of developing growth kinetic models is through conducting isothermal experiments with microorganism-inoculated samples stored at different temperatures of interest to collect microbial growth data and develop models. The experiments for isothermal studies are generally time consuming and labor intensive for a large number of samples and microbial samplings are required for data collection. In an attempt to simplify and expedite the model development, this study evaluated a new approach using inoculated samples stored at dynamic temperature conditions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Slices of cooked ham were inoculated with a 5-strain mixture of *Listeria monocytogenes* or *Salmonella* spp. and stored at 4-16°C. The storage temperatures were static (4, 8, 12, and 16°C) or dynamic (increased from 4°C to 16°C). The populations of *L. monocytogenes* or *Salmonella* during storage were used to develop linear lag phase duration (LPD; h) and square-root growth rate (GR; log cfu/g) models for each temperature (static temperature) or temperature segment (dynamic temperature).

RESULTS

The predicted LPD and GR obtained by the static model were average 10% and 14%, respectively, lower than the dynamic model and the differences were lower at lower storage temperatures. The predicted populations of *L. monocytogenes* and *Salmonella* obtained from the combined LPD and GR models were close with an average of 0.3 log differences over the temperature range. The pre-exposure temperature in dynamic-temperature storage did not appear to affect the subsequent growth behaviors of both pathogens.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study suggest that it is feasible to use the dynamic-temperature approach to develop temperature-dependent growth model for *L. monocytogenes* and *Salmonella* in cooked meat products. Additional studies may be needed to verify applications of this approach for developing growth models describing microbial growth as affected by other intrinsic and extrinsic food factors in addition to temperature.

P. 14.- BEHAVIOR OF *BACILLUS CEREUS* SPORES IN COOKED BEANS UNDER ISOTHERMAL CONDITIONS FROM 10 TO 49°C .

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Keywords: *Bacillus cereus* spores, cooked beans, growth, predictive modeling

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Bacillus cereus is a pathogen of significant concern to the food industry. Temperature abuse of cooked beans has been cited as a cause of numerous outbreaks of foodborne illness. Accordingly, the objective of this study was to collect the Kinetic growth/inactivation data of *Bacillus cereus* from spores in cooked beans at various temperatures ranging from 10 to 49°C

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Samples were inoculated with approximately 2 log CFU/g of heat-shocked (80°C/10 min) spores and stored at several isothermal temperatures. *B. cereus* populations were determined at appropriate intervals by plating on mannitol egg yolk polymyxin agar and incubating at 30°C for 24 h. Growth curve fitting of primary growth models, viz., three-phase linear, Gompertz, and Baranyi models was done using GraphPad Prism (Graphpad Software, version 7.0, San Diego, CA). Coefficient of determination (r^2) and sum of square error (SSE) of fit were calculated. Growth rates estimated from primary models were fitted using the expanded Ratkowsky square-root model $\sqrt{\mu_{max}} = b(T - T_{min})(1 - \exp(c(T - T_{max})))$. Death rates of germinated spores at 10°C and 49°C were estimated using the log-linear inactivation model.

RESULTS

When measuring the microbial growth of *B. cereus*, all three models provided high goodness of fit ($r^2 > 0.95$) for the temperature range conducive for bacterial growth (13-46°C). The growth rate estimated using Baranyi and Gompertz models were higher than those predicted for the three-phase linear model. Gompertz model provided a better overall fitting as compared to three-phase linear and Baranyi models. For Gompertz model growth rates, the theoretical minimum temperature (T_{min}), theoretical maximum temperature (T_{max}), and values of constants b and c for growth of *B. cereus* in beans were estimated as 7.09°C, 55.36°C, 0.046, and 0.066, respectively. Lag-time (LT) was modeled as a function of specific growth rate (μ_{max}) using exponential equation: $LT = 40.34 \times \exp(-3.44 \times \mu_{max})$. The inactivation rates of *B. cereus* in beans were very low at 10°C and 49°C and ranged from 0.00-0.04 log CFU/h

CONCLUSIONS

These results provide insight into microbial modeling and will help food microbiologists to predict *B. cereus* growth and inactivation in beans at varying temperature conditions

P. 15.- MODELLING GROWTH/NO GROWTH BOUNDARY CONDITIONS OF *BACILLUS* SPECIES SPORES.

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Keywords: Spoilage, Water activity, Growth probability, Neural network

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Comprehensive understanding of the growth limiting conditions of the targeted bacterium is crucial for developing control measures. Many studies have reported the growth limit of foodborne pathogenic bacteria; however, a few studies exist that have evaluated the growth limit of spores of spoilage bacteria, which persist in processed foods even after heating treatment. In this study, we focused on spores of *Bacillus* species that cause food spoilage, and aimed to elucidate the growth limit conditions of these spores as a function of environmental pH, water activity (a_w), and organic acid concentration. Furthermore, we aimed to develop a growth/no growth boundary model to predict probability of growth for *Bacillus* spores.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Cocktails of spores of plural strains of *Bacillus subtilis*, *B. coagulans*, and 8 strains of *B. megaterium* were used. The cocktail of spore suspensions was diluted to 10^4 CFU/mL using peptone water. The pH was adjusted (4.0–7.0) with hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide and a_w (0.85–1.0) with sodium chloride (NaCl) or glycerol. A 0.1-mL aliquot of the spore suspension was added to an airtight test tube containing 5 mL controlled medium and incubated at 35°C for 12 weeks. Growth or no growth was determined by evaluating turbidity of the media. The resultant dichotomous data set was analysed using logistic regression as a function of pH, a_w , acetic acid concentrations, and NaCl concentrations. Furthermore, the resultant data set was analysed using deep learning algorithm that creates plural layers of neural network by all the related parameters as input factors.

RESULTS

Differences in the growth behaviour of spores were observed at the same a_w level between the conditions adjusted with NaCl or with glycerol. At the same a_w level, compared to NaCl, glycerol showed greater growth inhibition of *Bacillus* spores. The growth limit conditions also differed slightly with respect to the species of *Bacillus*. Compared to other species, *B. coagulans* showed higher ability to persist in varying environmental conditions. A logistic regression model successfully described growth/no growth responses of the spores of all the *Bacillus* species included in this study. The resultant model accurately illustrated the growth boundary condition indicated by a higher value of the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (> 0.90). The model developed using deep learning algorithm, which includes all the environmental factors, demonstrated an equivalent or higher accuracy than that demonstrated by the logistic regression model.

CONCLUSIONS

A growth/no growth boundary model for spores of three species of *Bacillus* was successfully developed based on logistic regression and deep learning algorithm. The determination of growth limit conditions of food spoilage bacteria using the model developed in this study would contribute to food industry.

P. 16.- MODELLING OF TTI SMART LABELS RESPONSE FOR MONITORING SHELF LIFE AND HISTAMINE FORMATION IN AQUACULTURED MUGIL CEPHALUS FISH.

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Keywords: Cold chain; Time temperature integrators; smart labels; oysters

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Time Temperature Integrators (TTI) indicate via an easily measurable response the temperature history of the food product. A TTI based system can be used for a realistic control of the chill chain and efficient shelf-life management, quality changes and risk assessment of bacterial growth. *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* (Vp) contamination of oysters may reach 60% in seasons of high prevalence and Vp growth might occur due to the current practice for oyster harvesting and transportation at ambient temperature. The objective was to evaluate the applicability of TTI smart labels for monitoring Vp risk in oysters during transportation at ambient conditions and shelf-life under refrigeration up to the consumer's level

MATERIAL AND METHODS

TTI response based on a controlled enzymatic hydrolysis of a lipid substrate expressed as a pH dependent colour change of the solution (from green to yellow/orange and finally to red) was measured instrumentally with a CIELab colorimeter at isothermal and variable conditions (0-30°C). The parameters that allow targeted design of the response characteristics are the concentration of the enzyme (U) and the type of substrate. Oyster (*Grassostrea gigas*) flesh was inoculated with Vp and stored at isothermal and variable conditions (15-30°C). Vp load at predetermined times was estimated based on TTI response and was compared to experimentally measured numbers. Appropriate TTI was selected to fit to the predicted growth of three doublings of Vp in the range 15-30°C.

Aerobically packed, chucked oysters were stored at controlled isothermal and variable conditions (0-15°C). Spoilage bacteria load and sensory scoring at predetermined times were estimated and kinetically modeled. Temperature dependence of microbial growth was modeled using Arrhenius equation. Comparisons between the experimental and the predicted by the TTI quality indices were based on accuracy and bias factors and relative errors

RESULTS

A mathematical model for Vp growth in oysters was validated at 15-30°C and at variable conditions. The temperature effect on Vp growth rate was expressed by the activation energy ($E_a=78.9\text{kJ/mol}$). Spoilage of oysters during refrigeration was dominated by *Pseudomonas* spp. growth. Sensory rejection (score 5 for overall impression) and end of shelf-life coincided with a *Pseudomonas* spp. level of 6 logcfu/g. Shelf-life of oysters was estimated at 13, 8, 5 and 3 d at 0, 5, 10 and 15°C, respectively. A mathematical model which describes the effect of the enzyme concentration and the storage temperature on the response of the enzymatic TTI was developed ($E_a=143.4$ and 105.8kJ/mol for the range 0-15°C and 15-30°C, respectively)

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study indicate that the LP-200U (enzymatic TTI using a mixture of trilaurin-tripalmitin as substrate and 200 units of *Rhizopus oryzae* lipase) can be reliably used as predictive tool in validating improved handling, cooling procedures and recommended temperature during distribution and refrigerated storage of oysters

P. 17.- GROWTH PARAMETER ESTIMATES OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN COOKED CHICKEN: EFFECT OF PREPARATION OF INOCULUMS.

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Keywords: *Listeria*, challenge test, growth modelling

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Estimates of lag times and growth rates from growth curves for *Listeria monocytogenes* on slices of sous-vide cooked chicken breast were compared for four inoculum preparation procedures. Effects were investigated at different temperatures between 6 and 24 °C.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Slices of sous-vide cooked chicken breast (12 ± 2.7 g) were inoculated with five 10- μ l-spots of a four-strain cocktail of *L. monocytogenes* resulting in inoculation volumes of 0.44 ± 0.11 %. Each strain was inoculated into Brain Heart Infusion broth (BHI) and incubated at 30 °C for 24 h before sub-cultured in four different ways, mixing into a cocktail and used for inoculation; i) dilution in fresh BHI (direct30), ii) chilled incubation for 3 d before dilution in fresh BHI (coldBHI), iii) chilled incubation for 3 d before dilution in Maximum Recovery Diluent (MRD) (coldMRD) and iv) dilution in fresh BHI followed by chilled incubation for 3 d (direct8). Direct30 and direct8 procedures were tested against coldBHI at 8 and 19 °C, whereas the coldMRD procedure was compared to coldBHI in the temperature range from 6 to 24 °C. Growth curves were graphically compared and fitted to Baranyi & Roberts models using DMFit. Lag times (L) and max specific growth rates (μ_{max}) were used for statistical analyses using t -tests and for developing secondary models for the coldMRD and coldBHI procedures. Secondary models were cross-validated using bias (Bf) and accuracy (Af) factors.

RESULTS

Growth curves obtained at 19 °C showed signs of injured cells repairing during the first 3 h when the direct30 procedure was used compared to coldBHI. However, no clear statistical differences were found for L - ($P = 0.07$) or μ_{max} -values ($P = 0.50$). At 8 °C, growth curves obtained for direct30 and coldBHI were identical in the first 30 h then counts became more scattered with a tendency to have higher counts for the coldBHI procedure. Nevertheless, no statistical differences were found neither for L - ($P = 0.99$) nor μ_{max} -values ($P = 0.76$). The direct8 procedure resulted in significantly ($P = 0.04$) longer L at 19 °C but similar μ_{max} ($P = 0.12$) when compared to coldBHI. At 8 °C, growth curves obtained using the direct8 procedure appeared to have no lag phase when fitted. However, these curves showed clear signs of injured cells repairing during the first 5 – 7 h which suggested that the obtained L -values of 0 could be an artefact resulting from the curve-fitting procedure. Based on Bf, μ_{max} -estimates obtained using the coldBHI procedure were on average 12 % higher than results observed for coldMRD. An Af of 1.17 was found when coldMRD observations were used for validating the coldBHI secondary μ_{max} -model. In the opposite case, a slightly lower Af of 1.14 was found. Graphical comparison showed approx. 3-fold longer L for coldMRD below 10 °C.

CONCLUSIONS

Even with very low inoculation volume, estimates of lag times and growth rates of *L. monocytogenes* were significantly affected by the procedure used for preparation of the inoculum.

P. 18.- STAPHTOX RISK PREDICTOR – A DYNAMIC MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR PREDICTING THE RISK FOR STAPHYLOCOCCUS ENTEROTOXIN IN MEAT.

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Keywords: Staph. aureus growth, staphylococcus enterotoxin production, meat,

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Existing growth models for *S. aureus* predict growth in relation to temperature, aw/NaCl and pH, and the assessment of the risk for staphylococcus enterotoxin (SE) is solely based on the number of *S. aureus*. However, during the production of meat products such as fermented sausages and semi-processed hams, growth of *S. aureus* is a critical control point in the HACCP analysis, and there is a need to develop a model predicting the risk of SE formation based on the composition of the product, changes in pH or temperature during processing and the number of *S. aureus*. The objective was thus to develop a mathematical model that predicts both the increase in numbers of *S. aureus* and the risk of SE formation during heat treatment and fermentation of meat products.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 78 experiments were carried out using a meat model system. The experiments covered a range of different temperatures (10 – 40°C), pH (4.6 – 6.0), WPS (2.2 – 5.6%) and sodium nitrite (0 – 150 ppm). The meat model system was inoculated with approximately 10³ cfu/g of a multi-strain cocktail and incubated at the different temperatures. The cocktail consisted of 4 strains of *S. aureus* producing SEA to SED. Enumeration of *S. aureus* was performed up to 12 times during the incubation, and SE was extracted from samples with cell counts > 5 log cfu/g. An ELISA method was used for measuring the SEA-E content. The microbiological data, together with data for temperature, pH, WPS and sodium nitrite were used to develop a multiple linear regression model for the risk of SE and a neural network model for the growth rate of *S. aureus*.

RESULTS

The SE and growth models were validated on separate data sets (N=203, N=63, respectively). The SE-model showed an acceptable agreement between the validation data and the model predictions, and the growth model had a bias and an accuracy factor of 1.07 and 1.20, respectively, indicating acceptable models.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the models are applicable for predicting the risk for SE formation and increase of *S. aureus* during processing of meat products. The output is the increase in *S. aureus* during the fermentation process or heating/cooling process, the risk for SE formation and the degree hours for the fermentation process. The models will be available to producers and other interested parties at www.dmripredict.dk (in English).

P. 19.- ULTRASOUND ASSISTED THAWING OF COD FROZEN FILLETS.

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Keywords: ULTRASOUND, FISH, THAWING

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Process optimization is required in the Food Industry in order to minimize processing time and costs. All this, without adversely affecting the quality properties of the food product. In Food Industries in which their raw materials are frozen products, defrosting is an important step requiring long thawing periods in order to not compromise food quality, but considering the time-dependence of the hygienic quality of the product. This is an essential issue in fishery products. Due to this, the application of strategies which enable to reduce the thawing time without affecting food quality is essential. Ultrasound is a technology that could contribute to this point.

Ultrasounds generate shock waves through the phenomenon of cavitation favoring energy transfer phenomena, such as those produced during thawing. Although there are some data on the application of ultrasound when thawing, data available in fish products is limited. Moreover process optimization has not been investigated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Thawing curves of frozen cod fillets (2 kg) have been obtained in a water bath (2°C) assisting the process with the application of ultrasound (200W, 25 kHz, at intensities varying from 0 to 29.4 W/kg). The evolution of the fillet-
inner temperature and of the water through the time was evaluated and described by quadratic polynomial (response surface) equations for the effects of ultrasound power intensity and time. Backward stepwise regression was used to eliminate the parameters which were not significant in the final equation. The lack-of-fit test was used to determine whether the full polynomial equations or the simplified polynomial equation was more appropriate fit of the experimental data.

RESULTS

Two mathematical equations (R^2 -adj=0.90) were developed to describe the evolution of the inner temperature of the fish fillets and of the thawing water when applying ultrasound. Time was the main factor affecting the evolution of fish temperature and ultrasound power in the water temperature. The application of ultrasound reduced up to 82% (from 8.5 h to 1.5 h) the time required to increase the temperature from -13°C up to -1°C, without increasing the water temperature over 5°C. Ultrasound effect was faster when the lowest intensities were applied: 3 W/kg enabled to reduce 57 % the thawing time. Over this ultrasound intensity the thawing rate was reduced 16 fold. Therefore, 3 W/kg could be an adequate ultrasound power intensity for cod fillets thawing. Sensorial analysis, water retention capacity (WRC), and cooking lost (CL) indicated that this ultrasound power (3 W/kg) at 25 kHz hardly affected the texture of cod fillets, only reduced 3% WRC, and non-significant ($p=0.05$) differences were observed in the CL values when compared to control samples.

CONCLUSIONS

Ultrasound at low power intensities would be an interesting strategy to reduce the thawing time of frozen cod fillets, without compromising their quality.

P. 20.- THERMAL INACTIVATION KINETICS OF *SALMONELLA ENTERICA* SEROVARS AND *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* ARE PRACTICALLY SIMILAR.

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Keywords: Pasteurisation, sterilisation, strain variability, water activity, pH, process variability

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Meta-models of thermal inactivation kinetics from literature data do show large overall variability. Variability can be limited considerably by adjusting for the effects of especially water activity, pH and experimental conditions using multiple regression analysis. Strain variability and population heterogeneity is likely to account for the remaining variability. The objective of this study was to compare the kinetics of *Salmonella enterica* serovars and *Listeria monocytogenes*, hypothesised to have similar kinetics.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Data on D-values, strains, media and process conditions were collected from 70 publications since 1968 resulting in 514 experimental data sets for *Salmonella enterica* (26 serovars) and 807 for *Listeria monocytogenes* (57 strains). Missing information on water activity, pH, NaCl and sugar content were supplemented from other papers. 27 variables were tested for statistically significant effects ($p < 0.05$) using multiple regression analysis (all possible models, GenStat 17). Variables were culture conditions (growth phase, temperature, time, storage conditions, aw and pH adaptation) and heating conditions (method, heat shock, aw, pH, fat, sugar, NaCl).

RESULTS

Without adjusting for other variables, explained variances of the logD-temperature regression models (R^2) were 0.2% for *Salmonella*, 72% for *Listeria monocytogenes* and 46% for the combination (allowing for interaction between temperature and genus). After adjusting for all statistically significant variables, the R^2 of the model for the combined genera was 83%. The resulting model is $\log D = \log D_{\text{Tref}} + \text{Genus} + \text{Temp} * \text{aw} * \text{pH} + \text{logitSugar}$ (quadratic) + logitNaCl (quadratic) + heat shock + culture growth time + last temperature + heating method. At pH 7 and aw of 0.99, the z (-1 * reciprocal of the logD-T slope) was 5.8 °C and was not statistically different for *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Salmonella*. The thermal inactivation sensitivity to aw and pH was not found to be genus-dependent either.

The residual model standard deviation was 0.38 log(D, minutes), resulting in a 95% prediction interval of c. 0.75 logD at each side of the regression line. For *Salmonella*, the logD is 0.29 logD lower than for *L. monocytogenes* at each temperature, which is a difference that is statistically significant, but low compared to the overall model error.

CONCLUSIONS

The slopes (z-values) for the genera are not statistically different. The difference in logD, although statistically significant, is low compared to the residual model variability. This model allows for an easier and more accurate design of heat inactivation processes by the food industry. Z-slopes, not just for temperature, but for e.g. aw and pH as well, can be included in time-temperature designs, while safety margins can be limited and full strain variability remains included. This allows for a lower heat dose, resulting in better taste and lower energy costs at adequate safety levels.

P. 21.- INNOVATIVE MODELING TECHNIQUES FOR THE QUALITY AND MICROBIAL SAFETY OF FOODBORNE PATHOGENS IN LEAFY GREENS

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Keywords: Leafy greens, microbial safety, quality, nonlinear programming, system model

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Leafy green vegetables are highly susceptible to microbial contamination because those are minimally processed. In addition to the microbial safety concern from pathogenic bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* O157:H7, *Salmonella* spp., and *Listeria monocytogenes*, leafy greens also have quality issues as those are of highly perishable commodity. Considering the microbial safety and quality concerns, by using a nonlinear programming (NLP) approach, a computer model was developed to optimize the maximum temperature during the supply chain of leafy greens. Furthermore, as a first attempt toward developing a mathematical system model to understand the pathway of *E. coli* O157:H7 in leafy greens production, an innovative complex system model simulating a hypothetical farm was developed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The model for quality and microbial safety includes the cost of refrigeration, sensory quality parameters (i.e., fresh appearance, wilting, browning, and off-odor), and microbial safety. For this modeling effort, an interactive graphical user interface was developed in MATLAB. Pathogen growth were represented by three-phase linear and square-root models, and the loss of sensory quality parameters was expressed as Arrhenius equations. The objective function was refrigeration cost, which was to be minimized and the constraints were growth of pathogens and the loss of sensory characteristics. The system model consists of subsystems (soil and plant), inputs to the system model that affect the subsystems (irrigation, cattle, wild pig, and rainfall), harvested crop as the output of the system, and contamination in the soil at the time of harvest as the feedback, i.e., it would affect the soil conditions for the next crop. The model simulated planting, irrigation, harvesting, ground preparation for the new crop, contamination of soil and plants, and survival of *E. coli* O157:H7. The model was developed and simulated in MATLAB.

RESULTS

Results from the microbial safety and sensory quality modeling study indicate that pathogen growth is of more concern than loss of sensory quality in fresh-cut Iceberg lettuce when considering a shelf-life of up to two days. Browning is of maximum concern for fresh-cut Iceberg and Romaine lettuce, whereas off-odor is the biggest concern for fresh-cut chicory. Results of the system model indicate that the seasonality of *E. coli* O157:H7 associated leafy greens outbreaks was in good agreement with the prevalence of this pathogen in cattle and wild pig feces in California. Based on comparison among the results of different scenarios, it can be recommended that concentration of *E. coli* O157:H7 in leafy greens can be reduced considerably if contamination of soil with animal feces is mitigated.

CONCLUSIONS

The developed models have their significance in predicting the optimized storage temperature in the supply chain of leafy greens and in providing a better understanding of the seasonality in *E. coli* O157:H7 outbreaks associated with leafy greens.

P. 22.- MATHEMATICAL MODELS FOR DESCRIBING THE EFFECT OF ELECTROPORATION ON AUTOLYSIS OF YEAST CELLS.

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Keywords: yeast extract, pulsed electric fields, autolysis

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Yeast extract is a common natural flavoring substance used in the food industry. A mixture of peptides, amino acids and nucleotides is responsible for its flavor-enhancing effect. These components are formed during the process of autolysis, where endogenous enzymes of the cell break down intracellular macromolecules. The process relies on the cell's own enzymatic mechanism and can therefore be lengthy. Different methods are commonly applied to accelerate the process. These methods include the addition of salt, mechanical disruption of the cells and the use of exogenous lytic enzymes. Pulsed Electric Fields (PEF) processing causes electroporation of cells and can be used to accelerate the process of autolysis by facilitating the diffusion of autolytic products. In order to effectively determine the effect of disruption techniques on the kinetics of autolysis, the progress of the process has to be mathematically modeled. The effect of PEF processing on electroporation of yeast cells can be expressed through the cell disintegration index Z , based on the sample's electrical conductivity. This parameter is a useful tool to assess the extent of electroporation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

S. cerevisiae suspensions (1% w/v) were subjected to various PEF conditions (3-20 kV/cm, 10-500 pulses, 300 Hz, 15 μ s pulse width) and the dependence of the cell disintegration index on electric field strength and treatment time was determined. Suspensions were then treated at conditions corresponding to Z values ranging from 0 (untreated sample) to 1 (fully electroporated sample) and autolyzed at 52°C for up to 48 h. The course of autolysis based on the release of proteins, α -amino nitrogen and total solids was monitored.

RESULTS

The dependence of the cell disintegration index on PEF treatment time was described by a first order exponential model with very good agreement between predicted and experimental values. The single parameter of the model, τ_d (characteristic damage time) corresponds to the treatment time required to achieve a value of $Z=0.5$, for constant electric field strength and ranged from 5744 μ s to 213 μ s. The dependence of τ_d on electric field strength was described using a first order exponential model. The course of autolysis based on the release of proteins, α -amino nitrogen and total solids was modeled using a first order fractional model with a very good agreement between experimental and predicted values. The model contains three parameters: C_0 , expressing the value of each parameter at the beginning of autolysis, C_e , expressing the equilibrium value and τ which shows the time required for the concentration to reach 63% of C_e .

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of PEF treatment on yeast suspensions and the progress of autolysis of treated samples was modeled mathematically. Through the calculation of model parameters, it was determined that increasing cell disintegration index led to shorter autolysis times.

P. 23.- *ESCHERICHIA COLI* STRAINS ACID-ADAPTED TO A CONTROLLED LOW PH SHOW INCREASED HEAT RESISTANCE COMPARED TO NON ACID-ADAPTED

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Keywords: cross-protection; strain variability; linear mixed model; D-value

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Adaptation of bacterial cells to environmental stress can lead to increased resistance to a subsequent stress, a phenomenon known as cross-protection. Cross-protection has important implications in food safety and in food processing optimizations. For instance, the use of hurdle technologies, where sub-lethal or mild stresses are applied, may induce multiple stress responses reducing the efficacy of subsequent treatments. Given the importance of pH reduction and thermal treatment in food processing and preservation strategies, the cross-protection between acid adaptation and subsequent thermal inactivation for 48 *E. coli* strains was investigated. In addition, the effect of medium pH during heat inactivation and the strain variability were also studied

MATERIAL AND METHODS

E. coli cells were acid and non acid-adapted during overnight growth in controlled acidic pH (5.5) and neutral pH (7.0), respectively, in buffered Lysogenic Broth (LB). Then, the cells were washed and resuspended in fresh non-buffered LB adjusted to pH 6.2 and 7.0 for the heat inactivation at 58 °C. In total, four conditions were tested by combining medium pH during growth/inactivation: 5.5/ 6.2, 5.5/7.0, 7.0/6.2 and 7.0/7.0. Linear mixed models followed by a Tukey test were used to investigate the relationship between the *LogD-values* and the conditions tested, with conditions as fixed effect and strains as random effect. Distributions were fitted to the *LogD-values* to describe the heat resistance variability

RESULTS

Acid-adapted *E. coli* were significantly ($p < 0.05$) more heat resistant than the non acid-adapted. For instance, the median *D-value* was approximately 6 and 4 min for acid-adapted and non acid-adapted strains, respectively. The heat resistance of acid-adapted *E. coli* was significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher when inactivation occurred at pH 6.2 than at pH 7.0. For non acid-adapted *E. coli* cells, no significant difference was observed between both pH during heat inactivation. Variability in the heat resistance at 58 °C was observed for all pH combinations, with *D-values* from 1.0 to 69.0 min. Highly heat resistant strains were detected with *D-values* between 18 and 69 min, while *E. coli* O157:H7 showed *D-values* between 1 and 3 min

CONCLUSIONS

Cross-protection and *D-values* variation should be carefully assessed within the context of the food processing from a food safety point of view. In addition, it is important that the design of food processes using low pH and thermal treatment should carefully include the consequences of those effects. This is especially important for food business operators interested in introducing milder processing and preservation techniques. More information in Haberbeck, L.U., Wang, X., Michiels, C., Devlieghere, F., Uyttendaele, M., Geeraerd, A., 2017. Cross-protection between controlled acid-adaptation and thermal inactivation for 48 *Escherichia coli* strains. Int J Food Microbiology, 241, 206-214

P. 24.- IMPACT OF COOKING PROCEDURES AND STORAGE PRACTICES ON CONSUMER EXPOSURE TO *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* AND *SALMONELLA*.

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Keywords: *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella enterica*, cooking, storage, pork meat

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The objective of this research was to analyse the impact of cooking on gas hob and traditional static oven at different levels (i.e., rare, medium and well done) on the inactivation of *Listeria monocytogenes* (LM) and *Salmonella enterica* (SE) experimentally spiked on the surface of pork loin chops. Moreover, the consumer's exposure to both microorganisms after simulation of meat leftover storage at home was assessed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 160 packs containing 300 ± 20 g of loin chop spiked with a pool of LM and SE isolates were cooked according to different protocols and their survival was experimentally quantified. Then, the impact of different consumer storage practices was simulated to quantify the consumer's exposure to both pathogens at the time of consumption.

RESULTS

For samples cooked on gas, mean and standard deviation temperatures corresponded to 74.9 ± 3.3 °C for rare, to 85.8 ± 3 °C for medium and to 88.5 ± 2 °C for well-done. For samples cooked in static oven, they were 73.6 ± 3.3 °C, 87.7 ± 4.8 °C and 96 ± 2.9 °C for rare, medium and well-done, respectively. Samples positive for LM and SE were only found using the qualitative analytical method. The results for cooking combinations "gas_rare" and "oven_rare" showed that the probability of LM to multiply during leftover storage up to 2 log₁₀ cfu/g was 0.077. After cooking in "oven_medium" and "gas_well-done" the probability to reach the same concentration was 0.026. The combination "gas_medium" inactivated LM in 92.5% of the cases. For the 7.5% of cases of occurrence there was a probability of 0.039 to reach concentrations of 2 log₁₀ cfu/g. For SE the probability of inactivation was slightly higher in static oven than on gas. The worst case was the combination "gas_rare", associated to a probability of inactivation after cooking of 0.825. Simulating the leftover storage, the probability for SE to reach 2 log₁₀ cfu/g at the time of consumption was 0.085. For the combination "oven_rare", the probability to reach the same concentration was 0.073 and using the combination "gas_medium" was 0.036. The cooking combination "oven_medium" was effective in 95% of cases; the remaining 5% of samples in which SE occurred after cooking showed a probability to reach 2 log₁₀ cfu/g corresponding to 0.024. Occurrence after cooking on "gas_well-done" was 2.5% and the probability to reach 2 log₁₀ cfu/g was 0.012. A total inactivation of both pathogens was reached only after cooking with the combination "oven_well-done".

CONCLUSIONS

The results showed that well-done cooking on static oven was the only treatment able to inactivate the tested pathogens. The other cooking combinations allowed to reach in the product core temperatures always ≥ 73.6 °C, decreasing pathogens between 6 and 7 log₁₀ cfu/g. The few cells surviving cooking treatments can multiply during storage up to 1 log₁₀ cfu/g, with probabilities of 0.059 (gas hob) and 0.035 (static oven) for LM and 0.049 (gas hob) and 0.031 (static oven) for SE.

P. 25.- QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT (SPME/GC-MS) OF SPOILAGE COMPOUNDS AND EFFECTS OF THERMAL SHOCKS IN ALICYCLOBACILLUS SPP. SPORES.

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Keywords: Alicyclobacillus spp.; Spoilage; Fruit juices; SPME/GC-MS; Heat Resistance

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Alicyclobacillus spp. (ALI) is acidothermophilic sporeforming bacterium that causes spoilage of fruit juices and beverages. Thus, the objective of this study was to identify/quantify the production of spoilage compounds and to determine the effects of different thermal shock conditions on the recovery of ALI spores inoculated in orange and apple juice

MATERIAL AND METHODS

497 strains of ALI isolated from fruit juices and tomato-based products collected in Argentina and Brazil were evaluated. Micro-solid phase extraction by headspace (HS-SPME) and gas-chromatography with mass spectrometry (GC-MS) were used to identify and quantify volatile compounds produced by ALI positive strains for guaiacol production (enzymatic method). After the identification/quantification of spoilage compounds, spore suspensions of different strains of ALI were prepared. Then, the suspensions of spores were submitted to thermal shocks applied in oil bath at different times (min) and temperatures (°C): 10/80, 20/85, 10/90, 5/95, 5/100, 5/105, 5/110, 5/115, 3/120

RESULTS

165 out of 497 strains studied were confirmed by the enzymatic method to be able to produce guaiacol. The discrimination of volatile compounds (by CG-MS analysis) produced by these strains and the classification in terms of their response to the thermal shocks applied and the variability associated to their enumeration will be presented

CONCLUSIONS

This work will allow gaining insights on the spoilage potential and resistance to heat shocks of ALI strains isolated from a variety of fruit-based products

P. 26.- MODELLING BIOCIDES AND BACTERIA INTERACTION IN CHEMICAL DISINFECTION.

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Keywords: Kinetic inactivation models, chemical disinfection, mechanistic modeling.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Current chemical disinfection models assume that the concentration of the disinfectant remains constant or decreases following a first order reaction independent of the bacterial load. To optimize the dosification of the disinfectant it is fundamental to test whether these hypotheses are sufficient to obtain models with good predictive capabilities.

In this work we investigate different mechanisms of interactions for *Escherichia coli* inactivation with Benzalkonium chloride (BC). BC belongs to the group of Quaternary Ammonium Compounds, one of the most widely used disinfectants in the food industry and other settings like domestic and clinical environments. Non corrosive, low aggressive, odorless and high stability are some of the characteristics that make these agents especially suitable for the food industry.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Escherichia coli CECT4622 (*E. coli*) was cultured in sterile Tryptone Soy Broth at 37 °C. The cells were centrifuged at 9000 g for 5 min. Different inoculum concentrations were obtained by suspending the pellet in 0.85% NaCl and subsequent dilution.

BC solutions of different concentrations were dosed to 1 mL-aliquots of bacterial suspension (1:1, v/v) at room temperature. After exposure time, samples were split into two fractions. One was filtered by 0.2 µm to remove cells and filtrates were used for BC analysis (Ioannou et al. 2007). The other fraction was neutralized and used to determine the number of viable survival cells of *E. coli* by spreading on Trypticase soy agar.

Different interactions between BC and *E. Coli* were studied using dynamic models. The solution of the parameter estimation required the use of advanced numerical techniques. In this work, we made use of AMIGO2 (Advanced Model Identification using Global Optimization), a multi-platform toolbox implemented in Matlab which covers parameter estimation but also sensitivity analysis and experimental design (Balsa-Canto et al., 2016).

RESULTS

The assumptions of constant or first order decay of disinfectant are not sufficient to represent the dynamics of BC. We observed that, even with BC in excess and capable of killing the whole bacterial population, BC dynamics depend on the initial bacterial load. Therefore, we derive a new model describing the decay of BC as a function of the bacterial load.

CONCLUSIONS

We propose a new model describing the dynamics of *Escherichia coli* inactivation by Benzalkonium chloride. Models based on the usual assumptions were unable to reproduce the BC dynamics. We derive an alternative model that includes and shows how BC concentration changes as a function of the initial bacterial load.

P. 27.- MODELING *WEISSELLA VIRIDESCENS* INACTIVATION BY ULTRAVIOLET RADIATION.

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Keywords: Non-thermal processing, Ultraviolet radiation (UV-C), *Weissella viridescens* and mathematical model

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB), including *Weissella viridescens*, is among the main groups of microorganisms responsible for spoilage of refrigerated meat products, vacuum packed and under modified atmosphere. There is an amplified demand by consumers for minimally processed and safer foods, with retained original organoleptic attributes. Non-thermal processing of foods by application of radiation treatments like ultraviolet radiation (UV-C) is positively being accepted by the food industry and consumers. UV-C treatment is reported to induce minimal quality changes and is capable of reducing microbial load. The objective of this study was to obtain a mathematical model able to predict *W. viridescens* inactivation *in vitro*, under constant and variable UV-C radiation intensities.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Treatments were carried out in a camera (40 x 40x 40 cm) with ten germicidal UV-C lamps at 24 W with peak emission at 254 nm. The experiments were artificially inoculated with bacterium, with initial loads around 10^8 CFU/mL and then exposed to UV-C radiation and the treatment impact on microbial loads was assessed throughout exposure times. Five different radiation intensities (0.58; 1.10; 1.34; 1.68 and 1.98 W/m²) were applied to *W. viridescens* population and the concentration was measured over time.

RESULTS

Weibull model was fitted to experimental data to obtain inactivation parameters β and α (β is the location factor and α is the shape factor). After initial fit, α was fixed (1.26). Results showed that, for the highest intensity (1.98 W/m²) time to reach 6 decimal reductions (t_{6D}) was 2.3 s and for the lowest intensity (0.58 W/m²) was 12.4 s. So as highest the intensity of UV-C treatment used, lowest time was necessary to reach t_{6D}. The Weibull model described well the inactivation data of contaminated microorganisms. Exponential model was chosen to describe the influence of radiation intensity on β parameter. From the primary and secondary models it was possible to establish a dynamic model to predict the behavior of *W. viridescens* under radiation intensity variation. The proposed model was validated with experimental data and can correctly predict the inactivation of the studied microorganism.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded that UV-C radiation is a promising treatment with a drastic impact on the loads of *W. viridiscens*, especially when high intensities are used.

P. 28.- PREDICTING THE GROWTH OF SALMONELLA IN CHICKEN UNDER DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE PROFILES.

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Keywords: Salmonella, dynamic temperature profile, predictive microbiology

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Salmonella is a gram-negative pathogen that colonizes the gastrointestinal tracts of animals. Its importance relies on the high numbers of outbreaks and illnesses caused by this bacterium. Predictive microbiology is a mathematical tool that quantifies and generates patterns for microbial behavior. Its primary goal to the food industry is to assure food safety and quality. With the use of mathematical models, it is possible to evaluate bacterial growth both under isothermal and non-isothermal profiles found during processing and storage of food products. The objective of this study was to evaluate the growth of Salmonella in chicken submitted to different isothermal and time-varying temperature regimes through the use of a mathematical model

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 150 growth data of isothermal growth of Salmonella Typhimurium DT104 at 17 in grounded chicken breast at 17 different temperatures (10 °C, 11 °C, 12 °C, 14 °C, 16 °C, 18 °C, 20 °C, 22 °C, 24 °C, 26 °C, 28 °C, 30 °C, 32 °C, 34 °C, 36 °C, 38 °C, and 40 °C) were selected from Combase. The experimental data were selected from two papers of the same author (at least 5 experimental points for each temperature studied) and the other environmental parameters (pH and aw) did not differ significantly during the studies. Baranyi and Roberts (BR) primary growth model was fitted to the 150 isothermal datasets with the R package nlsMicrobio. The extended square-root model was used as a secondary model for the maximum specific growth rate and a logarithm function was adopted as a secondary model for the duration of the lag phase. Two different graphs containing non-isothermal growth data with temperature ranging between 5 °C and 20 °C (P1) and 7 °C and 25 °C (P2) of Salmonella in chicken from the literature were scanned and experimental points were digitalised. Subsequently, the primary models fitted to isothermal data were included in the differential equations that compose BR model and the resulting equations were used to predict the non-isothermal growth of Salmonella with the R package fme. Bias and accuracy factors were used to evaluate the results obtained for the dynamic temperature profiles

RESULTS

The two secondary models used in the study described with good accuracy the dependence with the temperature of the maximum specific growth rate ($R^2=0.93$) and of the duration of the lag phase ($R^2=0.91$). The parameters (and the standard errors) obtained for the Ratkowsky's extended model were: $a=0.043(0.002)$, $T_{min}=3.579(0.081)$, $b=1.137(1.646)$, and $T_{max}=41.646(2.356)$. In what concerns non-isothermal growth, there were obtained similar fits to both profiles with bias factor of 1.0063 and 1.0070, and accuracy factor of 1.0108 and 1.0119 for P1 and P2, respectively. The predictions were more accurate for the higher temperatures studied (above 15 °C)

CONCLUSIONS

The results showed that BR model can accurately describe non-isothermal growth of Salmonella in chicken. Further works are needed to increase the range of temperatures studied.

P. 29.- DEVELOPMENT OF A DYNAMIC MODEL FOR A REAL-TIME KIMCHI FRESHNESS MONITORING SYSTEM DURING DISTRIBUTION.

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Kimchi is a traditional Korean fermented food. Since it ferments continuously during distribution and storage, the extension of shelf life by preventing over-acidification is a major concern in the kimchi industry. Temperature maintenance is important for keeping quality of Kimchi during distribution. The objective of the current research was to develop dynamic Kimchi freshness monitoring system using real-time temperature logging technology, which included RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) and WSN (Wireless Sensor Networks).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Variations in microbial population, pH, and acidity with time were tested under constant and fluctuating temperatures as possible indicators of Kimchi freshness. The correlations between the organoleptic test results and the three indicators were compared for the Kimchi stored under different temperature conditions, i.e., 0, 5, 15, 20°C, 0-10°C and 5-15°C. The freshness assessment model with the modified Baranyi and Roberts model as the primary model and the Polynomial model as the secondary model was selected as the best one to use for the real-time Kimchi freshness monitoring system. The accuracy and bias factors, Af and Bf were used for validation.

RESULTS

Total acidity in Kimchi samples was used as freshness index based on correlation analysis. The accuracy and bias factors, Af and Bf for the Baranyi and Roberts coupled with the Polynomial model under constant temperature conditions and fluctuating temperature conditions were evaluated. The bias factor varied between 0.959 and 1.037 for the constant temperature cases, and it was found to be about 1 for the fluctuating temperature cases.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded that the models can be used to predict Kimchi freshness in terms of the total acidity at any temperature condition with in the range of 0-20°C during distribution. The models can simulate the freshness quality of Kimchi during storage in their supply chain during commercial display.

P. 30.- GROWTH AND SURVIVAL OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN BLUE MUSSELS (*MYTILUS EDULIS*).

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Keywords: *Listeria monocytogenes*, blue mussel, *Mytilus edulis*, growth, prediction

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Mussels have been reported as a source of human listeriosis. Although mussels, e.g. blue mussels, are seldom eaten raw they are usually subjected to only minimal heating prior to consumption. However the main purpose of that heating is to open the cells but not to cook the mussel or kill bacteria. In order to establish necessary D reduction values and from a risk assessment point of view it is important to know if *Listeria* can grow in mussels prior to heating.

Thus the objective this study was to observe the growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* in artificially contaminated Icelandic blue mussel at refrigerated temperature, also to examine the anticipated growth using predictive microbiology

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Fresh live mussels were contaminated by placing about 600g mussels in a container with 3000 mL of artificial seawater. Enriched culture of *L. monocytogenes* (DSM 20600) was blended to the seawater to give concentrations of 560, 7900 and 300.000 *L.monocytogenes* per mL. Mussel meat was also contaminated by mixing *L. monocytogenes* with 200g mussel meat in concentrations from few hundred to approximately hundred thousand cells per gram.

The live mussels and mussel meat was stored at refrigeration temperature (6-7°C) for one week. *L. monocytogenes* was enumerated using ISO 11290-1:2004(E) and ISO 11290-2:2004(E) on OCLA and OXFORD agar. The ComBase predictor (www.combase.cc, 2017) was used to predict the growth of the *L. monocytogenes* in blue mussels using the found average intrinsic values of pH 6.5 (range 6.08-6.77), water activity (aw) 0.989 (range 0.999-0.964) and calculated salt 1.8% in water phase and initial concentration of *L. monocytogenes* 10cells/g (phys.state 0.1)

RESULTS

The results showed that the mussel was easily contaminated with *L. monocytogenes*. However during the one week storage no change or slight decrease (0.5-0.8 log unit) or slight increase (0.5 to 1.0 log units) in numbers of *L. monocytogenes* in live mussels was observed. *L. monocytogenes* was able to grow in the contaminated seawater. The results for the mussel meat were also inconclusive. In four of eight trials the number increased one to two log units in the other half the number decreased half to three log units. The ComBase growth predictor predicted half, two, four and eight log units at 1°C, 4°C, 7°C and 15°C respectively. At the low boundary level (pH=6.1 and aw=0.964) an increase of 1.7 log units was predicted

CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded that blue mussels are easily contaminated with *L. monocytogenes* under experimental conditions and they survived well during one week storage at 7°C. However growth in contaminates live mussels as in mussel meat is inclusive as both increase and decrease was observed. Intrinsic parameters measured (i.e. pH, aw and salt) in blue mussels support growth. Mussels could possibly contain some natural inhibitors to *Listeria* growth

P. 31.- COMPARATIVE KINETIC STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF PULSED ELECTRIC FIELDS (PEF) AND HIGH PRESSURE (HP) PASTEURIZATION ON POMEGRANA.

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Keywords: pulsed electric fields (PEF), high pressure (HP), pomegranate juice, process design

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Pulsed Electric Fields (PEF) and High Pressure (HP) processing are among the emerging nonthermal pasteurization technologies in juice production. Modelling the effect of PEF and HP process parameters on food quality/safety indices can be used as effective tools for process design and optimization. The objective of this work was to mathematically model the effect of PEF and HP process parameters on pomegranate juice microbial and quality attributes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Fresh pomegranate juice (Wonderful cultivar, Ermioni, Greece) was used in PEF and HP treatments. PEF processing was performed at electric field intensities ranging between 4.5 and 13 kV/cm, in combination with pulses in the range of 70-2000 (bipolar rectangular pulses, 300 Hz, 15 μ s). HP processing was performed in the range of 200-800 MPa (ambient temperature) and treatment times in the range of 0-40 min. Microbial counts (total viable count, lactic acid bacteria, yeast and moulds), antioxidant activity (DPPH method), color and sensory attributes were determined after all process treatments.

RESULTS

A multilinear mathematical model was developed to adequately describe microbial destruction and antioxidant activity decrease as a function of PEF processing parameters i.e. treatment time, number of pulses and electric field intensity. HP treatments at pressures above 400 MPa led to a complete microbial destruction from the first two minutes of processing, thus a HP induced microbial destruction predictive model was not feasible. In the case of antioxidant activity decrease and color change a first order kinetics model was developed as a function of process treatment time by determining the respective rate constants. The effect of pressure on rate constant was successfully described by the Eyring model with an activation volume of -20 and -12 ml/mol for antioxidant activity decrease and color degradation, respectively. According to the results pasteurization could be achieved by applying PEF processing at electric field intensity of 13kV/cm for 300 pulses while an effective HP pasteurization could be achieved at 600 MPa (ambient temperature) and 5 minutes of processing.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this work enabled the development of microbial destruction and quality changes kinetic models for the PEF and HP induced pasteurization of pomegranate juice. The developed kinetic models can serve as tools to select the optimum PEF and HP process conditions.

P. 32.- EFFECT OF OREGANO ESSENTIAL OIL ON THE SHELF-LIFE OF VACUUM-PACKED SLICED HAM STORED UNDER NON-ISOTHERMAL CONDITIONS.

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Keywords: Oregano Essential Oil; Lactic Acid Bacteria; Vacuum-packed sliced ham; non-isothermal conditions

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Ready-to-eat meat products are consumed worldwide, and ham has a special importance because of its added value. The shelf-life of vacuum-packed meat products is limited due to the microbial deterioration, mainly by Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB). LAB can cause physic-chemical and sensorial changes, such as off-flavors, discoloration, gas production, pH decrease and slime production. The Oregano Essential Oil (OEO) has been used as a natural antimicrobial agent to increase the shelf-life of meat products. The shelf-life of ham is dependent of the refrigeration temperature, because temperature is the main factor that changes the dynamics of microbial growth in foods. The aim of this study was modeling the effect of OEO on the shelf-life of vacuum-packed sliced ham (VPSHam) stored under non-isothermal conditions, based on the growth of the LAB natural microbiota.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The ham was characterized by pH, water activity and sodium chloride concentration. The growth of the LAB in VPSHam were performed with 0.4% OEO (v/w) and without OEO, and under two different non-isothermal temperature profiles (TP1 and TP2, in the range from 5 to 25 °C). Baranyi and Roberts primary model and Exponential secondary model (parameters previously estimated with data under isothermal conditions) were used to predict the growth of LAB in VPSHam under non-isothermal conditions. The predictive ability of the mathematical model was evaluated by statistical indices (RMSE, bias and accuracy factors). The shelf-life of VPSHam was established as the time (in hours) that LAB reached 10^7 CFU/g. The LAB growth in VPSHam was further compared to *Weissella viridescens* growth in VPSHam and MRS culture medium (results from the literature).

RESULTS

The shelf-life of VPSHam was established as the time (in hours) that LAB reached 10⁷ CFU/g. The LAB growth in VPSHam was further compared to *Weissella viridescens* growth in VPSHam and MRS culture medium (results from the literature). The addition of 0.4% OEO increased the shelf-life of VPSHam (compared to samples without OEO) in 59% for TP1 (from 248.9 h to 397.4 h) and 39% for TP2 (from 62.3 h to 86.7 h). The mathematical model was able to predict the LAB growth under non-isothermal conditions, with better results of accuracy factor for samples without OEO (TP1 = 1,08 and TP2 = 1,09) than samples with 0.4% OEO (TP1 = 1,18 and TP2 = 1,10). The results of bias factor showed that the growth predicted by the model were fail-safe for TP1 (without OEO = 1,01; 0.4% OEO = 1,13) and fail-dangerous for TP2 (without OEO = 0,94; 0.4% OEO = 0,93).

CONCLUSIONS

Therefore, OEO showed relevant antimicrobial effect and the mathematical model was able to predict satisfactory the BAL growth in VPSHam.

P. 33.- MODELLING OF *ALICYCLOBACILLUS ACIDOTERRESTRIS* INACTIVATION IN APPLE JUICE USING THERMOSONICATION TECHNOLOGIES.

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Keywords: Thermosonication treatments, Apple juices, *A. acidoterrestris*, Inactivation

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Alicyclobacillus acidoterrestris is a thermoacidophilic, non-pathogenic, spore-forming bacterium, which is responsible for quality degradation of fruit juices. *A. acidoterrestris* has become an important concern, and it has been suggested as a target microorganism for the design of thermal processes of fruit juices. In single strength juice and under specific conditions these microorganisms may find a favorable environment for germination and growth that can lead to product deterioration. Thermal pasteurization is efficient in reducing the number of viable microorganisms in foods. However, to reduce the negative impacts of high temperature processes, alternative non-thermal technologies as efficient as thermal pasteurization ones, but with minor impacts on the products quality features, are promising fields of investigation. Ultrasound is capable of inducing cavitation to inactivate microorganisms in foods. However, as a preservation method, application of ultrasound alone is not efficient enough to kill all microorganisms. Combining ultrasound with a heat treatment (thermosonication, TS) may decrease the time for a target microbial inactivation, depending on the ultrasound wave's amplitude, composition and volume of food to process and temperature selected. Mathematical modelling of the kinetics of thermosonicated juices would allow to understand the impact of the process and predict microbial survival in treated juices.

The objective was to study the influence of ultrasounds (35 kHz frequency, 120-480 W power levels) and combinations with thermal treatments (70, 80, 85, 90 and 95 °C) on *A. acidoterrestris* spores inactivation in apple juices.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Commercially available juices were artificially inoculated with the bacterium and the juices were then exposed to the treatments. A Weibull model was successfully fitted to *A. acidoterrestris* spores inactivation as function of thermosonication exposure times.

RESULTS

Results showed that ultrasounds alone had no significant effect on spores' inactivation. However, when combined with temperature, a higher reduction of spores' loads was observed. As temperature increased, inactivation rates increased (from 0.005 ± 0.0002 min⁻¹ at TS-70°C to 0.124 ± 0.0140 min⁻¹ at TS-95°C). When compared to thermal treatments applied alone, thermosonication resulted in higher inactivation. For the highest temperature tested, thermosonicated samples had a reduction of 5 log-cycles after 20 minutes, while in thermal treated samples at 95 °C for the same time, only 3 log-cycles reduction was observed.

CONCLUSIONS

Overall it can be concluded that thermosonication treatments have significant impacts on the loads of *A. acidoterrestris* in apple juices and the kinetic Weibull model applied will allow to design efficient conditions for target decontaminations.

P. 34.- FIELD ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECT OF NATURAL NITRITE SUBSTITUTE ON THE GROWTH OF SPOILAGE ORGANISMS AND *CLOSTRIDIUM SPOROGENES* IN COOKED MEAT PRODUCTS.

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Keywords: Clostridium spp., natural antimicrobials

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Nitrites have been used in meat industry to achieve distinctive color and flavor as well as to effectively control the growth of pathogens such as *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Clostridium botulinum*. However, there is an emerging trend towards clean label products, using natural substitutes of nitrites. The objective of this study was to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of a commercial fruit- and spices- based natural antimicrobial (NA) against spoilage organisms and *C.sporogenes*, as surrogate for proteolytic *C.botulinum* in cooked meat products

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Four formulations (no nitrites, nitrites 150 ppm and two concentrations of NA) of deli-style turkey paste were inoculated in the industrial setting with *C.sporogenes* (100 and 10000 spores/g), while non-inoculated samples served as control. Final products were prepared according the commercial manufacturing process (heat treatment, smoking and High Pressure Processing-HPP). NA (extract of fruits and spices) was added in 0.5x or 1x of the concentration recommended by the manufacturer. 200g-pieces of product were vacuum packed, HPP treated and stored at different temperatures in order to monitor spoilage (5, 10, 15oC) as well as safety (6, 12, 15, 20, 25 oC) of the final product. Enumeration of *Clostridium* sp. and spoilage microflora was performed throughout storage for up to 3 months, while growth parameters (μ_{max} , lag phase- λ) were determined using DMfit. Storage under dynamic temperature conditions was used to further validate the developed growth models regarding spoilage and safety of cooked meat products

RESULTS

Formulations lacking antimicrobials allowed the growth of clostridia at all temperatures (except 6oC). NA performance against clostridia was concentration dependent. High NA concentration (1x) effectively inhibited growth of clostridia, regardless storage temperature, while nitrites only delayed the outgrowth of the surrogate ($\lambda=13.93$ days; $\mu_{max}=0.37$ d⁻¹, 25oC) compared to control ($\lambda=1.5$ days; $\mu_{max}=0.79$ d⁻¹, 25oC). While both antimicrobial agents had no significant effect on spoilage microflora (mainly barotolerant lactic acid bacteria), regardless of storage temperature, they may potentially result in distinct microbial profile as manifested by the acidification only of NA-containing samples at the onset of spoilage and additional rep-PCR analysis of spoilage isolates

CONCLUSIONS

Nitrites could successfully be substituted by natural antimicrobial agents, resulting in nitrite free products. However, extrapolation of the results in other deli meat products should co-evaluate the intrinsic characteristics of the product

P. 35.- MODELLING THE FATE AND SEROTYPE VARIABILITY OF ISOLATED *L. MONOCYTOGENES* STRAINS ON GRATED CURED EWE'S CHEESE AT DIFFERENT STORAGE TEMPERATURES.

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INTRODUCTION

Ewe's cheese from raw milk is one of the most representative traditional products produced across different Spanish regions. These are catalogued as semi-hard aromatic cheeses typically aged for three to six months. Since this product is defined as ready-to-eat since it is not submitted to any further treatment before consumption. Thus, foodborne pathogens such as *Listeria monocytogenes* can represent a health concern for susceptible consumers. In this study, the kinetic behaviour of four isolated *L. monocytogenes* strains (namely, ½ a, ½ b, ½ c and 4b) from cheesemaking factories was modelled on grated cured ewe's cheese at different isothermal conditions (4 and 12°C). Finally, variability was characterized over storage time through the isolation and identification of the most persistent serotypes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Twenty-five gram samples of grated cured ewe's cheese packaged in modified atmosphere (50% CO₂ + 50% O₂) were collected from a Spanish cheesemaking factory for microbial and physico-chemical analyses. Isolated *L. monocytogenes* serotypes were inoculated separately on the cheese surface together with a strain cocktail at an initial level of 10⁴ cfu/g. Samples were stored at 4 and 12°C for 90 days. Enumeration and detection of each *L. monocytogenes* serotype was carried out through plate counting (ALOA + Oxford agar) and confirmation was carried out with PCR from twenty isolated colonies per sample analytical point. Log-linear with shoulder, linear and Weibull models were fitted to observed data using GINaFit software v1.6. Kinetic parameters (inactivation rates, k_{max} (log cfu/h), shoulder length, SI (h), delta and p) were used to describe the dependency of each strain on storage temperature.

RESULTS

Inactivation models presented a good adjustment to observed data being able to describe survival patterns of *L. monocytogenes* (R² >0.75). Results showed a high variability in serotype behaviour at both tested temperatures. *L. monocytogenes* 4b presented a higher inactivation rate at 4°C (k_{max} > 0.040 log cfu/h) than at 12°C (k_{max} > 0.028 log cfu/h) while the opposite trend was found for serotypes ½ b and ½ c. Serotype ½ a presented an initial SI of 63.45h at 4°C while inactivation rates were similar at both storage temperatures. Inactivation patterns of the inoculated cocktail showed a higher survival period at 12°C, combined with a higher k_{max} at the same temperature. Regarding the persistence of the different serotypes, *L. monocytogenes* ½ a was the most prevalent during the first 3 days storage. However, *L. monocytogenes* ½ c was detected in higher proportion from the 8th day until the end of storage period at both temperatures.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that there was a high variability in microbial behaviour according to the *L. monocytogenes* serotypes presented in ripened ewe's cheese. While serotype 4b was the most sensible to refrigeration temperatures, *L. monocytogenes* ½ c exhibited the most resistant survival pattern at both temperatures tested yielding the lowest k_{max} values and being detected up to the end of the storage period. This study highlights the potential implications of *L. monocytogenes* contamination in cured cheese. Further, serotype variability should be considered when evaluating survival patterns in contaminated products.

P. 36.- MATHEMATICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE COMBINED EFFECT OF CHLORINE, BENZYL ISOTHIOCYANATE, EXPOSURE TIME AND CUT SIZE ON THE REDUCTION OF SALMONELLA IN FRESH-CUT LETTUCE DURING WASHING PROCESS.

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVE

Ready-to-eat and fresh-cut vegetables are among the most frequently foods implicated in food-borne outbreaks, with the enteropathogenic bacteria, Shiga-toxin producing *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* spp. being the most relevant causative agents.

Disinfection is one of the most critical steps in fresh-cut vegetable production as it may affect quality, safety, and shelf-life of the product. Although chlorine is still the most used disinfectant, due to its efficacy, low cost-effectiveness ratio, and simple use, future regulatory restrictions will probably require the development of functional alternatives. An alternative to reduce the use of chlorine are the natural antimicrobials, derived from microbial, plant, or animal sources. The benzyl isothiocyanate (BITC) is an isothiocyanate found in plants of the mustard family (*Brassicaceae*). The isothiocyanates have wide-spectrum antimicrobial activity.

This work aims to study the effect of two disinfectants (Sodium hypochlorite and BITC) in combination with typical washing process parameters (cutting surface and contact time) on the reduction of *Salmonella* in fresh-cut produce during washing operations under typical industrial conditions (temperature, water composition, and product/water ratio).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment followed a Central Composite Design (CCD) for the 4 factors considered (type of disinfectant, concentration, cut size and exposure time). Lettuce was cut at different sizes (9, 12, 15, 18 and 21 cm²) and inoculated with a bacterial suspension of the strain GFP-labeled and gentamicin-resistant *Salmonella enterica* subsp. *enterica* serovar Thompson. Inoculated lettuce pieces were treated in washing tanks with a model water containing the desired disinfectant level by addition of Sodium hypochlorite (50, 100, 150 and 200 ppm) and BITH (20, 40, 60 and 80 ppm), from stock solutions. The sanitation treatment simulated industrial conditions (water temperature at 4°C, and a ratio water/surface of 8.5 L/kg) at different processing times (30, 50, 70, 90 y 110 seconds).

The samples of 25 g treated were placed in bags containing Brain and Heart Infusion (BHI) broth and incubated at 10-12°C for 4 h to recover injured cells. Then, the samples were homogenized in 1% Peptone Water with stomacher and plated into Plate Count Agar (PCA) supplemented with gentamicin and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The characteristic colonies for *Salmonella*, growing in the supplemented PCA and showing fluorescent under standard UV light, were enumerated.

RESULTS

The initial concentration in the lettuce, just before treatment, corresponded to 6.6 log CFU/g. The average reduction obtained from the different experiments was 2.8 log CFU/g. The statistical analysis outcome showed that chlorine, contact time and cut size exerted a significant effect on the *Salmonella* reduction ($P < 0.05$),

confirming chlorine as a more effective disinfectant. On the contrary, the use of BITC did not produce a significant reduction of Salmonella populations under the experimental conditions studied.

The maximum reduction was estimated in the range 120-140 ppm free chlorine, and above these levels, disinfectant ability was slightly reduced. This decreasing trend observed in the highest chlorine concentrations could be related to the pH decrease, which is, at the same time, result from the increasing concentrations of chlorine in water.

Increasing exposure times resulted in higher Salmonella reductions ($> 2 \log$ CFU/g), though as in the above case, the maximum reduction was obtained in combination with relatively high free chlorine levels (100-140 ppm).

According to our results, the disinfectant ability of chlorine rose as the cut size augmented. A negative quadratic effect was observed for this factor, indicating that the disinfectant capacity of chlorine started to decrease from a certain lettuce cut size ($> 15 \text{ cm}^2$).

With the surface-response model developed in the present work, the optimum combination of the different variables was estimated. The highest reduction for Salmonella might be achieved by using lettuce cut size of 15 cm^2 , washed for 110-120 s (at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) with 120-160 ppm free chlorine and adding 40 ppm BITH (Figure 3).

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrated the efficacy of chlorine to reduce Salmonella populations in fresh-cut lettuce, during the washing step, while highlighting the importance of controlling the washing process parameters, such as pH, exposure time and lettuce piece in order to increase disinfectant efficacy and improve food safety. Results and models generated in the present study could be useful to complete or develop Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment studies, including the effect of the washing step and process parameters on the risk of enteropathogenic bacteria in leafy green products.

P.37.- INHIBITORY EFFECT OF *LACTOBACILLUS SAKEI* AGAINST *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* GROWTH IN SMOKED MEDITERRANEAN FISH PRODUCTS FROM MARINE AQUACULTURE.

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Keywords: biopreservation, *Listeria monocytogenes*, ready-to-eat fish, microbial growth

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Food biopreservation is a novel hurdle-technology with special relevance in the fish industry. It is well-known that handling during food processing usually encompasses recontamination of the product by pathogenic and/or spoiling bacteria. This can pose a significant risk for the safety of fish products, particularly for those developed as lightly preserved and eaten raw products, such as smoked fish. Most recent studies on the biopreservation of fish and fish products deal with applications in fresh or smoked salmon. Other fish species from aquaculture production are of special interest since their relevant consumption patterns and added value in Mediterranean countries. The aim of this work is to assess the inhibitory effect of a bacteriocinogenic lactic acid bacteria (LAB) against *Listeria monocytogenes* in smoked gilthead sea bream through the use of predictive microbiology models.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Lactobacillus sakei CTC494, previously isolated from fermented sausage, was selected as bioprotective culture for this study. Preliminary trials were carried out to test its antilisterial activity in sterile food-model systems (fish-based extract) under different experimental conditions. To validate its application in fish products, samples of gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) from marine aquaculture were collected and processed following a conventional smoking procedure. Smoked fish fillets were cut in pieces of ca. 10-15 g. Mono-culture experiments were performed by inoculating separately *L. monocytogenes* CTC1034 and the bioprotective culture over the surface of the fish samples at a level of ca. 2 and 4 log CFU/g, respectively. The inhibitory effect of the bioprotective culture was tested against *L. monocytogenes* by co-inoculation in the fish samples at a 1:2 ratio (using the above-mentioned concentrations). Samples were vacuum-packed and stored at 5°C for 21 days. A sensory analysis was carried out throughout the storage period to evaluate the *L. sakei* spoiling capacity at 3 initial cell densities (2, 4 and 6 log CFU/g). Four semi-trained panellists were required to make a comparative evaluation of the inoculated samples by scoring descriptors for smoked fish such as general appearance, fish odor, smoke odor and meat texture. Microbial and sensory analyses were performed on the same day at different time intervals during the storage period. The primary growth model of Baranyi and Roberts (1994) was fitted to microbial data and the estimated growth parameters were compared between mono and co-culture experiments.

RESULTS

The specific maximum growth rate and maximum population density (MPD) of *L. monocytogenes* was lower in co-culture experiments. The *L. sakei* grew faster at both experimental conditions, reaching MPD values of 9 log CFU/g. When the tested microorganisms were inoculated separately, *L. monocytogenes* was able to increase 4 log CFU/g, while in co-culture conditions, the pathogen only grew 1 log CFU/g. These results clearly demonstrate the inhibitory effect of the bioprotective culture on *L. monocytogenes* growth in the studied fish product. The sensory analysis showed greater sensory deterioration levels in samples inoculated with 4 and 6 log CFU/g after 5 days of storage. In contrast, at initial levels of 2 log CFU/g, the sensory degradation was similar to that observed in the control samples.

CONCLUSIONS

The present work demonstrated the potential of *L. sakei* CTC494 as bioprotective culture for smoked fish products from Mediterranean aquaculture during refrigerated storage. Implementation of the bioprotective culture at industrial-scale should be performed at levels < 3 log CFU/g. Further studies are required to include, in predictive models, the inhibitory effect of the bioprotective culture on *L. monocytogenes* growth.

SESSION 3: Individual-based models

P. 38.- MICROBIAL INACTIVATION BEHAVIOR: THE EFFECT OF THE ENVIRONMENT ON INDIVIDUAL CELL TIME TO DEATH DISTRIBUTION.

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Keywords: Single cell, distribution, temperature, secondary model, time to inactivation

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Recently, bacterial individuality attracted the scientific interest and an increasing number of studies consider microbial survival curve as cumulative probability of lethality events. From this probabilistic- vitalistic point of view, single cell resistance to lethal stresses is characterized by heterogeneity as it is reflected on the individual cell time to inactivation. In a previous work of ours, a modelling approach has been developed describing the variability of single cell inactivation behavior using either direct assessment (through microscopy) or indirect based on the cumulative probability distribution of single cell time to death. However, data about the effect of environmental parameters on the distributions of individual cell inactivation times and predictive models analogous to the traditional secondary ones are lacking. The objective of the present study was to describe the effect of temperature on the distribution of individual cell time to inactivation exposed to heat

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The inactivation of *Salmonella enterica* serotype Agona with initial concentration 10⁹CFU/ml was conducted in tryptone soy broth without dextrose at various temperatures (57, 59, 61, 63 and 65°C). For each temperature, a modelling approach based on the cumulative probability of individual cell time to death was adopted

RESULTS

Temperature affects microbial behavior and this was mirrored onto the respective probability distributions and the extend of the variability. Distribution parameters can be further used to develop a secondary model

CONCLUSIONS

The description and evaluation of the effect of environmental parameters on the variability of individual cell inactivation times is expected to be useful in the development of more realistic risk-based approaches for effective food quality and safety management.

SESSION 4: Modelling microbial dynamics in relation to food microstructure and the impact of microbiological interaction in foods

P. 39.- EFFECTS OF CELL PHYSIOLOGICAL STATES, FOOD-, AND PROCESS-VARIABLES ON THE UV-C INACTIVATION OF SALMONELLA ENTERIC.

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The antimicrobial efficacy of ultraviolet-C in food is known to be affected by intrinsic food properties and extrinsic process parameters. There is however, a dearth of information on the magnitude of the effects of these variables on microbial inactivation in food. Furthermore, evidences that the physiological states of a reference organism similarly influence the susceptibility or resistance of the cells. This study was therefore conducted to characterise, and if possible, quantify the effects of microbial-, food-, and process-related variables on the inactivation of *Salmonella enterica* in simulated fruit juices.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Salmonella enterica propagated in suboptimal growth conditions were first subjected to UV-C challenge to determine a physiological state that is resistant to UV-C. The identified UV-C resistant physiology was thereafter used in the establishment of a model for the effects of intrinsic properties (soluble solids: 0-70 Brix), insoluble solids (0-3 % wt/vol), and treated volume (250-1000 ml). A rotatable central composite design (CCRD) of experiments was employed to determine the combinations of the test variables necessary to establish the model.

The previously identified UV-C resistant *S. enterica* cells were propagated and subjected to UV-C challenge in the CCRD combinations. The UV-C inactivation rates (D values) were thereafter fitted into a second-order polynomial model. The model was subjected to validation to evaluate its predictive efficacy.

RESULTS

Results showed that among the tested physiological states, cells previously exposed to heat stress exhibited the greatest resistance towards UV-C. Results also showed that the D values of *S. enterica* fitted significantly into a quadratic model, with all individual linear effects of the variables significantly affecting the measured response. Only the quadratic effects of soluble and insoluble solids significantly influenced D values, while only the interaction of soluble solids and volume, and insoluble solids and volume significantly influenced inactivation. Predictive efficacy evaluation showed that the model predictions were within acceptable error margins.

CONCLUSIONS

The study demonstrated the importance of considering microbial-, food-, and process-related variables in the eventual establishment of a process schedule for fruit juices. Precise process schedules for specific food commodities with unique properties may be established.

P. 40.- COMPARISON OF OBSERVED AND PREDICTED GROWTH KINETICS OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN DICED COOKED HAM.

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Keywords: *Listeria monocytogenes*, predictive modelling, lactic acid bacteria, cooked ham

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Challenge tests and predictive models are both suggested by the European Union Food Law as tools to be used for the evaluation of microbial growth in foodstuffs, with particular reference to *Listeria monocytogenes*. Predictive models are obviously cheaper, but their use with different food products should be adequately validated considering the variability of the physical-chemical environment and of the autochthonous competitive microflora. Aim of this study was to compare predictions obtained from a model, originally designed to predict the kinetics of *L. monocytogenes* in the dynamic growth-death food environment of Italian style fresh sausages (Iannetti et al. 2017), with the results of challenge tests performed on another ready-to-eat meat product (diced cooked ham). The latter product presents, during its shelf-life, a constantly growth supporting environment, including an actively competitive microflora. Moreover, *L. monocytogenes* strains of different origin were tested (human and food derived), in order to evaluate predictions in these different cases.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Packages of diced cooked ham were separately inoculated with two *L. monocytogenes* strains, one isolated from a human clinical case of listeriosis, the other isolated from a meat product. After inoculation they were stored at 4° and 12° and analysed at day (D) 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 15, 19, 20, 25, 30, 35. The used predictive model was based on equations of Baranyi and Roberts (1994), including a rescaled version of water activity introduced according to Gibson et al. (1998) in order to get numerical stability. The effect of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) on the growth of pathogens is also included, with the specific rate observed in the product modulated by the factor $[1 - (x_L/x_{max})]$ where x_{max} is the LAB's maximum population density.

RESULTS

Observed maximum growth rate of the human strain was $0.00881 \pm 0.00398 \log_{10}$ CFU/h at 4°C and 0.0103 ± 0.000848 at 12°C, while for the food strain it was 0.0045 ± 0.000486 at 4°C and 0.0136 ± 0.00246 at 12°C. Predicted microbial kinetics were satisfactory for both the human and the food derived strain, at refrigeration (4°C) and abuse (12°C) temperature, with absence of statistically significant difference between observed and predicted values.

CONCLUSIONS

Predictive models are a useful tool for food industry, particularly to demonstrate compliance with legal microbiological criteria related to *L. monocytogenes*. Most predictions are based on *in vitro* observations, that usually do not consider the natural variability of foods, particularly when it comes to autochthonous microflora. The present study proved, on the basis of challenge tests made on cooked ham with the use of strains of different origin, the versatility of a model that takes into consideration the competitive effect of lactic acid bacteria.

P. 41.- MODELLING THE GROWTH BEHAVIOR OF HELICOBACTER PYLORI IN REFERENCE BROTH AND IN BRASSICA OLERACEA VAR. SABELLICA "KALE".

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Keywords: Helicobacter pylori, Kale, temperature, growth, Gompertz equation

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Helicobacter pylori is a Gram negative bacteria which infection is affecting the 60-80 % of the general population worldwide. This microorganism is the first bacteria classified up to date as biological carcinogenic agent, being the main concerning effects of H. pylori infection chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer, and upper intestinal tract cancer. DNA from H. pylori has been detected in some foods, like shellfish, meat and milk, among others. However, due to the exigent requirements of this bacterium to be cultured (temperature, nutrients and microaerobic conditions), additionally to its capability to enter into a viable but not culturable (VNC) stage, it results very difficult to isolate and study the H. pylori growth behaviour on real food matrices. Vegetables in contact with contaminated soils or irrigated with contaminated water have been identify as potential sources of H. pylori infection, due to the minimum processes at which are submitted previous to consumption. The Brassica oleracea var. sabellica "kale", mainly cultivated in Asia and the northern Europe, is a really interesting vegetable, nowadays considered as one of the most famous "superfoods", by its high antioxidant potential, and nutritional value.

The present study aims to compare by the first time, the kinetic parameter values defining the H. pylori growth in reference and vegetable matrices, at different incubation temperatures [5-37 °C].

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Ten grams of kale aerial parts were washed and sterilized by UV treatment (20min). Both sterile reference (Brucella Broth) and vegetable matrices were inoculated with H. pylori 103 cfu/mL. Inoculated substrates were incubated under microaerobic conditions at 5, 20, and 37 °C. The bacterial assays were carried out by triplicate. During the incubation period, aliquots were extracted from both substrates in order to register optical density (550nm) and bacterial counts up to 10 days. Gompertz modified equation was used to fit the obtained results.

RESULTS

At 5 °C, H. pylori remained in a viable-culturable stage in reference media and also in kale real matrix, being the culturability of bacterial cells decreasing as the incubation period increased. In reference broth the lag time (λ , h) increases from 21.95 ± 2.20 h to 48.71 ± 3.27 h due to reduction in incubation temperature from 37 °C to 20 °C. The maximum specific growth rate (μ_{max} , log(cfu/ml)/h) is reduced from 0.07 ± 0.003 to 0.04 ± 0.005 log(cfu/ml)/h due to the temperature decrease. In kale, inoculated bacterial load remains in a viable culturable stage during the complete incubation period at both 37 and 20 °C. However, no significant increase in growth was detected during the studied period ($\lambda = 0.320 \pm 0.025$ h; $\mu_{max} = -0.545$ log(cfu/ml)/h).

CONCLUSIONS

The present research is contributing to the state of the art regarding the growth modelling of this pathogen in food matrices in order to implement future risk assessment analysis.

P. 42.- SELECTION OF PRIMARY AND SECONDARY MODELS DESCRIBING MAXIMUM GROWTH RATE OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN PASTA SALADS.

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Keywords: *Listeria monocytogenes*, primary models, secondary models, pasta salads

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The aim of this study was to select primary and secondary models describing maximum growth rate (μ_{max}) of *Listeria monocytogenes* (LM) in two model systems reproducing different formulations of pasta salads stored under different temperatures (i.e., 4 and 12°C) and packaging conditions (air vs modified atmosphere). The suitability of the selected secondary models to predict LM μ_{max} under different temperature scenarios was validated in commercial pasta salads at the same temperatures.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Two formulations of full meal pasta salads with meat, cheese and vegetables were investigated. Six LM strains were selected for the challenge tests. The primary models assessed were Baranyi model, with or without lag phase and stationary phase, the Rosso model and a simple linear model. The secondary models investigated were square root and gamma models. Goodness of fit was evaluated considering the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the root mean square error (RMSE) between the observed data and the values expected by the model .

RESULTS

Baranyi no-lag with $m=1$ was the best models, fitting all datasets, except for the ones collected at 4°C, where the stationary phase was not reached and the linear model gave the best results. In the model systems packaged under modified atmosphere a simple square root model was good enough to describe the behavior of LM. However, for the model systems packaged under air, the gamma model was the most suitable to describe LM, in particular at abuse temperature (i.e., 12°C).

CONCLUSIONS

This study provides valuable models to predict the growth of *L. monocytogenes* in RTE pasta salads at different storage temperatures and packaging conditions. The models selected in this study can be implemented in risk assessment models for this specific food/biological hazard combination.

P.43.- FOOD MATRIX EFFECT FOR GROWTH AND INACTIVATION KINETICS OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* AND *LACTOBACILLUS PLANTARUM*.

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Keywords: food product validation, food matrix, variation, pathogen, spoiler

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Microbial growth and inactivation kinetics in food can be predicted when the effects of food properties and environmental conditions on microbial responses are available. However the effects of these intrinsic and extrinsic variables on microbial kinetics are often obtained using laboratory media, and deviations between predictions and true behaviour might occur if the specific effect of a food product is not known or considered in the prediction. Therefore, knowing the food specific effect on microbial kinetics might not only result in a more realistic growth and inactivation prediction, but also extend the knowledge on factors influencing growth and heat resistance. Furthermore its effect is compared to other variability factors.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In this study, growth predictions of *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Lactobacillus plantarum* obtained with gamma-models based on a large dataset including the effect of strain variability were validated in laboratory media and in milk and ham as model food products. Experimental results were compared in order to determine the effect of the food matrix in comparison with strain variability.

RESULTS

A good agreement between the predicted and observed growth kinetics in laboratory media highlighted the possibility to predict μ_{max} based on cardinal growth parameters obtained from OD-based measurement, for plate counts under different conditions in laboratory media. For the food product validation generally the obtained count data were within the 95% confidence bands. However these band widths were large due to strain variability. The large strain variability was expanded further by the fact that the estimated gamma product factors differed largely per strain. This strain dependency of food product specific effects further complicates accurate growth prediction. For both species the magnitude of the effect of strain variability on thermal inactivation was similar to the food specific effects, and the latter was mainly determined by the effect of ham as heating medium. The combination of both effects explained (almost) all variability found in literature, however, with some bias.

CONCLUSIONS

Food product specific effect should be included in models for realistic growth prediction. However certain effects are much larger than others, for example the effect of food product on heat resistance was mainly determined by the effect of ham as a heating medium. This effect was comparable to the effect introduced by strain diversity. Many variability factors can be quantified, and many show effects, but some much more than others. Quantifying and benchmarking these variability factors is crucial for prioritizing experimental work to characterise organisms but also to determine factors to better control food safety and spoilage.

P. 44.- EFFECT OF FOOD (MICRO)STRUCTURE ON GROWTH DYNAMICS OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN FISH BASED MODEL SYSTEMS.

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Keywords: *Listeria monocytogenes*, fish, microbial growth, model systems

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The effectiveness of predictive microbiology is hampered by the lack of knowledge concerning the influence of food (micro) structure on microbial dynamics. Traditionally, most predictive models are developed based on tests in liquid laboratory media. However, not all food products are liquid and the aforementioned models fail to take into account the influence of the specific food (micro) structure. The goal of this study is to investigate the effect of food (micro) structure on growth dynamics of *Listeria monocytogenes*. Therefore, a range of different fish-based model systems with various (micro) structures is developed, in which variation in composition and physico-chemical factors is limited.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The different model systems can be classified in the following categories, with respect to their (micro) structural characteristics: liquid, aqueous gel, emulsion, and gelled emulsion. The composition of the model systems is based on processed fish products. Among the various model systems, the (micro) structural effect on microbial evolution is isolated by minimising possible differences in compositional and physicochemical aspects (e.g., pH, water activity). Structural and rheological properties of the model systems are also characterised. For systems containing fat, the fat droplet size distribution is determined using laser diffraction. Growth experiments are conducted at 4 and 10°C. For gelled systems, both homogeneous and surface inoculation are performed. All model systems are inoculated with a cocktail of three *L. monocytogenes* strains (i.e., LMG 23773, LMG 23774, LMG 26484) to an initial cell density of 10² CFU/mL for homogeneous inoculation and 10² CFU/cm² for surface inoculation. Samples are taken at different time intervals and enumerated by plate counting. Finally, experimental data are fitted by the growth model of Baranyi and Roberts (1994) and growth parameters are compared between the different model systems.

RESULTS

First of all, it is demonstrated that the maximum specific growth rate of *L. monocytogenes* is higher in liquid and emulsion systems than in gelled systems due to the cells being immobilised in the gelled systems and resulting oxygen diffusion limitations, pH-gradients, etc. This effect can be included into secondary models by employing a factor related to the (micro) structure, i.e., gel firmness or rheological properties such as viscosity. Furthermore, the lag phase is shorter in systems containing fat droplets, suggesting a growth-stimulating effect of the fat droplets. In order to take this effect into account, the droplet size of the fat droplets is a possible factor to include in secondary models.

CONCLUSIONS

Further studies should focus on developing predictive models which incorporate the aforementioned factors. In general, the use of predictive models based on food model systems with various (micro) structures will lead to more accurate predictive models, and consequently, reduced food safety risks.

P. 45.- THE ROLE OF MILK COMPOSITION AND PACKAGING ON THE MICROBIOLOGICAL STABILITY OF WHITE SOFT CHEESE.

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Keywords: microbial growth, cheese, packaging, composition

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The highly nutritious nature of dairy products makes them especially good media for the growth of microorganisms. Factors that determine the rates of spoilage of cheeses are water activity, pH, salt to moisture ratio, temperature, characteristics of the lactic starter culture, types and viability of contaminating microorganisms, and characteristics and quantities of residual enzymes. With so many variables to affect deteriorative reactions, it is no surprise that cheeses vary widely in spoilage characteristics. In order to examine other important factors that affect the microbiological stability of Feta -the popular Greek P.D.O. white soft cheese- three model -cheeses were created and examined

MATERIAL AND METHODS

White cheeses were prepared following the traditional technique for Feta but each time by using only bovine, ovine or caprine milk respectively in order to examine the role of the milk composition. For the investigation of the role of packaging, the cheeses were stored in containers with brine, under vacuum with brine and under vacuum without brine for three months in temperature between 0 to 4oC. The microbiological parameters that were monitored were Total Plate Count, Psychrotrophs and Coliforms

RESULTS

Vacuum packaging with brine was proofed the most effective packaging while caprine cheese was the most stable, when total plate and coliforms were tested. Bovine cheese was more stable in terms of psychotropic bacteria growth

CONCLUSIONS

The results indicated a strong relation of the milk composition with microbiological stability while although vacuum packaging protected cheeses its role was different in the three model-cheeses

SESSION 5: Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment and Management

P. 46.- COMPARISON OF THE FATE OF THE TOP SIX NON-O157 STEC AND *E. COLI*O157:H7 DURING THE MANUFACTURE OF DRY FERMENTED SAUSAGES.

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Keywords: Non-O157 STEC, Dry fermented sausages

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The study examined the relative fate of the top six non-O157 shiga-toxin producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC) and *E. coli* O157:H7 during the manufacture of dry fermented sausages (DFS) that do not utilize heat to inactivate pathogens.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Three separate batches of sausages containing a five-strain cocktail for each serotype and uninoculated control were manufactured and subjected to identical fermentation, maturation and dry curing conditions. Changes in physicochemical properties and inoculated STEC numbers were enumerated at different stages during the 39 day DFS production process and log reduction and log reduction rates calculated.

RESULTS

Inoculation of very high concentrations (8 log CFU g⁻¹) of STEC in the sausage batter did not significantly ($P > 0.05$) affect the changes in the pH, aw, moisture, protein, fat content compared to the uninoculated DFS. There was a significant ($P < 0.05$) and rapid reduction in counts within the 48 hr fermentation for all STEC serotypes inoculated by about 0.97- to 1.42-log units. However, during the sausage maturation stage, all serotypes except O121 and O45 showed a significant reduction in numbers. During the extended 34 day drying stage, all STEC serotypes showed a significant reduction in counts reaching a 5-log reduction within 20 to 27 days of drying. ANOVA of the log reduction rates revealed significant differences in the reduction rates among the STEC serotypes examined. During the fermentation stage, serotype O45 had the highest reduction rate at 0.98-log CFU g⁻¹ day⁻¹ which was significantly higher compared to all other STEC serotypes ($P < 0.05$), while O26 was the most tolerant to the conditions encountered during the fermentation stage with a reduction rate of 0.49-log CFU g⁻¹ day⁻¹. However, during the extended 34 days drying stage all STEC serotypes showed a steady reduction in population with a reduction rate ranging from 0.11- to 0.18-log CFU g⁻¹ day⁻¹. Log reduction rate of *E. coli*O157:H7 was similar to serotypes O111 and O103, but was significantly lower ($P < 0.05$) than all other STEC serotypes examined in the study. Log reduction rates of serotypes O121, O45, O145 and O26 during drying were not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) from each other.

CONCLUSIONS

These results indicate that the lethality of DFS production processes observed against *E. coli*O157:H7 would result in a similar inactivation of the top-six non-O157 STEC.

P. 47.- BAYESIAN ANALYSIS OF SURVEILLANCE DATA FOR *CRONOBACTER* SPP. IN A DAIRY INGREDIENT PROCESS PLANT.

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Keywords: Microbiological Criteria; Cronobacter; Bayesian; food safety; sampling plan; uncertainty

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

High levels of uncertainty in the concentration of pathogen present can remain in the case of presence/absence sampling plans for pathogens. These sampling plans in powdered foods very often need to comply with legislative microbiological criteria. Taking into account the occurrence and distribution of *Cronobacter* spp. in dairy powders, and that there have been several reports their distribution is heterogeneous, a Bayesian model has been developed to quantify the uncertainty in concentration in a particular production batch. To date most information on the distribution of pathogens in powdered food has concentrated on powdered infant food (PIF), but there has been very little research done for other dairy ingredients (e.g. skim or whey milk powder) which may form base ingredients for PIF

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Over a one year period, nine sampling runs were undertaken for the occurrence of *Cronobacter* spp. in a dairy powder in a commercial production facility. A detailed surveillance was set up and powder samples were taken from the production line every 20 minutes over a six-hour production period. 10 g samples were subsequently tested for presence/absence of *Cronobacter* spp. using a selective chromogenic agar. In addition, whole genome sequencing was undertaken on some of the positive isolates, and compared to isolates taken from other locations, to assess the source of contamination. The results from the sampling plan were used in a Bayesian model to estimate the variation in concentration of *Cronobacter* spp. in the dairy ingredient powder from batch to batch

RESULTS

Positive samples were detected on a number of the tested batches. The positive samples were intermittent and appeared to be random in their distribution. The Bayesian analysis indicated that the true number of clusters present was very variable and could be as high as several thousand clusters per tonne. The upper bound (95th percentile) increased dramatically as the number of positives in a sampling run increased

CONCLUSIONS

Cronobacter was detected in a number of samples of the dairy powder tested. Bayesian analysis allowed an estimation in the uncertainty in the concentration of Cronobacter present in the powder. As the number of positives samples detected in the dairy ingredient powder increased, so did the uncertainty regarding the concentration of Cronobacter spp. clusters per tonne

P. 48.- DEVELOPMENT ALTERNATIVES OF CONSERVATION FROM VEGETABLE EXTRACTS AND BACTERIOCINS TO CONTROL FOODBORNE PATHOGENS.

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Keywords: Bactericide, Bacteriostatic, Blackberry, *Escherichia coli*, Moringa, *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

In the food industry to guarantee the safety is important, reducing the risk of contamination of pathogenic and altering microorganisms; the use of natural substances for the control of microorganisms has become an alternative as well as some extracts of plant origin, such as some metabolites of lactic acid bacteria (LAB), such as bacteriocins, which are low molecular weight peptides and Have antimicrobial properties have reported antimicrobial activity against pathogenic organisms causing foodborne diseases, reducing the risk of contamination; *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* is a pathogenic microorganism commonly found in water, transmission produces vibriosis become infected by consuming raw or undercooked seafood or exposing a wound to seawater; *Escherichia coli* is a bacterial found in the environment, foods and intestines of people and animals is the cause of great economic losses by clinical treatments. For the above, it is proposed to evaluate the antimicrobial effect of bacteriocins, blackberry (*Rubus glaucus*) and moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) extracts on *V. Parahaemolyticus* and *E. coli*

MATERIAL AND METHODS

To obtain the extract of moringa and blackberry, 10 and 20 grams of leaves and fruit were taken to maceration with 40 mL of ethanol at 50% were left for 24 hours at 150 r.p.m., after that time ethanol was recovered under vacuum conditions. For the bacteriocins were obtained from a LAB *Lactococcus lactis* ATCC19435 which was inoculated into brain heart infusion medium and incubated at 37 ° C for 48 hours, after which time it was centrifuged at 9000 r.p.m. at 4 ° C, the supernatants were taken and passed through 0.25um cellulose filters. The minimum inhibitory concentration is evaluated with *E. coli* ATCC11775 and *V. parahaemolyticus* ATCC17802 with 10exp 6 CFU/mL population; how metabolism indicator 2,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium chloride was used. Minimum inhibitory concentration was evaluated from 3.125- 6,250-12,5- 25- 50-75- 100% were served in wells and led to incubation at 37 ° C for 48 hours after this time by colorimetry and by counting in plate on selective media the bactericidal and bacteriostatic effect was determined

RESULTS

The results obtained with the blackberry extract show a bacteriostatic effect in *E. coli* at a concentration of 100% for *V. parahaemolyticus* a bactericidal effect at a concentration of 75%; the moringa extract had a bactericidal effect in 75% *E. coli* and 75% bacteriostatic *V. parahaemolyticus*; the bacteriocins in *E. coli* had a bactericidal effect at 75% and in *V. parahaemolyticus* 100% bactericide

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, the extracts evaluated as well as the bacteriocins can be converted into an alternative for reducing the risk of contamination of pathogens of public health importance, such as *E. coli* and *V. parahaemolyticus*, responsible for significant economic losses due to clinical and control treatments In the food industry

P. 49.- ESTIMATION OF ILLNESS ARISING FROM CONSUMPTION OF RAW OYSTERS EXPOSED TO WATER-BORNE NOROVIRUS.

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Keywords: risk norovirus shellfish oyster virus

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Norovirus causes over half of all foodborne microbial illness, in all regions of the world. This risk particularly affects consumers of shellfish. Infected humans shed tens of thousands of Norovirus copies into the sewage system. These copies enter the marine environment through wastewater effluent. Oysters growing in these environments filter hundreds of litres of water a day to feed, and accumulate hazardous levels of Norovirus copies in their digestive glands. The objective of this work is to provide a quantitative model for estimating the likelihood and severity of illness arising from consumption of contaminated oysters

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The risk estimate of this model considers the adverse health impact on an individual resulting from a single meal of oysters. This estimate integrates the results of two separate sub-models. First, the characterisation of the hazard and the quantitative dose-response relationship, carried out using previously published data. The exact dose-response relationship for Norovirus is unclear, and the impact of the food matrix unknown. Therefore several models were considered and compared. The second sub-model, quantifying exposure assessment, used experimental data to model the expected distribution of copies contained in individual oysters. The predicted quantities were verified using bootstrap simulation of supplementary oyster data. An exposure pathway framework was created which made assumptions and uncertainties explicit

RESULTS

Norovirus accumulates rapidly in oysters and stays stable for several months. Contaminated sites can show prevalences of 100%, with a wide range of potential concentrations per oyster. Concentrations were modelled as a lognormal distribution, with standard deviation of approximately 0.6 of the mean (derived from the experimental data). For a site with a relatively low mean of 200 copies per gram, this means that 95% of oysters contain between 50 and 500 copies per gram. The total number of copies ingested took into account the number of oysters eaten in a meal. The effect this total number has on the likelihood of illness depends on the choice of dose-response model. Median infectious doses vary from below 10 copies to over 1500, depending on what is known or assumed about the affected population

CONCLUSIONS

The combination of total copies consumed and their effect on consumer health provides the risk estimate of illness, which can vary significantly depending on initial assumptions. These assumptions mainly concern the infectious potential of the virus. The most severe estimate provided by this model can be taken as a worst-case scenario. The model makes assumptions and sources of uncertainty clear, as well as identifying the most significant gaps in data. It provides a baseline for judging the relative effectiveness and marginal benefit of specific risk intervention tolos.

P. 50.- DETERMINATION OF THE TOTAL VIABLE COUNT ON FRESH MEAT BY A HANDHELD FLUORESCENCE SPECTROMETER.

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Keywords: rapid methods, fluorescence spectroscopy, meat spoilage, total viable count

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

In recent years, research in the field of rapid methods to determine bacterial contaminations in food steadily increased. Generally, it has been shown that several spectroscopic methods can detect different kinds of bacteria. The detection of bacteria in liquids or simple matrices is possible, but it is still a challenge to perform quantitative microbial analysis in a complex food matrix like fresh meat. Also, spectroscopic handheld devices to analyse the bacterial load directly on-line during processing are still missing. Thus, the main objective of this study was to determine the microbial count on fresh meat in real time by means of fluorescence spectroscopy (FreshDetect GmbH, Pullach, Germany). Furthermore, the accuracy and applicability of the method under practical conditions was assessed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Storage tests with overall 860 cuts of porcine *longissimus dorsi* and a similar number of samples of pork belly cuts were conducted. The samples were stored for 10 days under controlled temperature conditions (7°C). After specified time intervals, spectroscopic measurements were performed and the total viable count (TVC) was analysed by classical microbial cultural enumeration technique. Other quality parameters like colour, sensory attributes, pH, aW and intramuscular fat (IMF) were also analysed to assess their impact on the spectroscopic values. After collection of spectral data in fluorescence spectroscopy and TVC in the classical microbiological tests, chemometric analyses were used for establishing the calibration and prediction models. The accuracy, robustness, and reliability were assessed by cross validation, calculation of statistical validation indices and by correlation with the other quality parameters.

RESULTS

The results showed a strong correlation between the spectral data and the TVC. A linear correlation was shown in the range between 2.0 log CFU/cm² and 8.0 log CFU/cm², with a prediction error (RMSE) of 1.1 log CFU/cm². The bias factor was determined as "fail safe" between 2.0 log CFU/cm² and 4.0 log CFU/cm². The accuracy of the results was not affected by intrinsic factors (IMF, pH, water content, aW) or meat colour.

CONCLUSIONS

The results illustrated that fluorescence spectroscopy can be used to determine the total viable count on fresh meat within seconds. Thus, it is a very promising technology for the meat industry, i.e. for incoming and outgoing inspection as well as a process control instrument. By knowing the microbial status of a product in real time, a prediction of the real shelf life of a product is possible by using predictive food models. Furthermore, the integration of this rapid method in a process analytical technology system (PAT) allows companies to optimize processes and their storage management which leads to a long-term reduction of food waste in meat chains.

P. 51.- EFFECT OF AROMATIZATION OF A VARIETY OF CHEESE (AMIR) BY ANISE: *PIMPINELLA ANISUM*.

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Keywords: Milk, cheese, Pimpinella anisum, synthetic flavor.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Thanks to its richness of elements and its variety of constituents, milk and its derivatives had long been the staple food for the man who is always looking for a natural and healthy product; Our study aims to study the effect of the natural aromatization of fresh cheese "Amir" by an aromatic plant; Green anise (*Pimpinella anisum*).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The cheese used (Amir®) is manufactured from local cow's milk, first the milk is collected from the dairy; it is then skimmed milk by centrifugation. The cream obtained is subjected to pasteurization and to a hard maturation of 4 to 5 hours. The physicochemical parameters measured in the fresh cheese are; the Dornic acidity measured by titration with NaOH in the presence of phenolphthalein, the density, rate of fat determined by the acid-butyrometric (Gerber method) and the pH value.

The antibiotics Search is done with the test of binding to receptors on an immuno-chromatographic medium to detect tetracyclines and β -lactams. Microbiological analysis are realized to detect total Coliform, fecal Coliform, Samonella species, pathogenic Staphylococci, yeasts and molds.

Flavored cheese and sensory test is carried out using three concentrations; 3, 4 and 5 g / 100ml. A taste panel consisting of 33 persons was used. The tasters were asked to classify the samples according to their overall preferences and taking into consideration the overall sensory quality of the cheese. The studied sensory attributes are: the smell, taste and aftertaste. The scale consists of a series of statements in which the taster expresses the degree of their satisfaction with the words: happy, normal, dissatisfied.

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RESULTS

The results show that the optimum concentration for flavoring is 4 g / 100 ml where the desired flavor has been obtained and that the plant does not affect the amount of lipids content. On the other hand, the acidity has increased from 130 D° to 145 D°, the pH also increased from 4.01 to 4.78. For the microbiological analyzes we found that there is no effect of our plant on the microbiological quality and finally for the organoleptic test, it was found that 81% of the people questioned on the sensorial quality liked the new taste of the cheese Flavored by Anis.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it is possible to substitute synthetic flavoring agents, for the adverse effects on human health, by natural substances used both in treatment and in food a long time ago without showing undesirable effects.

P. 52.- REDUCTION OF CONSUMER RISK FROM PORK BY HOT WATER AND LACTIC ACID DECONTAMINATION.

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Keywords: carcass decontamination, hot water, lactic acid, consumer risk

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

In Denmark, lactic acid decontamination is under consideration as an alternative to the hot water decontamination of pig carcasses currently in use. The aim of the study was to investigate experimentally the effect of decontamination of pig carcasses with hot water and lactic acid, and to estimate the consequential reduction in consumer risk of salmonellosis. Additionally, reduction of E.coli by treatment with hot water and blast cooling was explored, using data from a Danish abattoir investigation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Samples of fresh pork jowls excised from carcasses at the end of slaughter were inoculated with a mixed culture of E. coli, S. Typhimurium and Y. enterocolitica, to a final concentration of approximately 10^6 CFU/cm² of each species. Sterile water and lactic acid solutions of 1% and 2.5% (w/v) were applied at temperatures of $55^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ or $80^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$, for 5 and 15 seconds. After decontamination, reductions in log₁₀ counts were calculated and used for analysis of variance. For each decontamination method, the effect on consumer risk was estimated using a published quantitative risk model. The effect of the different techniques on the risk of salmonellosis was assessed in terms of mean relative risk.

Swab samples were collected in a Danish abattoir on three days, from 50 carcasses per day, before and after decontamination and after chilling. E.coli was enumerated and distributions were fitted to the counts and used for comparison between reduction by hot water with and without cooling.

RESULTS

In the experimental trials, hot water decontamination reduced microbial counts by a wide log₁₀ range (0.68 to 5.07), impacted by the duration of treatment. Higher reduction was found on the skin compared to the muscle surface. The results indicate a benefit of increasing the temperature of the lactic acid solution in alternative to applying lactic acid and hot water separately. To reduce tissue heat damage, 2.5 % lactic acid at 55°C could be used as an alternative to 80°C hot water.

The risk model used links consumer risk to pathogen concentration on carcass, and showed that the reduction in human cases also depends on the type of decontamination treatment and the type of tissue surface. The slaughter line investigation showed a reduction of E. coli comparable to the equivalent experimental trial.

CONCLUSIONS

End-slaughter decontamination reduces the consumer risk of salmonellosis from pork. When selecting a decontamination method, agent, temperature, time and tissue surface need to be considered due to their impact on reduction effectiveness and consumer risk. Decontamination with hot water or lactic acid may be an efficient way to improve food safety of pork until sufficient farm control is in place. Skin swab-based slaughter line investigations may overestimate the effect of decontamination, due to higher bacterial reduction obtained on skin compared to meat.

P. 53.- EVALUATION OF HEAT TREATMENTS OF LIVE BIVALVE MOLLUSKS.

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Keywords: live bivalve molluscs, shellfish, mussels, oysters, Hepatitis A virus, Norovirus, heat treatment

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Following a request from the European Commission, the Panel on Biological Hazards (BIOHAZ Panel) was asked by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to deliver a Scientific Opinion on the evaluation of heat treatments, different from those currently established in the EU legislation, that could be applied to live bivalve molluscs from B and C production areas, that have not been submitted to purification or relaying, to eliminate pathogenic microorganisms. Of particular relevance are the achievement of at least 90°C for at least 90 s in the mollusc flesh and the inactivation of viruses.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Hazard identification was performed to list the key viral hazards associated with consumption of bivalve molluscs. A model to evaluate the effect of temperature on heat inactivation of Hepatitis A virus (HAV) was developed and used to identify equivalent time–temperature combinations to the 'notional' heat treatment of 90°C for 90 s. HAV inactivation was also predicted for 'realistic' 90°C for 90 s processes (including heat-up and cool-down times) with various process designs.

RESULTS

Hazard identification concluded that Norovirus and HAV are the most important viral hazards associated with bivalve molluscs. A HAV thermal inactivation model was developed to identify equivalent processes to the 'notional' heat treatment of 90°C for 90 s (without heat-up and cool-down times) between 72 and 100°C. The mean D90 and z-values of the model were 54 s and 27.5°C. Theoretical and industrial profiles showed that significant variations in HAV log reduction are obtained depending on the process design. A risk assessment case study was developed to show the relationship between a Performance Criterion (PC) for the HAV reduction during heat treatment of bivalve molluscs and the human risk at consumption.

CONCLUSIONS

If risk managers establish an Appropriate Level of Protection (ALOP), this can be translated to a PC and a Process Criterion (PrC) using the HAV thermal inactivation model. An F-value is a more appropriate PrC than the current time–temperature combination since it takes into account the whole profile during heat treatment.

P. 54.- META-ANALYSIS OF OCCURRENCE OF OCHRATOXIN A (OTA), ZEARELENONE (ZEN) AND DEOXYNIVALENOL (DON) IN WHEAT BASED PRODUCTS.

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Keywords: Meta-analysis, ochratoxin A (OTA), zearalenone (ZEN), Deoxynivalenol (DON), wheat based products

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Mycotoxins are secondary metabolites may be formed by the mycotoxigenic molds when growing in contaminated foods at production, processing, transportation, and also during storage. The investigation regarding the contamination by mycotoxins in food products, as a significant threat to human health, attracted considerable attractions. The global contamination of foods as well as feeds with mycotoxins is a major problem which could cause damages in agro-economic as well a public health. The meta-analysis can be approached to gain insights on the occurrence of mycotoxins in food matrixes and on the construction of meta-analytical models to assess the effects of some unit operations on the levels of mycotoxins in foods. With the aid of meta-analysis, despite a large amount of available data, objective and replicable results regarding occurrence of mycotoxin can be obtained and consequence conclusions in order to control the targeted mycotoxins such as Zearalenone, Deoxynivalenol and Aflatoxin M1 in cereal based and dairy products can be conducted. The conducted systematic review as primary part of the current investigation could demonstrate the current situation of this safety issue.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

He present study was aimed to estimate the prevalence of ochratoxin A (OTA), zearalenone (ZEA) and Deoxynivalenol (DON) in wheat and wheat based products using a meta-analysis procedure. First, the systematic review was conducted based on all of the available sources such as Google, Scopus, and PubMe.

RESULTS

According to published articles, the highest incidence of OTA was reported in South Asia and Africa, also, in the case of ZEA, the highest incidence was observed in North and South America, Central Europe, Africa, and North and Southeast Asia, and the highest occurrence of DON were measured in samples from North America, Northern and Central Europe, Africa and North Asia. However, some of the biological factors, crop rotation, and cultivation of highly susceptible wheat cultivar without application of fungicide as well as storage and processing conditions are important, the climate conditions, such as heavy rainfall before harvest step and temperature, were found as the main reasons of wheat and wheat based products contamination.

CONCLUSIONS

Furthermore, the meta-analytic approach used here could provide reliable information regarding occurrence patterns, influencing factors and a solid basis for the development of specific actions aiming to reduce the exposure to OTA, ZEA, and DON through the consumption of the mentioned products.

P. 55.- UNDERSTANDING BACTERIAL TRANSFERENCE DURING WASHING PROCESS OF FRESH-CUT LETTUCE AND SPINACH IN SIMULATED REUSED FRESH-C.

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Keywords: food safety, bacterial transfer, ready-to-eat vegetables

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Inadequate quality of water used in the washing of fresh-cut produce has the potential to be a direct source of contamination and a vehicle for spreading bacteria.

This study aims to evaluate the influence of washing methods (time, temperature, water/produce ratio, NaClO concentration and effect of other disinfectants as isothiocyanates); wash water quality (organic matter, turbidity, conductivity, pH); source of contamination (produce or water); and type of fresh-cut produce in bacterial cross-contamination during the washing step.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Physical-chemical characterization of fresh-cut produce wash water was carried out from effluents of a local fresh-cut processing industry. 25 g of fresh iceberg lettuce pieces were inoculated with gentamicin-resistant *Salmonella enterica* (LFMFP 687) and washed in 1 L of simulated wash water under stirring at 260 rpm for 90 s at 4 °C, and repeated twice within 2 subsequent washing cycles with reused water. *Salmonella* concentration and load of natural microbiota in the produce were quantified in water and in the produce before and after the washing treatment. Similar experiments were conducted with fresh spinach. Color and microbial growth in the washed produce has been evaluated after 7 days of storage at 4 °C.

RESULTS

The main chemical properties of the prepared simulated wash water can be summarized as 150 mg/L TOC, 100 NTU, 1000 µS/cm, pH of 6.2. *Salmonella* has been transferred from the inoculated lettuce to the wash water, remaining in the reused wash water and accumulating after each subsequent cycle of washing (reaching concentration values up to 105 CFU/mL). Produce to water transfer ratio has been quantified for fresh-cut lettuce and spinach leading to similar values despite spinach washing gives rise to a notably increase in the concentration of suspended solids in the reused wash water. The tested temperatures of washing together with produce/water ratio do not seem to affect the sensorial properties and microbial growth of the washed samples in comparison with non-washed produce samples in absence of disinfectant.

CONCLUSIONS

Development of a solid understanding of the washing process and its effects on microbial growth is required to prevent cross-contamination, enhancing produce quality and safety.

P. 56.- QUANTIFY THE IMPACT OF MANAGEMENT MEASURES ON THE RISK OF SALMONELLOSIS WITH A TWO-DIMENSIONAL QMRA MODEL.

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Keywords: QMRA, uncertainty, sensitivity analysis, Salmonella

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

A quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA) model was developed for a strain of *S. diarizonae* and *S. Enteritidis*, both isolated from cheese. A two dimensional Monte-Carlo simulation model was used to evaluate separately the variability and the uncertainty in output. A sensitivity analysis was conducted to quantify the influence of the uncertainty due to the inputs on the model output. The effect of four scenarios was compared to a baseline scenario in terms of health benefit (risk reduction) and economic cost (number of batches rejected).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The uncertainty associated with the 7 estimated inputs parameters was modeled separately from variability. First, the uncertain inputs were randomly sampled from their respective distributions for i iterations. Thus, we obtained i combinations of uncertain inputs. Then, for each combination, variable inputs were randomly sampled from their distributions for j iterations. Iteration j corresponds to a simulated batch of cheeses.

The sensitivity analysis was conducted according to the method of Saltelli (2002) by decomposing the model output variance (risk at logarithmic scale) and by deriving Sobol's indices. Two measures of sensitivity are calculated: a first-order sensitivity index (S_i) and a total-effect sensitivity index (ST_i), which includes the first-order effect and all higher-order interaction effects. If the total-effect sensitivity is substantially higher than the first-order sensitivity index, it can be concluded that interaction effects make a major contribution to the variation in the outcome. Both measures are rescaled to the interval $[0, 1]$ and therefore are conveniently interpreted as the proportion of variance in the output variable that is attributable to variation of an input factor.

CONCLUSIONS

The two-dimensional model enables to highlight the part of variability and uncertainty associated with the inputs parameters.

The sensitivity analysis allows the quantification of the influence of the uncertainty due to the inputs on the model output.

Parameters that have no impact on the output can be modeled in a deterministic way to simplify the model and reduce the computing time.

The risk assessor is able to reduce the cost of data acquisition by targeting the most influent parameters. Despite the uncertainties, the percentage of risk reduction with scenarios S_2 and S_3 are important with a 1st and 5th percentiles highest than 80%.

This model can be used by risk assessors and risk managers to compare and verify the impact of measures on safety and economic objectives.

P. 57.- AN EXAMINATION OF MODELING ASSUMPTIONS IN OUTBREAK FOOD ATTRIBUTION STUDIES

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Keywords: Food Attribution, Burden of Illness

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Attributing foods to pathogens is a critical first step for QMRAs. Outbreak studies are often used as a basis for these estimates, but the plethora of studies examining outbreaks have used differing assumptions for both the shaping of the data set and attribution analyses. In this study, I examine the effect of various assumptions on attribution estimates for pathogens that are both well represented and underrepresented in the data.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

I use U.S. NORS outbreak data for 1998-2015 to examine attribution rates for meat and poultry products in relation to other products. An attribution study is conducted including varying assumptions regarding treatment of: 1. Older data, 2. Foods with implicated ingredients vs. those with more general food vehicle information 3. Simple vs. complex foods, 4. Suspected vs. confirmed etiologies, 5. Use of outbreak counts vs. illness counts, and 6. Multiple etiology outbreaks. Multiple pathogens reflecting different levels of representation in the data are examined.

RESULTS

Between 1998 and 2015 a total of 9,265 food-related outbreaks for which at least one food vehicle was identified were reported. The attributable share of outbreaks associated with meat and poultry varies by sample structure and treatment of complex foods. For the full sample, between 30.3% and 59.4% of outbreaks were associated with meat and poultry products (depending on whether inclusion as part of a complex food was given a weight of 0 to 1). Other exclusions yield the following. Exclusion of unknown etiologies (N=6,354): 32.2% to 57.9%. Exclusion of multiple etiologies (N=6,051): 31.9% to 57.6%. Exclusion of unclear vehicles (N=5,586): 34.3% to 61.9%. Exclusion of suspected etiologies (38.3%-62.5%). Exclusion if no identified ingredient (N=1,235): 58.1% to 63.5%. Exclusion of outbreaks more than five years old (N=1,158): 35.0% to 56.8%. For specific foods (e.g. beef) or less represented pathogens (e.g. *Listeria m.*), data limitations have more significant effects

CONCLUSIONS

Outbreak-based food attribution studies use a number of assumptions that often vary from study to study. Initial results suggest that differences in estimates are limited at the macro level where all pathogens are included and food categories are broad. At the more useful micro level typical of most QMRAs, attribution assumptions made for single foods or pathogens with limited representation in the data can have great effect on attribution estimates, suggesting the importance of understanding the trade-off between data quality and data quantity.

P. 58.- USING PREDICTIVE MODELLING IN INCIDENT INVOLVING SALMONELLA IN A HARD RAW MILK CHEESE TO ASSESS THE EFFECT OF MATURATION.

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Keywords: Raw milk, raw milk cheese, maturation, Salmonella

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Salmonella enterica subspecies enterica serotype Dublin (S. Dublin) was detected in clinical samples and in raw cow's milk (RCM) on Dairy Farm A, and also in hard cheese (Caerphilly type) made with RCM from Farm A at Business A (manufacturer) and B (maturer). S. Dublin is host adapted in cattle, but can cause severe invasive disease in humans. Although relatively few samples were collected, S. Dublin was detected in all of the ones taken at Business A (4/4) and B (2/2) of cheese made with a single batch of RCM from Farm A. This suggested a high prevalence of S. Dublin in these cheeses, although the level of contamination was unknown. As the production of the cheese did not include a heating step sufficient to eliminate Salmonella, there was a need for the Food Standards Agency (FSA) to assess the effect of maturation on the pathogen, in order to provide proportionate risk management (RM) advice.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The cheese was matured for a minimum of 10 weeks at 15°C and 90% humidity. The pH and water phase salt (WPS) of the core were 5.6 and 2.05% and of the rind 7.1 and 3.32%, respectively. To assess the effect of maturation, the FSA ran models of uncertainty for non-thermal inactivation of Salmonella on ComBase. The platform does not allow WPS content below 6.6% and thus, assessment of Salmonella die-off is likely to be overestimated. A 40-day maturation period was explored following a suggestion by Business A that this may be sufficient to destroy the hazard.

RESULTS

The models predicted a reduction of approx. 0.4 and 1.5 log₁₀ for Salmonella after 40 days and 10 weeks, respectively, at 15°C both in the rind and the core (although likely to be overestimations). The range of uncertainty around these estimations (associated with the pathogen's initial physiological state and the rate of inactivation), was very wide, including the possibility that no reduction may occur. Interestingly, Salmonella was detected in a sample of cheese made with the same batch of RCM and taken at Business A after 38 days of maturation. The isolate was not typed, but its detection suggested that maturation periods of approx. 40 days were not sufficient to ensure complete inactivation of Salmonella and thus the safety of this cheese.

CONCLUSIONS

The Risk Assessment (RA) concluded that, although it was likely S. Dublin would die-off to a degree during maturation, it was highly uncertain what the extent of such die-off would be and whether maturation could ensure complete elimination of Salmonella. The predictive microbiology allowed the FSA to assess whether proposed RM advice was proportionate and ensure the decision for the cheese, which had tested positive for Salmonella, not to enter the food chain (unless subjected to a suitable heat treatment to eliminate the pathogen) was appropriate. This demonstrates a practical application of a predictive microbiological modelling platform to support RA and subsequent RM decisions in the fast paced world of responding to routine microbiological food incidents.

P. 59.- THE USE OF RISK-BASED MODELLING TOOLS FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF FOOD SAFETY IN THE FRENCH DAIRY SECTOR: A FEEDBACK.

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

If contaminated, some dairy products may allow the development of pathogenic bacteria. The manufacturer must guaranty the safety of its products for the consumer. Next to GHP, HACCP plan and traceability, Quantitative Microbiological Risk Assessment (QMRA) coupled to predictive microbiology (PM) have emerged as useful tools to manage the safety of food products. Since 2003, the French dairy sector has developed risk-based tools to help dairy manufacturers in this purpose. The objective of this presentation is to provide a feedback on the use of these tools developed for the French dairy sector.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A statistical toolkit for microbiological dairy data analysis using non-conformity results regarding a given microbiological criterion is first proposed. Results obtained help assessing temporal trends and identifying seasonality for the raw milk contamination prevalence, quantifying the efficiency of intervention strategies, optimizing milk sorting...

The second tool is the construction of stochastic QMRA models that can be adapted to several cheese technologies and pathogenic bacteria. Inputs are the outputs of the first toolkit, the manufacturing process, physico-chemical parameters during process, challenge-tests results and information on the bacteria of interest. Monte-Carlo simulations allow to consider variability and uncertainty. The basic outputs of the QMRA models are the prevalence of contamination, the concentration of the product at each step of the process, and the associated risk of illness.

A web-based interface was developed to enable dairy operators to perform simulations with their data.

RESULTS

The objectives of the developed tools were to enable the food safety manager to validate and optimize food safety management options at each step of the process, including sampling, while minimizing the risk of illness.

Positive results were obtained, for example, when studies were performed collectively, to defend a (sanitary) position. Mixed results were obtained when the objective was to use QMRA and PM for an everyday use by quality managers.

Time and human resources are generally lacking for SME, next to the need of specific competences in modelling. The need for outputs focused on sampling strategy was clearly observed. Finally, raising awareness on the risk-based approach and on the tools with concrete applications through a regular communication is of particularly great importance.

CONCLUSIONS

The approach developed by the French Dairy Sector has now reached a mature stage, with French dairy companies being aware of the need of QMRA and PM to perform a risk-based approach, as recommended by health authorities. However, improvements for a better use of the existing tools by the quality managers are possible: being able to provide very concrete results for the validation of food safety management options, providing results on the best monitoring sampling plans, increasing the formation of future quality manager and inspectors from the food safety authorities.

P. 60.- IMPACT OF ROASTING SEVERITY AND VARIABILITY ON RISK OF SALMONELLOSIS FROM CONSUMPTION OF PEANUTS IN THE UNITED STATES.

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Keywords: peanuts, salmonella, risk assessment, low-moisture

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Peanut products were the target of the largest recall in United States history in 2008-2009, with over 3,200 products implicated, economic losses estimated at \$1 billion and over 700 reported illnesses and 9 deaths. Predictive modeling tools such as quantitative microbial risk assessment (QMRA) are often used to aid processors in making risk management decisions that can reduce the chances of foodborne illness. There is currently no published risk assessment for peanuts available to guide managers in designing and implementing appropriate process interventions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A QMRA was performed to quantify salmonellosis risk from consumption of peanuts in the United States. Prevalence and concentration data for *Salmonella* on raw, shelled peanuts was used in combination with probability distributions of simulated log reductions achieved during storage times and temperatures prior to consumption. Data for the time/temperature combinations used in each step were obtained from published literature, industry surveys, or expert opinion. Survival data for *Salmonella* on peanuts was obtained from the literature. A previously published beta-poisson dose-response model was used to predict probability of illness from ingestion of *Salmonella* cells. A worst case assumption that 1% of peanuts are consumed raw (based on the fraction sold as raw) was used. Various combinations of targeted log reductions (3, 5, and 7 log reductions) and log reduction standard deviations (0.5, 1, and 2 log reductions) were used in the model to estimate the impact of different log reductions and process variability. Five simulations of 10,000 iterations each were run for each combination of log reduction and log reduction standard deviation.

RESULTS

The model predicted a 79% chance of one or more illnesses per year based on worst case assumptions for consumption of raw peanuts. Sensitivity analysis showed that the initial *Salmonella* concentration had the biggest impact on predicted salmonellosis risk. When a 5 ± 1 log reduction (typical of a commercial roasting process) was applied to the entire crop, the probability of 1 or more illness per year dropped to ~8%. In general, increasing targeted log reductions decreased the probability of more than one illness per year ($P < 0.05$). Reducing uncertainty from 2 logs to 0.5 logs reduced the probability of expecting more than one illness per year from ~18% to ~5% when applying a targeted 5 log reduction and ~4% to < 0.05). However, applying 3 log reductions and decreasing uncertainty from 2 logs to 0.5 logs increased the probability of more than one illness per year from 48% to 49% ($P < 0.05$).

CONCLUSIONS

This study indicates that using a process of three log reductions may be insufficient to significantly reduce salmonellosis risk in peanuts. Careful monitoring of appropriate critical limits in peanut roasting processes should reduce foodborne illness risk if a less variable process is applied.

P. 61.- A COMPARISON OF THE USE OF FSO AND DOSE RESPONSE CURVE TO ASSESS FOOD SAFETY MARGINS OF LISTERIA IN SMOKED SALMON.

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Keywords: Safety margin, risk-informed, *Listeria monocytogenes*, smoked salmon, decision-making process

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

The concept of Food Safety Margin (FSM) and its formulation based on classical and probabilistic metrics was introduced in microbiological risk analysis as an alternative approach to risk characterization to support the risk-informed decision-making process. The food safety objective (FSO), defined as the maximum concentration of a microbial hazard in a food considered tolerable for consumer protection at the time of consumption, permits to convey the appropriate level of protection (ALOP) into goals that can be controlled by food producers and government agencies. This way, each FSO is intended to guarantee an appropriate safety margin of exposure to a particular microbiological load, which can be quantified using the above metrics.

The probability that a person shows an adverse effect after consuming a product with a given microbiological load is used to determine the FSO necessary to achieve the ALOP depending also on the expected population being exposed to this load. Then, not only exposure assessment but also dose-response analysis of the relationship between dose and the likelihood and severity of adverse health effects are necessary for a realistic risk characterization. However, the dose-response curve is affected not only by the level of a hazard but also by numerous parameters as the virulence of the pathogen, the age and immune status of the person, the food matrix, the product treatments, etc. Therefore, establishing a value for the FSO of one particular food is complex and it may be one of the main reasons why numeric safety goals have not been regulated yet for FSO.

In this framework, the objective of this paper is to present the fundamentals and discuss the results of the quantification of both classical and probabilistic safety margins of exposure to *Listeria monocytogenes* using the FSO as compared to the use of the dose-response curve with application to smoked salmon.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Food safety margin metric (1)

(1) Doménech, E. & Martorell, S. (2016). Definition and usage of food safety margins for verifying compliance of Food Safety Objectives. *Food Control*, 59, 669-674.

RESULTS

The result of the classical FSM obtained using the FSO provides a mean value of 0.98 as compared to the mean value of 0.99989 obtained when the dose-response curve is used. When the probabilistic FSM is quantified, the safety margins are 0.99 and 1 using the FSO and the dose-response curve respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

Then, one may conclude that using both FSO and dose-response curve provide similar results in this example of application. In addition, the FSO provides the lowest safety margins as expected provided that FSOs are established normally in a conservative way to guarantee consumer health.

P. 62.- INCLUDING GENOTYPIC DATA INTO MICROBIAL QUANTITATIVE RISK ASSESSMENT: APPLICATION ON *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN COLD SMOKED SALMON

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Keywords: clonal complex, genomics

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Listeria monocytogenes is a bacterial pathogen that causes the foodborne disease listeriosis. The most common route of human infection is the consumption of contaminated Ready-to-Eat foods (RTE). Within those, cold-smoked salmon is of particular interest as it presents high prevalence of *L. monocytogenes* at retail stage. Recent developments in genome sequencing open new opportunities for explaining the intraspecific variability of phenotypes (e.g. virulence, growth behavior). Successful association between WGS-data and specific phenotypes is thought to contribute to better predicting microbial behaviors. Implementing this information in hazard identification, exposure assessment, and hazard characterization processes will refine QMRA-models.

The aim of this study was to compare two QMRA approaches. In the first approach the association between genotypes and phenotypes was taken into account. These results were compared to those obtained with classical QMRA.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The used QMRA-model was previously developed for assessing the number of listeriosis cases associated to cold smoked salmon in France (Pouillot et al., 2009 and 2011) and for assessing the efficiency of communications targeting consumers (ANSES, 2015).

The global prevalence in the existing model was replaced by the specific prevalences for each clonal complex (CC). These relative prevalences were derived from the recent distribution observed in cold smoked salmon in Europe (Moller-Nielsen et al, 2017).

For risk characterization, the CCs were split in three categories of virulence according to a recent publication (Maury et al. 2016). The dose-response was assumed to be different between these categories. Lower, median and upper values of existing dose-response model (Pouillot et al., 2015) were associated to the three CC categories.

RESULTS

The exposure of consumers to the different CCs was estimated. The assumption for dose response permitted to calculate the relative contribution of CC to listeriosis cases. The rank of most important CCs in exposure was different from the rank of CCs that mostly contribute to listeriosis cases.

CONCLUSIONS

The CCs that contributed the most in exposure were not necessarily those that contributed the most to listeriosis cases. The assumptions of association between CCs and dose response parameter need to be reinforced. Considering genotypic data in QMRA, opens the way for the establishment of risk based measures specific to CCs.

SESSION 6: Predictive models for food process simulation

P. 63.- EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE GROWTH POTENTIAL OF SELECTED YEAST CONTAMINANTS IN FRESH FERMENTED DAIRY.

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Keywords: yeasts, fermented dairy, growth rate, chilled storage, consumer product abuse

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Fresh fermented dairy are widely consumed products whose shelf-life can be limited by the growth of yeasts resulting in discolouration, off-odours and flavours, changes in texture and gas production (Fröhlich-Wyder, 2003). The aim of this study was to model the growth of various dairy yeast contaminants of relevance to the storage of fresh yoghurt, skyr and quark.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Six species of spoilage yeasts (*Issatchenkia occidentalis*, *Candida intermedia*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Torulospora delbrueckii*, *Pichia norvegensis*, *Clavispora lusitaniae*) were inoculated at low levels (

RESULTS

Spiked products stored at 13 or 30°C spoiled very fast, i.e. within 3 days during storage at 30°C and within a week during storage at 13°C. All spiked products stored at 8°C spoiled within 2 weeks with the exception of *P. norvegensis* that grew more slowly than other strains in all products. Growth of yeasts in products stored at 5°C was slow with most species having concentrations up to 3 log CFU/g at the end of sampling. An exception to this were *C. lusitaniae* and *C. intermedia* that grew relatively faster and reached concentrations up to 4 log CFU/g.

CONCLUSIONS

- All studied yeast species were able to grow very fast in all tested products and spoil them within 3-6 days when stored at abusive temperatures ($\geq 13^{\circ}\text{C}$).
- Products stored at 5°C had a significantly longer time to spoilage in comparison to products stored at 8°C (2-3 times longer).

P. 64.- MODELING *WEISSELLA VIRIDESCENS* GROWTH ON HAM USING ACTIVE FILM INCORPORATED WITH OREGANO ESSENTIAL.

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Keywords: *Weissella viridescens*; vacuum-packed sliced ham; active film; oregano essential oil

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Lactic acid bacteria (BAL) are considered the main spoilage microorganisms in cooked meat products, vacuum packed, keep under refrigeration. Due to consumer demand for more natural food products, studies have focused on the incorporation of natural antimicrobial compounds, like essential oils, on packaging materials. Oregano essential oil (OEO) has been used as a natural antimicrobial agent to increase the shelf life of food products. The use of mathematical models describing the microbial behavior can be useful for predicting food shelf life. The aim of this study was to model the effect of the use of incorporated film with OEO as an antimicrobial agent on the shelf life of sliced vacuum packed ham in isothermal conditions, based on the growth of the *Weissella viridescens*, a well-studied BAL.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Fresh ham pieces (around 5,2 kg ($\pm 0,06$)) were previously sterilized, then aseptically sliced and each slice was inoculated with microbial suspension (around 10^4 CFU.L⁻¹) of *W. viridescens* with and without (used as control) the inclusion of active film in concentrations of 10 and 15% of OEO in the packaging. The samples were vacuum-packed and stored at 8 °C in a temperature controlled incubator. The primary Baranyi and Roberts model was adjusted to the growth data and the parameters μ_{\max} , λ , y_{\max} and the time (in days) to reach the end of shelf life (10^7 CFU.g⁻¹) were obtained. Its predictive ability was assessed through statistical indexes (Bias factor, accuracy factor, RMSE and R2), with good results.

RESULTS

The use of the active film incorporated with 10% of OEO led a small increase in λ , the same μ_{\max} , a small decrease in y_{\max} and an increase of one day in the shelf life of the ham in relation to the samples without the active film. This active film began to show antimicrobial effect only in the end of the exponential phase. However, the film incorporated with 15% of OEO decreased the μ_{\max} , increased the λ , which led to an increase in the shelf life of the product from 9 (control) to 16 days.

CONCLUSIONS

The results showed that the predictive model studied can be used to predict the shelf life of meat products, moreover the film incorporated with OEO (15%) showed a satisfactory antimicrobial effect.

P. 65.- MODELING *WEISSELLA VIRIDESCENS* INACTIVATION BY ULTRAVIOLET RADIATION. Cíntia Maia Braga, Isabella Medeiros Souza, Leticia Floriano, Larissa Ramos, Josamaique Gilson Venerai, Andreia Tremarin, Jorge Ninow, Gláucia Maria Falcão Aragão

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Keywords: *Weissella viridescens*; ultraviolet radiation UV-C; inactivation; mathematical model

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB), including *Weissella viridescens*, is among the main groups of microorganisms responsible for spoilage of refrigerated meat products, vacuum packed and under modified atmosphere. There is an amplified demand by consumers for minimally processed and safer foods, with retained original organoleptic attributes. Non-thermal processing of foods by application of radiation treatments like ultraviolet radiation (UV-C) is positively being accepted by the food industry and consumers. UV-C treatment is reported to induce minimal quality changes and is capable of reducing microbial load. The objective of this study was to obtain a mathematical model able to predict *W. viridescens* inactivation in vitro, under constant and variable UV-C radiation intensities.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Treatments were carried out in a camera (40 x 40x 40 cm) with ten germicidal UV-C lamps at 24 W with peak emission at 254 nm. The experiments were artificially inoculated with bacterium, with initial loads around 10^8 CFU/mL and then exposed to UV-C radiation and the treatment impact on microbial loads was assessed throughout exposure times. Five different radiation intensities (0.58; 1.10; 1.34; 1.68 and 1.98 W/m²) were applied to *W. viridescens* population and the concentration was measured over time. Weibull model was fitted to experimental data to obtain inactivation parameters β and α (β is the location factor and α is the shape factor). After initial fit, α was fixed (1.26).

RESULTS

Results showed that, for the highest intensity (1.98 W/m²) time to reach 6 decimal reductions (t_{6D}) was 2.3 s and for the lowest intensity (0.58 W/m²) was 12.4 s. So as highest the intensity of UV-C treatment used, lowest time was necessary to reach t_{6D}. The Weibull model described well the inactivation data of contaminated microorganisms. Exponential model was chosen to describe the influence of radiation intensity on β parameter. From the primary and secondary models it was possible to establish a dynamic model to predict the behavior of *W. viridescens* under radiation intensity variation. The proposed model was validated with experimental data and can correctly predict the inactivation of the studied microorganism.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded that UV-C radiation is a promising treatment with a drastic impact on the loads of *W. viridiscens*, especially when high intensities are used.

P. 66.- IDENTIFICATION OF AROMA AND COLOR METABOLITES TO ASSAY GENES INVOLVED IN THE ORGANOLEPTIC QUALITY OF STRAWBERRY FRUIT.

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Keywords: Strawberry; aroma profile; anthocyanins; fruit quality

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Strawberry is globally the most economically important soft fruit. Spain is one of the most important strawberry producer, being most of its production exported. However, the decrease of fruit quality, the important losses of fruit yield due to postharvest oversoftening and the increased competition of foreign countries, are reducing the trade value of this crop. Fruit development and ripening is a high complex process that involve different metabolic pathways and networks related with the main changes associated with receptacle fruit ripening as color production, firmness, taste and flavor. In consequence, this complex process must be strictly regulated through a network of ripening-related transcription factors (TFs). In spite of their scientific and biotechnological importance the regulatory processes that support the ripening process are very scarcely understood. Metabolomics is one of the most recently advanced '-omic' technologies, which analyze a great number of small metabolites of a different system or biological samples.

The present work shows the preliminary results of metabolomics analysis related with the characterization of the phenolic and aromatic profile of the strawberry without genetic alteration in order to improve the quality of the fruit

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A dynamic headspace sorptive extraction (DHS) combined with thermal desorption (TD) and coupled with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS) was developed.

Phenolic compounds were identified by comparing their retention times with those for standards, recording UV spectra on a HPLC-DAD and calculating the UV absorbance ratios for samples and standards simultaneously co-injected one at a time

RESULTS

59 volatile metabolites identified belonging to different chemical families (aldehydes, esters, alcohols, acids, terpenes, ketones, phenols, lactones, and others). The phenolic compounds identified were anthocynins, flavonols and flavan-3-ol derivatives

CONCLUSIONS

The identified metabolites will allow studying the genes involved in the regulation of process related to organoleptic quality

P. 67.- MICROBIOLOGICAL AND CHEMICAL SPOILAGE PREDICTION OF HIGH AND LOW FAT RAW GROUND MEAT.

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Keywords: meat spoilage prediction; pseudomonads; square root model; PLS regression

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Meat is subjected to chemical and microbiological deterioration, caused by oxidative degradation of meat fat and by the presence of microbial populations, particularly *Pseudomonas* spp.. Therefore spoilage can be monitored through their growth and changes in TBARS, thiols and carbonyls. The aim of the current study is to evaluate the correlation between chemical and microbiological data by PCA analysis and predict meat spoilage by pseudomonads contamination under isothermal and dynamic conditions or by chemical parameters in high and low fat ground meat by multivariate statistical analysis

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Beef ground meat containing a total fat amount of about 5% or 15% of fat was divided into 150 g portions, stored under isothermal conditions (0, 5, 10 and 15°C) and checked for the presence of *Pseudomonas* spp., *Brochothrix* spp., total viable count (TVC). Water loss, pH, thiols, carbonyls, TBARS, metmyoglobin, deoxymyoglobin, oxymyoglobin and colour changes were determined on all samples. All data were subjected to PCA analysis to evaluate the correlation between microbiological and chemical variables. Subsequently, a square root model was fitted to the growth rates of pseudomonads and used to predict spoilage of ground meat under isothermal and dynamic conditions. Additionally, multivariate statistical analysis was applied to fit a PLS (Partial Least Square Regression) model, aiming at predicting microbial counts of minced meat, based on chemical data, regardless of time-temperature storage profile

RESULTS

Growth models allow to predict the evolution of food spoilage during storage as a function of extrinsic conditions food characteristics. Results by the PCA analysis showed that, among microbiological and chemical indexes monitored during refrigerated storage, a positive correlation was found between increase in TBARS (0.70) and levels of pseudomonads, which were inversely correlated with thiols (-0.71) and oxymyoglobin (-0.81). Moreover, results demonstrated that the fat level of ground meat did not influence the growth rate of pseudomonads allowing the application of a single model for predicting the growth of pseudomonads and time to spoilage of ground meat given dynamic temperature conditions, regardless of fat content. PLS analysis was performed considering all the microbiological parameters as Y-variables, while the chemical data were used as X-variables. The model (R2CV 0.81, RMSECV of 0.68 for pseudomonads prediction) can allow to use chemical data to predict the microbial load of ground meat during refrigerated shelf life, regardless of fat content and time-temperature conditions. Moreover, the PLS model can allow to discriminate acceptable (TVC 7 log cfu/g; TBARS 0.13-1.33 mg/kg; thiols 52.94-73.06 nmol/mg protein) samples

CONCLUSIONS

Knowledge of perishability of food matrices associated to the storage history provide important information on the quality and edibility of food.

P. 68.- MODELLING THE GROWTH OF SALMONELLA IN CHICKEN UNDER ISOTHERMAL AND NON-ISOTHERMAL PROFILES.

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Keywords: Salmonella, dynamic temperature profile, predictive microbiology

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Salmonella is a gram-negative pathogen that colonizes the gastrointestinal tracts of animals. Its importance relies on the high numbers of outbreaks and illnesses caused by this bacterium. Predictive food microbiology is a powerful mathematical tool that quantifies and generates patterns for microbial behavior. Its primary goal to the food industry is to assure both food safety and quality. With the use of mathematical models, it is possible to evaluate bacterial growth both under isothermal and non-isothermal profiles found during processing/storage of food products. This study aimed to evaluate the growth of Salmonella in chicken submitted to different isothermal and non-isothermal regimes through the use of a mathematical model

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 150 datasets of isothermal growth of Salmonella Typhimurium DT104 in grounded chicken breast at 17 different temperatures (10 °C, 11 °C, 12 °C, 14 °C, 16 °C, 18 °C, 20 °C, 22 °C, 24 °C, 26 °C, 28 °C, 30 °C, 32 °C, 34 °C, 36 °C, 38 °C, and 40 °C) were selected from Combase. The experimental data were selected from two papers of the same author (at least 5 experimental points for each temperature studied) and the other environmental parameters (pH and aw) did not differ significantly during the studies. Baranyi and Roberts (BR) primary growth model was fitted to all datasets with the R package nlsMicrobio. The extended square-root model was used as a secondary model for the maximum specific growth rate and a logarithm function was adopted as a secondary model for the lag phase duration. Two different graphs containing non-isothermal growth data with temperature ranging between 8 °C and 35 °C of Salmonella in chicken obtained from the literature were scanned and experimental points were digitalised. Subsequently, the differential equations that compose BR growth model added with the inclusion of the parameters previously obtained (μ and λ) were used to predict the non-isothermal growth data of Salmonella with the R package fme. The accuracy and bias factors were used as statistical indexes to describe the predictive ability of the model under non-isothermal profiles

RESULTS

The two secondary models used in the study described with good accuracy the dependence of the maximum specific growth rate ($R^2=0.93$) and of the lag phase duration ($R^2=0.91$) on the temperature. According to the statistical indexes evaluated, the model provided a good fit to both non-isothermal profiles studied. Results obtained were better for profile 2 (temperatures ranging between 8 and 25 °C) in relation to profile 1 (temperatures ranging between 5 and 20 °C). This result may be due to the fact that the minimum temperature of growth obtained through the secondary model is close to the boundary of profile 1 (4 °C)

CONCLUSIONS

The results showed that the predictive model can be safely applied to describe Salmonella growth under a non-isothermal temperature profile. Additional studies are needed to describe bacterial behaviour close at growth boundaries

P. 69.- MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF ENTEROTOXIN PRODUCTION BY STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS IN DIFFERENT FOOD PRODUCTS.

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Keywords: enterotoxin, Staphylococcus aureus, Luedeking-Piret

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Staphylococcus aureus are bacteria that can produce enterotoxins capable of causing gastroenteritis in humans. Although thermal sterilization processes can inactivate the cells of *S. aureus*, the enterotoxins produced may not be eliminated during the process. Due to its pathogenicity, this bacteria is of high importance for the food industry. Therefore, the objective of this study is to model the enterotoxin production by *S. aureus* in different food products

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Thirteen published experimental datasets of *S. aureus* growth and enterotoxin production in different food products were selected. The food products studied include tuna, frankfurt type sausage, milk and culture media. Subsequently, the graphs were scanned and the experimental points were digitized. Baranyi-Roberts growth model was fitted to the growth data with the R package nlsMicrobio. The resulting mathematical expression was included in the Luedeking-Piret differential equation. This model proposes that the rate of product formation is directly proportional to the bacterial population (with a constant of proportionality denoted by a) and to the bacterial growth rate (with a constant of proportionality denoted by b). The resulting model was numerically integrated and fitted to the product formation data with the R package fme. The mean relative percentage error (MRPE) was adopted to assess the predictive ability of the model

RESULTS

The Baranyi-Roberts growth model successfully reproduced the *S. aureus* growth for all datasets studied with coefficients of determination ranging between 0.980 and 0.997. The mathematical function obtained for each dataset was transformed from $\log N$ to N due to the fact that the Luedeking-Piret kinetics includes as independent variable the bacterial population and not its logarithm. The results obtained varied significantly between datasets with MRPE ranging between 8% and 27%. Better fits were obtained for bacterial growth and enterotoxin production in culture medium in relation to the food products. Both the coefficients of proportionality obtained ranged from about 10^{-5} to 10^{-6} for all datasets considered. It was not observed correlation between the two empirical parameters. In addition, it was evaluated that, in average, 60% of the enterotoxin production occurred during the stationary phase of bacterial growth according to the model adopted

CONCLUSIONS

The results showed that mathematical models can be useful tools to assess the enterotoxin production by *S. aureus*. The Luedeking-Piret model, in general, accurately fit the toxin data. A future study can include the dependence of the temperature in the model and verify how it affects the empirical parameters of the model.

P. 70.- PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES AND STABILITY OF MARGARINE ENRICHED WITH OLIVE OILS.

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Keywords: Olive oil, margarine, tocopherols, polyphenol, oxidative stability, vitamin E.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Oxidation is a phenomenon that is widely spread in both food (lipid oxidation) and organism (oxidative stress). Among food products, margarine is a typical example because 82% of its content consists of fat which is the first target of oxidation. Indeed, lipid oxidation is a major cause of degradation of margarine during its manufacture and its conservation. The study aimed to substitute synthetic antioxidant vitamin E with natural substance olive oils

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Determination fatty acid in olive oil

According to methods described in EC Regulation 796/, 2002. Scavenger effect on DPPH (Brand-Williams and al., 1995). Pigment content determination Chlorophyll and carotenoid (Minguez-Mosquera and al (1991). Liquid-liquid extraction of phenolic compounds and determination (Tsimidou et al. 1992), The total phenolic content of the extract was determined by the Folin-Ciocalteu. Incorporation olive oil in margarine; Lipid (82%) and liquid (18%) phases were prepared. The lipid phase contained palm oil, sunflower oil and equivalent hydrogenated soybean and the liquid phase: b-Carotene (12mg/kg), aroma (diacetyl: 25ppm), salt (0.60%), lactic acid (0.5 ml/kg) and potassium sorbate (300mg/kg). The olive oil was incorporated in the lipide phase with percentage of 10%. Determination of the oxidative stability of margarines (Rancimat test). Determination of physicochemical properties of the margarines developed pH, salt content, determination of solid content (solid fat content), determination of melting point, peroxid index. Determination of microbiological properties of the margarines developed. Enumeration of microorganisms and looking for some pathogens (aerobic bacteria, yeast and molds, faecal coliforms, Staphylococcus aureus and Salmonella).

RESULTS

The gas chromatography of olive oil revealed the dominance of oleic acid as a major component of the fatty acid composition. The olive oil presented significant levels of phenolic compounds that play an important role against oxidation as shown by the antiradicalair activity. The pigment content is relatively low about 2.636 mg/Kg for chlorophyll and 1.52 mg/kg for carotenoid. Two spreadable margarines enriched with olive oil, has been developed. At 37 ° C, the SFC index is less than 6%, and thus the margarine melts easily in the mouth, a melting point of 35.4 °C for two margarines. The evaluation of oxidative stability was positive by the Rancimat test. Margarine enriched with olive oil without vitamin E, proved to be more resistant to oxidation than the margarine enriched with olive oil with vitamin E.

CONCLUSIONS

The results showed that the margarines elaborated with olive oil were more resistant to oxidation than the margarine reference with vitamin E. In addition, neither the physicochemical nor the microbiological properties were modified. Olive Oil contain bioactive substances that could be used in different food sectors

P. 71.- LACTIC ACID BACTERIA AS BIOPROTECTORS IN MINIMALLY PROCESSED FISH.
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Keywords: Lactic acid bacteria; *Listeria monocytogenes*; competition; fish

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

In the last years, research on natural antimicrobials (or bioprotectors) like acid lactic bacteria (LAB) has experienced a great development in response to consumers demand. Additionally, a growing interest in raw or minimally processed foods of animal and vegetal origin requires high standards of food safety and quality. In the present work, the antimicrobial capacity of two LAB strains against various pathogens has been investigated in culture broth and minimally processed fish.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Lactobacillus plantarum gp23 and *Lactobacillus sakei* 494 were challenged against the pathogens *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella enterica* and *Escherichia coli* through the spot-on-the-lawn test at optimal culture temperatures (30°C). In a further step, both LAB strains were challenged separately against *L. monocytogenes* at 8°C under anaerobic conditions in BHI broth. From results, one of these strains was submitted to challenge test in minimally processed fish (goldfish; *Sparus aurata*) in co-culture with *L. monocytogenes* at 8°C under anaerobic conditions.

RESULTS

The two LAB investigated produced growth inhibition of all pathogens mentioned through the spot-on-the-lawn test. However, when co-cultured at suboptimal temperatures (8°C) with *L. monocytogenes* in BHI broth under anaerobic conditions, *L. sakei* 494 presented major inhibitory capacity than *L. plantarum* gp23. The activity of *L. sakei* 494 against *L. monocytogenes* in food matrix (minimally processed goldfish) also showed inhibition in the growth of the pathogen, although in lesser extent when compared with results in BHI broth.

CONCLUSIONS

This study shows the potential of *L. sakei* 494 to be used as a bioprotective culture in minimally processed fish stored at refrigeration temperatures, although more research is needed in order to elucidate and characterize its inhibitory effect against several *L. monocytogenes* strains of interest.

P. 72.- FIELD ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECT OF NATURAL NITRITE SUBSTITUTE ON THE GROWTH OF SPOILAGE ORGANISMS AND *CLOSTRIDIUM SPOROGENES* IN COOKED MEAT PRODUCTS.
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Keywords: Clostridium spp., natural antimicrobials

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Nitrites have been used in meat industry to achieve distinctive color and flavor as well as to effectively control the growth of pathogens such as *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Clostridium botulinum*. However, there is an emerging trend towards clean label products, using natural substitutes of nitrites. The objective of this study was to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of a commercial fruit- and spices- based natural antimicrobial (NA) against spoilage organisms and *C.sporogenes*, as surrogate for proteolytic *C.botulinum* in cooked meat products

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Four formulations (no nitrites, nitrites 150 ppm and two concentrations of NA) of deli-style turkey paste were inoculated in the industrial setting with *C.sporogenes* (100 and 10000 spores/g), while non-inoculated samples served as control. Final products were prepared according the commercial manufacturing process (heat treatment, smoking and High Pressure Processing-HPP). NA (extract of fruits and spices) was added in 0.5x or 1x of the concentration recommended by the manufacturer. 200g-pieces of product were vacuum packed, HPP treated and stored at different temperatures in order to monitor spoilage (5, 10, 15oC) as well as safety (6, 12, 15, 20, 25 oC) of the final product. Enumeration of *Clostridium* sp. and spoilage microflora was performed throughout storage for up to 3 months, while growth parameters (μ_{max} , lag phase- λ) were determined using DMfit. Storage under dynamic temperature conditions was used to further validate the developed growth models regarding spoilage and safety of cooked meat products

RESULTS

Formulations lacking antimicrobials allowed the growth of clostridia at all temperatures (except 6oC). NA performance against clostridia was concentration dependent. High NA concentration (1x) effectively inhibited growth of clostridia, regardless storage temperature, while nitrites only delayed the outgrowth of the surrogate ($\lambda=13.93$ days; $\mu_{max}=0.37$ d⁻¹, 25oC) compared to control ($\lambda=1.5$ days; $\mu_{max}=0.79$ d⁻¹, 25oC). While both antimicrobial agents had no significant effect on spoilage microflora (mainly barotolerant lactic acid bacteria), regardless of storage temperature, they may potentially result in distinct microbial profile as manifested by the acidification only of NA-containing samples at the onset of spoilage and additional rep-PCR analysis of spoilage isolates

CONCLUSIONS

Nitrites could successfully be substituted by natural antimicrobial agents, resulting in nitrite free products. However, extrapolation of the results in other deli meat products should co-evaluate the intrinsic characteristics of the product

P. 73.- APPLICATION OF PREDICTIVE MICROBIOLOGY MODELS ON GEOTRICHUM CANDIDUM GROWTH **Lubomír Valík, Martina Koňuchová, Anna Šípkov**

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Keywords:

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Geotrichum candidum plays an important role in the ripening of many soft and semi-hard cheeses and make a positive contribution to the development of taste and aroma. It is an important component of the microflora of soft cheeses such as semi-fresh ewes' milk cheese, including Slovakian Bryndza cheese. However, in fresh cheeses like cottage cheese and quark, *G. candidum*, like other microorganisms, is considered as contaminant flora.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

DMFit software (IFR, Norwich, United Kingdom, version 3.5) by Baranyi and Robert (1994) was used to fit the growth curves of *Geotrichum candidum*. 18 isolates and 6 collection strains were compared with respect to their radial growth parameters at 15 °C, and moreover, growth rates of three of them were secondary modelled by the Cardinal Temperature Model with Inflection point (CTMI; Rosso, 1995) as function of temperature and water activity (*aw*). Additionally, the individual cultivation of the strain and co-cultivations with dairy starter cultures in milk were compared to each other with using the same type model.

RESULTS

Our findings have not indicated considerable strain-dependent growth potential of this dairy fungus as has been evaluated based on the estimated values of lag-phase and exponential growth. In general, colony growth rate (*rcol*) and lag phase durations (*t_λ*) were normally distributed. The colony growth rate values ranged from 0.114 mm to 0.197 mm per hour with the average *rcol* = 0.152 ±0.021 mm·h⁻¹/3.65 ±0.50 mm·d⁻¹; coefficient of variation CV = 13.7 %). Estimated average lag time was 31.2 h with standard deviation of 10.1 h.

Modelling colony growth rates of *G. candidum* strains (*rcol*) by the CTMI model as function of temperature (T) and water activity (*aw*) provided cardinal values of the environmental factors (*rcol* opt, *T*min, *T*opt, *T*max, *aw* min, *aw* opt, *aw* max). The estimated data, e.g. *T*opt = 25.4 – 25.9 °C or 28 °C and *aw* min = 0,948 – 0,959, *aw* opt confirmed optimal temperature range and salt sensitivity of *Geotrichum candidum* in general. Despite salt sensitivity, the separate existence of both cardinal values of *aw* opt and *aw* max (lower than 1.0) were found for growth all of the strains under study.

CONCLUSIONS

Data and descriptive statistics provided an interesting biological insight into variability in the specific growth parameters, and the variability between different strains. Furthermore together with other relevant factors, these microbial responses can help to assess the *G. candidum* growth prediction in term of cheese quality control.

P. 74.- MODELLING THE GROWTH KINETICS OF SALMONELLA SEROVARS DURING THE FERMENTATION OF YOGURT

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Yogurt is a fermented dairy product obtained as a result of lactic acid fermentation by starter cultures, *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*. Due to its nutritional value and positive effect on health, it has an important role in human diet.

The objective of this study was to evaluate the behavior of *Salmonella Enteritidis* and *Salmonella Typhimurium*, the two most important serovars associated with salmonellosis cases, during the fermentation of yogurt.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The microorganisms were enumerated in milk inoculated with *Salmonella Enteritidis* and *Salmonella Typhimurium* at three inoculum levels (3, 5 and 7 log CFU/mL) throughout the yogurt fermentation process. DMFit software was used to fit the growth model by Baranyi and Robert (1994) to the obtained count data (IFR, Norwich, United Kingdom, Version 3.5).

RESULTS

The models fitted to growth data satisfactorily. The analysis of the model output showed that the initial inoculum level did not affect the growth for both pathogens; thus, the μ_{max} values (maximum specific growth rate) were not significantly different for all contamination levels, ranging from 0.26 to 0.38 for *S. Enteritidis* and from 0.50 to 0.56 log CFU/g/h for *S. Typhimurium* ($P > 0.05$). However, the μ_{max} values significantly differed between the two serovars (P

CONCLUSIONS

The present study showed that this pathogen could grow and survive the yogurt fermentation process even at a low contamination level. In addition, the models might be integrated into quantitative risk assessment studies, providing a valuable tool for risk managers.

P. 75.- FOOD SAFETY KNOWLEDGE AND HYGIENE PRACTICES OF PRODUCE HANDLERS AT THE MAJOR FRESH PRODUCE MARKET IN DOHA, QATAR

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Food handling is one of the most important stages where microbes can be distributed through the infected food handlers or by cross-contamination. The Fresh produce wholesale-market in Doha is one of the major markets from which most consumers obtain their produce. However, there is no information available on the food safety and handling practices standards applied in this market. This study was carried out to assess the food safety knowledge level, attitudes, and practices of the produce handlers working at the major produce market in Doha, Qatar.

About 120 produce handlers were surveyed using a questionnaire containing 21 questions to determine their food safety knowledge and attitudes between January-February 2016. At the time of survey application, hand swab samples were collected to determine their hands' hygiene levels using standard microbial tests. Pathogens detected on swab samples were identified using molecular techniques.

The survey analysis revealed that none of the handlers received any food safety training related to produce handling practices before starting to work in this market. About 82.5%, of the workers' age was below 50 yrs; around 57.5 % of them had middle-school level education. Also, 63.3% of the workers claimed to wash their hands 4-5 times per day. The microbial analysis of hand-swab samples indicated that there is a deficiency in workers' hygiene practices since their hand swabs contained various pathogens, such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Enterococcus faecium*. Based on our observation, it was determined that the accessibility to close-by handwashing facilities equipped with clean water and soap might be important factors contributing to the improper hand hygiene. Overall, these results show inadequate hygiene practices of produce handlers, highlighting the need to train them on food safety and hygiene practices and adopt better control measures at the produce market to improve sanitary conditions.

P. 76.- INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE AND UV-C DOSE ON THE INACTIVATION OF SALMONELLA IN SOYMILK BY UV-C TECHNOLOGY.

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVE

The growing interest for soymilk and soymilk-based beverages is associated to soy's high-quality proteins, essential fatty acids, bioactive compounds and absence of cholesterol, gluten or lactose. Heat treatment, which is currently applied for pasteurization of soymilk, may adversely affect its colour, flavour, nutrients and bioactive compounds. To preserve the organoleptic and nutritional quality of soymilk, the Ultraviolet technology (UV-C) is proposed as a non-thermal pasteurization technology. In order to optimize UV-C application to inactivate microorganisms in soymilk, the influence of the most relevant technological parameters (i.e. UV-C dose, temperature) should be clearly understood and evaluated.

The aim of this study was to evaluate and model the influence of temperature and UV-C dose on the inactivation of *Salmonella* in soymilk to optimize UV-C technology application in food industries.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

UV-C inactivation studies were carried out by placing petri dishes containing 30 mL of inoculated samples (nearly 6 log cfu/mL of *Salmonella* Enteritidis) and magnetic spin bars on the top of a magnetic stirrer, located inside of a stainless-steel UV-C chamber. The chamber was equipped with a 9 W lamp that predominantly emits at 253.7 nm. The samples were exposed to different doses of radiation (0-10 mJ/cm²) at different temperatures (4-30 °C). The primary non-linear Weibull model was fitted to inactivation data (*N* versus *UV-C dose*). A secondary model relating the Weibull model scale parameter (δ) with temperature was also developed.

RESULTS

Salmonella inactivation levels increased with the increase in UV-C dose and by increasing the temperature from 4 to 18 °C, with maximum reductions ($\log N/N_0$) varying between -1.10 and -5.63 log cfu/mL. Although the increase in temperature from 18 to 30 °C did not influence inactivation levels ($P > 0.05$), at these temperatures more than 5 log-reductions were achieved by applying a UV-C dose of 10 mJ/cm², in agreement with the criteria of FDA for non-thermal pasteurization techniques. The Weibull shape parameters (ρ) were rather homogeneous at all temperatures tested (0.73 ± 0.17), and the Weibull models were re-fitted fixing ρ parameter to its mean value, to obtain δ estimates. A linear relationship was found between $\log \delta$ values and temperature, with δ varying from 8.61 to 0.90 (mJ/cm²)⁻¹ at 4 and 18 °C, respectively. The Z_{Temp} was estimated to be 14.5 °C. No significant differences were found between the δ values at temperatures ranging from 18 to 30 °C (0.93 ± 0.03 (mJ/cm²)⁻¹). Combining primary and secondary models it was possible to estimate the *Salmonella* inactivation values at various UV-C doses and temperatures.

CONCLUSION

The increase in temperatures and in UV-C doses potentiated the inactivation of *Salmonella* in soymilk by UV-C at the tested conditions. The predictive models developed in this study allowed to estimate inactivation kinetic parameters, thus providing baseline information for future establishment of UV-C process schedules for soymilk pasteurization.

P. 77.- MINIMUM EFFECTIVE DOSES OF ClO₂ FOR IRRIGATION WATER: MODELLING OF E. COLI INACTIVATION AND RESIDUAL ClO₂ CONCENTRATIONS.

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVE

Irrigation water can provoke fresh produce contamination with foodborne pathogens. Water disinfection treatments can help to improve the microbiological safety of the water used for irrigation. The minimum effective doses of disinfectant able to reach the desired microbiological goals should be established. The present study was dedicated to develop mathematical models for the determination of *E. coli* inactivation and residual concentrations of chlorine dioxide (ClO₂) in irrigation water treated with ClO₂. These models could help growers to select the suitable chlorine dioxide doses in function of the target residual ClO₂ and of the microbiological goal in irrigation water from different sources

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Different surface irrigation water types were treated with a range of ClO₂ concentrations (0.1-2.5 mg/L) at 21±2 °C for a contact time of 0.5-5 minutes. *Escherichia coli* concentration and the residual ClO₂ were assessed. Several physicochemical characteristics were analysed in irrigation water. Based on the obtained data, a model for ClO₂ decay and a model for *E. coli* inactivation were developed by linear regression. The initial set of variables used to explain ClO₂ decay included the linear, quadratic and interaction terms of physicochemical parameters and the initial concentration of ClO₂. The initial set of variables used to explain the inactivation included the linear, quadratic and interaction terms of the initial *E. coli* concentration, physicochemical parameters, and the initial concentration of ClO₂. A subset of data not used for model development was used for validation.

RESULTS

ClO₂ and *E. coli* concentration did not change significantly after 1 min contact time, thus only the data obtained after 1 min were used for model development. Absorbance of irrigation water at 254 nm (UV254) showed the strongest relationship with ClO₂ demand of water. The ClO₂ decay model (adjusted R²=0.93) had the initial ClO₂ concentration and the UV254 as explanatory variables, while the *E. coli* inactivation model (adjusted R²=0.77) had the initial ClO₂ concentration, the initial *E. coli* concentration, and the UV254 as explanatory variables. Validation had an adjusted R² value of 0.94 and 0.55 for ClO₂ decay and *E. coli* inactivation, respectively.

CONCLUSION

The developed ClO₂ decay model could be used for the prediction of ClO₂ decay in the bulk liquid phase of an irrigation network. However, total ClO₂ decay depends also on the reaction with pipe walls, biofilms and deposits that together with the decay in the bulk should be used to properly predict global ClO₂ decay. The *E. coli* inactivation model should be improved and validated in field conditions before it can be applied by growers.

P. 78.- STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT FACTORS RELATED WITH THE MICROBIOLOGICAL QUALITY OF RAW MILK.

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVE

The raw milk chain production is made up of three stages: cows milking and cooling on tanks, collection by trucks, reception of trucks by the industry. Time elapsed from milking at farms to industry depends of the location and number of farms to be collected. In addition, several factors (human, manufacturing practices on farm and trucks, facilities conditions...) can contribute to increase microbial populations in raw milk during these stages.

The objective of this study was to analyse the influence of the collection period at farms (24h vs 48h) and milking time (morning and afternoon) on the total aerobic mesophilic (AEM) and psychrotrophic bacterial (PSI) counts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 778 milk samples were collected from 29 trucks and 232 farms. The first factor analysed was the milking time, consisting of the morning milking (time 1, 6:00-9:00h) and the afternoon milking (time 2, 17:00-20:00). The second factor was the frequency of milk collection: milk collection every 48 h (C48) with 391 samples, and every 24 h (C24) with 383 samples.

AEM counts were determined by flow cytometry using BactoScan™ FC+ (Foss, Denmark) and PSI by culture in Plate Count Agar (PCA, Oxoid, Spain). A multivariate statistical analysis was performed with the obtained counts using SPSS 10.0 version (Chicago, Illinois, USA).

RESULTS

Results obtained showed that C24 led to a concentration reduction of 32 and 18 % for AEM and PSI in raw milk, respectively, with respect to those obtained with C48. Milking during morning showed a reduction of 4% for AEM and 5% for PSI counts compared to milking performed during afternoon ($P < 0.05$). Milk collection every 24 h would allow for a reduction of the heat treatment temperature of 4° C, resulting in energy savings of 14% with respect to the collection every 48 h.

CONCLUSION

Results obtained showed that C24 and morning milking improved milk quality and safety. Likewise, results highlight the importance of establishing suitable hygiene measures to improve energy efficiency in heat-treating operations in the dairy industry.

P. 79.- MODELLING THE INTERACTION OF GROWTH OF A BACTERIOCINOGENIC *LACTOBACILLUS SAKEI* AND *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN COOKED HAM

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Cooked ham can be contaminated with *L. monocytogenes* during slicing and packaging operations. The potential use of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) as antilisterial bioprotective cultures has been suggested to improve the safety of RTE cooked meat products. The objective of the present study was to evaluate and model the interaction between *Lactobacillus sakei* CTC494, a sakacin K producer strain, and *L. monocytogenes* CTC1034 in vacuum packaged sliced cooked ham, at different initial concentrations and storage temperatures.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Cooked ham was elaborated *ad hoc* (pH=6.1, $a_w=0.978$), aseptically sliced and inoculated with *L. sakei* CTC494 and *L. monocytogenes* CTC1034. Inoculum level was $ca.10^2$ CFU/g in mono-culture. For the experiments in co-culture, three initial concentrations ($ca.10^2$, 10^4 and 10^6 CFU/g) of *L. sakei* were combined with $ca.10^2$ CFU/g of *L. monocytogenes*. Samples were individually vacuum packaged and stored at constant temperature: 2, 5, 10 and 15 °C. Baranyi and Logistic primary models were used to determine the kinetic parameters, Ratkowsky model was used for the secondary modelling, while Jameson and Lotka Volterra models were applied to model the interaction between the two species.

RESULTS

Both primary models showed a good fit to the data obtained in co-culture ($R^2=0.88-0.99$). In mono-culture *L. monocytogenes* grew at all temperatures. In co-culture at 2 °C at initial levels of 10^4 and 10^6 CFU/g *L. sakei* CTC494 inhibited the growth of *L. monocytogenes*. At higher temperatures the pathogen grew although the maximum population density was much lower than the observed in mono-culture. The *in silico* simulation of the interaction between the two species showed that the most accurate results were obtained with the Jameson model modified to include a critical concentration parameter and the Lotka Volterra model, including two interaction parameters describing the inhibitory effect of *L. sakei* on *L. monocytogenes* and vice versa.

CONCLUSION

L. sakei CTC494 has a temperature dependent bioprotective effect on *L. monocytogenes* CTC1034, mainly related with the reduction of the maximum population density. Developed mathematical models successfully described the interactions between the two species and could be used by the food industry to evaluate the effectiveness of CTC494 in different scenarios and its feasibility as a control measure.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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SESSION 7: Systems biology and whole-cell modelling.

P. 80.- THE SYNERGISTIC EFFECT OF SOME FLAVONOIDS ON MULTI-RESISTANT STRAINS (BLSE).

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Keywords: Flavonoids and Polyphenols, Antibiotics, Synergy, Antibacterial activity

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

In this study, antibacterial and synergistic effects were evaluated for two multi-resistant strains isolated in the hospital of Ain el Kebira SETIF.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The antimicrobial susceptibility of clinical E. coli 526 and Enterobacter527 strains showed that they are resistant to Penicillin, Cephalotin and Amoxicillin + Clavulanic acid. However, they remain susceptible to Ampicillin, Colistin and Imipenem. The antibacterial effect of flavonoids was evaluated by the diffusion method on agar

RESULTS

For E. coli 526, the Ellagic acid, Propyl gallate and Methyl gallate have an important antibacterial effect, the three molecules induces inhibition areas of a diameter which varies between (14 -17 mm). For the other flavonoids (Morine, Naringenin, Trans-cinamique acid), they have no effect. For Enterobacter 527, all the flavonoids have no effect on this strain. For the synergistic effect between flavonoids, the combinations (Methyl gallate + Trans-cinamic acid, Methyl gallate+ Propyl gallate, Methyl gallate+ Morine) are most active.

The antibacterial effects of extracts and antibiotic combinations was tested. The results showed that all the flavonoids in combination with Ampicillin were less effective and have become antagonists.

CONCLUSIONS

It is possible that the antibiotic has canceled the effect of the extract or otherwise.

P. 81.- USE OF PREDICTIVE TOOLS TO RANK THE SAFETY OF RAW MILK CHEESES PROCESSES VS VEROCYTOTOXIC *ESCHERICHIA COLI*.

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Keywords: VTEC raw-milk cheese predictive model validation

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Verocytotoxin-(VT) producing *Escherichia coli* (EC) is a foodborne pathogen that can cause severe illness and death. Cattle is a natural reservoir of VTEC, consequently they may be isolated from raw cow milk and non-pasteurized dairy products, typically produced in many Italian regions. During the cheese making, the temperature is highly the most important control variable affecting the kinetics of the micro-organisms present in the milk and possibly surviving the process.

The aims of the study were i) validate a predictive model available in literature with VTEC data obtained in broth at dynamic conditions (temperature and pH) that mimic the conditions of different cheese making processes and ii) rank the cheese processes regarding the probability to find VTEC at the beginning of seasoning

MATERIAL AND METHODS

VTEC ATCC 35150 data was obtained in Brain Heart Infusion broth. A bio-reactor was used in this study and programmed with 8 temperature/pH dynamic profiles in growth region (15-20-25-30°C) and 16 profiles in survival region (55-52-50-48°C), pH (5.2, 6.5). The pathogen concentration was measured by plate count (ISO 4833-2:2013). The predictive model "*E. coli* safe ferment" proposed by Quinto et al. (2014) was validated by observed data obtained in this study. The accuracy factor (*Af*) and Bias (*B*) were calculated according to Baranyi et al. (1999).

Cheese making processes of Parmigiano Reggiano (PR), Grana Padano (Gp), Silter (S), Formai de Mut (FM), Formaggella della Valsassina (FV), Formaggella Luinese (FL) were taken from literature

RESULTS

In favorable condition, VTEC initial inoculum was 2.45 +/- 0.1 log CFU/ml, the observed log increase was 5.02 +/- 0.63 log CFU/ml (ranging from 2.5 log CFU/ml to 6.03 log CFU/ml). In hostile environment, VTEC initial inoculum was 5.65 +/- 0.67 log CFU/ml, the observed log reduction was 2.92 +/- 1.1 log CFU/ml (ranging from 5.42 to 1.19 log CFU/ml).

232 observed data, log VTEC CFU/ml, were compared with predicted values, *Af* and *B* between data were 1.36 and 0.86 respectively. During the cheese making, the model predict for PR and GP cheeses 4.1 log CFU/g and 3.02 log CFU/g VTEC reduction respectively; in cheeses S and FM the concentration remains almost constant, with a 1.19 and 0.89 log CFU/g increase, while in cheeses FV and FL the VTEC concentration increases of 2.5 and 3.26 log CFU/g

CONCLUSIONS

This study can be used to help the risk assessors, which have to judge the safety of the process of cheeses made by raw milk

SESSION 8: Data Bases, software and decision support tools

P. 82.- MODEL ELEMENTS AS COMPONENTS OF A FOOD-SAFETY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM UNDER DYNAMIC GROWTH/DEATH GENERATING CONDITIONS

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Keywords: time-dependent probability parameter; non-thermal inactivation; dynamic conditions

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Predictive food microbiology information needs, for increasing their manageability, to be implemented in decision-supporting tools, which can be practically used by a range of stakeholders to improve food safety.

To be more effective in managing food safety, especially under dynamic growth/inactivation processing conditions, a combination of growth and devitalization models could be advantageous. The aim of this research was to develop a set of elements, including a time-dependent probability parameter (PΔLog) for dynamically-changing growth/death conditions, to be included in a decision tool.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The effect of temperature, pH, aw, liquid smoke and lactic acid on *Listeria monocytogenes* inactivation was experimentally evaluated. The dependence of the probability of devitalization was ascertained and the inactivation rate (KD) was determined by building a regression on the pathogen viability data (Log CFU/ml) versus time, relying on the independent action of factors, as in the gamma approach.

RESULTS

Our decision support approach is based on the gamma concept and contains a set of elements, which pivot around the growth/inactivation partitioning parameter (P) in its dynamic version (Polese et al., 2011, 2017). The concept underlying the already validated time-dependent probability parameter (Pt) for growth (Polese et al., 2017) was extended to the devitalization region, yielding a new element, i.e. PΔLog, expressed as the probability to achieve definite log increase/decrease within a specified time of storage. With the purpose of realistically predicting PΔLog, the variability of growth and death observations was taken into account (Aryani et al., 2016). Considering datasets of *L. monocytogenes* behaviours collected from published data (Lindqvist & Lindblad, 2009), the performance of KD was found to be satisfactory. The PΔLog option was successfully validated on ComBase data from experiments with food products characterized by different combinations of controlling factors.

CONCLUSIONS

One of the main drawbacks of using the commonly available predictive software tools is the fact that in many products with a long shelf-life and dynamic internal environment, prediction can result in both growth and inactivation (Iannetti et al., 2017). Providing a decision support approach with model elements that allow both the probability and quantification of the pathogen increase/decrease for a given formulation or storage condition, could be a step in the right direction to overcome these problems.

P. 83.- LISTWARE PROJECT; DEVELOPING A NEW LISTERIA ASSESSMENT TOOL.

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1 Animalia Norwegian Meat & Poultry Research Centre

Keywords: Listeria software shelf-life

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Listeria is a challenge in ready-to-eat foods (RTE). The risk management involve large expenses and time spent for the food business operators (FBO). It is important for the food industry to reduce disease cases of listeriosis. The challenge arises when the industry simultaneously is urged by authorities to reduce food waste, and by retailers to prolong shelf life. Recalls and withdrawals can be detrimental to reputation and business.

FBOs are responsible for food safety according to the EU regulations. FBOs must document compliance with the microbiological criteria throughout the shelf-life of the product. The options for FBOs are either performing expensive laboratory challenge tests or apply predictive modelling.

There are several software tools on the market. However, the application of them in FBOs are limited. This project was initiated by the FBOs, as they needed better tools in their daily risk managements. In this way, the project is closely connected to its future software users, and the project work is always corrected by the FBOs practical needs for user-friendly and reliable software.

The objective of the ListWare project is to develop a user-friendly risk management software for reliable assessments of Listeria safety and shelf life in RTE meat products

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The project period is 2016-2019. In addition to researchers from Norwegian and European institutes and universities, five Norwegian FBOs are participating.

Quality assured data from challenge tests with product characteristics is collected from the industry and the literature. A major part of the work is identifying gaps in data and find which models give the best prediction by using meta-analyses of available data, existing software tools and predictive models.

New challenge tests and durability studies will be performed. The risk categorization of products will be improved according to predictive models results. A web based application will be developed to create a useful tool for product development, assessments of consequences of unintended variation, decision making, and benchmarking of products. A function for anonymization and quality assurance of data will be developed.

RESULTS

A database is established, and the data collected from Norwegian studies show that there are several gaps in information of criteria for products and processes in earlier studies. Apparently similar products produce results with large variations. It is important to find the criteria that vary and influence the shelf lives in each study. So far, only Norwegian data are collected. However, Listware is interested in cooperation with other companies with similar software and databases. There is an idea to establish a European "library".

CONCLUSIONS

The ListWare software will imply saving of time and costs for the food industry. To secure the best use of the tool, ListWare will also include support and consultancy service for the users.

P. 84.- META-ANALYSIS OF THE INCIDENCE OF FOODBORNE PATHOGENS IN VEGETABLES FROM RETAIL ESTABLISHMENTS IN EUROPE.

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Keywords: *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, packed, unpacked

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Over the last years, concerns regarding the effect of a healthy diet on one's quality of life have promoted the increase of vegetable consumption. However, these products can be contaminated by pathogens such as *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella* spp. and *Listeria monocytogenes*. Thus, this work aims to summarise the incidence of foodborne pathogens in vegetables sold at European retail stores.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Literature search was conducted to identify suitable scientific articles indexed since 2000 from Europe, using terms for combinations of the pathogen and the produce under study. Following study quality checking, forty-one primary studies remained, from which 284 observations of incidence (s positive samples/n total samples) of foodborne pathogens were extracted. Moderators such as country, vegetable class and packed/unpacked condition were codified. Separate multilevel meta-analysis studies were conducted: (i) on the incidence of pathogens in packed and unpacked vegetables; (ii) on the incidence of pathogens across four different vegetable categories; and (iii) on the incidence of pathogens in four specific packed and unpacked vegetable categories.

RESULTS

Results showed that the global mean incidence of pathogens in either packed or unpacked vegetables was 2.24% (95% CI: 1.81-2.75%), with unpacked vegetables having higher prevalence of pathogens (2.05%; 95% CI: 1.26-3.33%) than packed ones (1.67%; 95% CI: 0.97-2.86%). Shiga-toxin *E. coli* was the pathogen with the highest mean incidence in packed vegetables (2.48%; 95% CI: 1.50-4.10%) while *L. monocytogenes* had the top occurrence in unpacked vegetables (4.41%; 95% CI: 1.79-10.47%). Among salads, spices and herbs, sprouts and undifferentiated vegetables, sprouts were the most frequently contaminated by either *E. coli*, *L. monocytogenes* or *Salmonella* spp. (3.55%; 95% CI: 2.10-5.95%) while salads were the least contaminated (1.15%; 95% CI: 0.76-1.73%). Overall, *E. coli* was the main pathogen in the four categories of vegetables, packaged or not (3.41%; 95% CI: 2.42-4.79%) with *Salmonella* spp. being the pathogen of lower incidence (1.13%; 95% CI: 0.82-1.56%). Spain and the island of Ireland had the highest overall frequencies of contamination by the pathogens in the stated vegetable categories (6.03%; 95% CI: 3.83-9.36% and 5.65%; 95% CI: 3.72-8.50%, respectively), while Belgium and Great Britain presented the lowest levels (1.00%; 95% CI: 0.44-2.24% and 0.24%; 95% CI: 0.14-0.40%, respectively). There was no indication of relevant publication bias.

CONCLUSIONS

Since minimal processing technologies can reduce the levels of pathogens in packed vegetables, further research should be focused on the mitigation of *E. coli* and *L. monocytogenes* in such products. As control of pathogens in unpacked vegetables sold at retail may not be as easy, consumers must be further educated on ensuring proper washing and/or cooking of vegetables prior to consumption.

P. 85.- FSK-LAB - AN OPEN SOURCE FOOD SAFETY MODEL INTEGRATION TOOL.

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Keywords: mra knime fsk-ml modeling data-standards

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

In contrast to Systems Biology there is a large legacy of script-based models in the Microbial Risk Assessment (MRA) domain. As a result most MRA models are currently not released in a harmonized software independent representation. FSK-Lab aims at providing a solution for the MRA community that facilitate the free exchange of MRA models and modules thereof to allow future exchange, combination and distribution via online MRA model repositories. Among others features FSK-Lab supports the Food Safety Knowledge Markup Language (FSK-ML) that defines a framework for:

1. Encoding of model metadata using eXtensible Markup Language (XML)
2. Representation of models encoded in a software-independent format (e.g. PMF-ML or SBML) as well as in a scripting language (e.g. R, Perl, Python or MATLAB).
3. Describing experimental data as well as configurations of model-based simulations.
4. Exchanging of sets of heterogeneous files.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

To achieve a wide adoption of the FSK-ML it is necessary to develop supporting software resources, that e.g. simplify the creation, export and import of files complying to FSK-ML. Here we present a first software tool also serving as a reference implementation of FSK-ML. FSK-Lab has been built on top of the open source Konstanz Information Miner (KNIME) data analytics platform (www.knime.org). The KNIME graphical user interface (GUI) allows the creation of data processing workflows from modular building blocks (so called nodes). In addition, KNIME already integrates several scripting languages like R, Python and MATLAB. This means that scripts written in these languages may be executed within KNIME using existing KNIME nodes. The FSK-Lab tool exploits this feature.

RESULTS

The FSK reference implementation, named FSK-Lab, is an open source tool, implemented through a number of KNIME extension nodes. Relevant software libraries developed to handle the FSK-ML standard created in FSK-Lab are made available as GPLv3 open source software libraries to facilitate fast adoption of FSK-ML by other software developers.

CONCLUSIONS

The FSK framework provides the first set of rules and technical standards for harmonized annotations and representations of MRA models and simulations. Since such technical standards have been successfully applied in the Systems Biology domain the FSK framework likewise can lead the way towards the establishment of curated, community-driven MRA model repositories. Future work will focus on providing FSK support for additional software tools currently applied within the MRA domain.

P. 86.- OPENFOOD: DEVELOPMENT OF A FOOD MATRIX-RELATED ONTOLOGY FOR APPLICATION IN PREDICTIVE MICROBIOLOGY SOFTWARE

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INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVE

In the last decades, Predictive microbiology has undergone an important development due to improvements in computers and software engineering. Currently, the development of prediction software has enabled to transfer the knowledge on predictive microbiology to end-users in an easy fashion.

In predictive microbiology, food matrix is a key component in the development and application of the predictive models. The selection of the food matrix in the prediction software should consider the taxonomic classification, compositional structure and the manufacturing conditions.

The objective of this project was to develop a food matrix-related ontology to be used as a standard for predictive microbiology software.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Food matrix and culture medium lists were extracted from existing predictive microbiology data-bases (Microhibro, PMM Lab, ComBase). Then, selected items were structured using as basis the FoodEx hierarchical structure. The food matrix references, properties and definitions were based on suitable ontologies available in the libraries from the Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies (BioPortal, <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>), which is an on-line repository curated by the National Center of Biomedical Ontologies (NCBO): National Cancer Institute, Grow Medium Ontology, and SNOMED Clinical Term. The ontology was built with the Protégé software and later uploaded in the BioPortal website.

RESULTS

At the very top level, the developed ontology classified matrices into two main categories: culture medium-based matrices and food matrices. The core structure for the food matrices followed a taxonomical structure combined with a classification based on the industrial process, both adapted from the standard FoodEx. In the first level, food matrices were classified by considering a general taxonomical basis (e.g. plant and animal species), while at second and third levels, items were defined from both an industrial and taxonomical point of view as shown in the example below. Specific properties were also added to each food or culture medium item, including relevant aspects related to physicochemical characteristics (pH, water activity, etc.), formulation of preservatives and packaging type.

Example: Smoked Salmon ==> Food -> Fish -> Smoked fish -> Smoked salmon

 Fresh Salmon ==> Food -> Fish -> Fresh fish -> Fresh salmon

The Ontology developed in this project, called **OpenFood**, and available at BioPortal website was connected, in real time, to the predictive microbiology and quantitative risk assessment software, Microhibro (www.microhibro.com) with the application of APIs and NCBO widgets provided by BioPortal. This system enabled Microhibro to set a controlled vocabulary, based on the ontology **OpenFood**, so to define the field "Food Matrix" within the data-base of predictive microbiology models.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of standards for food matrix classifications can help users to better select and apply predictive models in different contexts and scenarios. The ontology proposed in this work, **OpenFood**, is an attempt to unify food terminology based on a classification driven by the predictive microbiology model application. As a proof of concept, Microhibro has been successfully updated to incorporate **OpenFood** into the data-base of predictive

microbiology models. This work can be considered as a first step toward the standardization in Predictive Microbiology, which has as paramount aim to facilitate an effective mathematical model exchange among predictive microbiology practitioners and developers (i.e. import/export systems in predictive software).

SESSION 9: Modelling approaches using metagenomics data

P. 87.- PREDICTION OF CHEESE DRY MATTER DURING CURD TREATMENT.

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Keywords: Generalized linear regression, Multimodel inference, Syneresis, Cheese production, Dry matter

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

During curd treatment, cheese curd grains show syneresis in a process that is crucial for the cheese making process, as the degree of syneresis determines the final cheese dry matter. This process is, however, affected by a number of environmental factors. In order to predict cheese dry matter during curd treatment for a set of environmental conditions, a generalized linear regression model was developed, varying seven numerical and two categorical predictors. Therefore, the proposed model facilitates the prediction of the final cheese dry matter for a large number of cheese types.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

To compare possible candidate models, we chose an approach based on information theory. Model selection was thus performed by use of Akaike's information criterion (with a correction for finite sample sizes, i.e. AICC), balancing predictive quality with model complexity.

The data consisted of about 1000 measurements of cheese dry matter, each corresponding to a specific set of predictor values. As most experiments have been repeated at least three times, this corresponds to about 300 unique sets. The numerical predictor variables were time, pH, temperature, curd grain size, fat content, homogenisation pressure and concentration factor, while the categorical predictor variables were acidulant and whether or not the curd was washed.

To determine appropriate regression terms, we used a two-step approach. In a first step, possible functional forms of the dependency of the response variable on each explanatory variable were examined and compared. This led to a simple linear regression model that yielded one or more appropriate terms for each explanatory variable. In a second step, these terms were consolidated to the full model, and terms corresponding to interactions between them were added. Visual inspection of the dependency of the response variable on the different explanatory variables for different values of the other explanatory variables was utilised to determine the interaction terms that were added to the full model.

As soon as a candidate set of terms and interaction terms had been found, we utilised the resulting full model as a base for selecting a candidate set of parsimonious sub-models of the full model. Model selection from the full model was done exhaustively, i.e. all sub-models of the initial model were considered, and their respective AICC-values were calculated. This was performed with the R package "MuMIn" for multimodel inference. Models with the lowest AICC-values were considered as candidate models. Instead of selecting the "best" model (i.e. the model with the lowest AICC) from this set, the entire set of candidate models was used for inference (therefore "multimodel inference") by calculating the Akaike weights of these candidate models, and using them to weight the predictions obtained by the candidate models. This procedure results in a more robust estimation, particularly in case of model selection uncertainty.

RESULTS

Our results show that the prediction of cheese dry matter during curd treatment with the suggested generalized linear regression model can be performed precisely. For that reason, the regression model is a useful tool for

cheese manufacturer to control variations in curd dry matter for cheese types whose process parameters fall within the range of the predictors.

CONCLUSIONS

The exhaustive approach is superior to the prevalent step-wise approach, which drops terms one at a time, as only the former is certain to arrive at the optimal model, that is, a model with the lowest AICC for a specified maximum number of terms. The developed model enables cheese manufacturer to more efficient processing and allows for an improved scope for product innovation and for the creation of new products with reduced effort.

P. 88.- MODELLING S. TYPHIMURIUM INACTIVATION UNDER A NATURAL ANTIMICROBIAL AND HHP EFFECT.

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Keywords: Predictive Modelling, Typhimurium, HHP, Natural Antimicrobials

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Nowadays, new non-thermal technologies have been developed to inactivate foodborne pathogens. Among them, High Hydrostatic Pressure (HHP) is the most used technology in food industry (Herrero and Romero, 2006). The application of sublethal HHP treatments combined with natural antimicrobials to find a synergistic antimicrobial effect is part of the called "Hurdle technology" (Leistner, 2000). The aim of this study is to evaluate the inactivation rate of *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhimurium (*S. Typhimurium*) under the effect of a natural antimicrobial extract from mandarin by-product combined with a sublethal HHP treatment

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Weibull distribution function was used to modelling *S. Typhimurium* inactivation when it was treated with a sublethal HHP treatment (200 MPa – 2 min), a mandarin by-product extract and the combination of both at 10 and 37 °C

RESULTS

The results obtained indicated that mandarin by-product extract exerted a relevant antimicrobial effect against *S. Typhimurium* at both tested temperatures (10 and 37 °C). Additionally, the application of sublethal HHP treatment did not caused death and only produced one log cycle of cellular damage in *S. Typhimurium* population. However, when both antimicrobial treatments were applied together, there was a synergistic antimicrobial effect between mandarin by-product extract and HHP sublethal treatment producing an significant increase of the inactivation rate of *S. Typhimurium*. Moreover, the results showed the effect of storage temperature on microbial inactivation. *S. Typhimurium* inactivation rate was higher at 37 °C (optimal growth temperature) than at 10 °C (stressful temperature), in all cases.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded that mandarin by-product extract could be used as a natural antimicrobial in fruit beverages that could be treated by HHP and stored at refrigeration temperatures as an additional measure to maintain the food safety in possible cold chain break situations

P. 89.- MODELING COMPETITION IN CO-CULTURES OF A *SACCHAROMYCES NON-CEREVISIAE* SPECIES AND *S. CEREVISIAE* IN WINE FERMENTATION.

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Keywords: wine fermentation, non-conventional *Saccharomyces* species, modeling growth and competition

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Wineries face unprecedented challenges due to new market demands and climate change effects on wine quality. Consumers demand products with lower alcohol content and fruitier aromas; while climate change influences grape must characteristics (acidity, content in sugars or tannins, etc.), impacting the quality of the final product.

New yeast starters formed by non-conventional *Saccharomyces* species, in coculture with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* - the primary responsible for wine fermentation- can help to deal with some of these challenges. Non-conventional *Saccharomyces* species, such as *S. kudriavzevii*, may exhibit good fermentative capabilities at low temperatures, producing wines with lower alcohol and higher glycerol amounts.

The present work proposes a model based approach to evaluate the potential of the combination of *S. cerevisiae* T73 and *S. kudriavzevii* CR85 during fermentation at different temperatures.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Experimental methods. Experiments were performed at several temperatures for the individual yeasts and in co-culture. Initial inoculum was modified in co-cultures to evaluate the effect of the relative amount of the different species. Substrates (yeast assimilable nitrogen in the synthetic must, glucose and fructose) were not growth limiting. The microbial load was measured at a minimum of 5 sampling times during fermentation. Three replicates were performed for each experiment to assess experimental variability.

Theoretical methods. We identified model parameters through multi-experiment data fitting using the AMIGO2 toolbox. We fitted the model using the log-likelihood approach to take into account experimental variability and global optimization methods to avoid sub-optimal fits. We tested the model predictive capabilities by comparing model predictions under untested experimental conditions with a new set of data.

RESULTS

The model combines a modified Baranyi-Roberts primary model with a secondary model which takes into account the role of the temperature. The model includes biotic competition using the competitive Lotka-Volterra equations. Final results show that the model can predict the system behavior with reasonable accuracy.

CONCLUSIONS

The model provides quantitative information on the relevance of biotic competition, showing that T73 is less sensitive to the presence of *S. kudriavzevii* CR85 at higher temperatures whereas CR85 becomes more competitive at lower temperatures. The temperature and the initial relative amount of the different species have a definite effect on the final number of cells in the fermentation. The model allows for coculture process design. Currently, we are asking the model if there are any conditions for which T73 and CR85 may cooperate instead of competing.

P. 90.- MODELLING AND STUDY OF DRYING VARIABLES IN THE DRYING OF GRAPE WITHOUT PEDICEL.

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Keywords: Grape; without pedicel; drying; mathematical models

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Drying can be considered industrially like a conservation method of fruit and vegetable, sure and environmentally friendly, because it does not use preservative chemistry. Drying decrease the moisture content and the water activity of food, preventing the growth and reproductions of microorganisms. Sun-drying is the most traditional and inexpensive method, but it has disadvantages like time, insect attack, intense solar radiation, occasional rain, fungi-producing toxins. For this reasons, artificial drying systems have been developed to control the temperature, relative humidity, and air flow.

This study aims to explain the changes in drying time, once the grape pedicel is take off, to fit the experimental data to four thin-layer drying models, and to determine the effective moisture diffusivity and the activation energy of grape

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Drying process. Grapes *Vitis vinifera* L. cv Tempranillo without pedicel were dried in a chamber at constant temperature at 30, 40 and 50 °C and with an initial relative humidity of 20%. The weight lost was measured during the drying process.

Mathematical models. The moisture ratio was calculated using the moisture content at each point of drying, and the drying curves were performed from the moisture ratio versus drying time. Determination of the effective moisture diffusivity and activation energy. The effective moisture diffusivity was determined using the solution of Fick's second law in spherical coordinates with the accepting of constant moisture diffusivity and temperature. For calculating the activation energy, the Arrhenius equation was used with some modification.

Statistical analysis. This analysis was carried out using Statgraphics Centurion XVI program

RESULTS

The moisture content decreased exponentially with the drying time. Besides, the temperature had a significant effect on the moisture content change. When this increased, the drying time decreased. The drying data were fitted to four thin-layer drying models (Newton, Henderson and Pabis, two term and approximation of diffusion models). Where, two term model was the better model for describing the characteristics of grape without pedicel drying at temperatures of 30 and 40 °C. However, the values obtained from approximation of diffusion model were more right for the temperature of 50 °C.

The calculation of the effective moisture diffusivity demonstrated that it carried up with increasing temperature

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this work demonstrated that the increasing temperature decreased the drying time and increased the effective moisture diffusivity. Besides, a minor energy of activation was obtained with grapes without pedicel dried in chamber, that with other method or pre-treatments of dried seen in the bibliography.

SESSION 10: Predictive Mycology

P. 91.- MODELLING THE EFFECTS OF PH AND TEMPERATURE ON THE MYCOTOXIN PRODUCTION OF ALTERNARIA ALTERNATA IN A TOMATO-BASED MEDIUM.

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Keywords: Alternaria mycotoxin production

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Alternaria species are ubiquitous and includes both pathogens and saprophytes that may damage crops and cause postharvest decay. Alternaria spp. are able to grow at low temperature and may responsible for spoilage during refrigerated transport and storage. Certain species are also capable of producing mycotoxins which can contaminate plant products. Due to their thin skin, tomatoes are particularly at risk of being infected by Alternaria, and rapid growth may occur in soft tissues, causing the well-known black mold. In that context, predictive models of mycotoxin synthesis may be helpful in determining the levels of these mycotoxins for conditions supporting growth of Alternaria spp. The objective of this study was to evaluate the effects of temperature and pH on the toxin production of an A. alternata strain in a tomato-based medium

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A full factorial design of six pH levels (ranging from 2 to 7) and 11 incubation temperatures (ranging from 3.2 to 37°C) was undertaken. Tomato-based agar plates at aw 0.99 were centrally inoculated with a standardized inoculum of 40 spores/5µL. Each experimental condition was tested in triplicate. For each of the 35 combinations supporting fungal development, mycotoxin accumulation was measured. Measurements of TeA, AOH and AME concentrations were performed on plates fully covered by the fungus, using HPLC. Quantification was performed by measuring peak areas at toxins retention time and comparing them with the relevant calibration curves. The experimental observations suggest that increasing pH induces a linear increase in the square root of mycotoxin synthesis, followed by a logistic decrease. The equation used to describe this relationship is based on the model of Bréand et al. (1997) and is defined by the following parameters: pHminTOX (minimum pH for toxin production), pHoptTOX (optimum pH for toxin production), TQoptTOX (toxin quantity at pHoptTOX) and TQminTOX (the toxin quantity at high pH values). Secondary models were developed to describe the relationship between temperature and the parameters (pHminTOX, pHoptTOX and TQoptTOX) while TQminTOX was assumed to be independent of temperature

RESULTS

TeA has been described as the major mycotoxin produced by Alternaria spp. on tomatoes. Perhaps not surprisingly, only TeA could be measured in this work while AOH and AME have not been detected. TeA measurements show an important contribution of acidic pH to mycotoxin synthesis, in particular near pH 4. At similar pH levels, incubation at low temperatures (from 6.5°C to 12°C) resulted in higher TeA production than at temperatures above 20°C. The developed model for TeA synthesis describes accurately the experimental data (R²=0.98)

CONCLUSIONS

The model for toxin production can be used together with a model of fungal growth to highlight at-risk storage conditions for which mycotoxin production is at its highest although fungal growth is rather small.

P. 92.- PREDICTING BYSSOCHLAMYS FULVA ASCOSPORES BEHAVIOR BASED ON CONIDIA DATA.

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Keywords: *Byssochlamys fulva*, ascospores, conidia, temperature, pH, water activity

INTRODUCTION AND OBJETIVES

Moulds are generally considered heat-sensitive and obligate aerobes but some species are able to survive mild heat treatments such as pasteurization, causing spoilage of processed fruit-based products and in some cases production of mycotoxins. There is currently no information on the growth kinetics of these heat resistant moulds in matrices containing different hurdles of relevance for the food industry. The aim of this study was to develop a growth kinetic model for a heat resistant mould that is of interest to the food industry.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The growth kinetics of *Byssochlamys fulva* DSM 1808 fresh conidia was assessed on malt extract agar of different pH values (2.0–6.5) and NaCl concentrations (0–15%) stored at different temperatures (10–45°C).

RESULTS

The effects of the environmental parameters on the radial growth (μ) and lag phase (λ) were modeled using secondary models. A multiplicative without interaction-type model, combining the models for temperature pH and water activity, was used to describe the combined effect of these three environmental parameters on μ and λ . Based on these data a growth kinetic model was developed for *B. fulva*. Although the kinetic model was derived from conidia data on a laboratory medium, its prediction efficiency was evaluated with ascospores on food matrices. The model successfully described the behavior of ascospores in terms of time to mycelium appearance and mycelium growth rate.

CONCLUSIONS

This is the first study that connects conidia with ascospores behavior. Beyond the scientific interest in studying the effect of common environmental hurdles on the growth of a heat resistant mould, the collected data should be useful tool for the industry in order to control its growth on the basis of product formulation and storage conditions.

Poster Competition

P. 02.- A STOCHASTIC PREDICTIVE MODEL TO ESTIMATE SURVIVAL PROBABILITY OF *SALMONELLA ENTERICA* DURING THERMAL INACTIVATION.

Hiroki Abe, Kento Koyama, Shuso Kawamura, Shige Koseki
Hokkaido University

P. 07.- GROWTH MODELING OF *WEISSELLA VIRIDESCENS* BY REAL-TIME QUANTITATIVE PCR (QPCR).

Wiaslan Figueiredo Martins, Danielle De Sousa Severo, Fernanda Cunha Marques, Gláucia Maria Falcão de Aragão
Federal University of Santa Catarina

P. 15.- MODELLING GROWTH/NO GROWTH BOUNDARY CONDITIONS OF *BACILLUS SPECIES* SPORES.

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P. 16.- MODELLING OF TTI SMART LABELS RESPONSE FOR MONITORING SHELF LIFE AND HISTAMINE FORMATION IN AQUACULTURED MUGIL CEPHALUS FISH.

Papamichael Eirini, Tsironi Theofania, Giannoglou Marianna, Ntzimani Athina, Taoukis Petros
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P. 25.- QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT (SPME/GC-MS) OF SPOILAGE COMPOUNDS AND EFFECTS OF THERMAL SHOCKS IN *ALICYCLOBACILLUS SPP.* SPORES.

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P. 27.- MODELING *WEISSELLA VIRIDESCENS* INACTIVATION BY ULTRAVIOLET RADIATION.

Cíntia Maia Braga, Isabella Medeiros Souza, Letícia Floriano, Larissa Ramos, Josamaique Gilson I Venera, Andreia Tremarin, Jorge Ninow, Gláucia Maria Falcão Aragão
Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC).

P. 32.- EFFECT OF OREGANO ESSENTIAL OIL ON THE SHELF-LIFE OF VACUUM-PACKED SLICED HAM STORED UNDER NON-ISOTHERMAL CONDITIONS.

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P. 33.- MODELLING OF *ALICYCLOBACILLUS ACIDOTERRESTRIS* INACTIVATION IN APPLE JUICE USING THERMOSONICATION TECHNOLOGIES.

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P. 34.- FIELD ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECT OF NATURAL NITRITE SUBSTITUTE ON THE GROWTH OF SPOILAGE ORGANISMS AND *CLOSTRIDIUM SPOROGENES* IN COOKED MEAT PRODUCTS.

Ifigeneia Makariti, Nikolaos Grivokostopoulos, Zavitsanou Artemis, Dimitrios Doultos, Panagiotis Skandamis

Agricultural University of Athens.

P. 36.- MATHEMATICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE COMBINED EFFECT OF CHLORINE, BENZYL ISOTHIOCYANATE, EXPOSURE TIME AND CUT SIZE ON THE REDUCTION OF SALMONELLA IN FRESH-CUT LETTUCE DURING WASHING PROCESS.

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P.37.- INHIBITORY EFFECT OF LACTOBACILLUS SAKEI AGAINST LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES GROWTH IN SMOKED MEDITERRANEAN FISH PRODUCTS FROM MARINE AQUACULTURE.

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P. 38.- MICROBIAL INACTIVATION BEHAVIOR: THE EFFECT OF THE ENVIRONMENT ON INDIVIDUAL CELL TIME TO DEATH DISTRIBUTION.

Zafeiro Aspidou, Kostas Koutsoumanis

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P. 44.- EFFECT OF FOOD (MICRO)STRUCTURE ON GROWTH DYNAMICS OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN FISH BASED MODEL SYSTEMS.

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P. 54.- META-ANALYSIS OF OCCURRENCE OF OCHRATOXIN A (OTA), ZEARELENONE (ZEN) AND DEOXYNIVALENOL (DON) IN WHEAT BASED PRODUCTS.

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P. 60.- IMPACT OF ROASTING SEVERITY AND VARIABILITY ON RISK OF SALMONELLOSIS FROM CONSUMPTION OF PEANUTS IN THE UNITED STATES.

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P. 62.- INCLUDING GENOTYPIC DATA INTO MICROBIAL QUANTITATIVE RISK ASSESSMENT: APPLICATION ON *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN COLD SMOKED SALMON.

Fritsch Lena, Guillier Laurent, Lebouleux Charlotte, Augustin Jean-Christophe

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P. 64.- MODELING *WEISSELLA VIRIDESCENS* GROWTH ON HAM USING ACTIVE FILM INCORPORATED WITH OREGANO ESSENTIAL.

Camila Casagrande Paganini, Denise Adamoli Laroque, Cristian de Oliveira Romera, Pedro

Henrique Hermes Araújo, Bruno Augusto Mattar Carciofi, Gláucia M.F. Aragão

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P. 65.- MODELING *WEISSELLA VIRIDESCENS* INACTIVATION BY ULTRAVIOLET RADIATION.

Cíntia Maia Braga, Isabella Medeiros Souza, Letícia Floriano, Larissa Ramos, Josamaique Gilson Venerai,

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P. 70.- PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES AND STABILITY OF MARGARINE ENRICHED WITH OLIVE OILS.

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P. 72.- FIELD ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECT OF NATURAL NITRITE SUBSTITUTE ON THE GROWTH OF SPOILAGE ORGANISMS AND *CLOSTRIDIUM SPOROGENES* IN COOKED MEAT PRODUCTS.

Ifigeneia Makariti, Nikolaos Grivokostopoulos, Zavitsanou Artemis, Dimitrios Doultos, Panagiotis Skandamis

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P. 74.- MODELLING THE GROWTH KINETICS OF SALMONELLA SEROVARS DURING THE FERMENTATION OF YOGURT.

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P. 75.- FOOD SAFETY KNOWLEDGE AND HYGIENE PRACTICES OF PRODUCE HANDLERS AT THE MAJOR FRESH PRODUCE MARKET IN DOHA, QATAR

Israa El-Nemr, Mohanad Mushtaha, Hammad Asim, Ipek Goktepe

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P. 76.- INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE AND UV-C DOSE ON THE INACTIVATION OF SALMONELLA IN SOYMILK BY UV-C TECHNOLOGY.

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P. 84.- META-ANALYSIS OF THE INCIDENCE OF FOODBORNE PATHOGENS IN VEGETABLES FROM RETAIL ESTABLISHMENTS IN EUROPE.

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P. 86.- OPENFOOD: DEVELOPMENT OF A FOOD MATRIX-RELATED ONTOLOGY FOR APPLICATION IN PREDICTIVE MICROBIOLOGY SOFTWARE.

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Álvarez Alonso	Antonio	O10, O14, P89
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Amézquita	Alejandro	
Antonia	Albrecht	O47, P50
Aragao	Glaucia	
Aspidou	Zafeiro	O17, P28
Attuah Ansah	Philip	
Audiat-Perrin	Frédérique	P56
Augustin	Jean-Christophe	P01, P62
Baranyi	Jozsef	O37
Bascón Villegas	Isabel	P36
Bolívar Carrillo	Araceli	P37, P44, P71
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Bover Cid	Sara	O28, O32, O34, P79
Bovo Campagnollo	Fernanda	O23
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Cadavez	Vasco	O03, O29, O43, P84
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Carrasco Jiménez	Elena	O44, P71
Cebrian Aure	Guillermo	O46, P19
Chaturongakul	Soraya	
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Costello	Katherine	O19
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Cuevas Roman	Francisco	
Dagnas	Stéphane	
Dalgaard	Paw	O08, O21, O34, O42
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Desvignes	Virginie	O42
Dolan	Kirk	O02
Domenech Antich	Eva Maria	
Einarsson	Hjorleifur	P30
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Fernandez Escamez	Pablo S	
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Stecchini	Mara Lucia	P82
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Valik	Lubomir	
Van Lieverloo	J. Hein M.	P20
Velliou	Eirini	O19
Vermeulen	An	O22
Vila Brugalla	Montserrat	
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